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Information Brochure of the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)

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Table 1: EQUIVALENCES

scientific literature	engineering acronym
PRE	BEFORE
POST	AFTER
A TRACE	AN EVENT LOG
A FINAL STATE	AN ERROR STATE

Figure 1: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

$Q0 := NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name).$

$Q1 := IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name).$

Figure 2: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine file. KEYWORDS belonging both to 'engineering (ERROR_STATE)', and 'science (START_STATE)' can be intermingled in the same SDMM specification file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE(d):NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)
4.   -> [in_sql_event_log('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(d))] / 'SELECT.department' ->
5.     ERROR_STATE(e): IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name).
6. }
  
```

Figure 3: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE.

Figure 4: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL EVENT LOG.

1 Developer Biography

Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.] is a CHRISTIAN BY FAITH, Cameroonian, born on September 16 1983 in DOUALA (LITTORAL region, CAMEROON). Xavier has a "Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)" qualification from the **University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** (May 25, 2007). XAVIER NOUNDOU IS A "Dr.-Ing. : Doctor of Engineering (PhD equivalent - Computer Software Verification & Analysis)" from **THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO (ON, CANADA)**; DECEMBER 20, 2011!

Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.] has worked together with **Pr. Prof. Dr. habil. Jan Peleska**, at AGBS-University of Bremen, GERMANY; and 2 years later at WatForm-University of Waterloo, ON, Canada, with **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam**.

Xavier could successfully work with **Dr. Frank Tip** at The University of Waterloo (Waterloo, ON, Canada) on his first JAVA dynamic program analysis.

Xavier also had the great opportunity through **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Marcel Mitran** and **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam**; to work as a graduate intern in Markham (Toronto, ON, CANADA) at IBM TORONTO SOFTWARE LABORATORY; in the JAVA-J9 Just-In-Time Compiler Optimization Team, together with **Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc. (McGill University, QC, Canada)**.

Xavier has following academic and professional engineering research contributions:

1. 'Statistical test case generation for reactive systems' at RTT-MBT at VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH (<https://www.verified.de>).

2. 'Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis For C using LLVM':

1. source code in C++:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>
2. full text:
<https://zenodo.org/record/8051293>

3. 'YERITH-ERP-3.0':

1. source code in C++:
 - a. YERITH-ERP-9.0:
<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>
 - b. YERITH-ERP-9.0 SYSTEM DAEMON:
<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

2. full text (ongoing publication):
<https://zenodo.org/record/8052724>

¹https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

²<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

2 Introduction

Figure 5: SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

YERITH_QVGE is a CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) design tool to generate "domain-specific language (DSL) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG"¹ files, to be inputted into the "compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP", so to generate C++ files for the runtime verifier tester "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"² that allows for manual verification of SQL correctness properties of Graphical User Interface (GUI) software.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF inputs SQL correctness properties expressed using the formalism state diagram mealy machine (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG). Figure 5 illustrates a software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, together with the monitored program under analysis. The Free Open Source Code Software (FOSS) tool-chain of development testing is located as follows for free, EXCEPT for "YERITH_QVGE" that is a Closed Source Code Software (CSCS):

- COMPILER (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP):
https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
- RUNTIME VERIFIER TESTER (i.e.: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF):
<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
- state diagram mealy machine UNIT TESTS CODE (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS):
https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
- state diagram mealy machine (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG):
https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

3 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Project Dependency

Table 2: YERITH_QVGE Design and Testing System Dependencies

PROJECT	Required Library
1) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG	
2) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP	1)
3) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS	1)
4) YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	2)

Table 2 illustrates for each library project, which others it depends on.

3. Software design properties with SQL
4. Software design properties including event sequences over different layers of software system architecture
5. Class diagram with sequence diagram.

5 Advantages of YERITH_QVGE

Figure 6: YERITH_QVGE software library dependencies.

Figure 6 show a diagram overview of the presentation in Table 2. The step of the unit tests is colored in gray because it is only for developers of YERITH_QVGE intended.

4 Potential Uses of YERITH_QVGE

YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) could be used for the following automatic generation, analysis, verification, and validation tasks:

1. Automatic generation of runtime monitoring module program to prove whether a test procedure, automated, or not, is correct with regards to a test and / or design STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE.

In effect, let the test execution be runtime monitored to watch whether accepting error states would be found.

For instance, Junit testing environment could automatically integrate an automatically generated runtime monitor infrastructure for unit testing.

2. Automatic generation of runtime monitoring module program for any software that can emit Dbus messages.

Such runtime monitoring modules are for interest for special LTL model checking properties that cannot get a definite answer through use of a conventional model checker.

Figure 7: Workflow.

A sample state diagram mealy machine is shown in Figure 2.

WITH manual drawing of SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTY MODEL, you are freed from manually writing "state diagram mealy machine text files" that could be tedious and lengthy. Also, editing state diagram mealy machine files manually could be more error-prone than letting a compiler (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP) do it for you.

6 Conclusion

YERITH_QVGE costs only 2,500 EUROS. WE ONLY SUPPORT DEBIAN-LINUX (<https://www.debian.org>).

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state diagram mealy machine, 2

CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering), 2

domain-specific language (DSL), 2

runtime verifier tester, 2

SQL correctness properties, 2

User's Cheat Sheet for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF : A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine)

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Table 1: STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE SPECIFICATION KEYWORDS IN YRI_QVGE. 'AUTO' KEYWORDS SPECIFIES ALSO SQL QUERY FOR GOING OUT AUTOMATICALLY FROM A FAIL (FORBIDDEN) STATE. ("SEE SECTION ??.")

N°	scientific keywords	engineering keywords
1.	in_set_trace	in_sql_event_log
2.	not_in_set_trace	not_in_sql_event_log
3.	recovery_sql_query	recovery_sql_query
4.	STATE	STATE
5.	START_STATE	BEGIN_STATE
6.	FINAL_STATE ("FINAL_STATE_AUTO")	END_STATE ("END_STATE_AUTO") / ERROR_STATE ("ERROR_STATE_AUTO")
7.	IN_PRE	IN_BEFORE
8.	IN_POST	IN_AFTER
9.	IN_POST_NOP	N/A
10.	NOT_IN_PRE	NOT_IN_BEFORE
11.	NOT_IN_POST	NOT_IN_BEFORE
12.	NOT_IN_POST_NOP	N/A

Figure 1: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

$Q_0 := NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name);$ $Q_1 := IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name).$

Figure 2: YERITH-ERP-9.0 administration section displaying departments (-Q0).

Figure 3: YERITH-ERP-9.0 stock asset window listing some assets (Q1).

Figure 4: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine file. KEYWORDS belonging both to 'engineering ("ERROR_STATE_AUTO")', and 'science (START_STATE)' can be intermingled in the same SDMM specification file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE (d) :NOT_IN_BEFORE (YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)
4.   -> [in_sql_event_log ('DELETE.departement.YRI_ASSET', STATE (d) )] / 'SELECT.department' ->
5.     ERROR_STATE (e) :IN_AFTER (YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name) .
6. }
  
```

Figure 5: SAMPLE INTERNET-RELATED USE CASE SCENARIO OF "SDMM".

Listing 1: Sample real world "C++" code as opposed to PSEUDO-CODE "C++" code; as modified by a developer after automatic generation of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

```

1  bool YERITH_QVGE_sample_PAPER_extended_version_PROPERTY::DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_tL_PROPERTY(
2  QString sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number,
3  uint sql_record_qty_MODIFIED,
4  YRI_CPP_UTILS::SQL_CONSTANT_IDENTIFIER cur_SQL_command)
5  {
6  QStringList sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number.split(";", Qt::KeepEmptyParts);
7  QString sql_table_name = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(0);
8  QString CPP_FILE_NAME = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(1);
9  QString cpp_line_number = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(2);
10
11  switch(cur_SQL_command)
12  {
13  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::INSERT:
14      break;
15
16  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::SELECT:
17      if (YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Utils::isEqualsCaseInsensitive(sql_table_name, "departements_produits")) {
18          return YRI_SQL_SELECT_departements_produits();
19      }
20      break;
21
22  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::UPDATE:
23      break;
24
25  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::DELETE:
26      break;
27
28  default:
29      break;
30  }
31
32  return false;
33  }
    
```

Figure 7: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL EVENT LOG.

Figure 6: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI_QVGE.

1 Motivation for SDMM's Runtime Monitoring Verification Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF"

Currently, I develop an enterprise resource planning software called `YERITH-ERP-9.0` (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9.0>). THIS open-source project is having at time 390 000 lines of physical C++ code.

I had certain issues with the database, as one could remove a "stock category" but still have that stock category written as an existing stock category string for a set of stocks.

THIS is somewhat ugly. I then decided to create a tool that would find between non-conform irregular logical facts and running code defects.

To maximize efficiency and code easiest way to do modifications, I created a Domain-Specific Language (DSL) to describe running code defects called `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG` and a running time library to express these defects via a C++ library called `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF`!

Table 2 details which library is needed to work with `YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF`, which is the C++ verification program analysis tool on which this work is based!

1.1 A Sample Use-Case Scenario of "SDMM"

Internet is very important nowadays. Web application servers that dispatches internet connectivity to millions of users by showing content of websites; And by giving website applications capabilities and content to its users are really important to protect against attacks from malevolent users.

Figure 5 shows a protection scenario of sample web application server called "IBM-Websphere" that encompasses following :

- a developer creates a cyber-security related SDMM using `YERITH_QVGE`'s drawing tool called "YRI_QVGE" (Figure 6);
- Based on afore created SDMM diagram drawing, corresponding state diagram mealy machine file ending with a '.sd_mealy file' is generated;
- Then runtime monitor container `YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF` loads generated SDMM, and checks running that such a failure state diagram doesn't occur.

1.2 Another Sample Use-Case Scenario of "SDMM"

Figure 1 shows a State Diagram Mealy Machine that expresses whenever a stock department is deleted, this department shall not be anymore in stock. Figure 4 shows how figure 1 is expressed using SDMM.

Whenever this asset department still exists ("YRI_ASSET"), a new department bearing the same name shall be created again in order to maintain logical consistency for the System Under Test (SUT); "YERITH-ERP-9.0" in this case.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrates 2 figures that respectively shows a screenshot of the window where asset department "YRI_ASSET" was deleted, And a screenshot where an asset that still belongs to asset department "YRI_ASSET" exists.

Figure 4 illustrates the content of figure 1 using `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG`!

1.3 WHY DO I NEED FORMAL METHODS

I HAVE interest in developing mathematical definitions and demonstrations for formal methods for following reasons :

1. any developer and / or BSC student can write code that compiles, run, and has JUnit classes testing code that passes.

In effect, JUnit tests only stipulates that a running program does what a programmer had in intent; BUT not by any means exactly what a stakeholder needed.

2. BUT what demonstrates that the written and running program does what the primordial first intent of the developer and of his stakeholders was !?
3. THIS is exactly what formal methods (mathematics for computer science oriented towards testing and verifying; making sure, that a software program does what its intent is) does.

1.3.1 "C++ library YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" : Expressing of sequencing of actions in time (temporal usage rules for system safety)

Specifying temporal usage rules for system safety is primordial for ensuring a proper quality assurance of a system that is aimed to be more productive and safer in its usage by users, and / or maintainers.

THIS is why we created the C++ library `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF`. "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" is an acronym for **YERITH_State_Diagram_Runtime_Verification**.

1.4 Comparison with Unit Testing

1.4.1 Unit Testing

UNIT TESTING [Zel09]; [Nou09] (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444>) consists in creating System Under Test program execution sequences with certain data & certain test criteria so to assert following statements over a program under test :

1. a specific input data in a unit test module method generates a pre-defined certain output data; Thus developers must provide test input data for each test case runtime execution.

UNIT TESTING is a kind of what is called :

- o **White-box testing** [Zel09, MYE20]; meaning a developer knows intrinsics (inside details) of the system-software under test;
- ⇒ Another kind of testing is called **BLACK-box testing** [Zel09, MYE20]; meaning a developer doesn't need any inside source code details knowledge of the system-software under test.

Sample unit testing frameworks are for instance :

- a) **JUnit testing framework** (<https://www.junit.org>) for JAVA programs;
- b) **Qt Test testing framework** (<https://doc.qt.io/qt-5>) for Qt Graphical User Interface programs;

`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF` [NN25] (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) is a simpler and more offering alternative; especially for software integrating testing (See Subsubsection 1.4.3)!

However, it is more appropriate for people with a strong mathematical background (set algebra & formal methods);

- c) **CppUnit testing framework** (<https://freedesktop.org/wiki/Software/cppuni>) for C++ software.

1.4.2 Automated Unit Testing

Automated Unit Testing consists in automatically generating a System Under Test program execution sequences with certain data & certain test criteria so to assert following statements over a program under test :

1. a specific input data in a unit test module method generates a pre-defined certain output data; Thus developers receive automatically test data & test cases for each test case runtime execution.

Such generator systems like for example **RT-Tester MBT** (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>) from "Verified System International GmbH" (<https://www.verified.de>), generally require a specification of the software and / or program under test; So to be able to perform the automatic code source generation for the Embedded Unit Tester "RT-Tester MBT (Model Based Testing)".

RT-Tester MBT, for example, inputs a "David Harel Statechart" (See Subsubsection 1.7.1) specification as for instance generated by a plug-in for "Borland Together 6", delivered as a by-product by "Verified System International GmbH".

A detailed algorithm and function description of **RT-Tester MBT** could be found in Subsection 1.7!

1.4.3 Runtime Monitoring Verification

RUNTIME MONITORING Verification with state diagram mealy machine on the other side consists in :

1. specifying a wrong system under test program logical sequence using a mealy automaton as defined for instance in Subsection 1.6;
2. it is possible to specify conditions that trigger event between SDMM states : **guarded condition**; A guarded condition is placed between squared brackets (**'[guarded_condition]'**).

Example :

```
->[in_sql_event_log('guardedevent',STATE(d))]'event1'->
```

The previous example guarded condition (**in_sql_event_log('guardedevent',STATE(d))**) transition means that : 'event1' occurs only if event 'guardedevent' has previously occurred and is an element all events that lead to mealy machine state STATE (d).

The arrows signs ('->') around depicts this is a transition.

3. YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF observes monitors the SUT and emits all events as described and specified by developers; Thus developers don't provide test cases and / or test data !

Developers execute normally the System Under Test, by providing a normal system execution time run.

1.5 State Diagram Mealy Machine : Usages & Advantages

1.5.1 Usages

- o Software code program testing & verifying require means of expressing requiring in a form that can be used and executed by a computer program.

"SDMM" is a textual (See Figure 4) and graphical (See Figure 1) representation of software system requirements; HOWEVER, requirements expressed using "SDMM " are fail (forbidden) requirements : I.E., software system execution run that shall never happen !

- o During software development, developers need to characterize effects of program statements onto software program behavior.

For instance, what causes the deletion of a database table column department value at the level of the software user-scale (Example in Figure 2). Figure 2 could also be represented by a *state diagram mealy machine* as illustrated in Figure 1.

1.5.2 Advantages

- o **WHITE-box** as Well As **Black-box testing** is possible and / or available at once for any developer in testing; Depending on how YOU specify your runtime monitoring diagram & code (See Section 4.1).
- o Software developers could implement code source checking of **LTL-model checking formulas** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Linear_temporal_logic) for their fail (forbidden) program requirements;
- o I hope to also have sample **LTL-model checking formulas** implemented in future releases of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, which is a runtime monitoring verification container provided to work with the **"YRI_QVGE Design & Verification System"**.
- o Software developers that create & maintain fail (forbidden) program requirements mustn't have a perfect knowledge of code sources of the System Under Test.

1.5.3 Cases of Practical Usages of "SDMM"

- o Automobile industry "car-automobile-breaking safety & security usage rules" on-the-fly to avoid thousands of car-recall because of a bug (E.g.: **Toyota Camry 2009** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2009%E2%80%932011_Toyota_vehicle_recalls));

A car defect could only just be fixed at any Toyota registered auto-car-dealer by inputting a "SDMM" fix specification into an in-car placed YRI-QVGE-PC-Tablet device; Instead of sending it back to a Toyota car factory!

1.6 State Diagram Mealy Machine : Brief Summary Explanation

"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" has following usages and advantages:

- 1.) **Formalism STATE DIAGRAM mealy machine** for system specification: Mealy Machines are kind of state machines where output states depend only on input on a source state.

STATE DIAGRAM mealy machine as defined by myself is a finite state automaton that only has following characteristics:

- a.) Each automaton / machine only has 1 start state S_0 , and 1 final state S_f that is an accepting / error state.

A final, accepting, or error state is a state that shows a defect status of the system under analysis (SUA / PUA / SUT).

- b.) Each state S_i only has 1 outgoing state transition to an output state S_0 .
- c.) Each transition T , except a start transition "start", could have a **pre-condition, and post-condition**; That both are

called or named state-edge-condition (**pre-condition on T_1** : " $\underline{T_1}$ "; **post-condition on T_1** : " $\overline{T_1}$ ").

A state S_i has a state-condition either as pre-condition " $\underline{T_1}$ " on a state transition Or as a post-condition " $\overline{T_1}$ " of a state transition T_1 .

In Figure 1, state-conditions are for instance " $\underline{Q_0}$ ", and " $\overline{Q_1}$ ".

Each state-condition " S_i ", and / or pre-condition; And / or post-condition is an algebra set specification that uses set inclusion operations : \in, \notin .

d.) A set inclusion operation as state-condition for a state S_i could for instance be :

- 1.) $\underline{Q_0} := \text{IN_BEFORE}(y, D)$ **is to read** "BEFORE next event, variable y is IN set D ($y \in D$)". THIS boolean first-order preposition is assigned into variable $\underline{Q_0}$; the "underlining" illustrates that this is a pre-condition : "**meaning a condition That shall hold before (PRE) next event to occur in software system.**"
- 2.) $\overline{Q_1} := \text{IN_AFTER}(y, D)$ **is to read** "AFTER next event, variable y is IN set D ($y \in D$)". THIS boolean first-order preposition is assigned into variable $\overline{Q_1}$; the "over-lining" illustrates that this is a post-condition : "**meaning a condition That shall hold after (POST) next event to occur in software system.**"
- 3.) $\text{IN_BEFORE_NOP}()$: THIS boolean first-order preposition means that this pre-condition ('True') holds before (PRE) next event to occur in software system.
- 4.) $\text{IN_AFTER_NOP}()$: THIS boolean first-order preposition means that this post-condition ('True') holds after next event to occur in software system, after (POST) previously occurred event.
- 5.) $\underline{Q_0} := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(y, D)$ **is to read** "BEFORE next event, variable y is NOT IN set D ($y \notin D$)". THIS boolean first-order preposition is assigned into variable $\underline{Q_0}$; the "underlining" illustrates that this is a pre-condition : "**meaning a condition That shall hold before (PRE) next event to occur in software system.**"
- 6.) $\overline{Q_1} := \text{NOT_IN_AFTER}(y, D)$: THIS boolean first-order preposition means that this pre-condition ('False') doesn't hold before (PRE) next event to occur in software system.'
- 7.) $\overline{Q_1} := \text{NOT_IN_AFTER}(y, D)$ **is to read** "AFTER next event, variable y is NOT IN set D ($y \notin D$)". THIS boolean first-order preposition is assigned into variable $\overline{Q_1}$; the "overlining" illustrates that this is a post-condition : "**meaning a condition That shall not hold after (POST) next event to occur in software system.**"
- 8.) $\overline{Q_1} := \text{NOT_IN_AFTER_NOP}()$: THIS boolean first-order preposition means that this post-condition ('False') doesn't hold after (POST) next event to occur in software system.'

II.) A C++ library that implements runtime monitoring and fail-state recovery as a static library : (https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif).

III.) A Free and OPEN SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (Foss) implementation of a runtime monitor for using state diagram mealy machine specifications; BY means of a QT-dbus software communication stack with your own software : "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF" (<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>).

YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF's formal description of the state diagram formalism follows **Mealy machine** [Wik22] added with **accepting states (final or erroneous states), and state diagram transition pre- and post-conditions** : "state diagram mealy machine" ("SDMM").

Another excellent, detailed with proofs and theory presentation of mealy automata [PIH21] is available. In comparison to statechart [Har84], which is a **visual formalism** for states diagrams, YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF doesn't support at time for instance the following features: *hierarchical states (composite state, submachine state), timing conditions.*

A sample state diagram mealy machine is pictured in Figure 1. D is the start state,

1.7 Related State Diagram Formalisms

We here cite sample state diagram formalisms and the theory behind them for checking and / or verifying **software design & programming properties**.

- Statechart by David HAREL : A statechart is here a visual formalism-description to enable a description of a complex software system that can also have states with substates; And / or timing conditions on states entries, and / or transition triggering conditions.
- "Kripke structure" with THEORY & formalism called "MODEL Checking"; mainly by DAVID-Emerson & CLARKE-Edmund [CGK+18] (<https://mitpress.mit.edu/books/model-checking-second-edition>)

Software tools to perform model checking are called **model checkers**. Sample model checkers are NuSMV (<https://nusmv.fbk.eu/downloads.html>); SMV (<https://mcmil.net/smv.html>); Spin-model checker (<https://spinroot.com/spin/whatispin.html>).

1.7.1 David Harel Statechart : A Visual Formalism for State Diagram

Figure 9: A Sample David HAREL-Statechart model of the temporal property expressed in fig. 4 : —"Whenever department YRI_ASSET was deleted (event 'DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET'); querying stock table shall not find again an inventory stock in any department named YRI_ASSET"—.

Statechart [Har84], as defined and proposed by David HAREL; Represent diagrams, sometimes composite with internal states

that are used to describe reactive systems, meaning systems that react and act based on environmental input and interaction.

QT development library professional supports statechart as defined by David-Harel. SCXML is used to specify a state machine. (<https://doc.qt.io/qt-6/qtsxml-index.html>)

Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System (TDIOHS) as defined by Peleska et al. [BFPT06] implements David-HAREL statechart full compatibility incorporating the following elements for software system specification & elicitation :

- 1.) A software system behavior and actions can be represented as finite set of configurations; A configuration is an assignment of variables to values that situates a software system evolution over time;
- 2.) A set of configurations of a software system as a finite states graph representation where nodes represent software system states, And edges represent transition between software system states;
- 3.) Start- & End- (Final-, Accepting-, Erroneous-) state to represent INITIAL & FINAL software system state.
A reactive system has a particularity that it doesn't define a final-accepting state as it continuously reacts with its environment : it loops around its start state;
- 4.) Software system states transition defined as graph-edge between software system configuration-states;
- 5.) Software system state transition "Event" as label between graph-nodes;
- 6.) Guarded condition as behavioral condition that must hold in order for a state transition event to trigger & thus send the software system into a new configuration;
- 7.) Timing condition
- 8.) hierarchical states (composite states, submachine state)

1.7.2 Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System (TDIOHS)

Figure 10: A STCT-symbolic test case tree randomly generated by manual drawing for explanation purposes.

TDIOHS-Timed-Discrete-Input-Output-Hybrid-System [BFPT06] is a statechart compatible state diagram formalism defined by "Peleska et al." at the University of Bremen in Germany.

"Peleska et al." define a test mechanism to generate test cases from TDIOHS statechart visual description; The generated test cases abide to "Marie-Claude Gaudelle" algorithm defined in [DGG04] to statistically and uniformly-distribute test cases around a tree that describe all potential program code execution paths : STCT (Symbolic Test Case Tree).

A System Under Test (SUT) tree execution paths could then be traversed based on the real test data generated by a symbolic test data generator component as illustrated for instance in [nf10].

A sample STCT is illustrated in Figure 10; "N₀" is a start node of the program tree.

1.7.3 TDIOHS in Action within "Borland Together 6" with RT-Tester of 'verified.de'

Xavier NOUNDOU, myself, wrote together with Verified Systems International GmbH a plugin that enables developers to automatically create C++ testing code for design drawings created in the CASE-Computer Aided Software Engineering Design tool "Borland Together 6" (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Micro_Focus_Together).

I performed this task under supervision and advising of "Jan Peleska", as a student in Computer Science at the University of Bremen in Bremen-Germany in years "2006 / 2007".

Based on the automatically generated C++ module code, a developer could then use the UNIT Testing Framework for embedded systems RT-Tester of Verified.de (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>) to create software module unit testing code with following criteria :

- 1.) **MCDC (Modified Condition Decision Coverage) : test cases & data for checking any outcome of any boolean assignment of variables involved & used in a conditional IF-Then-Else branching statement;**
- 2.) **Uniformly statistically distributed test cases [NN07] & test data [nf10] from all possible test runtime execution of the Program Under Analysis (PUA) [NN07, BFPT06];**
- 3.) **Myself I only received "2,000 Euros" as fund collected as money-rewards-intellectual property out of this work since "May 2007" when I delivered program code software as part-deliverable to acquire my "Diplom-INFORMATIKER" qualification from the department of Mathematics & Computer Science ("Fachbereich 3") of the "UNiversity-racist of Bremen-Germany".**

1.7.4 TDIOHS in Action by "Automatic Test Cases / Data Generation"

Master Thesis [NN07] in Computer Science of "Xavier N. NOUNDOU", at the University of Bremen in Bremen-Germany; demonstrates an implementation of uniform distributed statistically algorithm for selecting paths for creating test cases from a Statechart designed in "Borland-Together 6".

The statechart is first of all transformed into a Symbolic Test Case Tree (STCT) before "MARIE-Claude Gaudelle" [DGG04] modified algorithm by [NN07] is applied.

In [CHKS12], Tatiana Mangels & Jan Peleska present "CTGEN", a Unit Under Test (UUT) test cases and test data generator for embedded system written in the C programming language.

More information and contacts for buying and / or trying this software product can be found at following URL : <https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>, from the German society "Verified Systems International GmbH".

2 Mathematical Formal Definition of SDMM

THIS section gives a mathematical theoretical definition of state diagram mealy machine (abbreviated "SDMM"), as conceived originally by us for our project YERITH-ERP-9.0 [Nou22] runtime monitoring verification started in year 2022 in Yaounde (Centre region, Cameroon).

YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF's formal description of the state diagram formalism follows **Mealy machine** [Wik22] added with **accepting states (final or erroneous states), and state diagram transition pre- and post-conditions**: "state diagram mealy machine". Another excellent, detailed with proofs and theory presentation of mealy automata [PIH21] is available. In

comparison to statechart [Har84], which is a **visual formalism** for states diagrams, YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF doesn't support at time for instance the following features: *hierarchical states (composite state, submachine state), timing conditions.*

2.1 Definition 1 : A state diagram (for mealy machine).

A state diagram is an 8-tuple $(S, S_0, C, \Sigma, \Lambda, \delta, T, \Gamma)$ where:

- S : a finite set of states
- $S_0 \in S$: a start state (or initial state)
- C : a set of predicate conditions; pre-conditions are underlined (e.g.: $\underline{Q0}$), and post-conditions are overlined (e.g.: $\overline{Q1}$). A pre-condition is comparable to a Harel-statechart *guarded condition*.
- Σ : an input alphabet, $\Sigma := \{False, True\}$.
'False' means no input from SUT into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
'True' means any input could come from SUT.
- Λ : an output alphabet (of program events $e_n (n \in \mathbb{N})$), ϕ the no program event. A program event generally corresponds to a function or method call at a SUT source code statement (or program point).
- $\delta : S \times C$: a 2-ary relation that maps a state s to a state-condition c as either a state diagram transition pre-condition (\underline{c}), or as a state diagram transition post-condition (\overline{c}).
- $T : S \times \Sigma \rightarrow S \times \Lambda$: a transition function that maps an input symbol to an output symbol and the next state.
- δ : a 2-ary relation that maps a state diagram transition to a guarded condition expression.
- Γ : a set of accepting states; $\Gamma \in S$.

For instance, for the motivating example described in Figure 1 we have:

- $S = \{D, E\}$;
- $S_0 = D$;
- $C = \{\underline{Q0}, \overline{Q1}\}$;
- $\Sigma = \{False, True\}$;
- $\Lambda = \{\phi, 'SELECT.department'\}$;
- $\delta = \{(D, \underline{Q0}), (E, \overline{Q1})\}$;
- $T = \{((D, False), (D, \phi)), ((D, True), (E, 'SELECT.department'))\}$;
- $\Gamma = \{E\}$

2.2 Definition 2 : A pre-condition.

A pre-condition of a state diagram transition is a predicate hat must be true before the transition can be triggered. A pre-condition $\underline{Q0}$ could have 2 forms:

- $\underline{Q0} := \text{IN_PRE}(X, Y)$ that means value "X" is in (\in) database column value set "Y".
- $\underline{Q0} := \text{NOT_IN_PRE}(X, Y)$ that means value "X" is not in (\notin) database column value set "Y".

2.3 Definition 3 : A post-condition.

A post-condition of a state diagram transition is a predicate that must be true after the transition was triggered. A post-condition $\overline{Q1}$ could have 2 forms:

- $\overline{Q1} := \text{IN_POST}(C, B)$ that means value "C" is in (\in) database column value set "B".
- $\overline{Q1} := \text{NOT_IN_POST}(C, B)$ that means value "C" is not in (\notin) database column value set "B".

For state diagram mealy machines with more than 2 states, only the first transition has a pre-condition specification (IN_PRE, or NOT_IN_PRE). Each other transition only has a post-condition specification (IN_POST, or NOT_IN_POST). Since each state only has 1 outgoing (edge) state transition, the post-condition of the previous (incoming) state transition acts as the pre-condition of the next transition.

IT is also for user interest to have following NO-Operation post-conditions when working with state diagram mealy machines with more than 2 states :

- IN_POST_NOP
- NOT_IN_POST_NOP

OUR experience, not reported at time anywhere, shows that *state diagram mealy machine* with more than 2 states are really more for parallel system modeling; I.E. systems that work in GUI with timers and several threads of work at anytime.

"In such cases, subsequent linearly placed states may not belong to same thread of execution: this is kind of what is called in CSP (Communicating Sequential Processes) [RBH81]; Parallel Composition."

Subsection 2.7 details better and well this correlation between "CSP" [RBH81] & "SDMM".

2.4 Definition 4 : A trace.

A trace $T_n = \langle e^0, e^1, \dots, e^n \rangle$ is a sequence of SUT events (or SUT program points) $e^{i, i \in \{0, \dots, n\}}$ of length n . $trace(D)$ is the trace of SUT events up to state D. For instance, for the motivating example described in Figure 1 we have: $trace(E) = trace(D), \langle 'SELECT.department' \rangle$.

2.5 SUT Event Processing Method YRI_trigger_an_edge_event

Listing 2 illustrates the pseudo-code of YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF SUT event processing method `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)`. 'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)' is responsible for interpreting a monitor at runtime, based on its current state, and on the current event received from SUT. Each state in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF states diagrams shall have only 1 outgoing edge (transition), by specification and construction, as explained in Proposition 2.5.1 in Section 2.

The algorithm in Listing 2 demonstrates that, given correct trace and event information from SUT, YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF always exactly matches the user specification. Thus never giving false warnings.

2.5.1 Proposition 1: NO FALSE WARNINGS.

YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF only allows 1 outgoing edge or transition for a state in its specifications, and for *not desirable (forbidden) behavior*, as illustrated in Figure 1. These 2 properties, together with algorithm 'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)' (Listing 2) of YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF, ensures that there are no false warnings during YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF analyses.

For example, the opponents runtime monitoring and / or verification tools-systems [BH12, BRBY00, AAC+05, Bod05, CR07] may give false warnings.

We need to also report that if a developer doesn't well specify to the runtime verifier tester where to emit event, as for instance in "Listing 1", false warnings (false positives) may occur.

Listing 2: C++ Pseudo-code for `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)`: `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF` method for triggering state diagram events (edges or transitions).

```

1  bool MONITOR::YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)
2  {
3      MONITOR_EDGE cur_OUTGOING_EDGE = _cur_STATE.outgoing_edge();
4
5      if (cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.evaluate_GUARDED_CONDITION_expression() &&
6          (an_edge_event == cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.edge_event_token()))
7      {
8          bool precondition_IS_TRUE = cur_OUTGOING_EDGE
9              .CHECK_SOURCE_STATE_PRE_CONDITION(_cur_STATE);
10
11         if (precondition_IS_TRUE)
12         {
13             set_current_triggered_EDGE(cur_OUTGOING_EDGE);
14
15             MONITOR_STATE a_potential_accepting_state =
16                 cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.get_TARGET_STATE();
17
18             if (CHECK_whether__STATE__is_Final(a_potential_accepting_state))
19             {
20                 CALL_BACK_final_state_FUNCTION(a_potential_accepting_state);
21             }
22             return true;
23         }
24     }
25     return false;
26 }

```

2.5.2 Explanation on HOW to avoid code that creates False Warnings (False Positives)

2.6 Guarded Condition Expression Specification in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF

Guarded conditions expressions can be specified using one of the `yr_create_monitor_edge` method and a boolean expression of type `YR_CPP_BOOLEAN_expression`. An edge without an explicit guarded condition has an *implicit* `[True]` guarded condition on it. The implicit guarded condition `[True]` mustn't be identified as an implicit input event `'True'`, as specified in Definition 1.

Guarded conditions are meant to be trace set specification on program events. For instance in Figure 1 (motivating example): `"[in_set_trace ('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(D))]"` means that a SQL `'DELETE'` event removing a department named `'YRI_ASSET'` from MariaDB SQL table `'department'` must have occurred in the trace leading to state `'D'`, before event `'SELECT.department'` can be triggered. A guarded condition could have two practical forms:

- `"[in_set_trace ('event', STATE(D))]"` is equivalent to: `'event' ∈ trace(D)`.
- `"[not_in_set_trace ('event', STATE(D))]"` is equivalent to: `'event' ∉ trace(D)`.

where `'event'` is an input event ($\text{event} \in \Sigma$) and `'D'` a state diagram state ($D \in S$).

2.7 SDMM for modeling parallel-concurrent software system

A state in a *state diagram mealy machine* specification acts as a parallel concurrent process state.

IT means each state transition represents a parallel-concurrent process synchronization event as for example defined

in a formalism named CSP (Concurrent Sequential Processes) as a parallel composition operator (`"||"`).

For instance, in Fig. 1, Processes D & E could be specified in communication in CSP like: `"(D || B) over event SELECT.department"`!

After this event (`'SELECT.department'`) has occurred, "Process E" enters a deadlock while "process D" might continue running.

2.8 SDMM in Action within YRI_QVGE by 'Yerith R&D'

A screenshot of a fail (forbidden) *state diagram mealy machine* is illustrated in Figure 6.

This fail fail (forbidden) *state diagram mealy machine* is the same described in Figure 4 with "YRI_QVGE Design & Verification System" domain specific language (DSL) `"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG"`.

The program-DSL code source illustrated in Figure 4 was automatically generated by myself by *"Saving a design as a DOT/GraphVIZ"* document.

"Saving a design drawing as a DOT/GraphVIZ" creates source code in domain specific language `"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG"` within a file ending with `'.sd_mealy'`.

2.9 SDMM in Action by automatic "Runtime Monitors Automatic Generation"

I created `YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF` so to allow automatic generation of runtime execution time monitoring modules for *state diagram mealy machine* defined using a Domain Specific Language (DSL) called `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG`.

`YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF` enables expression and description of state diagram mealy machine specification.

THE Domain-Specific Language (DSL) definition in *Backus-Naur-Form (BNF)* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Backus%E2%80%93Naur_form) of this DSL called `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG` is printed in the USER'S guide of `YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF` (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>).

3 HOW TO Setup C++ Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" for Usage in A C++ PROGRAM SOURCE CODE

When you build runtime monitoring verification library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF", a static binary library is newly generated.

YOU then need to copy this newly created static binary library into your C++ project. YOU then need for instance using QT, to put a line as follows so to be able to use "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF":

```
LIBS += -L$$PWD/lib_SD -lyri_sd_runtime_verif
```

in your project file ending with following string '.pro' (e.g.:qt-project.pro");

Whereas string "-L\$\$PWD/lib_SD" represents a path that leads to where "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" is stored. String "-lyri_sd_runtime_verif" mentions to link ("-l") runtime monitoring library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" during your build process!

3.1 Development Toolchain

Table 2 illustrates for each library project, which others it depends on.

1.) The runtime monitoring interface static library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" enables users to express software

program states, that are incorrect, USING mealy machines since mealy machine transitions depends only on the current state and its current input;

- 2.) "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS" is only required in case you modified the FOSS library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" and would like to apply some unit tests to check your modifications.
- 3.) The LIBRARY and / or language that enables to specify "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF" state diagram mealy machines is called "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG";
- 4.) The LIBRARY that creates for you the incorrect mealy machine as a C++ code, by describing it using either a text file, and / or a state machine described using YRI_QVGE ("YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG") as a design drawings; IS coined the name "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP";
- 5.) NORMALLY you wouldn't need to directly invoke the compiler / translator "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP". This is best done by the runtime monitor generator "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF".

The user's guide for "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF" (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) explains how to do so.

Table 2: YRI_QVGE Toolchain

PROJECT	Required Program / Library
1) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF	"Qt-trolltech" (https://doc.qt.io/qt-5)
4) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS	1)
2) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG	1)
3) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP	2)
5) YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	3)

4 METHODS of C++ Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF"

Table 3: Sample important classes (prefix YRI_CPP_ to class name) & Methods of C++ Library "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF".

N°	CLASSES	METHODS	UTILITY
1.	MONITOR	CREATE_MONITOR	Creates a new runtime monitor
2.	MONITOR	YRI_register_set_final_state_CALLBACK_FUNCTION	register a C++ method a the callback function in case an error state was found.
3.	MONITOR	RESET_RUNTIME_MONITOR	Sets the current state TO the start state.
4.	MONITOR	YRI_trigger_an_edge_event	"TRUE" is returned in case an edge event "an_edge_event" was triggered.
5.	MONITOR	create_yri_monitor_state	Creates a runtime monitor state.
6.	MONITOR	create_yri_monitor_edge	Creates a runtime monitor edge.
7.	MONITOR	find_yri_monitor_state	Search for a runtime monitor state within a runtime monitor.
8.	MONITOR	set_RUNTIME_MONITOR_NAME	Sets an identity name to a runtime monitor.
9.	MONITOR	IS_in_TRACE_LOG	Checks whether a token is in trace of current system trace
10.	MONITOR	TRACE_LOG_current_RECEIVED_EVENT_TOKEN	appends to current event trace this event token given as parameter
11.	MONITOR	GET_root_edge	Returns a root edge (first usable edge) of this runtime monitor trace log
12.	MONITOR	DELETE_yri_monitor_edge	Removes this given as argument edge from this monitor trace log
13.	notinset_inset_TRACE_expression	YRI_CPP_notinset_inset_TRACE_expression	Creates an expression to be used as an edge token expression
14.	notinset_inset_TRACE_expression	set_USE_SQL_SYNTAX_event_logging_FOR_PRINTING	Use SQL syntax (e.g.: in_sql_event_log instead of scientific in_set_trace)

Table 3 gives sample important methods of YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. For the sake of space and for clarity, we have removed prefix 'YRI_CPP' string in a table presentation from all class names!

Using Domain-Specific Language (DSL) we created to describe wrong behavior of your code might allows not to directly call these

methods, but to let a compiler (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP) do this for you.

Also simply putting your (.sd_mealy) description file within a project folder in the runtime verifier container (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF) will call the compiler for yourself.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF will generate a class file bearing the name of your '.sd_mealy' file but ending with 'hpp' and 'cpp' for you.

Subsection 4.1 talks in more details of the method you need to modify code so to use them easily.

4.1 Generated Method YOU need to code

The method

```
virtual bool DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY(QString sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number,  
                                               uint sql_record_qty_MODIFIED,  
                                               YRI_CPP_UTILS::SQL_CONSTANT_IDENTIFIER cur_SQL_command =  
                                               YRI_CPP_UTILS::SQL_CONSTANT_IDENTIFIER::UNDEFINED_SQL_COMMAND);
```

is the one where you need to implement your analysis and / or verification code.

From its arguments you have access to the following code information :

- 1.) a SQL table name that is used by events so to perform actions on user program;
- 2.) a software program code source file where the call occurred;
- 3.) a source code line number where the event occurred in afore given source code file;
- 4.) a SQL command that was sent, And that is exactly one of: 'INSERT', 'SELECT', 'UPDATE', 'DELETE' !

5 A Hardware Dedicated Device : YRI-QVGE-PC-Tablet

A hardware dedicated device: YRI-QVGE-PC-Tablet running a runtime monitoring verification container program called `YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF` is in creation by myself.

Such a dedicated hardware would be connected to a running computer via a USB port, or an RS-232 socket, or an Ethernet port.

6 Detailed Scientific and Engineering Presentation Document on 'zenodo.org'

Detailed formal scientific and engineering contributions of design and testing system `YRI_QVGE` can be found in **JOURNAL ARTICLE "Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"** [nN23].

7 Conclusion

The graphical drawing tool `YRI_QVGE` (Figure 6) costs only 2,500 EUROS. WE ONLY SUPPORT `DEBIAN-LINUX` (<https://www.debian.org>).

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User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)

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Table 1: STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE SPECIFICATION KEYWORDS IN YERITH_QVGE. 'AUTO' KEYWORDS SPECIFIES ALSO SQL QUERY FOR GOING OUT AUTOMATICALLY FROM A FAIL (FORBIDDEN) STATE. ("SEE SECTION 9.")

N°	scientific keywords	engineering keywords
1.	in_set_trace	in_sql_event_log
2.	not_in_set_trace	not_in_sql_event_log
3.	recovery_sql_query	recovery_sql_query
4.	STATE	STATE
5.	START_STATE	BEGIN_STATE
6.	FINAL_STATE ("FINAL_STATE_AUTO")	END_STATE ("END_STATE_AUTO") / ERROR_STATE ("ERROR_STATE_AUTO")
7.	IN_PRE	IN_BEFORE
8.	IN_POST	IN_AFTER
9.	IN_POST_NOP	N/A
10.	NOT_IN_PRE	NOT_IN_BEFORE
11.	NOT_IN_POST	NOT_IN_BEFORE
12.	NOT_IN_POST_NOP	N/A

Figure 1: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

$Q_0 := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{department.department_name})$; $Q_1 := \text{IN_AFTER}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{stocks.department_name})$.

Figure 2: YERITH-ERP-9.0 administration section displaying departments ($\neg Q_0$).

Figure 3: YERITH-ERP-9.0 stock asset window listing some assets (Q_1).

Figure 4: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine file. KEYWORDS belonging both to 'engineering ("ERROR_STATE_AUTO")', and 'science (START_STATE)' can be intermingled in the same SDMM specification file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE (d) :NOT_IN_BEFORE (YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)
4.   -> [in_sql_event_log ('DELETE.departement.YRI_ASSET', STATE (d) )] / 'SELECT.department' ->
5.     ERROR_STATE (e) :IN_AFTER (YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name) .
6. }
  
```

Figure 5: SAMPLE INTERNET-RELATED USE CASE SCENARIO OF "SDMM".

Listing 1: Sample real world "C++" code as opposed to PSEUDO-CODE "C++" code; as modified by a developer after automatic generation of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

```

1  bool YERITH_QVGE_sample_PAPER_extended_version_PROPERTY::DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_tL_PROPERTY(
2  QString sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number,
3  uint sql_record_qty_MODIFIED,
4  YRI_CPP_UTILS::SQL_CONSTANT_IDENTIFIER cur_SQL_command)
5  {
6  QStringList sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number.split(";", Qt::KeepEmptyParts);
7  QString sql_table_name = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(0);
8  QString CPP_FILE_NAME = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(1);
9  QString cpp_line_number = sql_table_ADDED_with_file_AND_line_number_LIST.at(2);
10
11  switch(cur_SQL_command)
12  {
13  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::INSERT:
14      break;
15
16  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::SELECT:
17      if (YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Utils::isEqualsCaseInsensitive(sql_table_name, "departements_produits")) {
18          return YRI_SQL_SELECT_departements_produits();
19      }
20      break;
21
22  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::UPDATE:
23      break;
24
25  case YRI_CPP_UTILS::DELETE:
26      break;
27
28  default:
29      break;
30  }
31
32  return false;
33  }
    
```

Figure 7: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL EVENT LOG.

Figure 6: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE.

1 Introduction

Figure 8: SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

This user's guide helps briefly and concisely how to create a binary executable of the runtime monitoring testing tool **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** having user defined runtime monitors. The guide also specifies keywords allowed within runtime monitor specifications as State Diagram Mealy Machines.

YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) could be used for the following automatic generation, analysis, verification, and validation tasks:

1. Automatic generation of runtime monitoring module program to prove whether a test procedure, automated, or not, is correct with regards to a test and / or design STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (formally described in [Nou23]).

In effect, let the test execution be runtime monitored to watch whether accepting error states would be found.

For instance, Junit testing environment could automatically integrate an automatically generated runtime monitor infrastructure for unit testing.

2. Automatic generation of runtime monitoring module program for any software that can emit Dbus messages.

"Such runtime monitoring modules are for interest for special LTL model checking properties that cannot get a definite answer through use of a conventional model checker".

3. Software design properties with SQL
4. Software design properties including event sequences over different layers of software system architecture
5. Class diagram with sequence diagram.

¹https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

²<https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

³Scientific: fail (forbidden) trace.

⁴Structure Query Language.

2 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Short Overview

Figure 9: YERITH_QVGE software library dependencies.

YERITH_QVGE is a CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) design tool to generate "domain-specific language (DSL) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG ¹" files, to be inputted into the "compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP", so to generate C++ files for the "runtime verifier tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF ²" that allows for manual verification of SQL correctness properties of Graphical User Interface (GUI) software.

Figure 10 illustrates a workflow diagrammatically of the afore described process.

Figure 9 show a diagram of the afore described process; The step of the unit tests is colored in gray because it is only for developers of YERITH_QVGE intended.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF inputs SQL correctness properties expressed using the formalism "state diagram mealy machine (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG)". Figure 8 illustrates a software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, together with the monitored program under analysis. The Free Open Source Code Software (FOSS) tool-chain of development testing is located as follows for free, EXCEPT for "YERITH_QVGE " that is a Closed Source Code Software (CSCS):

- COMPILER (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP): https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
- RUNTIME VERIFIER TESTER (i.e.: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF): <https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
- state diagram mealy machine UNIT TESTS CODE (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS): https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
- state diagram mealy machine (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG): https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

3 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Project Dependency

Table 2: YERITH_QVGE Design and Testing System Dependencies

PROJECT	Required Program / Library
1) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG	
2) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP	1)
3) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS	1)
4) YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	2)

Table 2 illustrates for each library project, which others it depends on.

4 Advantages of YERITH_QVGE

A sample state diagram mealy machine is shown in Figure 4.

WITH manual drawing of SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTY MODEL, you are freed from manually writing "state diagram mealy machine text files" that could be tedious and lengthy. Also, editing state diagram mealy machine files manually could be more error-prone than letting a compiler (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG) do it for you.

5 State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM)

TABLE 1 depicts scientific keywords and their engineering counterpart that can be used in describing NOT DESIRABLE ³ SQL ⁴ call sequence state diagram mealy machine in YERITH_QVGE Design and Testing System.

A STATE DIAGRAM mealy machine specification is compiled into C++ code that describes a runtime monitor to be executed in the runtime monitoring tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. Figure 4 depicts a sample State Diagram Mealy Machine specification on a NOT DESIRABLE SQL call sequence.

5.1 HOW TO READ A "SDMM"

Figure 1 shows a finite automaton representation of the mealy machine description in Figure 4. It shall be read as follows:

- The program is in a start state *D*; state *D* is a start state since there is incoming "START" arrow into it.
- (Pre-) Condition Q_0 : "department name ' YRI_ASSET ' is not in table column ' department_name ' of database table ' department ' "; applies in state *D*.
- Whenever GUARD CONDITION : *in_sql_event_log(' DELETE . department . YRI_ASSET ' , STATE (d))*: "event ' DELETE . department . YRI_ASSET ' appears in SQL event log (trace) leading to state *D*"; applies in state *D*, system under test (SUT) event ' SELECT . department ' could occur.
- When SUT event ' SELECT . department ' occurs, SUT is now in state *E*; state *E* is an error state because the node that represents it in Figure 1 has 2 circles on it.
- (Post-) Condition $\overline{Q_1}$: "department name ' YRI_ASSET ' is in table column ' department_name ' of database table ' stocks ' "; applies in state *E*.

This shall not be the case since department ' YRI_ASSET ' is no more defined in SUT database table ' department ' .

5.2 "SDMM" WITH MORE THAN 2 STATES

State Diagram Mealy Machines (SDMM) with more than 2 states have following characteristics, as detailed in scientific and engineering journal paper [Nou23] in preparation:

- Only the first transition has a pre-condition specification
- Each other transition only has a post-condition specification
- Since each state only has 1 outgoing state transition, the post-condition of the previous (incoming) state transition acts as the pre-condition of the next transition.

6 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Workflow

Figure 10: Workflow explanation.

The "Design and Testing System" YERITH_QVGE works with following workflow, as illustrated graphically in Figure 10, and in Figure 5:

1. Draw Structure Query Language (SQL) temporal safety property using drawing tool YERITH_QVGE;
2. copy the generated ".spec_sd_mealy" files into a user project directory in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF home development folder: "\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF";
3. follow the steps described in Section 7 so to gather a single executable that defines all specified runtime monitors.

7 Custom User Project (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)

Table 3: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF Directories

Variable for illustration purposes	Meaning
\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	root directory of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF
\$YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/\$USER_PROJECT	root directory of user project

Table 3 illustrates directories that will be used to describe a process to generate a single binary executable for a user's custom project with several runtime monitor specifications.

Figure 7 illustrates a screenshot of the Graphical User Interface (GUI) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. You can get a copy of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF using the following command:

git clone https://www.github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif

Creating a binary executable for State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) specifications consists of the following elements:

1. **'MariaDB' database connection configuration file:** this file defines settings to connect to the system under test (SUT) application database; it is located in path: "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF-GUI-ELEMENTS-SETUP/yri-db-runtime-verif-database-connection.properties`".

A database connection to the SUT application database is required in order to check LTL property through the SDMM application library `YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG`.

2. **Property configuration file:** this file defines environment variables necessary for building a binary executable for the user; it is located in path: "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/$USER_PROJECT/bin/configuration-properties.sh`".
3. "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/$USER_PROJECT/sd-mealy-machine-specs`": this directory contains user defined State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) specifications to generate Corresponding runtime monitors within a single binary executable.
4. **Generate an executable for a user defined runtime monitor:**
 - a) A following command MUST be renewed each time you are new in a bash-shell environment; execute following command in directory "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF`":


```
./YRI-create-executable-for-user-SDMM.sh -d $USER_PROJECT
```
 - b) modify the LTL verification code part within the generated source code files.

Then execute following command in directory "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF`":

```
./yr_db_runtime_verif_BUILD_DEBIAN_PACKAGE.sh
```

- c) uninstall YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF with following command in directory "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF`":


```
./yr_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_uninstall.sh
```
- d) re-install YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF with following command in directory "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF`":


```
./yr_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_INSTALL.SH
```
- e) **Redo [1st-step] in case you add or modify a '.spec_sd_mealy' specification file in folder "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/$USER_PROJECT/sd-mealy-machine-specs`"!**

8 HOW TO START YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

- The "ELF-x64" binary executable, in the source development directory is located in full path: "`YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF/bin`".
- The **DEBIAN-LINUX** icon () of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is located in "Applications" menu under section "Programming", and section "Accessories".
- The "ELF-x64" binary executable, after installation of the **DEBIAN-LINUX** package 'yri-db-runtime-verif.deb' is located in full path: "`/opt/yri-db-runtime-verif/bin`".

Figure 11: SAMPLE sql recovery state diagram model in YERITH_QVGE

9 SQL QUERY Recovery execution on demand

A user can specify which SQL command query to execute whenever a System Under Test (SUT) lands in an accepting error state. This is done using keywords ending with "AUTO", used for meaning "AUTO RECOVERY FROM FAIL STATE":

1. `recovery_sql_query`
2. `END_STATE_AUTO`
3. `FINAL_STATE_AUTO`
4. `ERROR_STATE_AUTO`.

The use of an "AUTO" keyword shall be accompanied with a use of keyword `recovery_sql_query`, that specifies a SQL command query to run when landing in this fail error accepting state.

9.1 Automatic SQL Command Query Generation

YERITH_QVGE implements an automatic SQL query generation strategy in case a user don't specify a SQL command query, since it could be leaved empty: Subsections 9.1.1, 9.1.2, 9.1.3, and 9.1.4 describe the strategy implemented.

9.1.1 ERROR ACCEPTING STATE for sdmm 1.

$$\frac{\text{not in_before}(YX, YY) \quad \text{ACTION}(V)}{\text{in_after}(DD, YR)}$$

9.1.2 RECOVERY 1.

$$\frac{\text{in_after}(DD, YR) \quad \text{ACTION}(\text{RECOVERY_ND})}{\text{not in_after}(DD, YR)}$$

9.1.3 RECOVERY 2

$$\frac{\text{in_after}(DD, YR) \quad \text{ACTION}(\text{RECOVERY_D})}{\text{in_after}(YX, YY)}$$

9.1.4 Concrete RECOVERY 2 action (Practical solution to be implemented in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

$$\frac{\text{in_after}(YX, YY) \quad \text{insert_RECOVERY}(YX, YY)}{\text{in_before}(YX, YY)} \bullet$$

10 HOW TO USE a user interface

Figure 12: YERITH_QVGE user interface screenshot.

11 YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE

Figure 13 illustrates a "Backus-NAUR form (BNF)" of our specification language for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF tool.

12 Formal Scientific and Engineering Project Description

Detailed formal scientific and engineering contributions of design and testing system YERITH_QVGE can be found in **JOURNAL ARTICLE "Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"** [Nou23].

13 Conclusion

The graphical drawing tool YERITH_QVGE (Figure 6) costs only 2,500 EUROS. WE ONLY SUPPORT DEBIAN-LINUX (<https://www.debian.org>).

References

[Nou23] Xavier Noundou. A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime. <https://zenodo.org/records/13232567>, October 2023.

Figure 13: Grammar in Backus–Naur Form (BNF) of YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG Mealy Machine STATE DIAGRAM Specification Language.

```

<specification> ::= yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec '{' (mealy-automaton-spec) '.' '}'
<mealy-automaton-spec> ::= <sut-state-spec>
    | <sut-state-spec> '→' <sut-edge-state-spec>
<sut-edge-state-spec> ::= <sut-edge-mealy-automaton-spec> '→' <mealy-automaton-spec>
<sut-edge-mealy-automaton-spec> ::= <edge-mealy-automaton-guard-cond> <event-call>
<edge-mealy-automaton-guard-cond> ::= /* empty */ '/' | '[' <trace-specification> ']' '/'
<trace-specification> ::= <in-sql-event-log> | <not-in-sql-event-log> | <in-set-trace> | <not-in-set-trace>
<sut-state-spec> ::= <start-state-property-spec>
    | <start-state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
    | <state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
    | <final-state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
    | <final-state-auto-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification> ':' <recovery-sql-query-spec>
<algebra-set-specification> ::= <in-algebra-set-spec> | <not-in-algebra-set-spec>
<in-algebra-set-spec> ::= <in-spec> '(' <prog-variable> ',' <db-table> '.' <db-column> ')'
    | <in-spec-nop> '(' ')'
<not-in-algebra-set-spec> ::= <not-in-spec> '(' <prog-variable> ',' <db-table> '.' <db-column> ')'
    | <not-in-spec-nop> '(' ')'
<in-sql-event-log> ::= in_sql_event_log '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<not-in-sql-event-log> ::= not_in_sql_event_log '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<in-set-trace> ::= in_set_trace '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<not-in-set-trace> ::= not_in_set_trace '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')'
<in-spec> ::= IN_BEFORE | IN_AFTER | IN_PRE | IN_POST
<in-spec-nop> ::= IN_POST_NOP
<not-in-spec> ::= NOT_IN_BEFORE | NOT_IN_AFTER | NOT_IN_PRE | NOT_IN_POST
<not-in-spec-nop> ::= NOT_IN_POST_NOP
<start-state-property-spec> ::= start_state '(' AlphaNum ')'
<state-property-spec> ::= state '(' AlphaNum ')'
<final-state-property-spec> ::= end_state '(' AlphaNum ')' | final_state '(' AlphaNum ')' | error_state '(' AlphaNum ')'
<final-state-auto-property-spec> ::= end_state_auto '(' AlphaNum ')' | final_state_auto '(' AlphaNum ')'
    | error_state_auto '(' AlphaNum ')'
<recovery-sql-query-spec> ::= recovery_sql_query '(' <db-table> ',' <sql-recovery-query> ')'
<sql-recovery-query> ::= String
<event-call> ::= String
<prog-variable> ::= AlphaNum
<db-table> ::= AlphaNum
<db-column> ::= AlphaNum

```

YERITH_QVGE : A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime

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Abstract

Software correctness properties are essential to maintain quality by continuous and regressive integration testing, as well as runtime monitoring the program after customer deployment. This paper presents an effective and lightweight C++ program verification framework: **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, to check SQL (Structure Query Language) [1] software correctness properties specified as temporal safety properties [2]. A temporal safety property specifies what behavior shall not occur, in a software, as sequence of program events. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** allows specification of a SQL temporal safety property by means of a state diagram mealy machine [3]. In **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, a specification characterizes effects of program events (via SQL statements) on database table columns by means of set interface operations (\in , \notin), and, enable to check these characteristics hold or not at runtime. Integration testing is achieved for instance by expressing a state diagram that encompasses both Graphical User Interface (GUI) states and MySQL [4] databases queries that glue them. For example, a simple specification would encompass states between 'Department administration' and 'Stock listing' GUI interfaces, and transitions between them by means of MySQL databases operations. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** doesn't generate false warnings; **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** specifications are *not desirable (forbidden) specifications (fail traces)*. This paper focuses its examples on MySQL database specifications, labeled as states diagrams events, for the newly developed and FOSS (Free and Open Source Software) Enterprise Resource Planing Software YERITH-ERP-3.0 [5].

Keywords: model-based testing, reactive system analysis, computer software program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software integration testing with SQL and GUI, runtime monitoring

Fig. 1: **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** WORKFLOW (diagram inspired from operation diagram in [6]).

1 Introduction

Table 1: YERITH-ERP-3.0 RELEVANT SOFTWARE SYSTEM METRICS

Software System Metric	Value
User Interface (windows, dialog) number	60
MariaDB SQL table number	38
MariaDB SQL table column number	320
Source lines of code (SLOC)	300,000

1.1 Motivations

This paper describes an effective dynamic analysis framework, based on runtime monitors specified in C++ programs (implemented in the software library `yri_sd_runtime_verif`), to perform software temporal safety property checking of GUI (Graphical User Interface) based software.

GUI based software are very comfortable and handy to use. However, tools to perform temporal safety property verification of GUI software are almost not available as FOSS. The testing of

combinations between GUI windows and database queries that glue them to make sense to the user, is almost unavailable as FOSS, or at all to the best of the knowledge of the author of this paper. The FOSS C++ library `libfsmtest` [7] provides test suite generation support for source code behavior specifications as mealy automata. However, `libfsmtest` only allows for *desirable* correctness properties, and doesn't provide GUI (interaction) support or as plugin-based.

Unit or integration testing for GUI widgets is available by use of "NUnit" testing frameworks like e.g. `Qt-Test` [8], `CppUnit` [9], etc.. Software testing across GUI widgets (and MySQL queries) is however limited in support by these "NUnit" framework. To the best of the knowledge of the author of this paper, `DejaVu` [10] provides some support for Java 'record and replay' testing while `FROGLOGIC` [11] provides support for C++ GUI software 'record and replay' testing technology. 'Record and replay' testing means a user performs a sequence of events that are recorded by testing infrastructure and automatically replay later on to see if expected events thereof occur. However, none of this 'record and replay' technology tool enable temporal safety property specification as FOSS, with SQL as plugin.

As we will see in the related work, section 7, of this paper, most of software correctness property checking frameworks don't put an emphasis on checking temporal safety property of GUI software. Characterizing the effects of program statements (via SQL statements) on database table columns, and to check that these characteristics hold or not, is of predominant importance for large software systems with an impressive number of database tables. Table 1 illustrates for instance FOSS YERITH-ERP-3.0 relevant software system metrics.

It means it can be very difficult for developers to keep application related logical requirements between the tables without appropriate software testing or analysis tools.

A large amount of former work on runtime monitoring assumes for a sequential program, or an abstraction of the program as one single source code, on which program analysis is performed [12–16].

The program analysis technique the author of this paper presents here abstract SQL events, GUI events, or sequences of them, as a state diagram, and enables developers to run them sequentially against a runtime monitor specified as a C++ program. In particular, the example presented in Section 3 specifies results of GUI windows events as SQL database pre-conditions on state diagram transitions; SQL events are specified as state diagram transition events. Figure 1 shows a high level overview of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** workflow.

1.2 Main Contributions

This paper presents 3 original main contributions:

- an industrial level quality framework (**YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>), that solves temporal property verification by dynamic program analysis. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** makes use of the C++ Qt-DBus library, to input a *runtime monitor specification* (`yri_sd_runtime_verif`) as C++ program code, that also enables software-library-plugin checks;
- a C++ library: `yri_sd_runtime_verif` (https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif); modeling a state diagram runtime monitoring interface using only set

algebra inclusion operations (\in , \notin) for state diagram program state specification as pre- and post-conditions.

`yri_sd_runtime_verif` only enables the specification of states diagrams specifications as *not desirable (forbidden) behavior specifications (fail traces)*. Thus, **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** doesn't generate any false warning. A violation of a safety rule has been found whenever a final state could be reached. On the other hand, not reaching a final state doesn't mean that there is not a test case (or test input) that cannot reach this final state.

- An application of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** to check 1 temporal safety property error, found in the ERP FOSS YERITH-ERP-3.0.

Previous version of this paper

This paper extends a previous version [17], currently in conference proceedings **SPLASH-ICTSS 2023** submission, with state diagram with more than 2 states, guarded conditions specifications, 2 new keywords for state diagram transition trace specification ("`in_sql_event_log`", "`not_in_sql_event_log`"), 2 new keywords ("`IN_POST_NOP`", "`NOT_IN_POST_NOP`") for no-operations state post-conditions; And **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** binaries with more than 1 runtime monitor.

1.3 Overview

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents formal definitions of the principal concepts used in this paper. Section 3 presents a motivating example that will be used throughout this paper to explain the presented concepts of this paper. Section 4 presents the software architecture of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, our GUI dynamic analysis framework. Section 5 introduces the C++ software library `yri_sd_runtime_verif` to model states diagrams, and reused by **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. We evaluate our dynamic runtime analysis in Section 6. Section 7 compares this paper with other papers that achieve similar work or endeavors. Section 8 concludes this paper.

2 Formal Definitions

`yri_sd_runtime_verif`'s formal description of the state diagram formalism follows *Mealy machine* [3] added with *accepting states (final or erroneous states), and state diagram transition pre- and post-conditions*: "state diagram mealy machine". Another excellent, detailed with proofs and theory presentation of mealy automata [18] is available. In comparison to statechart [19], which is a *visual formalism* for states diagrams, `yri_sd_runtime_verif` doesn't support at time for instance the following features: *hierarchical states (composite state, submachine state), timing conditions (timing conditions on states entries, and / or transition triggering conditions)*.

Definition 1 : A state diagram.

A state diagram is an 8-tuple $(S, S_0, C, \Sigma, \Lambda, \delta, T, \Gamma)$ where:

- S : a finite set of states
- $S_0 \in S$: a start state (or initial state)
- C : a set of predicate conditions; pre-conditions are underlined (e.g.: $\underline{Q0}$), and post-conditions are overlined (e.g.: $\overline{Q1}$). A pre-condition is comparable to a Harel-statechart *guarded condition*.
- Σ : an input alphabet, $\Sigma := \{False, True\}$.
'False' means no input from SUT into **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**.
'True' means any input could come from SUT.
- Λ : an output alphabet (of program events $e_n (n \in \mathbb{N})$), ϕ the no program event. A program event generally corresponds to a function or method call at a SUT source code statement (or program point).
- $\delta : S \times C$: a 2-ary relation that maps a state s to a state-condition c as either a state diagram transition pre-condition (\underline{c}), or as a state diagram transition post-condition (\overline{c}).
- $T : S \times \Sigma \rightarrow S \times \Lambda$: a transition function that maps an input symbol to an output symbol and the next state.
- $:$: a 2-ary relation that maps a state diagram transition to a guarded condition expression.
- Γ : a set of accepting states; $\Gamma \in S$.

For instance, for the motivating example described in Figure 2 we have:

- $S = \{D, E\}$;
- $S_0 = D$;
- $C = \{\underline{Q0}, \overline{Q1}\}$;
- $\Sigma = \{False, True\}$;
- $\Lambda = \{\phi, 'SELECT.department'\}$;
- $\delta = \{(D, \underline{Q0}), (E, \overline{Q1})\}$;
- $T = \{((D, False), (D, \phi)), ((D, True), (E, 'SELECT.department'))\}$;
- $\Gamma = \{E\}$

Definition 2 : A pre-condition.

A pre-condition of a state diagram transition is a predicate that must be true before the transition can be triggered. A pre-condition $\underline{Q0}$ could have 2 forms:

- $\underline{Q0} := \text{IN_PRE}(X, Y)$ that means value "X" is in (\in) database column value set "Y".
- $\underline{Q0} := \text{NOT_IN_PRE}(X, Y)$ that means value "X" is not in (\notin) database column value set "Y".

Definition 3 : A post-condition.

A post-condition of a state diagram transition is a predicate that must be true after the transition was triggered. A post-condition $\overline{Q1}$ could have 2 forms:

- $\overline{Q1} := \text{IN_POST}(A, B)$ that means value "A" is in (\in) database column value set "B".
- $\overline{Q1} := \text{NOT_IN_POST}(A, B)$ that means value "A" is not in (\notin) database column value set "B".

For state diagram mealy machines with more than 2 states, only the first transition has a pre-condition specification (**IN_PRE**, or **NOT_IN_PRE**). Each other transition only has a post-condition specification (**IN_POST**, or **NOT_IN_POST**). Since each state only has 1 outgoing (edge) state transition, the post-condition of the previous (incoming) state transition acts as the pre-condition of the next transition.

IT is also for user interest to have following **NO-Operation** post-conditions when working with state diagram mealy machines with more than 2 states :

- **IN_POST_NOP**

◦ **NOT_IN_POST_NOP**

OUR experience, not reported at time anywhere, shows that *state diagram mealy machine* with more than 2 states are really more for parallel system modeling; I.E. systems that work in GUI with timers and several threads of work at anytime.

“In such cases, subsequent linearly placed states may not belong to same thread of execution: this is kind of what is called in CSP (Communicating Sequential Processes) [1]; Parallel Composition.”

Definition 4 : A trace.

A trace $T_n = \langle e^0, e^1, \dots, e^n \rangle$ is a sequence of SUT events (or SUT program points) $e^i, i \in \{0, \dots, n\}$ of length n . *trace(D)* is the trace of SUT events up to state D. For instance, for the motivating example described in Figure 2 we have: $trace(E) = trace(D), \langle 'SELECT.department' \rangle$.

Proposition 1: NO FALSE WARNINGS.

`yri_sd_runtime_verif` only allows 1 outgoing edge or transition for a state in its specifications, and for *not desirable (forbidden) behavior*, as illustrated in Figure 2. There is no need to specify the red colored edge in Figure 2 because it represents runtime cases where no input events arrive from SUT into **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. These 2 properties, together with algorithm `'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)'` (Listing 3) of `yri_sd_runtime_verif`, ensures that there are no false warnings during **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** analyses. For example, the runtime monitoring or verification systems [12–16] may give false warnings.

2.1 Guarded Condition Expression Specification in `yri_sd_runtime_verif`

Guarded conditions expressions can be specified using one of the `yr_create_monitor_edge` method and a boolean expression of type `YR_CPP_BOOLEAN_expression`. An edge without an explicit guarded condition has an *implicit* `'[True]'` guarded condition on it. The implicit guarded condition `'[True]'` mustn't be identified

as an implicit input event `'True'`, as specified in Definition 1.

Guarded conditions are meant to be trace set specification on program events. For instance in Figure 2 (motivating example): `"[in_set_trace ('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(D))]"` means that a SQL `'DELETE'` event removing a department named `'YRI_ASSET'` from MariaDB SQL table `'department'` must have occurred in the trace leading to state `'D'`, before event `'SELECT.department'` can be triggered. A guarded condition could have two practical forms:

- `"[in_set_trace ('event', STATE(D))]"` is equivalent to: `'event' ∈ trace(D)`.
- `"[not_in_set_trace ('event', STATE(D))]"` is equivalent to: `'event' ∉ trace(D)`.

where `'event'` is an input event (`event ∈ Σ`) and `'D'` a state diagram state (`D ∈ S`).

Fig. 2: A motivating example, as current bug in YERITH-ERP-3.0.

$\overline{Q0} := \text{NOT_IN_PRE}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{department.department_name}).$
 $\overline{Q1} := \text{IN_POST}(\text{YRI_ASSET}, \text{stocks.department_name}).$

Fig. 3: YERITH-ERP-3.0 administration section displaying departments ($\neg Q0$).

Fig. 4: YERITH-ERP-3.0 stock asset window listing some assets ($\overline{Q1}$).

3 Motivating Example: missing department definition

3.1 The Enterprise Resource Planing Software YERITH-ERP-3.0

YERITH-ERP-3.0 is a fast, yet very simple in terms of usage, installation, and configuration Enterprise Resource Planing Software developed by Noundou et al. [5] for very small, small, medium, and large enterprises. YERITH-ERP-3.0 is developed using C++ by means of the Qt development library. YERITH-ERP-3.0 is a large software with around 300 000 (three hundred thousands) of physical source lines of

code. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** could be used for integration testing of YERITH-ERP-3.0, among different software modules.

3.2 Example Temporal Safety Property

The motivating example of this paper consists of the temporal safety property stipulating that *"A DEPARTMENT SHALL NOT BE DELETED WHENEVER STOCKS ASSET STILL EXISTS UNDER THIS DEPARTMENT"*. This statement means that a user shall be denied the removal of department 'YRI_ASSET' in Figure 3 because there are still a stock asset listed within department 'YRI_ASSET', as illustrated in Figure 4. Figure 2

Fig. 5: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF graphical EDITOR viewing interface demonstrating that a final state has been reached (Section 6 analyzes these results).

illustrates the above temporal safety property as a simple state diagram.

3.2.1 State Diagram Explanation

'D' is a *start* state as illustrated by an arrow ending on its state shape. 'E' is a *final* (error, or accepting) state as illustrated by a double circle as state shape.

The pre-condition Q_0 (as a predicate) in state 'D':

"NOT_IN_PRE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)" means:

- a department named 'YRI_ASSET' is not in column 'department_name' of MariaDB SQL database table 'department'. This might happen whenever

button 'Delete' in Figure 3 is pressed when item 'YRI_ASSET' is selected.

Similarly, the post-condition $\overline{Q_1}$ (as a predicate) "IN_POST(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name)", in accepting state 'E', means:

- a department named 'YRI_ASSET' is in column "department_name" of MariaDB SQL database table 'stocks'.

The state diagram event transition in Figure 2: 'SELECT.department' denotes that when in 'D', a SQL 'select' on database table "department" has occurred; 'E' is then reached as an *accepting state*.

Guarded Condition Expression

The guarded condition expression "[`in_set_trace ('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(D))`]" means a SQL 'DELETE' event removing a department named 'YRI_ASSET' from MariaDB SQL table 'department' must have occurred in the trace leading to state 'D'.

Yri_sd_runtime_verif Specification Code

The source code specified in Listing 2 also illustrates a specification in C++ using software library `yri_sd_runtime_verif` of the state diagram specification above.

3.3 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF Analysis Report

The motivating example automaton in Figure 2 is analyzed by **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** as follows:

- whenever department 'YRI_ASSET' is deleted in YERITH-ERP-3.0, as done in Figure 3, the runtime monitor state 'D' with a state condition Q_0 is entered
- when MySQL library (plugin) event 'SELECT.department' occurs, in Figure 3 because of YERITH-ERP-3.0 displaying the remaining product departments, the guarded condition for edge event 'SELECT.department' is automatically evaluated to 'True' by C++ library `yri_sd_runtime_verif`, because no other guarded condition was specified by the developer
- `yri_sd_runtime_verif` enters the runtime monitor state to 'E' and state condition Q_1 via method `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)` because there are still assets (`yerith_asset_3`) left within product department 'YRI_ASSET', as illustrated in Figure 4. 'E' is then an accepting (or final or error) state.

Figure 5 illustrates an analysis result of the afore described process, which gets evaluated and described in Evaluation Section 6.

Fig. 6: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: simplified software system architecture.

4 The Software Architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

4.1 Dynamic Analysis

4.1.1 SUT Source Code Instrumentation.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runs as a separate Debian Linux process from the application to dynamically analyze (YERITH-ERP-3.0 in this case). Figure 6 illustrates a software system architecture layer of a software system that uses **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. Figure 6 and Figure 7 illustrate how YERITH-ERP-3.0 is instrumented to send MySQL database events, as they occur on due to the GUI of YERITH-ERP-3.0, to process **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, so it can perform runtime analysis of the monitor implemented within it.

4.1.2 Debugging Information.

Each GUI manipulation of YERITH-ERP-3.0 in its instrumented source code part could generate a state transition within the analyzed runtime monitor state diagram in **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. Visualize "line 35" of Figure 5 to observe that a specific analysis message is sent to the console of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** in cases where a final state has been reached; the message at "line 33" is for an

Fig. 7: YERITH_QVGE software library dependencies.

accepting (final) state of the state diagram specification of the motivating example presented in Figure 2.

4.2 SQL Events

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF currently only processes the 4 SQL events in Table 2.

4.3 A Runtime Monitor (An Analysis Client)

Listing 1: "XML file adaptor for YERITH-ERP-3.0 test cases (reduced from 4 to only 1 SQL event for paper)."

```
<!DOCTYPE node PUBLIC "-//freedesktop//DTD D-BUS Object
Introspection 1.0//EN"
"http://www.freedesktop.org/standards/dbus/1.0/introspect.
dtd">
<node name="/YRruntimeverification">
  <interface name="com.yerith.rd.IYRruntimeverification">
    <method name="YRI_slot_refresh_SELECT_DB_MYSQL">
      <annotation name="org.qtproject.QtDBus.QtTypeName.In0"
        value="QString"/>
      <annotation name="org.qtproject.QtDBus.QtTypeName.In1"
        value="uint"/>
      <annotation name="org.qtproject.QtDBus.QtTypeName.In2"
        value="bool"/>
      <arg type="QString" direction="in"/>
      <arg type="uint" direction="in"/>
      <arg type="bool" direction="out"/>
    </method>
  </interface>
</node>
```

An user (an analysis client) of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** needs to subclass class `YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Monitor`. The UML class diagram in Figure 8 displays the class structure of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. Qt-Dbus communication adaptor `IYRruntimeverificationAdaptor`

Table 2: SQL Event Dbus Method Interface

SQL Event	Dbus Method Interface
DELETE	YRI_slot_refresh_DELETE_DB_MYSQL(QString, uint)
INSERT	YRI_slot_refresh_INSERT_DB_MYSQL(QString, uint)
UPDATE	YRI_slot_refresh_UPDATE_DB_MYSQL(QString, uint)
SELECT	YRI_slot_refresh_SELECT_DB_MYSQL(QString, uint)

Fig. 8: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: simplified class diagram in UML [20].

shall be generated by the user of this library (on **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** side) using Qt-Dbus command `qdbusxml2cpp` and an XML file, similar to the one displayed in Listing 1:

An analysis client must first override method **'DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ItI_PROPERTY'** of class **'YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Monitor'** so to implement a checking algorithm for each event received from SUT, as for instance the events illustrated in Figure 2 of the motivating example. The analysis client then calls method **'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)'** (Listing 3) of class **'YR_CPP_RUNTIME_MONITOR'** of C++ library `yri_sd_runtime_verif` for each corresponding state diagram transition event.

Fig. 9: Class diagram in UML [20] to model a State Transition Diagram.

Fig. 10: Class diagram in UML [20] to model state diagram transition trace conditions in yri_sd_runtime_verif code.

Listing 2: yri_sd_runtime_verif C++ code modeling a current bug in YERITH-ERP-3.0 (Figure 2).

```

1 YRI_CPP_MONITOR_EDGE *a_last_edge_0 = create_yri_monitor_edge("D",
2 "E",
3 "select.departements_products");
4
5 a_last_edge_0->get_SOURCE_STATE()->set_START_STATE(true);
6
7 a_last_edge_0->get_TARGET_STATE()->set_FINAL_STATE(true);
8
9 a_last_edge_0->set_PRE_CONDITION_notIN("YRI_ASSET",
10 "departements_products.nom_departement_produit");
11
12 a_last_edge_0->set_POST_CONDITION_IN("YRI_ASSET",
13 "stocks.nom_departement_produit");
14
15 YRI_register_set_final_state_CALLBACK_FUNCTION(&YRI_CALL_BACK_final_state);

```

5 yri_sd_runtime_verif: A C++ Library to Model States Diagrams

5.1 Structure Of yri_sd_runtime_verif

yri_sd_runtime_verif is a state diagram C++ library the author of this paper created to work with the dynamic analysis program YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. Figure 9 and Figure 10 represent the class structure, in UML, of yri_sd_runtime_verif. Listing 2 shows the C++ code that models the motivating example in

Figure 2, and that uses runtime monitoring C++ state diagram library yri_sd_runtime_verif.

There is no need to write C++ code for the red specified edge of Figure 2; this represents runtime cases where no input event arrives from SUT into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Table 3 specifies which class is in yri_sd_runtime_verif code for each runtime monitor/state diagram element.

5.2 Methods for Pre- and Post-Condition Specifications

Table 4 illustrates methods for specifying pre- and post-conditions of a runtime monitor

Table 3: Runtime Monitor Specification Classes

State Diagram Feature	Class
State	YR_CPP_MONITOR_STATE
Transition	YR_CPP_MONITOR_EDGE
Event	YR_CPP_MONITOR_EVENT
Trace at state level	YR_CPP_MONITOR_TRACE_EVENT
Guard Condition	YR_CPP_BOOLEAN_expression
Set Trace Inclusion at edges	YR_CPP_in_SET_TRACE_expression
Set Trace non Inclusion at edges	YR_CPP_not_in_SET_TRACE_expression
Runtime Monitor	YR_CPP_MONITOR

Table 4: `yri_sd_runtime_verif` Methods for Pre-/Post-Condition Specification

Class <code>YR_CPP_MONITOR_EDGE</code> Methods	Utility
<code>set_PRE_CONDITION_notIN(QString, QString)</code>	sets a NOT IN DATABASE pre-condition
<code>set_PRE_CONDITION_IN(QString, QString)</code>	sets an IN DATABASE pre-condition
<code>set_POST_CONDITION_notIN(QString, QString)</code>	sets a NOT IN DATABASE post-condition
<code>set_POST_CONDITION_IN(QString, QString)</code>	sets an IN DATABASE pre-condition

state diagram transition. Each method takes in 2 arguments of string ('QString') type: 'DB_VARIABLE', 'db_TABLE_db_COLUMN'.

The first method argument: 'DB_VARIABLE', specifies which variable is to be expected as value for the specification of the second variable argument 'db_TABLE_db_COLUMN'. The second variable gives in a string to be specified in format "DB_table_name.DB_table_column"; and its supposed value is the returned value of the first variable argument 'DB_VARIABLE'.

These 4 pre- and post-conditions methods make assumptions that a **program variable value** 'DB_VARIABLE' is in set "DB_table_name.DB_table_column" or not; if the value of 'DB_VARIABLE' is in the database table column, it means it is **in the set** (\in) of values "DB_table_name.DB_table_column"; and not being in the table column means it is **not in the set** (\notin).

Example from the motivating example in Section 3

Listing 2 of the runtime monitoring specification stipulates for instance in its "line 12", as post-condition:

```
a_last_edge_0->
  set_POST_CONDITION_IN("YRI_ASSET",
    "stocks.nom_departement_produit");
that 'YRI_ASSET' shall be a value in the value set ( $\in$ ) of SQL table 'stocks' column 'nom_departement_produit'.
```

5.3 SUT Event Processing Method `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event`

Listing 3 illustrates the pseudo-code of `yri_sd_runtime_verif` SUT event processing method `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)`. 'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)' is responsible for interpreting a monitor at runtime, based on its current state, and on the current event received from SUT. Each state in `yri_sd_runtime_verif` states diagrams

Listing 3: C++ Pseudo-code for `YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event): yri_sd_runtime_verif` method for triggering state diagram events (edges or transitions).

```

1  bool MONITOR::YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)
2  {
3      MONITOR_EDGE cur_OUTGOING_EDGE = _cur_STATE.outgoing_edge();
4
5      if (cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.evaluate_GUARDED_CONDITION_expression() &&
6          (an_edge_event == cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.edge_event_token()))
7      {
8          bool precondition_IS_TRUE = cur_OUTGOING_EDGE
9              .CHECK_SOURCE_STATE_PRE_CONDITION(_cur_STATE);
10
11         if (precondition_IS_TRUE)
12         {
13             set_current_triggered_EDGE(cur_OUTGOING_EDGE);
14
15             MONITOR_STATE a_potential_accepting_state =
16                 cur_OUTGOING_EDGE.get_TARGET_STATE();
17
18             if (CHECK_whether__STATE__is__Final(a_potential_accepting_state))
19             {
20                 CALL_BACK_final_state_FUNCTION(a_potential_accepting_state);
21             }
22             return true;
23         }
24     }
25     return false;
26 }

```

shall have only 1 outgoing edge (transition), by specification and construction, as explained in Proposition 2 in Section 2.

The algorithm in Listing 3 demonstrates that, given correct trace and event information from SUT, `yri_sd_runtime_verif` always exactly matches the user specification. Thus never giving false warnings.

Table 5: SUT (YERITH-ERP-3.0) "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF graphical EDITOR" error states (Figure 5).

SQL EVENT	SUT PROGRAM POINT (TRACE)
"SELECT.department"	"src/yerith-erp-windows.cpp:992"

6 Evaluation

The main experimental results in this paper demonstrate the efficacy of our tool to find errors in the SUT (YERITH-ERP-3.0), presented in Subsection 3.2.

Qualitative Results.

SUT (YERITH-ERP-3.0) TRACING.

Table 5 illustrates SUT source code trace information as presented in **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** console output in Figure 5. We have translated from French to English the MariaDB SQL table names.

SQL EVENT CALL SEQUENCE.

A careful observation of the output in Figure 5 illustrates the following sequence:

- **line 23:** at state D , execution of the state diagram event "'SELECT.department' " (SUT button 'Delete' has been pressed at **line 21**)
:
select * from departements_produits WHERE nom_departement_produit = 'YRI_ASSET';
- **line 28, line 29:** evaluation of the precondition Q_0 of state D stating that product department 'YRI_ASSET' is not existent evaluates to 'TRUE' (triggering of event "DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET' " by pressing of SUT button 'Delete' at **line 21** has removed any asset department name 'YRI_ASSET').
*[YRI_CPP_MONITOR::CHECK_PRE_CONDITION_notIN:] precondition_IS_TRUE: True **
- **line 31, line 32:** checking post-condition Q_1 in state E (there are still stocks in stock department 'YRI_ASSET') evaluates to 'TRUE', thus state E is reached as an accepting state, because department name 'YRI_ASSET' still exists in SUT SQL table "stocks", as illustrated in Figure 4 of the motivating example:
"execQuery: select * from stocks WHERE nom_departement_produit = 'YRI_ASSET';"
*[YRI_CPP_MONITOR::CHECK_post_condition_IN:] postcondition_IS_TRUE: True **

Runtime Performance.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF and **yri_sd_runtime_verif** don't incur a runtime supplemental overhead to the SUT, apart from emitting SQL events from SUT to **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** as they occur, since no hand-shaking mechanism is used between **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** and the SUT. The emission of an SQL event from SUT to **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** doesn't cost more than 2 statements execution time (getting a pointer to the DBUS server, and calling a method 'YR_slot_refresh_SELECT_DB_MYSQL' or other similar 3 methods (for INSERT, UPDATE, and, DELETE) on it).

7 Related Work

- **SUT source code instrumentation with runtime monitor specification.** "Clara" [12] enables to express software correctness properties using **AspectJ** and *dependency state machines (related to trace-matches [21])*, both as instances of the *typestate* formalism, a formalism that is merely used for checking correctness of programs by a static compilation (analysis) technique called *typestate checking*. The Clara framework weaves (instruments), and annotates a program with runtime monitors using **AspectJ**, then tries to optimize the weaved program by static analysis. The "residual program", meaning the weaved statically optimized program is then executed and runtime monitored by developers to detect runtime errors. Runtime monitoring tools [13–16] work as similar as the Clara framework does.
YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF doesn't instrument the System Under Test (SUT) with any specification. It runs the runtime monitor concurrently from the analyzed SUT, but not with hand-shaking mechanism, thus not increasing runtime execution of the SUT. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** specifies the runtime monitor as a *state diagram mealy machine*, a subset of *typestate*, specified as a C++ program, and extended with accepting states and state transition pre- and post-condition.
- **SUT binary code instrumentation with a runtime monitor.** With **tracerory** [6, 22]", **Jon Eyolfson and Patrick Lam** use runtime program binary code instrumentation technique in **INTEL-pin** [23] to instrument running programs for purposes of detecting unread memory. I.e., **tracerory** doesn't generate itself a runtime monitor, it uses **INTEL-pin** [23] to generate a runtime monitor for its verification purposes. "**Purify**" [24] doesn't allow for SUT user correctness property specification. It has built-in memory access safety properties to check *offline* on program execution, after instrumentation of the SUT, its third-party, and vendor object-code libraries.

In contrast, with **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**, the user instruments the source code of the analyzed C++ program at compile time with SQL events emitting code. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** could also be used to perform memory write integrity check like **tracerory**. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** monitors program trace events at database level (also source code statement level by mapping to SQL query statements), and not at program counter level as **tracerory** does. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** inputs a SUT correctness property specification as a *state diagram mealy machine* (as a subset of LTL [2]); **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** is a runtime monitor container; **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** also generates itself a runtime monitor whereas **tracerory** doesn't.

- **Source code automated test case generation for C++ with TDIOHS [25], or FOSS library libfsmtest [7].** "Peleska et al." created a Framework for generating Harel-statecharts fully compatible state diagrams as Test programs as C++ object-oriented program code; Based on "Peleska et al." formalism of Time Discrete Input/Output Hybrid System (TDIOHS). TDIOHS models state systems that handle real and discrete real number data as input to the system under test; TDIOHS models SUT execution by a so called SYMBOLIC TEST CASES TREE (STCT) that represents all possible runtime execution paths of the SUT by means of symbolic test cases data. Symbolic test cases data are data that cannot be used in a runtime execution, BUT that are generated outside from STCT tree by a symbolic test data generator algorithm. The SUT sample tree execution paths are then traversed based on the real test data generated by a symbolic test data generator component [26].

In contrast, the framework **YERITH_QVGE** runtime monitors a program under analysis only for specified fail (forbidden) trace behaviors as given by users.

- **Specification as set interface operations.** "Hob" [27, 28] is a program verification framework that enables to: characterize effects of program statement on data

structures by means of all (\forall , \exists , etc.) algebra abstract set interface operations; and to check that these characteristics hold or not, using static analyses.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is a program verification framework that enables to: characterize effects of program statements via SQL [4] (Structure Query Language) on database table columns by means of set interface operations (\in , \notin); and to check that these characteristics hold or not, using dynamic runtime analysis.

- **Concurrent Event Stream Analysis.**

"DejaVu" [29] enables to check safety temporal property expressed in **first-order past linear-time temporal logic (FO-PLTL)** for events that carry data. **DejaVu** inputs a trace log (*offline*) and a FO-PLTL formula, and outputs a boolean value for each position in the inputted trace. "LOGSCOPE" [30] checks, *offline*, software systems correctness properties expressed using a rule-based specification language over state machines. It is not very precise what type of state machine is created and processed. "LOGSCOPE" translates specifications into C++ monitors (that could carry data). "EventRaceCommander" [31] repairs in web applications (*online*), event race errors, a kind of safety error.

States diagrams specifications are implemented as C++ program monitors using C++ library `yri_sd_runtime_verif`. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** outputs a developer given (by means of a callback function, as seen in 'line 15' in Listing 2) string message ¹ in case an accepting state was entered, and a trace event of YERITH-ERP-3.0 leading to it. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**'s monitors need not store data, as **DejaVu** monitors must. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** events also carry data (database table and column name, records quantity modified by current SUT event). Runtime monitors could be checked against programs written in any programming language or framework, as

long as they emit necessary SQL events to **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**.

¹'YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Monitor_notify_SUCCESS_VERIFICATION'
in this paper motivating example in Figure 5.

Fig. 11: A Mealy Machine State Diagram Specified Using `yri_sd_runtime_verif` Specification Language.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yri_missing_department
2. {
3.   START_STATE(d):NOT_IN_PRE(YRI_ASSET,department.department_name)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('DELETE.departement.YRI_ASSET',STATE(d))]/'SELECT.department'->
5.     ERROR_STATE(e):IN_POST(YRI_ASSET,stocks.department_name).
6. }

```

Fig. 12: 'YERITH_QVGE' model for the example specification in Figure 11.

8 Conclusion And Future Work

This paper has presented a lightweight C++ Qt-DBus [32] tool to check a program against a runtime monitor using set interface operations (\in , \notin) on program statement: **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** doesn't generate false warnings; **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** specifications are *not desirable (forbidden) specifications (fail traces)*. Since the concurrent communication between **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** and a program occurs over the RPC (Remote Procedure Call) instance **DBus**, a runtime monitor could be checked against programs written in any programming language or framework, as long as they emit the necessary SQL events to **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**.

Future work would be a tool-chain to validate `yri_sd_runtime_verif` models as represented in this paper.

Also, the author of this paper has developed a graphical drawing tool (**YERITH_QVGE**) for in Section 2 defined state diagrams. A model of **YERITH_QVGE** is shown in Figure 12. It is an extension of the FOSS (Free and Open Source Software) Qt Graphviz [33] drawing tool **QVGE** [34]. **YERITH_QVGE** generates, from a model, an input file for the compiler `yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang_comp`.

Listing 4: 'DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY': YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF's overridden method for processing SUT event stream C++ pseudo-code.

```

1  bool DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY(
2      QString sql_table_NAME,
3      SQL_CONSTANT_IDENTIFIER cur_SQL_command)
4  {
5      switch (cur_SQL_command)
6      {
7          case SELECT:
8
9              if ("department" == sql_table_NAME)
10             {
11                 return YRI_trigger_an_edge_event("select.department");
12             }
13             break;
14
15         default:
16             break;
17     }
18     return false;
19 }
20

```

A Processing of SUT Event Stream By An Analysis Client

B YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE

Listing 4 illustrates the pseudo-code of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** SUT event processing method 'DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY'. An analysis client must first override method 'DO_VERIFY_AND_or_CHECK_ltl_PROPERTY' of class 'YRI_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF_Monitor' so to implement a checking algorithm for each event received from SUT, as for instance the events illustrated in Figure 2 of the motivating example.

The analysis client then calls method 'YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(QString an_edge_event)' of class 'YRI_CPP_RUNTIME_MONITOR' of C++ library `yri_sd_runtime_verif` for each corresponding state diagram transition event.

Fig. 13: Grammar in Backus–Naur Form (BNF) of `yri_sd_runtime_verif` Mealy Machine State Diagram Specification Language.

```

<specification> ::= yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec '{' <mealy-automaton-spec> ',' '}'
<mealy-automaton-spec> ::= <sut-state-spec>
                        | <sut-state-spec> '→' <sut-edge-state-spec>
<sut-edge-state-spec> ::= <sut-edge-mealy-automaton-spec> '→' <mealy-automaton-spec>
<sut-edge-mealy-automaton-spec> ::= <edge-mealy-automaton-guard-cond> <event-call>
<edge-mealy-automaton-guard-cond> ::= /* empty */ '/' | '[' <trace-specification> ']' '/'
<trace-specification> ::= <in-sql-event-log> | <not-in-sql-event-log> | <in-set-trace> | <not-in-set-trace>
<sut-state-spec> ::= <start-state-property-spec>
                  | <start-state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
                  | <state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
                  | <final-state-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification>
                  | <final-state-auto-property-spec> ':' <algebra-set-specification> ':'
                  | <recovery-sql-query-spec>
<algebra-set-specification> ::= <in-algebra-set-spec> | <not-in-algebra-set-spec>
<in-algebra-set-spec> ::= <in-spec> '(' <prog-variable> ',' <db-table> ',' <db-column> ')
                        | <in-spec-nop> '(' ')'
<not-in-algebra-set-spec> ::= <not-in-spec> '(' <prog-variable> ',' <db-table> ',' <db-column> ')
                          | <not-in-spec-nop> '(' ')'
<in-sql-event-log> ::= in_sql_event_log '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')
<not-in-sql-event-log> ::= not_in_sql_event_log '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')
<in-set-trace> ::= in_set_trace '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')
<not-in-set-trace> ::= not_in_set_trace '(' <event-call> ',' <state-property-specification> ')
<in-spec> ::= IN_BEFORE | IN_AFTER
            | IN_PRE | IN_POST
<in-spec-nop> ::= IN_POST_NOP
<not-in-spec> ::= NOT_IN_BEFORE | NOT_IN_AFTER
              | NOT_IN_PRE | NOT_IN_POST
<not-in-spec-nop> ::= NOT_IN_POST_NOP
<start-state-property-spec> ::= START_STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
<state-property-spec> ::= STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
<final-state-property-spec> ::= END_STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
                          | FINAL_STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
                          | ERROR_STATE '(' AlphaNum ')'
<final-state-auto-property-spec> ::= END_STATE_AUTO '(' AlphaNum ')'
                                | FINAL_STATE_AUTO '(' AlphaNum ')'
                                | ERROR_STATE_AUTO '(' AlphaNum ')'
<recovery-sql-query-spec> ::= recovery_sql_query '(' <db-table> ',' <sql-recovery-query> ')
<sql-recovery-query> ::= String
<event-call> ::= String
<prog-variable> ::= AlphaNum
<db-table> ::= AlphaNum
<db-column> ::= AlphaNum

```

Fig. 14: YERITH-ERP-3.0 Maintenance Verification Interface.

C YERITH-ERP-3.0 MAINTENANCE VERIFICATION INTERFACE

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SAINT: SIMPLE STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS TOOL

User's manual

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August 30, 2015

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1 Author's Biography

Figure 1: The author Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU

Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU is from CAMEROON and holds the title Diplom-Informatiker [DIPL.-INF.] ¹ (roughly equivalent to a canadian Master's degree in Computer Science) of the **University of Bremen** ² in Germany.

After his Diplom-Informatiker degree, he worked 21 months (November 2007 – July 2009) as Software Developer for **Siemens Healthcare** ³ in Erlangen (Germany).

After **Siemens**, Xavier started his doctoral research in Program Analysis and Software Engineering in the **Watform Lab** at the **University of Waterloo** ⁴ (Waterloo, Ontario, Canada).

From January 2012 to August 2012 (8 months), Xavier worked in the Java J9–JIT compilation team of **IBM Toronto Lab.** in Markham (Ontario, Canada) as a graduate intern in compiler optimization.

Xavier is professionally proficient in the French, English and German languages.

For his DIPL.-INF. degree, Xavier worked on the automatic generation of test cases for reactive systems. The algorithms he developed are used by the German company

¹<http://www.inb.uni-luebeck.de/~boehme/diplinf.html>

²<http://www.uni-bremen.de>

³<http://www.healthcare.siemens.com>

⁴<http://www.uwaterloo.ca>

Verified Systems International GmbH⁵. The title of his diplom-informatiker thesis was "Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems".

Xavier currently works on his PhD degree. His research focuses on program analysis and software engineering. He is the creator of **SAINT**⁶, which is a tool to perform static taint analysis on programs written in the C programming language.

2 Introduction

Businesses increasingly use software. This is even more relevant for companies relying on e-commerce. However, software is error-prone and contain several bugs. Security bugs are one of the major problems faced by companies today. In the worst case, security bugs enable unauthorized users to gain full control of an application.

My PhD thesis introduces the concept of *tainted paths* and describes techniques and algorithms to compute them in any imperative programming language that uses pointers (C, C++, Java, etc.). I implemented these algorithms in **SAINT**.

SAINT does not require the developer to annotate the program under analysis. **SAINT** implements a flow-sensitive, interprocedural and context-sensitive analysis that computes tainted paths in C programs at compile-time.

3 Installation Instructions

This section explains how to install **SAINT** on a "Linux" machine. We haven't tested **SAINT** on a "Windows" or "Mac OS" machine, but the installation should follow similar steps.

3.1 Required Software

This section enumerates all software that you need to run **SAINT**.

- **SAINT**: <http://github.com/xnoubissinoundou/yeroth.rd.saint>
- The compiler infrastructure LLVM, version 3.3: <http://llvm.org>
- The DSA pointer analysis poolalloc: <http://github.com/llvm-mirror/poolalloc>

3.2 Environment Variables

Table 1 that shows all environment variables that you have to define and export in order to successfully run **SAINT**.

✓ You define and export an environment variable **ENV_VAR** by writing the following commands in your "\$HOME/.bashrc" file:

⁵<http://www.verified.de>

⁶<https://www.github.com/xaviernoubis/saint>

Environment variables	Description
<code>SAINT_HOME</code>	SAINT home folder (e.g. <code>/home/user/saint</code>)
<code>SAINT_BIN</code>	SAINT binaries folder (e.g. <code>SAINT_HOME/bin</code>)
<code>LLVM_HOME</code>	llvm home folder (e.g. <code>/home/user/llvm</code>)
<code>LLVM_LIB</code>	llvm compiled libraries folder (e.g. <code>LLVM_HOME/build/Release+Asserts/lib</code>)
<code>LLVM_BIN</code>	llvm compiled binaries (e.g. <code>LLVM_HOME/build/Release+Asserts/bin</code>)
<code>POOLALLOC</code>	poolalloc home folder (e.g. <code>/home/user/poolalloc</code>)
<code>CLANGLLVMLIB</code>	clang+llvm binaries' folder (e.g. <code>/home/user/clang-llvm/bin</code>)

Table 1: Table with all environment variables required to install and use SAINT

```
ENV_VAR=path_to_folder
export ENV_VAR
```

4 How to Configure "clang+llvm" for use with SAINT

- a) Download and unpack clang+llvm, version 3.3.
- b) Add the bin folder to your environment variable `PATH`.
 ✓ For instance by adding the following line in your file `HOME/.bashrc`

```
PATH=$PATH:$CLANGLLVMLIB
export PATH
```

5 How to Configure "LLVM" for use with SAINT

- a) Open the file `LLVM_HOME/lib/Analysis/Makefile` and append the string "saint" to the "DIRS" variable. Following is an excerpt of the file.

```
##===- lib/Analysis/Makefile -----*- Makefile -*===##
#
#                               The LLVM Compiler Infrastructure
#
# This file is distributed under the University of Illinois Open Source
# License. See LICENSE.TXT for details.
#
##===-----##
```

```

LEVEL = ../..
LIBRARYNAME = LLVMAnalysis
DIRS = IPA saint
BUILD_ARCHIVE = 1

include $(LEVEL)/Makefile.common

```

b) Run the script `saint-configure.sh`.

6 Folder Structure

The following folders constitute `SAINT`'s directory structure:

1. `bin`: folder with the scripts:
 - `saint-gen-ir.sh`: generates the LLVM IR for code analyzed by `SAINT`.
 - `saint-run-llvm-opt.sh`: runs LLVM (`opt` binary) with `SAINT` as plugin.
 - `saint-configure.sh`: configures and compiles `poolalloc` and LLVM for `SAINT`.
2. `benchmarks`: folder with sample scripts to run `SAINT`.
3. `cfg`: folder with source, sink, and sanitizer configuration files
4. `projects`: folder with sample projects.
5. `doc`: folder with the manual.
6. `src`: folder with all C++ source files, and Bash scripts to compile and run `SAINT`.

7 How to Compile and Run SAINT

✓ You need to execute the command `"make -f Makefile.saint"` within the folder `"$LLVM_HOME/lib/Analysis/saint"` to compile `SAINT`.

Also, `SAINT` gets compiled when you run it using the Bash script `saint-run-llvm-opt.sh`.

7.1 Configuration Files

Configuration files are found in the folder `"$SAINT_HOME/cfg"`. There are three configuration files:

- `sources.cfg`: taint sources configuration file
 - Each line of the file specifies a function name and an integer `"x"`. `"x"` is the argument of the function that is tainted.
 - If `"x"` is zero (0), then it is the return value of the function that is tainted.

```
fopen,0  
fgets,1
```

The previous lines specify that `fopen` returns a tainted value, and that `fgets` taints its first argument.

- `sinks.cfg`: taint sinks configuration file
Each line of the file specifies a function name and an integer "y". "y" is the argument of the function that must not received a tainted value. "y" is never equal to zero (0).

```
sprintf,1
```

The previous line denotes that `sprintf` must not received a tainted value as its first argument (i.e. `sprintf` is sensible function.

- `sanitizers.cfg`: sanitizers configuration file
`SAINT` doesn't yet implement this functionality.

7.2 How to Run SAINT

Among others, `SAINT` source folder contains the following two important Bash scripts:

- `saint-gen-ir.sh`: this script is used to generate and merge `llvm` intermediate representation (IR) files.
- `saint-run-opt.sh`: this script is used to run the analysis of `SAINT` on the program under analysis.

We encourage users to look at the sample scripts in the folders "projects" and "benchmarks" to learn how to use `saint-gen-ir.sh` and `saint-run-opt.sh`.

7.3 How to Get Debug Messages from SAINT

Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM

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Abstract

Software security vulnerabilities are a major threat for software systems. In the worst case, vulnerabilities in software enable users to gain unauthorized access or unauthorized control of an application. A large amount of software security vulnerability exploits such as buffer overflows, SQL injections, cross-site scripting attacks, etc. are caused by data flowing from untrusted program input sources into sensible program functions. We define a *tainted path* as a program execution path from an untrusted program input source into a sensible program location. This paper presents a static taint analysis that computes tainted paths in C programs and that doesn't require any program annotations. Our static taint analysis algorithm is built upon the iterative dataflow framework [11, 17] and has been implemented in the tool SAINT (Simple Static Taint Analysis Tool). Our static taint analysis is interprocedural, flow-sensitive, and developers can choose to run it either with context-sensitivity or without. We have implemented our analysis using the LLVM compiler infrastructure.

Categories and Subject Descriptors CR-number [subcategory]: third-level

General Terms Software Security Vulnerabilities, Program Analysis, Static Code Analysis, Static Taint Analysis

Keywords tainted path, static taint analysis, static code analysis

1. Introduction

Software vulnerabilities are security threats that exist in an application. Software vulnerabilities allow malvolent users to exercise unauthorized control of the application through supplied input. There are several kinds of software vulnerabilities: buffer overflows, format string attacks, SQL injection, etc. Researchers have worked on dynamic [6, 10], static [2, 4, 5, 9, 10, 15, 22, 25], and hybrid techniques [24] to find security vulnerabilities in software.

This paper introduces the concept of *tainted path*. A tainted path is a program execution path from a program input source into a sensible program location. A tainted path represent a software vulnerability. This paper presents a static taint analysis that computes tainted data and tainted paths in C programs. Our implementation of the taint analysis uses the LLVM framework [12], and does not

require user annotations. Our static taint analysis is flow-sensitive, interprocedural, and developers can choose to run it with context-sensitivity or without. In taint analysis, a *source* is a program location that allows a value from the environment into the program. This may occur through the return value of a system call, user input, etc. A value from the program environment that has not been *validated* and *sanitized* is called a *tainted value*. A *sink* is a program location that uses a tainted value.

Data validation is the process of checking that data has the expected form. For instance, checking that a string input has the format of an email address. *Data sanitization* is the process of checking that validated data is safe in a particular context. For instance, escaping string input before using it in a SQL query. A function that sanitizes application's external input is called a *sanitizer*. Once a value has been sanitized, it is tagged as *not tainted*. In the following, we assume that sanitized data has been validated.

Static taint analysis searches for tainted values and warn developers for each tainted value so they can validate and sanitize the tainted value to avoid software vulnerability exploits at runtime. Taint analysis proceeds by first tagging values from sources as tainted. Once tagged, the tainted values are propagated through the entire program.

Taint propagation is the process of marking values as *tainted* if they result from an operation that involved tainted data. This can be an arithmetic operation (addition, multiplication, etc.), a program assignment or other type of program instructions. Finally, a taint analysis emits a warning whenever a tainted value is used at a sink location. Taint propagation can be *data-flow* or *control-flow* based. Data-flow based taint propagation exists due to data dependencies in the program (e.g. assigning the value of tainted variable s_u to another variable s_d). Control-flow based taint propagation is due to control dependencies (e.g. if tainted variable s_t is used in a branch condition, values from program instructions inside that branch become tainted.). Data-flow based taint propagation is also called *explicit taint propagation*, and control-flow based taint propagation is called *implicit taint propagation*. Our static taint analysis searches for *tainted paths* and implements both control-flow and data-flow based taint propagation.

This paper makes the following contributions:

- It introduces the concept of *tainted path*, which is a program execution path from a taint source to a taint sink.
- It shows that several static analysis problems can be reduced to a tainted path computation problem.
- It describes SAINT, a whole-program static taint analysis that is flow-sensitive, interprocedural and context-sensitive. SAINT computes tainted paths in C programs and is available for download at <https://github.com/xaviernoumbis/saint>.

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ABSTRACT INSTRUCTIONS	DESCRIPTION	CODE IN C	FORMAL DESCRIPTION
ALLOC	Memory allocation	$v = \text{malloc}(\dots)$	$v \in \mathcal{T}$
COPY	Copy instruction	$p = q$	$p, q \in \mathcal{T}$
LOAD	Load instruction	$p = *q$	$p \in \mathcal{T}, q \in \mathcal{A}$
STORE	Store instruction	$*p = q$	$p \in \mathcal{A}, q \in \mathcal{T}$
CALL	Call instruction	$r = \text{call func}(p)$	$r \in \mathcal{T}$

Table 1: LLVM abstract instructions types. In LLVM intermediate representation, \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{T} represent respectively the set of address-taken variables and the set of top-level variables.

SAINT’s taint analysis is sound (i.e. all tainted paths are reported).

To the best of our knowledge, SAINT is the only tool that implements static taint analysis for a static language using the iterative dataflow framework [11, 17]. Please look at Table 7 in Section 6.

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the concept of tainted path. Section 3 introduces our running example, and Section 4 gives an overview of the LLVM intermediate representation. Section 5 presents the taint analysis algorithm, and Section 6 presents experimental results. Finally, Section 7 discusses related work and Section 8 concludes.

2. Tainted Paths

```

1      void mysql_taint(uint); //taint sink
3      uint calculate(uint x) {
4 L1:   uint sum = 0;
5 L2:   uint i = 0;
6 L3:   if (x == 2)
7 L4:     scanf("%d", &sum); //taint source
8 L5:   else
9 L6:     sum = 0;
10 L7:  if (i >= x)
11 L8:    goto L12;
12 L9:  sum = sum + i;
13 L10: i = i + 1;
14 L11: mysql_taint(i);
15 L12: goto L6;
16 L13: return sum;
17     }
```

Figure 1: Code example in three-address format

In this section we introduce the term *tainted path*. We define a *tainted path* as a program execution path from a taint source to a taint sink. Let us consider the three-address code in Figure 1; we represent a line of code with Lx where L means line and x represents a line number. The program path $\langle L4, L7, L9, L10, L11 \rangle$ defines a tainted path while program paths $\langle L4, L7, L9, L10 \rangle$ and $\langle L4, L7, L8 \rangle$ don’t define tainted paths. We postulate that several static analysis problems can be reduced to a combination of tainted paths computation and test data generation. For instance, this is the case for the following static analysis problems:

- Buffer-overflow detection.
- SQL injection vulnerability detection.
- Format string vulnerability detection.
- Automatic test cases and test data generation.

2.1 Buffer-overflow detection

2.2 Automatic test cases and test data generation

Given a tainted path, one can combine *symbolic execution* and *constraint solving* to generate data needed to execute the tainted path. The generated data, along with the given tainted path represent a test case (or an exploit). Developers can then change the code that cause the bug (or vulnerability).

3. Motivating Example

```

1  void func_sql(int); //sink
3  int compute(int x) {
4      int sum = -1;
5      if (x == 2)
6          sum = func_sql(x);
7      return sum;
8  }
10 int main() {
11     int x, y;
12     scanf("%d", &x);
13     y = compute(x);
14     return 0;
15 }
```

Figure 2: Motivating example

This paper uses an example inspired from the example described in [3]. Figure 2 shows 2 functions: `main` and `compute`. In `main`, the function `scanf` from the C standard input/output library gets an integer input from the user at line 3 and stores it in variable `x`. `x` then becomes tainted because it holds a value from the environment which has not been validated and sanitized. `x` is later used as argument to function `compute` at line 4. In `compute`, variable `sum` gets tainted at line 10 through function `scanf`. The formal parameter `x` gets tainted if only if a tainted actual argument was passed at calling sites. This is for instance the case at line 4 in function `main`. Observe that if a tainted parameter `x` is used at the calling site of line 4 in function `main`: this leads to a case of control-flow based taint propagation at line 10 and at line 11 of function `compute`. Variable `sum` also becomes tainted at line 11 because the statement at line 11 is control-dependent of the conditional expression at line 10.

4. LLVM

This section gives an overview of LLVM¹ (*Low Level Virtual Machine*) and its intermediate representation (IR), which we use as

¹ <http://llvm.org>

ABSTRACT INSTRUCTIONS	CODE IN C	GEN-SET	KILL-SET
ALLOC	$s: v = \text{malloc}(\dots)$	\emptyset	\emptyset
COPY	$s: p = q$	$\{p\}$ iff $q \in \text{IN}[s]$	\emptyset
LOAD	$s: p = *q$	$\{t_j \mid t_j = \text{toplevel}(a_j) \wedge a_j \in \text{points_to}_{[s]}(q) \wedge t_j \in \text{IN}[s]\}$	\emptyset
STORE	$s: *p = q$	$\{t_j \mid t_j = \text{toplevel}(a_j) \wedge a_j \in \text{points_to}_{[s]}(p)\}$ iff $q \in \text{IN}[s]$	\emptyset

Table 2: Gen- and kill-sets for the abstract instructions **ALLOC**, **COPY**, **LOAD**, and **STORE**

basis for the description of our taint analysis. LLVM is a compiler framework [12] that contains several components and libraries that help developers in building compilers and compiler tools (e.g. static analyses, etc.). LLVM primarily processes source code written in C, C++, and Objective C. LLVM libraries are written in C++. Table 1 shows the abstract instruction types we consider in the LLVM IR for our analysis. In the following, we present the LLVM intermediate representation. Our presentation is based on the descriptions given by Hardekopf et al. [8] and by Lhoták et al. [14]. LLVM’s IR uses partial static single assignment (partial SSA) and assumes the existence of two types of variables in C code: *top-level* variables and *address-taken* variables.

4.1 Top-level variables

Top-level variables are variables that are never accessed via a pointer in the program code. LLVM converts top-level variables into SSA form when building the LLVM IR. The memory address of top-level variables is never copied to another variable (i.e. they are never applied the address-of operator (&) in the C programming language). In the LLVM IR, top-level variables are only accessed using **ALLOC** and **COPY** instructions. This paper denotes the set of top-level variables with \mathcal{T} . In Figure 2 $b1$, and $b2$ are top-level variables ($\{b1, b2\} \in \mathcal{T}$).

4.2 Address-taken variables

Address-taken variables are never accessed directly through their first declared name. Address-taken variables are only accessed indirectly with pointer variables and **LOAD** and **STORE** instructions. In fact, address-taken variables are those ones on which the address-of operator (&) was applied. This paper uses \mathcal{A} for the set of all address-taken variables. Variable x in Figure 2 is for instance an address-taken variable ($x \in \mathcal{A}$).

4.3 Representation of program expressions

5. Staged Static Taint Analysis

Our taint analysis is interprocedural and runs either context-insensitively or context-sensitively. Any form of the interprocedural analysis is always preceded by an intraprocedural analysis that computes initial taint information that is reused by the interprocedural analyses. The intraprocedural analysis detects taint sources and initializes a summary table which contains taint information about program functions’ formal parameters and return value. The use of a summary table allows fast access to key information about program procedures. This is especially useful during the subsequent interprocedural phases. For instance, the intraprocedural analysis would detect that variable `sum` of procedure `compute` in Figure 2, which also holds the return value of `compute`, may be tainted due to the call to `scanf` at line 12. Figure 3 shows the architecture of our taint analysis SAINT and Table 2 shows the transfer functions for the abstract program statements **ALLOC**, **COPY**, **LOAD**, **STORE**, and **CALL**. These transfer functions apply for the intraprocedural and the interprocedural analyses.

5.1 Taint sources and taint sinks

Program statements that initially taint variables (*taint sources*) are discovered during the intraprocedural analysis, described later in this section. The analysis handles per default a subset of the C standard library as taint sources: `getc`, `scanf`, `gets`, `fopen`, etc. Functions that use tainted variables (*taint sinks*) are gradually discovered during the various phases of the analysis. SAINT has a configuration file where developers can register additional taint source and taint sink functions.

5.2 Taint propagation

SAINT performs *explicit* and *implicit* taint propagation (data- and control-flow taint propagation). Explicit taint propagation tracks variables that are tainted due to assignment statements. The assignment in line 6 of Figure 2 is an instance of explicit taint propagation. Variable y becomes tainted since it gets assigned the return value of `compute`, which is a tainted value.

Implicit taint propagation takes into account tainted variables used in control conditions. In Figure 2 for instance, variable x is passed to the function `compute` as actual parameter as a tainted variable during the context-sensitive analysis. This implies that variables `sum` and `i` becomes tainted at line 15 of Figure 2 because x is tainted and is part of the for-loop boolean condition at line 14.

5.3 Sanitizers

Sanitizers are functions that developers use to make sure that tainted data are safe to use in sensible (or vulnerable) program functions. SAINT creates *kill-sets* whenever a sanitizer is found on a tainted path.

Figure 3: SAINT analysis architecture

5.4 Formalisms

This paper uses the following elements to describe the taint analysis as an instance of the iterative dataflow analysis framework [17]:

Var is the set of all program variables, $Proc$ is the set of all program functions and procedures², $Inst$ is the set of all program statements, $formals : Proc \rightarrow 2^{Var}$ returns the set of formal parameters of a function, $toplevel : \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ returns the top level variable of an address-taken variable, $taint : Proc \times Integer \rightarrow bool$ returns **true** if function f always taints its k^{th} formal parameter, and $aliases : Var \rightarrow 2^{Var}$ returns the alias set of a variable as returned by the pointer analysis.

The analysis dataflow set is $Inst \times 2^{Var} \cdot 2^{Var}$, the powerset of all program variables (Var) is by definition a lattice. In effect, $Inst \times 2^{Var}$ is a mapping from the set of all program instructions $Inst$ into 2^{Var} . $Inst \times 2^{Var}$ is therefore a lattice by definition³

At a statement labelled s , the incoming dataflow set $IN[s]$ is the set of all program variables that are tainted before statement s . If a variable v is not tainted before statement s , then $v \notin IN[s]$; otherwise $IN[s]$ contains v .

The execution of the transfer function at a statement labelled s eventually discover new tainted variables. $OUT[s]$ describes the new set of tainted variables after statement s .

The function $sumTable : Proc \times Integer \rightarrow \{True, False\}$ describes the summary table, and reveals for a procedure $f \in Proc$ and its k^{th} formal parameter whether the k^{th} formal parameter is tainted or not. For instance $sumTable[f][2] = True$ means that the third formal parameter of function f is tainted.

We use ret to represent the return value of a function f . ret is tainted implies that $sumTable[f][ret] = True$, otherwise $sumTable[f][ret] = False$. $points_to_{[s]}(q)$ describes the set of aliases of variable q before statement s .

$read_taint_arg : Proc \rightarrow Integer$ reads

5.5 Handling of pointers

Our taint analysis is designed to work using the results of a previously computed pointer analysis. SAINT uses the pointer analysis DSA (Data Structure Analysis) [13] which is implemented in the tool `poolalloc`⁴. DSA is a field- and context-sensitive pointer analysis. DSA uses full heap cloning (by acyclic call paths) and scales well with programs in a size range of 100K-200K lines of C code. $points_to_{[s]}(q)$ describes the set of aliases of variable q before statement s . Our taint analysis uses the results of a pointer analysis via the function $points_to$ to update dataflow sets.

5.6 Intraprocedural analysis

The intraprocedural analysis always runs first, before any interprocedural analysis, and is responsible for discovering taint sources. During the intraprocedural analysis, program functions are analyzed in the reverse topological order of the call graph (i.e starting from the leaves of the callgraph). The analysis works on each function body and do not take into account interprocedural control flow. The computed data flow sets are reused later by the subsequent interprocedural analyses. In particular, taint information about function formal parameters and return value is kept in a summary table. All variables tainted due to source functions are found during the intraprocedural analysis. In Figure 2 for instance, the intraprocedural analysis detects that variable `sum` in function `compute` may be tainted at line 12 due to the call to `scanf`, which the analysis considers as a taint source. Algorithm 1 shows the flow function for function call statements, which handles the discovery of taint sources during the intraprocedural analysis. Flow functions for all other statement types are same as the ones in Algorithm 3 of Appendix A. Table 4 illustrates the summary table after execution of

² We will use the terms function and procedure interchangeably in the remainder of this paper

³ Please consult the axiomatic propositions that define lattices

⁴ <https://github.com/poolalloc>

input : caller : $Proc, s : Inst, k : Integer$

output:

```

1 switch TypeOf(s) do
2   case CALL [r = call source(a0, a1, ..., an)]
3     k := read_taint_arg(source)
4     foreach vj ∈ points_to[s](ak) do
5       if vj ∈ IN[s] then
6         | OUT[s] := OUT[s] ∪ {vj}
7       end
8     end
9   end
10 endsw
11 foreach fk ∈ formals(caller) do
12   if IN[s] ≠ OUT[s] and fk ∈ OUT[s] then
13     | sumTable[caller][k] := True
14   end
15 end

```

Algorithm 1: Intraprocedural analysis transfer function for CALL statements.

the intraprocedural analysis of the running example presented in Section 3.

	Untainted variables	Tainted variables
main	{ b_1, b_2, y, ret }	{ x }
compute	{ x, i }	{ sum }

Table 4: Summary table after the intraprocedural analysis. ret represents the return value of the function.

input : caller : $Proc, s : Inst$

output:

```

1 switch TypeOf(s) do
2   case CALL [r = call func(a0, a1, ..., an)]
3     if True = sumTable[func][ret] then
4       foreach vj ∈ points_to[s](r) do
5         if vj ∈ IN[s] then
6           | OUT[s] := OUT[s] ∪ {vj}
7         end
8       end
9     end
10    foreach k ∈ {0, 1, ..., n} do
11      if True = sumTable[func][k] then
12        foreach vj ∈ points_to[s](ak) do
13          if vj ∈ IN[s] then
14            | OUT[s] := OUT[s] ∪ {vj}
15          end
16        end
17      end
18    end
19  end
20 endsw

```

Algorithm 2: Context-insentive interprocedural transfer function for CALL statements

5.7 Context-insensitive analysis

The context-insensitive analysis algorithm performs in the topological order of the call graph (i.e. the algorithm runs from the program entry point to the leaves of the call graph). The context-insensitive

PROGRAM (VERSION)	DESCRIPTION	#SLOC	TAINTED VALUES (%)	#TAINTED PATHS	TIME (SECONDS)
mongoose (4.1)	Web server	4k			2.14s
vlc-input (2.1.2)	Media player	16k			0.03s
openssl-ssl (1.0.1f)	Communication Protocol	40k			0.44s
apache (2.4.7)	Web server	144k			n/a

Table 3: SAINT’s taint analysis experiment results

	Untainted variables	Tainted variables
main	$\{b_1, b_2, ret\}$	$\{x, y\}$
compute	$\{x, i\}$	$\{sum\}$

Table 5: Summary table after the context-insensitive analysis

analysis only uses taint assumptions from the summary table to update data flow sets at program points. For instance, the intraprocedural analysis of function `main` marks the return value of `compute` (stored in variable `sum`) as tainted in the summary table. At line 6 in `main`, the context-insensitive analysis would take into account that the return value of `compute` is stored into variable `y`. Thus, `y` becomes a tainted variable during the context-insensitive analysis. Algorithm 2 in the following illustrates the context-insensitive flow function for CALL statements.

The context-insensitive algorithm implements the interprocedural *functional approach* by Sharir and Pnueli [23]. This is evident because SAINT only uses the interprocedural information stored in the summary table during the context-insensitive analysis.

Table 5 illustrates the summary table after execution of the context-insensitive analysis of the running example presented in Section 3.

	Untainted variables	Tainted variables
main	$\{ret\}$	$\{x, y\}$
compute	$\{i\}$	$\{x, sum, ret\}$

Table 6: Summary table after the context-sensitive analysis. `ret` represents the return value of the function.

5.8 Context-sensitive analysis

The context-sensitive analysis algorithm works in the topological order of the call graph, and uses information from the summary table that were produced by previous analyses. Even if the context-insensitive analysis was run before, the context-sensitive analysis eventually writes more precise information in the summary table. At call sites, the context-sensitive analysis propagates actual parameters taint information from the caller into the callee. At callee exits, newly computed taint information are propagated back from the callee context to the caller context. Algorithm ?? illustrates the flow function for CALL statements during the context-sensitive analysis. On the other hand, algorithm 3 in Appendix A presents the full context-sensitive algorithm for all handled type of program statements.

The context-sensitive algorithm implements the interprocedural *call-string approach* by Sharir and Pnueli [23]. The call-string length in SAINT implementation is 2, which means that 2 is the depth at which context-sensitive calls are made. It also means that SAINT only analyzes the first two calling contexts of a recursive procedure. Developers can specify longer or shorter calling contexts. We have implemented the call-string approach in SAINT using recursion, as illustrated in lines 10 – 12 of Algorithm ?. Table 6 illustrates the summary table after execution of the context-sensitive analysis of the running example presented in Section 3.

5.9 Arrays and C structures

6. Experimental Evaluation

We evaluated our taint analysis by attempting to detect format string vulnerabilities of `printf`-like functions in four different open-source C programs (`mongoose`, `vlc`, `claws`, `apache`). In the C programming language, *format string vulnerabilities* happen a call to a variable-length function has an incorrect number of arguments. For instance, a call such as

```
printf(buf); // format string vulnerability
```

may cause the program to crash because the function `printf` expects its first parameter to be a format string. For instance `printf("%s", buf)` would be a correct call. For this experiment, the taint analysis emits a warning whenever a format string vulnerability is encountered, or whenever a tainted variable is used in a sink function (e.g. `snprintf`). We ran the analysis on an Intel i7 @ 3.4GHz with 4 cores and 16 GB of RAM, running Debian Linux. Table 3 shows the analysis results of the taint analysis, ran in the following order: intraprocedural analysis, context-sensitive analysis, and context-insensitive analysis. The first column of the table entails the program name and its version in parenthesis.

We could not get the taint analysis running on the `apache` web server because of a crash happening during initialization of the DSA points-to analysis. We note that the analysis of `vlc-input` (the input module of `vlc`) with only 16k LOC requires more analysis time than `claws` which has 144k LOC. We believe this is due to the high amount of tainted values within `vlc-input`. Because of the high amount of tainted values, the analysis spends more time when checking if a value (argument of call) is tainted or not. We believe that our current implementation performs in an acceptable time, since the developer has to wait for a maximum of 56 seconds for a project with around 140k lines of code.

7. Related Work

There has been a lot of work in the area of taint analysis and its applications. This section presents some taint analysis-based projects that rely on static, dynamic, hybrid analysis or symbolic evaluation.

7.1 Static analysis for vulnerability detection

`Parfait` from Oracle Labs checks for bugs in C programs [5]. `Parfait` is built on top of LLVM and uses a demand driven analysis to mitigate scalability issues inherent to standard forward dataflow analysis techniques. `Parfait` does not require annotations from developers and is advertised to scale to millions of lines of code. For security vulnerabilities, `Parfait` implements a taint analysis [21] as pre-processing filter that is linear in the number of statements and dependencies. `Parfait`’s taint analysis is formulated as a graph reachability problem. `Parfait` implements both a context-insensitive and a context-sensitive solution for its taint-analysis, and adds a may-function alias analysis to LLVM to better support the accuracy of the taint analysis. Similarly to `Parfait`, SAINT may also perform either a context-insensitive or a context-sensitive analysis. SAINT is also based on LLVM, and do

```

input : caller : Proc, s : Inst, k : {1, 2, ..., n}, cnfMax : {1, 2, ..., n}
output:
1 switch TypeOf(s) do
2   case COPY [p = q]
3     if q ∈ IN[s] then
4       | OUT[s] := OUT[s] ∪ {p}
5     end
6   end
7   case LOAD [p = *q]
8     foreach aj ∈ pointsto[s](q) do
9       | tj := toplevel(aj)
10      if tj ∈ IN[s] then
11        | OUT[s] := OUT[s] ∪ {tj}
12      end
13    end
14  end
15  case STORE [*p = q]
16    if q ∈ IN[s] then
17      foreach aj ∈ pointsto[s](p) do
18        | tj := toplevel(aj)
19        if tj ∈ IN[s] then
20          | OUT[s] := OUT[s] ∪ {tj}
21        end
22      end
23    end
24  end
25  case CALL [r = call func(a0, a1, ..., an)]
26    if caller ≠ func then
27      foreach fj ∈ formals(func) do
28        if False = summary[func][j] then
29          foreach vj ∈ pointsto[s](aj) do
30            if vj ∈ IN[s] then
31              | OUT[s] := OUT[s] ∪ {vj}
32            end
33          end
34        end
35      end
36      if k < cnfMax then
37        k := k + 1
38        csInterFlow(caller, func, k, cnfMax)
39      end
40      foreach fj ∈ formals(func) do
41        if False = summary[func][j] and OUT[fj] ≠ IN[fj] then
42          summary[func][j] := True
43          foreach vj ∈ pointsto[s](aj) do
44            if vj ∈ IN[s] then
45              | OUT[s] := OUT[s] ∪ {vj}
46            end
47          end
48        end
49      end
50    end
51  end
52 endsw

```

Algorithm 3: csInterFlow: Context-sentive analysis algorithm

TOOLS	LANGUAGE	REQUIRES ANNOTATION	TECHNIQUE	AVAILABILITY	APPEARANCE YEAR
PARFAIT [20]	C, C++		Graph reachability algorithm	Commercial	2008
COVERITY	C, C++, Java		?	Commercial	
FORTIFY	C, C++, Java		?	Commercial	
VERACODE	C, C++, Java		?	Commercial	
TAJ [25]	Java		Program slicing	Commercial	2009
PIXY [9]	PHP		Iterative dataflow framework	Research	2006
FLOWDROID [1]	Java (Android)		IFDS framework	Research	2014
CQUAL [22]	C	✓	Type system	Research	2001
STAC [3]	C	✓	Type system	Research	2009
* SAINT	C		Iterative dataflow framework	Research	2015

Table 7: Static taint analysis tools for security vulnerability search

not require any annotations from developers. It is not possible to use a third party alias analysis with `Parfait`. In contrast, `SAINT` users have the possibility to change the pointer analysis library it uses.

`Pixy` is a tool that statically scans for cross-site scripting vulnerabilities in PHP scripts [9]. `Pixy` implements a flow-sensitive, context-sensitive dataflow analysis. `Pixy` also creates and uses an alias and literal analysis for PHP.

Livshits et al. present a tool for finding security vulnerabilities in web applications written in Java [15]. The tool is based on `bdbdbdb`⁵, which automatically generates context-sensitive program analyses for specifications written in `DataLog` [27]. `bdbdbdb` uses binary decisions diagrams to represent and manipulate points-to analysis results for different contexts in a Java program. The authors implement taint propagation on top of the points-to analysis results generated by `bdbdbdb`. In effect, developers specify vulnerabilities in the PQL language [16], which is a syntactic sugar for `DataLog`. That is, each vulnerability specification corresponds to a set of PQL queries.

`CQual` by Shankar et al. detects format string vulnerabilities in C programs [22]. `CQual`'s analysis is based on type qualifiers [7] and type inference. Given a C program, an initial subset of the program is annotated with the type qualifiers `tainted` and `untainted`. `CQual` then uses a set of inference rules to generate type (qualifier) constraints over the program. Pointer reasoning is done via some rules of the type system. The analysis then warns the user of a format string vulnerability whenever the program does not type checks due to an unsatisfiable constraint. According to results published in [22], `CQual` performs on average 85s for a code base of 20k lines of code, and takes 268s to analyze the largest program of 43k. In contrast to `CQual`, users of `SAINT` may experiment with different pointer analysis libraries and choose among them. `SAINT` also do not require any annotations.

FLOWDROID [1]

TAJ [25]

7.2 Dynamic analysis for vulnerability detection

TaintDroid

`DyTan` is a framework that generates dynamic taint analyzes for x86 binaries [6]. `DyTan` does not need access or recompilation of program source code. Developers specify an analysis by giving taint sources, taint sinks, and a propagation policy. Taint sources can be variable names, function-return values, and data read from I/O stream (e.g. file, network connection, etc.). Taint sinks are specified by memory or code location. Sinks can also be based on usage scenarios (e.g. perform a check before execution of jump instructions). Clause et al. report performance overhead up to 30 times for data-flow propagation only. The slowdown goes up to 50 times for combined control- and data-flow propagation. In contrast, `SAINT` is used during the development phase and does not incur any performance slowdown during program execution.

`TaintCheck` by Newsome et al. implements a dynamic taint analysis that relies on runtime emulation of programs [19]. `TaintCheck` is implemented as an extension of `Valgrind` [18] and detects vulnerability exploits at the time tainted data is used by the program. `TaintCheck` does not require access or special compilation of application source code. The analyzed program is instrumented at runtime, and the taint analysis code allocates a data structure for each identified tainted data. Each allocated data structure records a copy of the tainted data, a snapshot of the current stack, and a system call number when the tainted data originates from a system call. Each byte of memory (e.g. registers, stack, etc.) has a four-byte shadow memory that stores a pointer to a tainted data structure if that memory location is tainted or a NULL in case of an untainted location. The paper argues that `TaintCheck` is able to detect previously unknown exploit attacks, and automatically create corresponding signatures. `TaintCheck` is meant to be an emulation container for a running application, and thus incurs some performance overhead. The authors of `TaintCheck` reports slowdown of up to 40 times for their benchmark programs. On the other hand, `SAINT` is meant to detect vulnerabilities during the development phase of an application, does not incur any performance overhead at program runtime.

`Libsafe` 2.0 by Avaya Labs is a library that detects and avoids some instances of format string vulnerabilities [26]. `Libsafe` operates in three steps: interception, safety check, and violation handling. The installation of `Libsafe` automatically redirects all calls to functions of the C standard library to their equivalent `Libsafe` functions. Once a function call is intercepted, `Libsafe` checks call arguments and either executes the original C function (e.g. `sprintf`), or calls its safer alternative (e.g. `snprintf`). `Libsafe` applies a special handling for functions `IO_vfprintf()` and `IO_vfscanf()` on which all other `*printf` and `*scanf` func-

⁵ <http://suif.stanford.edu/bdbdbdb>

tions rely. For these two functions, Libsafe checks that the associated pointer argument of each %n specifier do not point to a return address or frame pointer. Libsafe also checks that all call arguments of the function are contained within a single stack frame. If any of these checks fails, then Libsafe found a violation. Libsafe handles violation by terminating the running process. There are few exceptions where Libsafe may authorize further execution of the process. For a proper behavior, Libsafe 2.0 requires special compilation of programs and usage of some specific C libraries. The paper does not report the performance slowdown incur by Libsafe usage.

7.3 Hybrid analysis for vulnerability detection

[24]

7.4 Symbolic execution for vulnerability detection

ARDILLA by Kiezun et al. is a tool that uses concolic execution to automatically create input leading to SQL injection and cross-site scripting attacks for web applications written in PHP [10]. ARDILLA does not require any annotations. Developers define a time limit within which ARDILLA attempts to create input data that exercise security vulnerabilities present in the application. For that, ARDILLA uses an input generator to create new input for the application. During application execution, the input generator records path constraints that capture the control-flow paths taken by that specific execution. The input generator then automatically and iteratively creates new input data by negating the obtained path constraints. The web application then runs with the newly created input data and flows along program paths different from previous executions. The input data generation continues until all program paths are covered or the time limit set by the developer exceeds. During program executions triggered by the input generator, ARDILLA tracks tainted values. More importantly, ARDILLA also tracks tainted values that are stored into the database. That is, tainted values stored into the database are also marked as tainted at their retrieval.

8. Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented SAINT, a whole-program static taint analysis that is flow-sensitive, interprocedural and can be run either with context-sensitivity or without. SAINT computes tainted paths in C programs and is available for download at <https://github.com/xaviernoumbis/saint>. SAINT's taint analysis is sound. To the best of our knowledge SAINT is the only tool that implements static taint analysis for a static language using the iterative dataflow framework [11, 17]. The staged nature of SAINT makes it suitable for integration in integrated development environment (e.g: Eclipse, Anjuta, etc.).

A. Complete Algorithm

In this section, algorithm 3 shows the full pseudo-algorithm for the context-sensitive analysis described in Section 5. Only the handling of the CALL statement is specific to the context-sensitive algorithm. All other flow functions are common to the intraprocedural and context-insensitive analysis, both described in Section 5 as well.

Acknowledgments

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Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

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Winter 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 9.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

Fall 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: **04/30/2015**

Milestones

Program: **Engineering Doctoral**
 PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: **Completed**
 Date Completed: **12/20/2011**
 Grade: **CR**

End of Graduate Official Transcript

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Ontario Education Nbr: 445938806

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

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Winter 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 9.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

Fall 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: 04/30/2015

Milestones

Program: Engineering Doctoral
 PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: Completed
 Date Completed: 12/20/2011
 Grade: CR

End of Graduate Official Transcript

NOUMBISSI Noundou [PR. PROF. DR.-ING.], XAVIER

PROFESSOR PROFESSOR DOCTOR-ENGINEER (DISTRIBUTED & OPERATING COMPUTING SYSTEM — CONSTRUCTION & ANALYSIS & VERIFICATION & VALIDATION)
CONVICTIONS ABOUT CIVIL SOCIETY

- "Datou, **KEMAJOU**" Cameroonian's gendarmerie colonel indic PAULETTE AZEFA tried to ASSASSINATE myself, openly, in front of at least 7 people, on Yaounde street, on January 09th, 2024.
- Kemajou spouses talk to people walking across roads that they shall't perform christian cross-signs since these interrupts sorcery they are doing on people walking on roads (June 3rd, 2024).
- Secret (hidden) orders of any type SHALL be out of civilian society.
- Cameroonian SHALL DEACTIVATE any kind of army soldiers estate, as SWITZERLAND has done in the past.
- Its not a good idea to judge people based on suspicious behavior, and not, real proven or not lived really facts.
- ROSE sangoun, a BIRTH GIVER of mine, SHALL'NT ANYMORE be causing so much trouble into my life because she entertains a rosiocrucian affair with Prof. Dr. rer. pol. JEAN-CLAUDE SHANDA-TONME; AND with 'DORIS betebug Gweh', 'tchoutchui-teutchou-noumeni-ingrède-ingrid-Chandriandri', 'Hugues Ntomani Tiako'; 'Dr. Henriette Pola', and her spouse "Dr. Laurent tchandeu".
- People such as KEMAJOU, who acts as a colonel gendarmerie of Cameroon army ARE ALWAYS TRYING to overcome criminal laws of Geneva.
- I don't want to be living with people who has as profession the killing of other people.
- Rose sangoun sister, (Justice) DOROTHEE SHANDA NDJATIE, HAS TRIED to kill me by police force illegally in February 2021, as I have a file on judge HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA at DOUALA-ndokoti JUSTICE Palace ! • LAQUINTINE'S Psychiatrist EYOUN CHRISTIAN, MD, was involved together with 8 other persons at night around 11 : 30PM so to hijack my privately owned property in Douala-CITE-DES-PALMIERS. • JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMAI from same tribal tribe as ACCUSED psychiatrist main offender (sawa-douala) ! • IT SEEMS "Dr christian eyoum, MD" the corrupted CPDM psychiatrist wanted myself to be sodomized by "BERTRAND" who broke the seal of my gate in steel.
- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shall'nt hire anymore incompetent persons like "Peter Alan Burth" Emmanuel; baleba-faux-pasteur "Brigitte-ekindi" magne-narcisse-qc-satan "robert-billy-joe-bob-tabet-depse-pd" NDZIE "PRC-présidence de la république du Cameroun" "CHAPELLE DE LA GLOIRE DE CHRIST - marc denis djeng djeng - alias pasteur marcou" "jp-kamgain" "psy-acteur-Ebongue (ing. pétrolier)" "EMMANUEL-idiot; hors-mis agent-immobilier-soumbil (6 90 60 75 63)" "santaire;SAPEUR-POMPIER-de-malheur-anti-gang;civil;indic-gendarme-policier-uniforme-medec" "NORBERT tchatat" "Bitoungi (douanes)" "David Moniaux" "Aurélie Yagno Kamdoum" "DR. FOSSO-séd" "Soot-canadian" "sarah-landy-canadian-citizen" 'tchangoue-labforge.ca' "carine-alias-edith - LEBE - NJOUGE - TCHANA" "Julien-mboutou; santé publique" "Dan Wasula doua" - so called pastor baptist church "KAMGA adamo - demon" "Cameroon-chief-of-state; CAMEROUN:" "SANDRINE yimbu" "CHENGWA" "DJOMO-Sawa-gilles-échéliel" "dioti-ruben" "mama-fouda" "INES ngakou" "Serge Achille Popoussi NONO - sed - cmr" [ingrède-tchoutchui-noumbissi;ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi;ingrède-teutchou-noumeni;ingrid-teutchou-noumeni]; [NROUWANG] (djome) [TCHUHDJANG-séd-pré] [NGONGANG] "assassins;délingués." "LAURENT-tchandeu-henriette-pola" "VOUFFOU manuela-psy-malade-mentale" "alain-elame" "Francis magloire come nkoulou" "ZOUUMPE-jacky-diane" "Pélagie METOUM, epe tchoutou; hors-mis maître Pélagie METOUM, epe tchoutou" "BIYA (Paul et Chantal en particulier)" "DAMLERCHRYSLER AG" "Belvianne meleu nossi" "Jean LOÏC sieve" "GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl" "maman THÉRÈSE de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël." "rigobert; géomètre; JEAN-bernard de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël." "Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA; hors-mis maître Synclaire SCHULZE-SMIDT" "Franck biya" "M. onguéné (S2TBED-biya-franck)" "David (GATE SOLUTION CENTER)" "KREYENHOP (BLG logistics, CDU politicians)" "Achilles Kouam (PAUL fokam kammgone)" "Thierry Nyamen (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)" "catholic-church" "Criminal-DST;" "MOISE-yamkam-tebiwo" "REZA kopae (riskview inc.)" "Thomas NDIE DJOTIO" "Christelle-akamba-et-autres-noms-de-akamba" "VALERIE" "ALT LE PLUS" "Nestor KENPACK (N.K. quincallerie)" "atanga-nji-paul" "Daniela-siemens-OCS-erlangen" "Menguéné Mvindi" "TCHOUFFA" "Audrey NGUETTE tchanga" "MBA-Claude bisseg" "samaneh navabpour; amirhossein vakili" "JHANE-ayachi" "ZABER-algérien-bremen" "DZUKOU-tate-foiso-viviane" "ROSTAND-moungam" "KOM-marcel-rostand-mepo" "Irene-ines-ngakou-temou-FAINEANTE-suisse-bordelliere" "VANELLE-JUNIOR-laure AZEFA-gang" "GODRICK chekete H." "pasteur Landry" "Eric Joël KOM SIPA" "Grégoire Owona (CPDM general secretary)" "SANGO (Spouse Bernadette NOUNDOU(CMR-dgre)" "gendarme essono en civil (loga-loga-aurelien)" "GÉNÉRAL DE CORPS D'ARMÉE boubou." "consortium-conrad-black-ROTHSCHILD" "GALAX-YVES-LANDRY-ETOGA-chien" "jean-yang-CMU" "HOGA-HOGA-AURELIEN" "BORIS tossou; mbuembe-kevine-laure." "mezang-atome INGRID." "TOM ball-msr" "maître-docteurs-professeurs." "JEAN-pierre moubé" "Chef-supérieur-douala.deido.-3ème degré" "CHRISTIAN eyoum; laquintine; psy" "SHANDA NDJATIE" "MAXIME napoa eteme" "sandy-séd-beidu; jo-ate" "joanne atmé" "chauffeurs-souders-souffleurs-gardiens-jaune-SARL-société" (a so called baptist church pastor) Dr. PAUL SIMON nomo, Psy.D. "Majeed Mike (quantstamp.com)" "LEO passos (quantstamp.com)" "Iuc; masc. hypolithe tekeu." "Eunice GAPIE Yemte" "Yves Francis DANTEU" "TEUNTCHOU-chandriand-noumeni" "Winnie-shanda-joël..." "Alexis TCHEUYA" "Gervais Nana" "JEAN CLAUDE SHANDA TONME" "JACKSON-séd-njeutcha (Conquete.)" "Jean-Paul YAMTICHE (Afriand first bank; Intelligensia)" "BISSACK; nkondo-sodomiseur" "JEAN-PIERRE kamgain" "Bernadette NOUNDOU, Epe SANGO (cmr-dgre)" "agent-santé.-Gaëlle-idiote-dodo;" "RAOUF Prince njonkep (SED)" "ERIC BODEN" "Prof. Dr. Xavier Siew Noundou (CMR-dgre)." "M. André Édouké" "Michèlle mvondo-psy;biya-régime" "JULES neta noundou -cmr-dgre)" "temp FABRICE-WILFRIED-siemens-canadian-armed-forces;" "Prof. Dr. med. Norbert SIEMENS (CMR-séd)" "Pharmacy fiango-ngoe-peter-AKUME" "Ondréj Lhoták" "Dr. Chantal NOUNDOU, Epe ... (cmr DGRE)" "ANNIE METIAM" "terreur - ;HONORÉ WOUCHE" "POKAM-KWAM" "Serge, jérusalem apostolat" "NOUMBISSI" "Guimezap" "GEORGETTE" "Victor Noundou Koliou cmr-séd" "CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong" "Hilaire-yimido-bertrand-nguere; ancien-séd-grav-savoys" "igc-clovis-telecom-assassin;" "CLOVIS-kemmege" "Jeanne MVONDO" "CHETA" "rodrigue-alain-sienchie-ngongang" "angela WOLFGANG fernand JR owona" "fanfan (GAUTHIER) SHANDA tonme" "DR. GADJEU francis aimé tchana" "lute" "Patrick lam, Ph.D., P.Eng." "JON eyolfsson" "Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Jan Peleska, Patrick"; ALL-others to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.
- People like PAUL BIYA shall'nt be called president of all Cameroon anymore because as CPDM ruling party, they harass people that don't call themselves from RDPC!

CONTACT

- Address: YECEFOIQ - "Immeuble YERITH"- barrière - Simbock, Mfoundi 6, Yaounde, Cameroon
- located opposite side of Biya's S2TBED forestry society (since 2015 officially) !
- Email: Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com

CITIZENSHIP ; PLACE OF BIRTH

Cameroonian , no other citizenship ; Douala (Littoral, Cameroon)

UPLOADED a copy of national id (N.20190242230510554) onto "https://www.facebook.com" this year 2024.

TEACHING STATEMENT

- [Teaching] and [Advising] is my priority at time since in Cameroon Software inception is very long and tedious because Cameroon authorities, Especially SED.
- My 1st professor and best educator is [prof. dr. rer. nat. habil. JAN-peleska], at the University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany; The 1st best teacher as of now was "prof. dr. ULRICH KRAUSE-dépse, at the University of Bremen; as well"; THE 1st best leader & 2nd best teacher as of now was "Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick] Lam, at the [University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA]".
- I endeavor to teach what makes my research vivid ["RM: Program Software Runtime Monitoring"] and useful for young and adult people around the world; I can teach almost everything in Computer Sciences; I haven't practiced Computer Graphics, and Computer Imaging programming at all.

RESEARCHING GOALS IN COMPUTER SOFTWARE ENGINEERING - [CONTINUED]

- Create a very cheap and pragmatic Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) software: (e.g. [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM\[?\]](#)).
- CREATE a market place where stock exchanges occur real-time; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME] is used as platform for valuation of stocks; And for stock exchanges. THE market place is a physical place in "YERITH-R&D building"; THE physical stock exchanges occur outside of "YERITH-R&D building"; just a plot of land '5 meters' away on the opposite side of road leading to "YERITH R&D" !
- CREATE a computing device for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that would be a certified product with at least ISO, and CE stamps : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]; See also Fig. 22.

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING ASSOCIATIONS MEMBERSHIPS

- Current: "acm: The Association for Computing Machinery"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING LITERATURE REVIEWS

- OOPSLA 2010

PROFESSIONAL INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOPS AND CONFERENCES

- IMRT radiation therapy at SIEMENS OCS Erlangen-BAVARIA-Germany 2008; [FSE-soqua 2006]; PLDI 2009; IBM CASCON 2010; MITACS ONTARIO 2012; PLDI 2012

PROFESSIONAL RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS / INTERESTS

- [JUDICIAL information] | [PUBLICATIONS] | [Figures] | [Tables] | [Trang] | [TALKS] | [Latest] | [Resume / CV - Overview] | [Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise] | Publications list on "www.zenodo.org"
- Operating System Debian Linux Distribution Contribution for customers of "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"; "YERITH-NISSI". Bash; DEBIAN LINUX; Jan. 2017 -
- ERP-trading Stock Exchange Software: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0> C++; Qt 5; Mar. 2015 -
- Software Engineering-Formal Methods [?][1]C / Software Validation / Software Verification CASE tools [MBT\[1b\]](#)]
- Software Testing [22.22] (also with "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH" .) [JUNIT 4 Tutorial\[1\]](#)]
- A. Web [JAVA Dynamic Taint Analysis\[3\]](#) | Qt 5-Designer as WYSIWYG Tool | Development (YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0) | Cyber-Safety | Security
- 1. JudoDB, with "Dr. Patrick Lam (doctor-Ph.D. advisor of mine)" ; <https://github.com/patricklam/judodb> GWT, PHP; JAVA; June 2014 - Nov. 2014
- B. [WEB Cyber-Security\[2\]](#) [?] [3] [?] (PLG SEMINAR AT DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)
- C. Information Flow Policy Control; Typstate-API usage rule checking; [Dynamic Program Analysis Monitoring](#)
- 1 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; June 2022 -
- 1 [YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of \[GUI\] Software at Runtime](#)
- FOSS Code location, EXCEPT for commercial CASE drawing tool : <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> C++; Qt-Dbus; June 2022 -
- 3 <https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis> JAVA; Firebug; Jan. 2013 - Apr. 2013
- D. [Static Program Code Analysis Verification; Compilers; Verifiable DSL \(Verifiable Domain-Specific Languages\)](#)
- 20.20 Open Source (FOSS) Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; https://github.com/yerthd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; July 2023 -
- 1d [Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata](#) Set-Algebra; Sep. 2004 - Dec. 2004
- 34 <https://github.com/AmesianX/saint> LLVM; C++; JAVA
- 1d https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; Apr. 2023 -
- 32 [Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software](#) LLVM; SOOT; JAVA

SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION — HIGHLIGHTS — [CONTINUED]

- "Management Psy Human Resource Course" - Collège Integ, Douala, Littoral, Cameroun — Taught by "Dr. Jean Moubé, Psy.D." Jan. 2020 - June 2020

CHEIFTAICY / MISCELLANEOUS

- KING YERITH-NISSI. (Prophet of Jeovah-nissi, "Isaiah 45" (SINCE nov. 14; 2014) in HOLY BIBLE, PAROLE DE VIE-(Amis pour toujours) - French language)
- I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 12".
- I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 1", named "Fidèle, et Véritable".
- Creator and Professor at YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), a subsidiary of YERITH R&D
- "High Qualified Person-migrant in CANADA (Québec, then Ontario) for 9 years until August 2014".
- Driving license class B - Cameroon & Canada

PROFESSIONAL TOOLS AND PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0, MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** YRI_QVGE[13.13], UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, VALKYRIE YERITH[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming & Compiler Frameworks:** DIFF, Patch, Tx1, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

UNIVERSITY LEVEL TEACHING (AS A TEACHING ASSISTANT PH.D. CANDIDATE; THEN A "DOCTOR-PHD")

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (OCTOBER 2009 – APRIL 2015)

- **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Compilers (ECE 351) | [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)].**

ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 1

- **Start-up YERITH R&D, Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON** March 2025 – Currently
PROFESSOR PROFESSOR DOCTOR-ENGINEER (PR. PROF. DR.-ING.) for Computer Engineering ([RESEARCH] & [TEACHING]), at YECEFOIQ, CEO
- **IUC (Institut Universitaire de la Côte), Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON** 2019
Web Software Developer Consultant (NUMERHIS-ERP Web Application Development); advised by Hypolithe Tekeu, MASC
- **IAI (Institut Africain d'Informatique) Cameroon, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON** 2016
Professor (Prof.) – Consulting Lecturer (Computer Architecture for Software Engineers in anglophone section); advised by: Ing. (B.Sc.) Salabessi (and Mr. Nanga)
- **Professional and Academic Degree [Ph.D. in Computer Science (Specialization : Programming Languages)]** March 10, 2015 !
University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA
PhD Comprehensive Examination (DR.-ING. (PhD)) – ECE-University of Waterloo December 20, 2011 !
PhD Research Seminar [TALK] – ECE-University of Waterloo April 16, 2014
PhD Dissertation Defence (Ph.D.) – CS-University of Waterloo January 2015
doctoral "Ph.D. degree" dissertation (Excerpt of Full not required text, by Patrick LAM, Ph.D.): *Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM*
(December 12, 2025) Addendum of co-related research in Program Analysis: *Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software by Program Analysis FOR Safety & Security* (<https://zenodo.org/records/10990601>)
- ★ **The University of Waterloo (ECE at WatForm), Ontario, CANADA** September 01, 2012 – March 10, 2015
Professor (PostDoctoral Fellow; Prof. – Expert in a domain of science) for Computer Engineering ([RESEARCH] & [TEACHING]) at ECE (program analysis & software testing research, and teaching (also related courses) | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 8 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.
"Graduate-student 1: Divam Jain (CS-MMATH, JAVA-SOOT) | Graduate-student 2: Zheng (Felix) Fang (ECE-MASc, Divam's research continuation) | [ALL STUDENTS]"
"Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Igor Ivkovic | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Vijay Ganesh | Advisor 3: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Sivoththaman Siva"
"Colleague 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Colleague 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naem | Colleague 3: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Fabrice Wilfried Siemeni | Colleague 4: Pr. Prof. Dr. Godrick H. Chékété | Colleague 5: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. mahesh tripunitara | Colleague 6: Pr. Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside | Colleague 7: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. LEO passos | | "Colleagues in christianity (Prof. Dr. Yaw Boakye-Agyeman, Nana Yaw, Eric Brefo-Mensah, Chiwanza Kasanga, Mushota Kasanga and spouse Timi) – -ATTENDED "koinonia church in bloomingdale, ON"; "apostle continuation church in brampton, ON"."
- **IBM CANADA Ltd., Markham, Ontario, CANADA (SABBATICAL-year from The-University-of-Waterloo-Ontario-Canada.)** January 01, 2012 – August 31, 2012
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer IBM Canada LTD before starting employment.
Graduate Intern (JAVA-J9 Just-In-Time Compilation Optimization for IBM Websphere); advised by Prof. Vijay Sundaresan; and Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam
- ★ **PROFESSIONAL (AND ACADEMIC) DEGREE. Doctor of Engineering (academic equivalent to a "doctoral PhD in Electrical and Computer Engineering") [D.ENG. (DR.-ING. in "French")] | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 7 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.**
Engineering Doctoral Ph.D. degree Program (Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD) at The University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011 !
► **"DOCTOR-ENGINEER [DR.-ING. (D.ENG. in "English")]" degree Program (Specialization : Software Engineering & Testing & Verification & Analysis)**
► **Successfully Passed PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011" – Overall Grade 88% [A+] Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering (ECE)**
Research Proposal (doctoral Ph.D. Thesis in Electrical and Computer Engineering): *Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software*
Mathematics Subject Classification: 68—Computer Science
Computer Science Subject Classification: Software Engineering, Program Verification, Program Analysis (static code analysis, dynamic program analysis)
Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naem | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Advisor 3: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- **The University of Waterloo (ECE at WatForm), Ontario, CANADA** September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011
Teaching Assistant & Research Assistant for Computer Software Engineering (program analysis (static code and dynamic analysis) research, and teaching assistantship in computer software engineering); Advised by Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, and Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- **Post-Master Work with SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), Erlangen, Bayern, GERMANY** November 01 2007 – July 31 2009
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer "SIEMENS AG" before starting employment.
Software-Engineer (Junior Software Developer) (CE-FDA certified software code development; Radiation Therapy DMIP communication control protocol C++ development); advised by: Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAVALIA, and Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG.
- ★ **PROFESSIONAL (AND ACADEMIC) DEGREE. Diplom-Informatiker (academic equivalent to a "Master 2 in Computer Science"; 270-ECTS points) | around \$400 Euros for a semester payment; 11 semesters including GERMAN language courses time included.**
I HAVE SACRED this diploma certificate ("Duplicate by Prof. Dr.-Ing. UTE bormann and Prof. Dr. Kerstin Schill; from November 01, 2017)" in front of BISHOP at St-Patrick Church in Toronto-downtown, ONTARIO, CANADA; just 3 weeks after resigning my shit-CANADIAN CITIZENSHIP at KITCHENER-WATERLOO criminal justice court [Living in Salvation Army Shelter near Justice Court.].
Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree in Computer Science Program at The Elite-University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY October 01, 2002 – May 25, 2007
► **"DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER" degree Program (Specialization : Software Engineering & Testing) – Grade 1.6/4 [A+] Department of Mathematics and Computer Science**
Diplomarbeit (Master Thesis): *Statistical test case generation for reactive systems* | Advisor: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- **AGBS at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** September 01, 2006 – February 28 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (A 'UML 2.0 profile statecharts' plugin for 'Borland-Together'); advised by: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- **"IMMIGRATION CANADA delivers myself a High Qualified Person-migrant permanent residency for CANADA"** 2005
FORMER-family member in Canada : "Théodore Wandji Ngongang (5850 Rue Souart Apt 7, H3S 2E8, Montreal, QC, Canada)"
I already passed my Bachelor's degree in CS ("Vordiplom in Informatik Certificate") before gaining High Qualified Person Permanent Resident Card
- **Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY** March 01, 2005 – April 31, 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (WERKSTUDENT) (JAVA servlet and C++ communication protocol development); advised by: Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH (and Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER)
- **ZMML at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** February 01, 2003 – February 28, 2005
(Part-Time) WEB AND "RAD" APPLICATION DEVELOPER (Creating websites, and RAD-server self tests evaluation programs); advised by Prof. Dr. rer. pol. Klaus Jürgen Bönkost

CONVICTIONS ABOUT CIVIL SOCIETY – CONTINUED – 2

- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shalln't hire anymore incompetent persons like 'Jeanne-chantal andela;vendeuse-sauvette.' 'nguema;huissier-de-justice;tchopba' 'churches; in USA-abroad; or whatsoever similar; so-called humanitarian.' 'road-seller; seller anywhere else' 'relatives' 'agent' 'SOLITA-voisine-sed' 'IRIS Mbieukop; pof.' 'agent-ministère-défense-cameroun.' 'MARTIAL takala; DELAURE takala' 'JEAN LOUIS ROSTAND mougam; et associés' 'YVES mogo' 'henri-bertrand-ngatchou (Best Car Care & SERVICES)' 'YAGER MABOMA; to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.

		SCHOLARSHIPS & AWARDS
• Ontario Graduate Scholarship (OGS; 4000–\$CAD per term)		2009 – 2015 (a total of 15 terms)
		FREE TIME HOBBIES
• Aikido, Swimming, and "Gospel Choir 'GEORGIA MASS CHOIR'" listening.		
		ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 2
■ HABILITATION, equivalent ♦ Topic: "Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime" Start-up YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON Proposal: YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (Details at link 1)		June 01, 2022 – Currently
■ Start-up YEROTH R&D, Yaoundé, CENTER region, CAMEROON Software Verification & Validation Fellow, CEO		October 2018 – November 2023
■ Start-up Yeren Labs, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO		September 2017 – September 2018
■ Start-up Yeren, Yaounde, CENTER region, CAMEROON CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO		April 2015 – August 2017
× [PKFokam Research Institute, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON] Professor (Prof.) Ph.D. secker (Static Code Analysis Research from WATERLOO.); advised by: [Dr. PAUL fokam kammogne], & [Dr. Ing. JUSTIN bomda]; [and M. Samuel DIMITE] "JAN-peleska" & "University of Waterloo" try to hijack myself through this 2-days-job-contract [All people pro-eminent persons I have seen at his banks, "including Deceased gay-pd GERVAIS mendoze", are in prison !!! (419–scam)]		
■ Judo–Québec, Montreal, Quebec, CANADA (Part–Time) Web Development Consultant (JAVA SE 7, GWT, PHP) for JUDODB; advised by: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam		JUNE 2014 – NOVEMBER 2014
■ RiskView Inc., Toronto, Ontario, CANADA Software Consultant for Finance Software Security (SCALA servlet development for Finance); advised by: Reza Kopae, M.Sc.		January 2013
■ We4IT GmbH, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Software Development Internship (J2EE, MySQL web application for medical personal training management); advised by Dipl.–Inf. Stephan Sucker		June 2005 – July 2005
■ SGS Cameroon, Douala, littoral REGION, CAMEROON System administration internship (Computer networked installation; employee desktop technical support; (MS Windows NT, MS Windows 2000, etc.); advised by CHENGWA, & ...)		September 2004
■ bremen4u GmbH, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Web development internship, System Administration (MySQL, RedHat linux, JSP, PHP, HTML5, CSS); advised by Martin, B.Sc.		March 2004
■ IWT at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY (Part–Time) Student Metal Processing & Measurement Helping Scientist; advised by: Dipl.–Ing. Sven Bengelsdorf.		October 2002 – January 2003
■ DaimlerChrysler AG, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Industrial Chain Worker (Kfz–Schlosser Helper); setting of Mercedes personal cars seat belts		June 2002 – August 2002
■ Briel & Kjær, Technology Park – University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY (Part–Time) Student Helper (event management); advised by: Dipl.–Pol. Torben (and Dr. Woehring)		July 2002 – September 2002
■ Cyberix, Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON Web Development Internship (HTML, CSS); advised by: Ing. Fogueum (and Théodore Wandji Ngongang)		October 2001 – November 2001
■ GCE A Level in Exact Sciences; BACCALAURÉAT C (Mathematics, etc.) Grade of "11.59 / 20" Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		2000
■ GCE O Level in Exact Sciences; PROBATOIRE C (Mathematics, etc.) Grade of "12.09 / 20" Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1999
■ B.E.P.C (Brevet d'Études DU PREMIER CYCLE) Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1997
■ C.E.P.E (CERTIFICAT D'ÉTUDES PRIMAIRES ÉLÉMENTAIRES) Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1993

PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION LANGUAGES

- | | |
|---|---|
| • FRENCH, and ENGLISH | CAMEROON; NATIVE |
| • "GERMAN DSH LANGUAGE CERTIFICATE", Sehr Gut (Very Good) | April 2002 (UNIVERSITY OF DORTMUND, DORTMUND, NRW, Germany) |
| • "ENGLISH USA TOEFL–IBT", Grade 86 | June 2018 (Hamilton, Ontario, Canada) |

[SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION] – ADDENDUM

- | | |
|---|-----------------------------|
| • "Online Software Security Course" – Stanford University, California, USA | June 2013 – August 2013 |
| • "CUT 1 – Certificate in University Teaching1" – University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA | 2010 |
| • "First Summer School on Formal Techniques" – NSF, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA | May 22, 2011 – May 27, 2011 |
| • "Graduate Student English Training Course" – Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Montreal, Quebec, Canada | Aug. 2009 |
| • "Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) Preparation Course" – Concordia University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada | June 2007 |
| • "C Programming Language Preparation Course" – UY 1, ENSPY, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon — Taught by "Master–1 Mr. Donfack (ENSPY)" | Aug. 2001 – Sep. 2001 |

5. **CREATE** a software component full-featured that enables ERP-stock data import using a technology Kind-of VOICE-to-text !
6. Create a framework that allows for formal method specification of static dataflow analyzes as temporal property verification formulas;
Such a framework generate code software as static staged dataflow analyzes for its users.
More importantly, I will try to reuse previous work done for [YRI_QVGE\[13.13\]](#) research work, as part deliverable.
7. TRY to integrate research results on software security in "YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum "; from Vijay GANESH research (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>); MOST possibly using "SDMM".
8. Automatic generation of web HTML pages from a Domain Specific Language (DSL) that is more approachable for a high level programming language perspective (i.e: similar to C++ / JAVA): YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0[27.27].
9. Create and render software analysis, debugging, and testing tools as easy as possible to use, with only finite automata theory background; and / or Typestate-API usage rule checking typestate-API knowledge (e.g.: [YERITH-SAINT\[34\]](#), [SDMM\[1d\]](#), [YRI_QVGE\[13.13\]](#), VALKYRIE-VALGRIND[20.20]).
10. Prepare a course on "Software System Security Vulnerability Detection and Analysis". I prepare this course material so to implement a software system for protecting other software from malware.
11. Create a stand-alone software product that enables medical physician to augment their efficiency in terms of patient work flow throughput : 'yerith-sante-organigramme'
Even Dr. Christian EYOUM find this utility-tool very impressive in terms of effectiveness & simplicity if this could be really in his world (PSY) implemented !
12. Create a stand-alone tool that generates code for creating statechart C++ code for mealy machine state diagram ([SDMM\[1d\]](#)).
This tool is specifically created and programmed for generating code that uses checkboxes to select options for Graphical User Interface [GUI] code.
13. Position "static dataflow analysis research and techniques" as similar as runtime verification (i.e.: circle 4 in Figure 18; e.g.:PH.D. THESIS[32], [YERITH-SAINT\[34\]](#)).
14. Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an CE—ISO—related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE—ISO certifications for Healthcare : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

1.1 CAMEROON new country name based on CHRISTIANITY-jesus-of-nazareth-NAME-and-TRIBES-number

Changing CMR onto YERITH as country name since JESUS-OF-Nazareth utilizes 12 237 as number of tribes for its ISRAEL tribe.

2.2 National Currency BILLS and / or COINS

- CMR YERITH NATIONAL Money currency as 'YERITH-dollar ("JESUS-OF-Nazareth"-dollar)'.

THIS money currency bill and / or coin system will be backed by computing systems from YERITH R&D; AS open-sourced products :

- 1.) YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME; A software-system product created out of Enterprise Resource Planing Software YRI_QVGE[13.13.7] that is also usable as an algorithmic trading system !

3.3 National Identification

1. A system allowing any of the 3 documents cited below as valid official identification for any official or unofficial activity shall be implemented in Central CEMAC:

1. Valid NATIONAL IDENTITY CARD
2. Valid PASSPORT CEMAC—CEDEAO
3. Valid bank account id.
4. ALL PERSONS working with weapons or force by law have to be identified with names on badge wherever they are outside of their working places.

A bank account id IS in effect linked to a Valid national identity card.

""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" for instance, a cousin paternal "French—germain" of mine, Could afford for a law school with a bank account that wasn't really linked with his by birth official IDENTITY documents !"

MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87) also possesses a diplomatic passport at least or equivalent because he also works for MINREX.

IN effect, "MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" was a diplomat before joining the LAW-school in LAGOS—corrupt.

I could notify this since the law school of lagos he attended didn't issue for a certificate with exact same official birth identity names as written thereof.

THIS COUSIN OF MINE IS A CRIMINAL in all systems of justice worldwide.

2. 1 system, computerized, and / or, a text registry book shall be created to register any Cameroon citizen with no need for any citizen to walk around with a national identity card.
3. There are some drawbacks as for instance mentioned on the website of FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION, in the United States of America (USA), to have a centralized registration system for citizen or People living inside a country !
4. "A gervais nana (gersatelgmail.com)" I know somewhere in YDE, seems to be connected as a free-mason to ""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO"" .
"GERVAIS NANA" must be investigated since I know "TEBIWO—YAMKAM—MOÏSE" Is a murderer in all systems.
5. I remember having an issue with a screen of a laptop I bought to a place (GERSATEL) owned by "Gervais NANA" ; after 1 day, A blur appeared on the screen and I wasn't reimbursed.
6. It seems "WELADJI" a burglar that I went with at Gendarmerie D'AKWA—SUD in 2023 because he apparently tried to steal 20, 000 FRANCS as a non used money for a purchase item that I ordered from his shop at DLA—douala—bar;

"WELADJI" WAS NOW in position in another shop where I started buying stuff for my customers. "Moubeb-Jean" is working just at opposite side of this computer hardware shop in Douala: "COLLEGE INTEG".

7. "ISAAC TEUNTCHOU-poltron-peggist" , a father in law of 1 uterine sister of my person; "Ingride NOUMBISSI TCHITCHUI (heiratet (SPOUSE): Dipl.-Ing. (FH) CHANDRIAND Teuntchou Nouneni, MSc.)" is trying to hijack from my propriety all my real-estate.
8. ~~shanda tonne jean-claude; bob tabet-peggist-Deido-plage-poisson-braisé, (the idiot that sleeps with rose-sangnou my genitor; AND with her sister Dorothée shanda owona " (LEVITICUS 20 : 12 – 14)."~~
"OLAMCAM (tel.:6 52 12 65 57 --georges-kamdem) (peggist working in Douala shipment-haven) owner Tabet-bob (OWNING a house in "bonaberi"; money from bribery in ONTARIO according to JP-kamgain sayings) & friends GEORGES-kamdem; & JP-kamgain; they have tried to sodomize myself with Christian-eyoum-c.p.d.m [by trying to say to JP-kamgain-to act as a friend-of-myself]. "
"BOB-tabet is an ancient jail-black-attendee of ONTARIO justice system that escaped Canada by talks I heard [of KAMGAIN].""
"[Culprit-JP-kamgain] told me once [TABET-ROBERT] wanted HR-module payment services for his employees in DOUALA.'
9. ISAAC-teuntchou, the idiot that sleeps with his daughter-in-law; TEUNTCHOU-nouneni-chandriand is currently trying to hijack my property of DLA-cité-des-palmiers-beedi, BY Sending INGRID to my attorney of law so to try to say that SHE wants some money from my current ongoing rental agreement with a so called MELEU-belvianne, AND her fiancée called SEWE-idiot-toie.

10. "Audrey-NGUETIE-tehamga" shalln't anymore go and seek people from my former places of work to try to tell them I abandon her after 1—night.

THIS disgusting megere wasn't capable of understand I cannot be fornicating with someone that Cannot imagine herself as a wife in a non-gay homosexual matrimonial house AS i could observe from her gay—white-salsa friends & sister "YOLLANDE-nguetie married at that other senegalese in Montreal

"TCHAMAHA ntaata GUTTEMBERG" & "Remi POUASSI-taata" who are my blood-family (father-theo-chien-noumbissi-batchieu—babouantou) cousins & 'also blood-village people of MAURICE-nguetie' & 'Audrey-nguetie-tehamga; SHALL know that Homosexuality is a disease from a BORN—again christian point of view: ITS cure is living without any sexual encountering as proclaimed in " 1 Corinthians 7 : 1 " & " 1 Corinthians 7 : 38–40 " !

11. When you say to your children not to open a door when a child of you senior or whoever arrives at your home when you are not there; YOU—victor should think that you were coming to my house when I was aged under 7 years old.

YOU should think that never my father or my mother said that to you. IT means you were may be trying to kill someone in that marriage; AS you are coined today by ROSE who told me not to eat anymore from your household !

12. VICTOR-koliou-serpent—Tchandeu-gay thinks he is linked to myself by my late father; I Have already told this culprit & wretched canadian-traveler as a assassin that could be even arrested just at airport; Like I was faultily arrested by canadian-faked police so to destroy my luxurious image !

THIS criminal worldwide, since he even called before I attended 3 days & nights at his junior-est brother DEMO—noundou house in Hamburg—Germany; to say that Demo could even not even respond to any call of myself because I did not notify him—demo when I was leaving Cameroon.

There is a fake idolatry—people like "bamileke" demo & tchandeu-family-noundou; That if you want to attend a living at someone place, you must call onto him before you arrive. THIS kind of guja—assassin—diplomat schizophrenic-idea is in fact to listen to calls & organize fake routes with spies everywhere so to dictate how your daily life shall look like !.—MVONDO.

Following items from previous page; JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

9. Multiple or DOUBLE citizenship **SHALL NOT be allowed** since Africans are not well behaved to use and observe strict rules that are due to protect civilians with only 1 citizenship appurtenance.
10. Double citizenship with following countries that harasses honest Cameroonian like myself shalln't be allowed:
- Canada
 - United States of America (USA)
 - Germany
 - Any country where a gay-homosexual-marriage is pronounced in a so-called **"JESUS-OF-NAZARETH"** congregation: I.E: such a country shall be considered a scam **"(LEVITICUS 20 : 12 – 13, and Romans 1 : 26 – 28) !"**

SIMPLICE-kameni and alike people must be imprisoned.

HJACKING properties and down-casting businesses of elite-intellectualist from abroad like myself and others I may not even know about is what make them have a life luxurious around C.P.D.M and SED-yves-landry-galax-etoga-idiot; so called secret-services.

" THERE is also another "negger" working on behalf of simplice-kameni as LEAD of the so-called-cocaine-reseller wood-factory S2T-BED, called IDIOT-repeating-christian-signs; that behave like so-called "TONTON-makout' in HAITI-movies; (<https://wwwurl>) YOU see this kind of people that kills under behalf of a politician like BIYA; AND that you cannot even prosecute because there is no whereabouts of his origins or identities here in Cameroon-official-Communaute-URBAINE-de-YAOUNDE. "

" !! ALSO this biya-cpdm-gang against a proper african descendant on AFRIKA-soil Has a motto: ABSURDITY !!! "

FACTS:

1. kill where life is supposed to be saved;
Example: USE your own blood-giver to hijack your life and properties [REFERENCE.]

HOSPITAL is used to destroy lives.

2. destroy where it is supposed to be killed;

POLICE and ARMY kill people that go to them for seeking help after being robbed or whatsoever here in AFRIKA;

so called **UNITED-nations** (<https://www.un.org>) are only a replacement for colonies by white-supremacists.

- IT seems it is cameroon-cpdm-people who are UNITED nations workers here in CMR; HERE.

4.4 JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

1. [~~Dr. PAUL Siméon nomo, from MONATÉLÉ came to my private house in YDE-AAHALA, to arrest illegally without any notification or whatsoever, using a firefighter truck and 3 firefighter to molest myself in front of several neighbors so to discredit my life as a peaceful citizen of Cameroon.~~]
~~HE seems this criminal assassin from BIYA private places is now living in Maryland, USA; since I went back to Canada to resign from CANADIAN shit citizenship.~~
 Another cousin of mine so called "~~Rodrigue Alain Sienchie~~", told me that 1 day armed soldiers with uniforms came to arrest him in the house of his parents, sent by "~~Dorothée SHANDA-NDJATIE OWONA~~"; THEN went to sodomized him at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL.
 "SO I SUSPECT this criminal ~~LAURENT TCHANDEU-DJATIE DOROTHÉE OWONA~~ to have sent to my private house in Yaounde in 2017 this 'so called baptist church pastor Dr. SIMEON NOMO, PSY.D.'."
2. "~~Eyoum Christian~~" idiot's immunity of justice because he is a psychiatrist Must be investigated !
3. '~~S2TBED~~', finally repairs our main common road: They destroyed a previous road with LATERITE so much that IT must be fixed with concrete !
4. '~~S2TBED~~', biya's illegal industrial forestry enterprise society, an illegal neighbor of "Immeuble YERITH" of mine, IS constantly disrupting electrical energy current supply.
5. ALL my real estate in Douala (3 3-bedrooms apartments) need to be released by a genitor of mine THAT is not anymore wanted in my life because of all atrocities SHE CONSTANTLY commits with SHANDA GREGROIRE OWONA Wolfgang TCHAMOU angela ndjatie. !!!
 SISTER'S of Rose Sangnou my genitor, Dorothée Shanda Ndjatie, IS CONSTANTLY harassing her to take me to any psychiatric institute by force, Even though there is already a criminal investigation against her and Rose Sangnou at DLA-ndokoti justice palace; DOROTHÉE is a criminal PERSON !
6. 'MADO's brother CAPTAIN pierre marcellin emana nkoa' must reimburse back my 210 000 FRANCS since SEMIL (Sécurité Militaire) told me in 2016 THAT THEY CANNOT convoke them SINCE receipts were signed by his cousin "JEAN-DE-DIEU onana".
 "MY NEIGHBOR CARINE LELE NJOUGEPE TCHANA", seems to be here because of them, so to deteriorate the quality of life of legal people living here, and promote their own-beings through propaganda LIKE 'it seems THE colonel living THERE above of the hill IS the one that FIXED the road leading to your compound !
7. JUSTICE FOR BREAKING AND torturing myself (Xavier noumbissi Noundou [DR-ING. PR. PROF.]) in front of at least 17 people in front of my inherited personal domicile in Douala-Béedi-Cite-des-Palmiers MUST be finalized before Cameroon election 2025.
8. 'JUSTICE president and certain types of judges must be apolitical: I.e.: THEY CANNOT BELONG TO A POLITICAL PARTY !
9. MARTINEZ ZOGO assassin AMOUGOU BELINGA justice criminal court must be finished before Cameroon election 2025.
10. PEOPLE responsible for the drama of Edea Railway Failure in .. MUST be judged in a civil criminal court before Cameroon election 2025.
11. MILITARY SOLDIERS that killed about "7 women and their teddies in north Cameroon must be judged."
12. "EDGARD ALAIN MEBE NGO'O" criminal procedure in military justice courts must be achieved before Cameroon election 2025.
13. Military Soldier must have their own facilities and amenities in cities, and not mixed intermingle anymore with civilians, AS THIS IS CURRENTLY THE CASE when they DON'T wear military attire uniform !
 In fact, MILITARY SOLDIERS or Alike don't have a same behavior justice as civilians; Not talking about habits and gesture.
14. Bepanda drama because of 'general MPAY' must be re-recovered in a justice palace court of civilians and / or military justice !

5.5 ACADEMY and Technology Research Institutions

1. Promote creation of research centers for solving problems located specifically in central west Africa:
 1. Another source of revenue for CMR
 2. Improving life conditions for CMR and neighboring friend countries.
2. Enable a financing WITH non reimbursement option for doctors in science and / or engineering.

6.6 Employments and JOBS creation for adult people

1. THERE must be a minimum amount of jobs offer for each society that was funded by the government for researching and improving life quality in CMR and neighboring countries.
2. *WOMEN that are selling goods outside of their home like "CAROLE mangue" (la fille de "MA-bernadette" au secrétariat-d'état-yves-idiot.) shalln't be part of SED or any governmental secret or not agencies !!!*
THIS culprit shall also try to not resell goods that were illegally imported into CMR.
3. ALL PEOPLE that were trained by the BIYA-regime as illegal para-military personal, MUST go into peace-keeper corps organization of the UNITED NATIONS or somewhere else so to keep cities and villages free of fire and all other destructive people.

FOR instance people like "PASCAL dayang", working at "S2TBED" of the culprit franck-biya has insinuated to myself that HE will disrupt any business activities that I-doctor-of-engineering Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU will perform in my compound !!!

["S2TBED"- "PASCAL dayang mercenary SED soldier" as threat in CMR !!!]

4. Transform all wood factories within city of YAOUNDE in computer desktop and / or laptop assembly production units

7.7 JUSTICE and DIVINITIES

1. *Destruction of all secret services units in Cameroon !!*
 1. "OUATARA people shall not anymore be opponent to christian people here in Cameroon as it is the case with Shanda-TONME jean claude" presently.
 2. People like SHANDA OWONA harass other people because they feel as safest as possible because of some kind of impunity based on their appurtenance to DGRE special unit forces ("JEAN CLAUDE shanda tonme and spouse" weren't for instance infringed in DLA-NDOKOTI palace for breaking into my compound, closed at night, with around 9 burglars; So called Technicians of "PSY-laquintinie"; around 23 : 30 at night while I was sleeping IN february 2021 in DOUALA).
 3. Politicians shall be reduced to be people applying criminal and civil laws instead of people trying to make their own ideas come through via ENTERING private life of people like "Shanda TONME jean claude" has done in the past 30 alike years with my personal family and life ('Family NOUNDOU michel', and 'Family JEAN NGONGANG') !
 4. 'SEMIL' and special alike units of Cameroonian army shall be dismantled because of reported proved or not really ATROCITY facts.
 5. 'SEMIL', 'DGRE', 'SED', etc.; all former people wearing weapons shall be displaced into military caserns so to avoid mixing MILITARY alike people with civilians !
 6. IMPUNITY of all people wearing weapon must cease with tribunal applications of criminal laws.
2. *Create an electoral public and common website for all information, and / or official application documents for all elections in Cameroon !!*
3. *Create a website for publication of all laws in Cameroon; including presidential decrees, acts, and / or acts, and so on ...!*
4. *Reforming judicial system with computer software digitization so to PROMOTE equity and justice by laws !*
5. *EACH CITIZEN or person living in Cameroon SHALL officially declare its lifestyle philosophy and / or religion at a 'Chefferie De Block' when moving inside that area of the city !*
 - a. This enables to solve issues based on this declaration in a fairly manner; according to a new reformed judicial criminal law system !
6. *PROHIBIT any type of religious or associations that don't have well openly presented and written codes of laws, Abiding to CAMEROON criminal laws !*

8.8 TRANSPORTATION and CITIES transportation

1. *Reduce airplane travel costs between cities in Cameroon.*
INSTANCES:
 - a. {DLA → YDE} with one way at 12 000 FRANCS.
 - b. {YDE → BAFOUSSAM} with one way at 18 000 FRANCS.
 - c. Etc..

9.9 Technology And Development

1. *Schooling shall be created and managed to be in harmony with Religious, and / or Philosophy lifestyle of parents that intend to have children in a school; BOTH primary and secondary.*
UNIVERSITIES could mix students of all horizons: so the student and leaders of next Coming Cameroon could learn how to live harmoniously.
2. *State schools for civil servants shall be banned in favor of UNIVERSITY education and of an additional training on the job when hired !*
3. *Universities shall be autonomous and not depend anymore of the PRESIDENCY OF THE REPUBLIC*
4. *Create an industry for solar electrical energy with cars and buses as consumers in a lapse of time of 12 years starting 2026.*
5. *Assemble DIGITAL computers in Cameroon in less than 12 years of presidency.*

10.10 MARRIAGE and INTER-PERSONAL sexual corporal Relationship

1. *PROHIBIT sexual actions IN OUTDOOR by laws.*
2. *REMOVE TRADITIONAL SYSTEM of justice because of its unfairness; Based on WOMAN precedence in power:*
 - a. *SINCE Christians don't need to marry to a woman or any gender, as described in 1 CORINTHIANS 7 : 38 – 39 !*
 - b. *SINCE people could stay without marriage, In Christianity, marriage is THE EXCEPTION, But not a sin;*
 - c. *Any person that is not married and that is a born-again Christian cannot be managed by a married person ! THIS is because A MARRIED person couldn't qualify to understand a life at a certain level as He is living constantly with another gender !*
 - d. *People that have marriage in traditional system normally cannot undergo a civil marriage in a christian church (I.E: TRADITIONAL system allows for Impudicity, Which is prohibited in Christianity !).*
 - e. *Born-Again Christians don't marry at all in any type of marriage !*
 - f. *"SHANDA-TONME jean claude's first and last son": Late (justice of attorney) "Me. Shanda Sanou Cabral Patrice" was apparently killed brutally since his body was missing from people assisting SHANDA's family for obituaries.*
 - g. *"HIS (jean-claude shanda-tonme) OBITUARIES in next coming years must not be public since He hasn't been a good citizen for at least hundreds of young cameroonian" that I have hear about for the last 12 years since I started by immigration process back to my homeland country Cameroon of C.P.D.M-R.D.P.C !*
3. *Automatic Splitting OF INHERITANCE after parental death between children:* Because there are a lot of troubles to leave this task to a family with not enough money for paper and bureaucracy work at notary justice palaces !
4. *LEGALIZE homosexual UNION.*
 - a. *People in this union cannot have children adopted from another non-homosexual union at ALL; AND VICE-VERSA for couple married in non-homosexual life style !*

11.11 MUNICIPALITY Reform (AND WASTE and DISPOSAL of garbage)

1. *chefferie de block: This administrative territorial unit is based on traditional tribal lineage ! THIS SHALL BE ENDED AS EACH CITIZEN is subject to the same civil law:*
 1. *currently, a 'chefferie de block' is based on common and traditional law. Since common law has precedence over tribal traditional law, A CITIZEN living must be subject only to COMMON CIVIL LAW where he is living, OR NOT.*
2. *There shall be created AN INDUSTRY for recycling and displacement of waste-garbage USING ecologic burning container:* Each "chefferie de block" shall have its own burning destroying waste-garbage ecologic container.
3. *There shall be at least 1 municipal playing and recreational area of at least 400 m² in each city quarter ("quartier").*
4. *There shall be at least 1 municipal library in each city quarter ("quartier").*

- UNITED STATES OF AMERICA (U.S.A)

- 1.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), CONCORD, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (JANUARY 2008)
- 2.) SRI International, MENLO COLLEGE, MENLO PARK, ATHERTON, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (May 2011)

- CANADA

- 3.) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ON, canada 2009 – 2015
- 4.) MITACS ONTARIO, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, CANADA (October 2012)
- 5.) IBM CASCON 2010 (IBM CENTRE FOR ADVANCED STUDIES CONFERENCE), Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham, Conference Centre, Markham, ON, CANADA (November 2010)
 I attended this conference to present "my doctoral thesis in a simple manner that could be defended in front of several researchers worldwide" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); With different backgrounds; As well as practitioners from IBM toronto software laboratory in MARKHAM (<https://www.ibm.com/ca-en>) .
- 6.) PLDI conference (Programming Languages Design And Implementation), Toronto, ON, CANADA (November 2009)
- 7.) Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) PREPARATION COURSE, CONCORDIA UNIVERSITY, MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (June 2007)
- 8.) Graduate English Training Course, UNIVERSITÉ DU QUÉBEC à MONTRAL (UQAM), MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (AUGUST 2009)

- GERMANY

- 9.) UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY 2001 – 2007
- 10.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY 2007 – 2009
- 11.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), HEIDELBERG, BADEN-WÜRTTEMBERG, GERMANY 2007 – 2009

This section reports and summarizes our current and actualized knowledge on the subject of software licensing.

20.20 SOFTWARE LICENSes

- o "Summary of MOSTLY used software-licenses":

[Software ~~Hardware~~ Certification authorities; "O.H.A.D.A"; CENELEC; CE; ISO; "A.R.I.N.C"]

Table 1: Software LICENSes summary table.

SOFTWARE license type	Peculiarities	Uses	URL for legal writing specification
1. "CSCS : Close Source Code Software"	Software / Programs AUTHOR exclusive copyright & ownership	YOU use only a binary.	Each retailer provides this on a case by case request.
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			

- CSCS : Close Source Code Software (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- Open source code software (OSS (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)) :

- OTHER forms of free software license (FOSS (<https://www.wikipedia.org>))

- APACHE-BSD license (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- APACHE
- ["BSD"]

- GNU licenses : (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- GPL
ANY software that uses this piece of whole source code and / or binaries have to also be licensed GPL.
- "Lesser GPL - LGPL" ✓
Program binaries could be used in a commercial project without any request and / or payments to the owner of the source code. Modifications of the source code follows certain rules specified as follows :
 - 1.) Mention of the authors have to be explicitly written in headers of code sources as directed by rules explicitly sampled at following URL : (<https://>).
 - 2.) YOUR own using software source code must also abide to the LGPL GNU software license according to what is written at following URL : (<https://>).

- BERKELEY-style license (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- BSD

- MIT-license; "also called AS-IS-no-warranty-AT-ALL" (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- MIT ✓
THIS kind of Open-Source Software (OSS) programs is provided in a state that no reclamation could be done because it could be very tedious to determine liabilities between parties such as a provider, and a customer and / or client.

The so-called MIT License are part of the AS-IS no-warranty code; ALSO all GPL typed licenses in general.

Programs using AS-IS no-Warranty code software licenses generally stipulates either following text, OR similar surrounding text around following :

- o ["The program is provided AS IS with NO WARRANTY OF ANY KIND, INCLUDING THE WARRANTY OF DESIGN, MERCHANTABILITY AND FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE."]

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

21.21 Documents for certification for "YERITH R&D" software – hardware PRODUCTS engineered in AFRICA–main–land

Table 2: *Design Documents* for the CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool YERITH_QVGE.

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

Table 3: *Design Documents* for the Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF].

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

Table 4: *Design Documents* for the Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

A personal computer tablet for SIMPLIFYING runtime monitoring on–the–fly

Figure 20, Figure 21, and Figure 22 illustrates a sample product usage of the toolkit YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that permits and allows for its users following actions and tasks to be solved fluently :

1. Send tracing logging for a developer and / or engineer trough 1 of the following communication interfaces :
 - 1.)

- 1.) *Design Documents Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification;*
- 2.) *USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);*
- 3.) *Module Description (Module Functional Specification).*

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

22.22 TOOLS used for Qualification AND / OR Certification of Software-hardware PRODUCTS at "YERITH R&D"

Table 5: Tools used for Qualification and / Or Certification at YERITH R&D.

TOOL	VERSION	Uses	LOCATION
1. "BUGZILLA (https://www.bugzilla.org)"	"N.A"	Bugs and Defects registration & following-up.	
2. "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (https://www.gnupg.org)"	2.2.27-2	Digital signing check-in source code & documents.	
3. "Git (https://www.git.org)"	1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2	COMMIT, and following-up source code for certification authorities.	

Table 5 illustrates some programming and / or debugging tools I use at YERITH R&D for developing certified products with "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)", etc.; Certification organizations :

- o **Bugs and Defects Management Software** : "BUGZILLA (<https://www.bugzilla.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current BUGZILLA software installations" : "N.A".
 2. "Location of BUG report-free database website URL" : "www.digital.ocean.com/YERITH_QVGE_HTTPS_url (<https://www.digitalocean.com>)".
 3. "Location of BUGZILLA software installation" : "Intern to YERITH R&D".
- o **Software for electronically signing (e.g.: Source code, Design Documents, etc.)** : "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (<https://www.gnupg.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current GNU Privacy Guard-GPG software installations" : "2.2.27-2".
- o **SCM (Source code Management) software** : Version Control Management Software : "Git (<https://www.git.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current Git software installations" : "1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2".

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

23.23 Yerith_QVGE Legal Software and/or Hardware CERTIFICATION Artifacts

- o "Yerith_QVGE Legal Software CERTIFICATION Artifacts":

- YERITH_QVGE DESIGN AND TESTING SYSTEM[13.13] : A product for qualification; CE.

23.23.1 "CERTIFICATION Tools used at YERITH R&D"

[Certification TOOLS.]

23.23.2 "PRODUCTS for Engineering And/ OR Finance Engineered Computing"

- 1.) YERITH_QVGE software design CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“June 2022” – Currently]

Figure 1: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

- 2.) YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET ; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“Nov. 2024” – Currently]

Figure 2: A screenshot of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL error event log running on YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.

Figure 3: A sample YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET in action.

THIS hardware computing device, WITH software that uses "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could be used for "on-the-fly" runtime verification monitoring & Recovering manifold :

- One connects YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET to either an Ethernet network connection, or serial interface communication port RS-232, and / or Universal Serial BUS-USB interface port ;

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (a screenshot is found in Figure 2) is started on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET", and connects to specified processes, on the attached connected other computing device (E.g.: in Fig. 3, a control console for "Siemens-LINAC"); In a configuration panel. THE open source version of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) is a bit different of the non-free upgraded version installed on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET".

This section reports and summarizes all efforts needed as far AS I could learn and experienced as seasoned software developer at "IBM-toronto-software-laboratory"; And at "Siemens-medical-solutions".

24.24 Years of experience as Software Developer for Legally APPROVED products

o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact":

- **YERITH_QVGE LEGAL documents for Qualified Products from AFRICA—main—land.**
- **[SOFTWARE licensing.]**
- **"Communauté Économique et MONÉTAIRE de l'Afrique Centrale – (C.E.M.A.C)" (<https://www.cemac.int>) :** THIS central Africa certification applies for Accounting and Finance.
 - I.) **"O.H.A.D.A (<https://www.cemac.int>)" ; for "FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE"**
- **TüV-Nord (<https://www.tuv-nord.com>) in North-West GERMANY :** This german authority in Science and Engineering reflects better our initial commitment as a **"DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]**, even before a **[MASTER-OF-SCIENCE]** degree was created at the **UNIVERSITY-racist of Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)**.
 - A.) **"CE - EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en)" ; "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)" ; "FDA - FEDERAL DRUG ADMINISTRATION (U.S.A) (<https://www.fda.gov>)" for "MEDICAL SOFTWARE"**
 1. **Bugs and Defects** are to be managed by a software such as **"IBM-CharmNT (<https://www.ibm.com/us>)"** ;
 2. **Design Documents** are to be updated annually at maximum time based on regulatory deadlines of **AUTHORITIES That Delivers Certificates "; I think at least ONCE-ANNUALLY"**;
 3. **Design Documents** are electronically signed by an author and reviewers;
 4. **Design Documents** are saved in an ERP software such as **"SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)"**, etc.;
 5. **Design Documents** have a table to indicate changes within the document for each modification of it;
 6. **Design Documents** USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);
 7. **Design Documents** Module Description (Module Functional Specification) with Diagrams; E.g.: **"Finite State Machine Diagrams"**, etc.;
 8. **Design Documents** Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification;
Runtime Memory Error Detection TOOLS.
 9. **Source code** is to be stored in a control version management system such as **"Rational-ClearCase"**, etc.;
 10. **Source code** changes are to be reviewed and electronically signed using a key-card like the ones used by **["SIEMENS-healthineers-OCS"]**;
 - B.) **CENELEC (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>) for "RAILWAY"**
A sample railway software related product regulation is : **"CENELEC EN50128" (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>)**.
 - C.) **A.R.I.N.C (<https://www.aviation-ia.sae-itc.com>) for "AVIONICS SOFTWARE"**
Sample A.R.I.N.C specifications : **"RTCA D0178-B"**; **"RTCA D0178-C"**.
 - **Static Code Analysis Verification conforming to "MISRA-C" (<https://www.misra.org>) ;**

["MISRA-C"]

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

25.25 Years of PRE-Doctoral & years of Doctoral Research at University-racist OF waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA

ML; C++; Java; OSI; Eclipse; Intel-Pin; Open-MP Haskell, GWT, Python, IBM, Quercus, Bash-scripting	<i>Program Analysis (Static, Dynamic).</i> a-la-KILDALL-Gary;LFDS-Reps; datalog; Soot; LLVM	Courses taught: 1. Software Testing, Quality Assurance & Maintenance 2. Programming for Performance 3. Tools & Methods for Software Engineering 4. Foundations of Software Engineering 5. C++ Programming Laboratory 6. Compilers 7. Computer Networks
<i>(ADVANCED) Compiler Technology</i> Yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang; Alias Analysis, Comp. Opt.	<i>Program Verification (Isa.-HOL, etc.); Model Checking</i> SDMM; CAV - Computer-Aided Verification; NuSMV; Alloy	
Programing Languages OOP; Functional	Software; Programming; Testing Alg.; Rel. Eng.; Security; Par.-Comp.	} Foundations of My Doctoral Ph.D. / Post-Doctoral Works in Computer Science (Software Engineering)
	Formal Methods; Kripke Structures Automata theory (NFA, DFA, etc.)	

- o [PublicaTIONS.]
- o "Software LICENSING".
- o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact".
- o Contacts with NORTH-AMERICAN scientists
- o Contacts with other Scientists
- o Issues & MISUNDERSTANDINGS at the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada
- o TIME at the University-racist-of-BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, Germany:
 1. "2 years" STudent Software Developer PART-TIME job – Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH), Germany.
 2. "2 years" WERKSTUDENT at ZMML-university-sexist-racist of bremen, BREMEN, GERMANY.: February 2003 – February 2005.
 3. "4.5 years PRE-time" in GERMAN-racist program : "'DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]"
- o Doctoral years of research at the university-racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA-idiot:
 1. "2 years PRE-time" at SIEMENS-idiot medical solutions.: November 2007 – JULY 2009.
 2. "Summary of teaching training certificates
 3. PAPER conference peer reviewed : OOPSLA 2010.
 4. GIVEN PREsentation : IBM CDp Cascon 2010.
 5. Visited courses.
 6. Independent assisted research summary as a "Master of Science (M.Sc.)"
 7. VISITed SUMMER-school /workshops / conferences summary
["1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"-2011] | [PLDI 2009] | [IBM CDp Cascon 2010]
 8. PSYCHOLOGICAL-Care with PRACTICE of SWIMMING at THE university-racist of waterloo every other day during almost 4 years – "Degree-Swimmer-5 / degree-MASTER-Swimmer-6" successfully attended.
 9. "Year 1" : 09/2009 – 08/2010;
 10. "Year 2" : 09/2010 – 12/2011 – [with PhD Comprehensive Examination.];
 11. Doctoral THESIS Presentation / PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011"

- o QUALification as a "Professional Engineer in Ontario, CANADA":

THE requirements to qualify myself as Professional Engineer in ONTARIO are all met after 1 year supervision under PATRICK LAM "(2011)"; because I have already 48 months of professional engineering work experience before entering the professional academic doctor of engineering program in ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER Engineering at university-racist-white of waterloo.

"AS a "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" graduate [abbreviated "Dr./PhD" in French; In french, "Dr./PhD" only nowadays means doctor in engineering; and no fellowship at all; I AM A FRANCOPHONE.]; THERE shouldn't be any need to again acquired a professional designation "Professional Engineer", since "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" is already an Engineering titled degree. So as a francophone from dark-afrika-heimat, I am not interested anymore in any Engineering, or whatsoever designated vocational position in whiteist-world !"

"ALSO as a born-again christian, I CANNOT BE member-ed in any fellowship of iron-rings, female-peggist; etc. ."

"JON eyolfson for instance has a "Bachelor-of-Engineering"; so he doesn't need to apply for a "Professional Engineer"; BUT [Wenzhu-man has a "Master of Applied Science (MAsc)"]; AND no "Engineering titled degree from CANADA and /or USA"; SO for her needs she must apply for P.Eng.; so to get government oriented positions !"

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

26.26 Years of POST-doctoral Research; a Summary Report – 2nd page

- o *POst-Doctoral (Ph.D.; Prof.) years of research at the university–racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA–idiot:*
 1. "Year 1": 01/2012 – 08/2012 – [*PROfessional Internship at IBM Toronto–idiot Software Lab..*]
 2. "Year 2": 09/2012 – 08/2013
 3. "Year 3": 09/2013 – 08/2014
 4. "Year 4": 09/2014 – 04/2015
 5. STUDENT advising summary
 6. TEACHing assistantship summary
 7. "Summary of teaching training certificates"
 8. *Independent & Collegiate Research Summary as "D.ENG. [DR.–ING. in 'French language'] (PH.D.)"*
 9. Visited courses as post–doctoral (POST-DOCTORAL STUDIES) fellow.
 10. VISited ONLINE courses /workshops / conferences summary
[Software-Security–online–"stanford.edu" 2013] | [MITACS ONTARIO 2012] | [ICse 2012]
 11. RESEARCH outcome hindrance
 12. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism
 13. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism-continUED
 14. GIVEN–co–taught courses at the University–racist of Waterloo in ONTARIO, Canada
 15. ACADEMIC HELP from other people aside from DEAR-idiot PATRICK-lam
 16. *!!! PhD Research Seminar TALK. as an ECE graduate talk. !!!*
 17. *!!! PhD Dissertation Defense at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015" !!!*
 18. *IAI–cameroon–bande–d'idiots au service d'1 B.E.P.C–chantoux*
- o [TRAINING on the job of young engineers]:
 - Runtime monitoring for Web Apps
 - API usage rule checking for 'C' programs (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)
- o *STARTUP entrepreneurship research & development project YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM:*

After I left the university–racist–of–waterloo in ontario, IN MARCH 2015; I went to live in Cameroon–yaounde for almost 2 years, working on a free and open source software for Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP).

POST-Doctoral Research at YERITH R&D since MARCH 2015:

 - I) *Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise;*
 - II) *YERITH_QVGE legal artifacts for QUALIFICATION certified products Engineered in AFRICA;*
 - III) *A web-site Domain-Specific Language (DSL) Processor for generation of HTML5, PHP, CSS, etc. combined web–applications named YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (Accompanied with a WYSIWYG-Tool : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL !)*
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9>
 - IV) *A realtime component (for operating system DEBIAN LINUX) is in preparation for trading stock exchange erp system "YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME": YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM;*
 - V) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification "state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)" C++ Library :*
 https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf [1f]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
 - VI) *A State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) translator–compiler :*
[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567\)](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567) [1c]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
 - VII) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification runtime container for "SDMM" :*
 [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481\)](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481) [1b]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
 - VIII) *Simple to use and pragmatic Enterprise–Resource–Planing (ERP) software :*
 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) [?]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 (Cyber-Security & Web Deployment Development)

27.27 WEB PAGES HTML and others Generation with YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0

27.27.1 Motivation

Table 6: A SOFTWARE architecture overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (["An SDMM usage scenario by IBM-websphere"].)

Figure 4: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 generates legacy web files from Qt 5 interface files (".ui" files).

Figure 5: A Stack Stapled Architecture Overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0.

YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 is a novel project that constitutes the base for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM ([git https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem](https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem)) that endeavors to create web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations that use YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM without much additional programming of web interfaces and / or interactions; AT such, web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations will emerge as easy as pressing a button.

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 is a Domain Specific Language to [describe WEB SITES programmatically]; SUCH as a C++ program imperatively, AND well structured; So to automatically generate STATIC DYNAMIC WEB SITES BASED ON HTML (HYPERTEXT MARKUP LANGUAGE) AND CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) language constructs : [WWW - World Wide Web \(WWW\) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)".

Numerous companies in Cameroon might evaluate this new research software system product to simplify and speed up their software development process :

1. "Dr.-Ing. PAUL dayang (2013, University of Bremen)"; currently employed at the University of Ngaoundere in Far North of Cameroon.
 - This researcher and lecturer, employed by the University of Ngaoundere, has never replied to my long time email as an alumni of the prestigious University of Bremen in Germany where I graduated with a "Diplom-Informatiker degree 2 years before him !"
 - I could see he started a web graphical system (also with "ANDROID-google platform" (https://)) html-based to promote online afore-provisional shopping of food provisions in Africa for his dissertation as a "Doctor of Engineering". I was sad not to see this project emerge as a commercial start-up here in Cameroon where there is only "www.cm.coinafrique.com" (<https://www.cm.coinafrique.com>) that I deem as a serious competitor in this era of work.
 - I believe the programming abstraction I will provide for "DAYANG and RÖDIGER (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/~roediger>) work" would help them both in "Ngaoundere" and in "Bremen" to promote Free and Open Source web shopping for Africa where even a clean market is not existing in Main city Yaounde !
 - AT the university of bremen-white-racist, I Visited a course titled "E-business technologies 2"; I don't remember the name of the professor but I DID SO while I WAS in my 3rd year as part of so called "ANGEWANDTE INFORMATIK" ("Applied Computer Science"). IN graduate level course "E-business technologies 2", I learned about n-tiers web architectures, SOAP-Service Oriented Architecture Protocol, etc.

ALSO, in my 2nd year, there was a small "practicum" where I learned on PHP, and MariaDB; "ERIC-cuon-pd STREIBL" was the organizer.

2. "DUT-Diplôme Universitaire de Technologie" CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong" (Start-Up)

CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong is a seasoned software developer that creates large to medium-sized websites; AND Google-android mobile applications for his clients around world.

"CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong, that I schooled with in Douala secondary school — "ALFRED SAKER HIGH SCHOOL" — would also not be against such a tool-framework that could reduce his development time and effort, since BLACK-USA entrepreneurs cannot afford tremendous amount of money for tools sold by MICROSOFT CORP., FACEBOOK INC., etc. ! " (<https://www.creezycreates.com>)

3. "Dr. (B.Sc.) Claudel Noumbissi" (Start-Up)
4. "Ing. (B.Sc.) Arthur Zang" (Start-Up)
5. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Ibrahim Nguena Moukouop" (Start-Up)
6. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Thomas Djotio Ndié" (Start-Up)
7. "Institut Universitaire de la Cote", Douala (Start-Up)
8. "Santa Lucia – AHALA", Yaounde (Currently using Odoo ERP web & thick-client) !
9. "DR. (M.Sc.) Fabrice Wilfried Siemeni" (Start-Up)

Fabrice WILFRIED siemeni could generate sample website pages with no programming knowledge at all.

10. etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 – CONTINUED –

Table 7: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL keywords and meaning (An excerpt).

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 keyword	(level) Nested in keyword	Programming related meaning
1. yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN		Contains web site all pages description
2. web_html_page_menu_bar_headers	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Contains web site each page menubar pages names
3. web_html_page	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	A HTML page description
4. yri_html_page_title	(3) web_html_page	A HTML page title
5. yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar	(3) web_html_page	Inputs a menubar onto this HTML page
6. yri_html_page_text_SECTION	(3) web_html_page	Describes a text section on a HTML page
7. VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH	(6) yri_html_page_text_SECTION	Defines text paragraph within a HTML page
8. text_yri_font_size	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a font size
9. text_yri_width_box	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a width for a text paragraph

Figure 6: Webbrowser-based software architecture : at least 4 layers logical software architecture (Image modified from online pdf paper "FlashCache: A NAND Flash Memory File Cache for Low Power Web Servers" [<https://doi.org/10.1145/1176760.1176774>] by Trevor et al.). YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runtime monitors communication layers.

27.27.2 RELATED WORK at YERITH R&D; Software System Architecture of ERP Systems

- "Our paper not for publication in a conference paper, [SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0\[?\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf) : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); reveals common web system architecture patterns and structure, INCLUDING ([CYBER-SECURITY\[34\]](#)) software system security vulnerability analysis; As observed these last 10 years at least from "December 12, 2025".
- ["WE have visited, in year 2013, an online software security vulnerability detection and protection course with the STANFORD-university-racist while attending our degree [DOCTORAL PH.D.-program at the University of Waterloo;] THIS required acquired knowledge helps us creating safe and secure software systems by Construction."]
- "WE previously, in our "3rd semester", at the University-racist of Bremen, Bremen, GERmany-idiot; Have visited a course for undergraduates named "Information Security 1" given by "TZI.DE (Technology Center for Computer Science) (<https://www.tzi.de/en>)" founding member "Prof. Dr-Ing. Carsten-cuon-obèse Bormann-nazi" (<https://user.informatik.uni-bremen.de/cabo>)."
- ★ ★ "I could also achieved a running taint analysis ([git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)) for the Quercus PHP JAVA web application server during my post-doctoral studies & work at the university-racist of waterloo in ontarian Canada-idiot. IT was a graduate course taught by "Frank-idiot-nazi TIP-gay-cuon"." ★ ★

27.27.3 WHAT YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 Would Service & Provide

- "Qt 5 software development platform" enables auto-deployment for Android-google platform." (<https://>)
 YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem>) will reuse this functionality to generate legacy web source code files (HTML5, PHP, CSS, Javascript (GWT (Google Web Toolkit))); VIA a translation program-technology from "Qt 5-ui (user-interface)" files onto YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 input file coin as DSL-specific YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 files ("spec_html"); Figure 4.;
- We at YERITH R&D could then use any "Qt 5-Designer tool as a WYSIWYG Tool for generating Web-HTML-PHP pages : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL" !
- "We plan at mid-term to be able to generate "Software architecture proof testing-programs", both for GUI-interfaces (thick-client), and Web-interfaces (thin-client); automatically just by specifying certain behavioral interactions using state diagram mealy machines ([SDMM\[1d\]](#)).";
- "The so-called "Software architecture proof testing-programs" will have certain warranties about [cyber-security], about [cyber-safety], [runtime-memory usage] and [user-defined usage rules]."

27.27.4 Implementation Technologies

I use "flex and bison compiler / translator generation technology" for creating YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL. I plan to automatically generate code for enabling runtime monitoring of the generated web sites. A first version of this FOSS (Free And Open Source Software) is available at URL: [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9) .

27.27.5 YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL Keyword Table

Table 7 depicts and explains commands and directives for creating web-based HTML pages sites.

We plan also the generation of web sites based on an "n-tiers architecture pattern", illustrated for instance in Figure 6; that demonstrated solid resistance in practice for more than 10 years now as demonstrated by applications server existence and usage such as :

1. Apache tomcat application server
2. Glassfish application server: mainly used in combination with JAVA OSI component-based software development architecture.
3. Quercus PHP server interpreter application server
4. IBM websphere

All this work has to solve the issue of generating certain portion of web sites for customers and users of ["YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM"\[?\]](#) Enterprise Resource Planing software in a time period in-between of 3 years from this year 2024 !

"ALL THIS UNDER THE PROTECTION OF OUR LORD AND SAVIOR JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN."

28.28 Securing Websites

Figure 7: A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine file.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_TaintAnalysis
2. {
3.   START_STATE(T0):NOT_IN_BEFORE(in,yri_tainted_analysis.sanitizers_methods)
4.   ->[not_in_sql_event_log('SELECT.i0#sanitize',STATE(T0))]/'INSERT.i0#in'->
5.     FINAL_STATE(TF):IN_POST(i0,yri_tainted_analysis.tainted_values).
6. }

```

Figure 8: A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine.

$\underline{Q_0} := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(op, yri_tainted_analysis.sanitizers) ; \quad \overline{Q_F} := \text{IN_POST}(i0, yri_tainted_analysis.tainted).$

28.28.1 Motivation

Numerous security vulnerabilities towards and against web applications exist :

- **“SQL injection”** : “A user tries to make a software execute a SQL query on a software-connected database by passing for instance; **THROUGH user credential input SQL-code to destroy part or all your database.**

user-name: 'Insert into users ('user_name', 'user_password') values ('drop table users', 'drop database');

- **“Format Strings”** : A software has part of it receiving directly input from an outside-world interface and using it without checking it is proper formed. Any malformed input can cause a mal-interpretation of data & could then caused for instance; **A CRASH of the software under analysis !**

int variable_x = 0; scanf(%, variable_x); // Wrong format is expected by scanf !.

// scanf currently expects a string instead of an integer.

- **“Cross-site scripting attacks”**; **“Buffer-overflow”**; **“Man-in-the-Middle”**; etc.
- **ALL cyber-security types** We previously wrote about in this listing items could be detected by removing all tainted values of an application; I.E.; provide a validation function and / or method, for each tainted value.

THIS is best done during testing of the software product before delivery of an end-product to clients and / or customers.

A recovery from a fail state accepting error program location can be done by adding a generic recovery validating function and / or method that Could identify; and provide; best sanitizing / validating method for each tainted input.

SINCE YERITH_QVGE provide only forbidden trace specification, a recovery and detection is generally only possible after at least 1 violation of the SDMM specification property automaton has been achieved !

A usage scenario with in future coming dedicated PC-Tablet computer YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF; could be found in Figure 1.

Our approach to add more security & safety to open-source webshops generated by our technology YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL is manifold :

- 1.) **USE of runtime verification & monitoring platform YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) :
 - **USE of standard security vulnerability breaches detection mechanisms** as for Instance illustrated for Taint Analysis in this Subsection 28.28.3 !
 - **USE of developer-otherly specified security vulnerabilities patterns** expressed as SDMM, & similarly described as for instance in Figure 8 !

28.28.2 Event Race Parallel-Concurrent Processes

- 1.)

28.28.3 Dynamic Taint Analysis for Web Security

- 1.) *IN a previous work at the university–racist of waterloo, in Canadian–whitte ontario [3], we've implemented in web–server Quercus; A dynamic taint analysis using JAVA as programming language.*

We plan to re–use Quercus as web–application server for generated webshops from YERITH–WEB–DESIGN–TOOL.

- 2.) *Currently, we have created YRI–DB–RUNTIME–VERIF, 1 runtime monitoring container generator that enables creation of taint analysis engine with no coding for a developer; IT only requires to deliver a state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) specification expressed using a textual description DSL–language called **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG** [1c] : Figure 7;*

This textual description (Domain-Specific Language) offers also, when a state diagram mealy machine has more than 2 states, a reference communicating processes parallel specification for the problem under analysis since processes are synchronized on each event after a 1st event because each state of the state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) represents a potential other parallel running process state; Illustration follows for instance in Figure 8.

28.28.4 Warranties on Web Pages–Security

- 1.) *[Warranties on Cyber–Safety].*

29.29 WEB-QT Assembly : A comparison with [YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL](#)

- WebAssembly-technology of QT-trolltech uses a platform independent binary format (called emscripten) to deliver website functionality for QT-application out-of-the-box;

Technology emscripten is not open-sourced and it is not as simple as "use of [YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL](#)".

30.30 WYSIWYG-Tool for generating websites

Figure 9: YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL : A SCREENSHOT of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 generator within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.

Figure 9 illustrates a design engineering modeling window frame originating from ERP-software YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for automatically generating webshop for its users.

30.30.1 Motivation

Numerous users of ERP-YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum would be also interested in having a WWW-online presentation for interacting with their clients and / or customers.

In our white-black paper [SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0\[?\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf) : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); we motivate why we prefer fat-client software-system architecture over thin-client (also called website-architecture).

However we also want to enable our users to be online on the web easily by just pressing a button since costs to develop another system might be very impressing. THAT is why YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum offers now for its users and / or developers an interface for automatically generating and deploying website-webshops solutions that reuse any information already present in the database created & running as a fat-thick-client (QT) architecture.

30.30.2 Steps & Technology

- Selecting QT-trolltech ui files to transform into web-HTML5 and / or PHP files;
- Pressing a button that generates PHP-HTML5 files via a step-by generation of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 files.

Our use of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 has advantages of preventing us of drastic changes in either HTML5 standards or platforms since YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 represents a website architecture as a high-level programming language (e.g.: C++, JAVA, etc.).

Listing 1: A sample very limited for explanation & illustration purpose YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 Source code !

```

1  yerith-web-pages-generator-MAIN YECEFOIQ-WEB-PAGES
2  {
3
4  web-html-page index
5  {
6  yri_html_page_title: 'Bienvenue au centre de formation qualifiante Yecefoiq !';
7  yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar[web-html-page-menu-bar-headers];
8  yri_html_page_MENU_BAR_link_string: 'yri_index !';
9
10 yri_html_page_text_SECTION (HTML_HEADER_H/3; 'Description du Centre de Formation')
11 {
12 VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH variable_paragraph_1
13 {text-yri-font-size = 5} :
14 {text-yri-width-box = 5cm} ==
15 "PLEASE read following list items ordered !:"
16
17 li_begin: '1st list item'
18 li: '2nd list item.'
19 li_end: 'Last list item.'
20 };
21 };
22
23 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers {
24 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers_Position = 'vertical-left';
25
26 yri_html_page_section[index,
27 programme_des_cours,
28 contenu_des_cours,
29 impressum];
30 };
31 }

```


31.31 Software Validation with YERITH_QVGE (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)

Figure 10: A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart; Example created and / or inspired from QT-trolltech sample; in Documentation present; Statechart found in some place I don't remember yet..

Figure 11: A sample ping-pong parallel process depicted in Figure 10.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_PingPong
2. {
3.   START_STATE(pinger)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('ping', STATE(pinger))]/'pong' ->
5.     STATE(ponger): IN_POST_NOP
6.     ->[in_sql_event_log('pong', STATE(ponger))]/'pong' ->
7.       FINAL_STATE(pinger_two): IN_POST_NOP.
8. }

```

Software System Validation checks whether certain software system properties are **IMPLEMENTED CORRECTLY** according to its specifications.

1. Software **VALIDATION** as an automatic test case generation runtime monitoring instance from **YERITH_QVGE** !

a.) A test case is generated without checking for test data using a constraint solver engine because it can be acquired only by manual interaction with the software under analysis.

31.31.1 Cyber-Safety Warranties & Others

1.) **Warranties on Cyber-Security**.

12.12 Software Verification Engineering Modeling with SDMM

Figure 12: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE(dept_exists):NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('DELETE.dept.YRI_ASSET', STATE(dept_exists))]/'SELECT.dept'->
5.   ERROR_STATE(dept_exists):IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET,stocks.dept_name).
6. }

```

Figure 13: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A SQL-database based only in a disk-file with not much roundabout code could also be used instead of a full-featured database management system such as MariaDB (<https://www.mariadb.com>).

$Q_0 := NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name)$; $Q_1 := IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.dept_name)$.

"SDMM state diagram formalism is more powerful and expressive than David-harel statechart formalism. I.E. As depicted in fig. 15, a drawing-design is not well capable of scaling for a software-system with for instance 9 sub-systems events and / or states."

Figure 14: A David-harel statechart modeling of a temporal property expressed as a finite state diagram machine of mealy-GEORGES in fig. 13.

Figure 15: A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart.

1. Software Engineering Design & Verification using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM), runtime monitoring & static code analysis :

- WE are working & researching on translating automatically viable statechart specification onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) runtime monitoring verification specifications;
- USER requirement elicitation & specification is easily transcribed into a formal SDMM automaton-formula; Even by a mathematician with not much knowledge in Computer Technical Programming; As THIS is required when developers use David-Harel Statechart visual formalism as you can observe in Figure 14 !

A temporal property specification using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) only requires use of the following mathematic elements :

- Logic formulas to describe propositional formulas as conditions to trigger software system state-transitions; AND also to describe "GUARD-condition" to be checked 'VALID' before a software-system state-transition is triggered & executed by YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, a runtime monitoring verification container.
- Variables : to describe states & state-conditions (pre- & post-conditions).
- Formulas mustn't be drawn because there exists also a textual description language coined as a Domain-Specific Language called YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG [1c] : Figure 12 illustrates for instance a textual description for the mealy machine state diagram drawn in Figure 13 !
- "Statecharts by David-Harel, BECAUSE it is a visual formalism; Requires knowledge of code of drawing squares & other signs and keywords." !

- Modeling a temporal property specification added with state-transitions pre- & post-conditions is very tedious and complicated to realize using David-harel Statechart.

THIS kind of modeling is impressively more easy to realize using finite automata formalisms such as depicted in Figure 13; This figure depicts a temporal software system safety property designed with Mealy-machine, "And formalized as a state diagram mealy machine (SDMM (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [1d]) by myself" !

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is extremely efficient in usage and / or specification because state-conditions ("pre-condition underlined" & "post-conditions over-lined" are executed by a runtime execution "expansion algorithm" called "Method YRI_trigger_an_edge_event" that checks at no costs for users.)

- With statecharts, specification of software system with parallel subsystem doesn't scale well starting for instance with 8 subsystems, because all 8 subsystems must be drawn 1 inside others !

ON the contrary side, state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) only requires specifying an finite state automaton with more than 2 states, and linear in space & traversal algorithm complexity; Which is done automatically for a developer by the runtime monitoring verification generator-container YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !.

- "OPEN-source version of the software system programming library QT-trolltech offers since version (at minimum number) 5.15 (around year 2020) a package called SCXML that implements David-harel statechart programming capabilities" !

13.13 Software Verification with YERITH_QVGE

A library or plugin at any layer (OR a combination mixture of layers) of a software system architecture could be verified and validated using YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF by applying a receipt: IT would be sufficient to map each system call wanted for call sequence verification and / or validation to a MySQL query: So one doesn't need to re-create new QT-DBus interfaces for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: E.g.: "SYSTEM V libc". [A sample use case for IBM-Websphere server web !]

Figure 16: Software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: it is also a runtime monitor container for software verification.

Figure 17: YRI_QVGE software stack dependencies.

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR DYNAMIC runtime analysis and monitoring of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software (Figure 17 illustrates graphically interdependency between these under described sub-projects.).

- a. **YRI_QVGE** (an extension of Qt-QVGE): A "CASE (computer-aided software engineering)", CLOSED SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (CSCS), for creating and generating MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAMS as GUI (GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE) TOOL. [06/2022 – CURRENT]
[model-based testing, DSL – domain-specific languages]

"[THE GUI TOOL YERITH_QVGE] (See Figure 23) GENERATES A FILE CONTAINING A MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAM SPECIFICATION using YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG; this file could be used as input for the compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP, so to gather a C++ package to run as runtime monitor within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. THIS TOOL COSTS 2,500 EUROS."

- b. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**: A Dynamic Program Monitoring Recovering Analyzer Generator for any software emitting QtDBus messages per sockets (See subsection 13.13.3 (Runtime Verification), and / or Figure 21; and / or Figure 24).

"THIS IS at time (December 12, 2025); State-of-art technology; comparable technology are for instance RT-Tester with TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System); State Diagram formalism From "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (RT-Tester, MBT[?]). TDIOHS complies fully with all semantic elements of HAREL-statecharts !

"AND technologies "IBM Purify Plus"; "LOGSCOPE" ("Specification-Based Monitoring in C++") and "DejaVu" ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic") by [Dr. Klaus Havelund] at N.A.S.A (https://www.nasa.gov)."

- YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

- c. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP**: a compiler using flex and bison, for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF specification language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG), so to automatically generate C++ code for runtime monitors implemented in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. [04/2023 – CURRENT]
[compilers, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages]

"COMPETITORS from LOGSCOPE and DejaVu; AND RT-Tester, MBT[?]; have similar description state diagram language; but work all of them as SPECIFICATION OF WISHED PROGRAM BEHAVIOR; whereas SDMM[1d] works at SPECIFICATION OF FORBIDDEN (fail) PROGRAM BEHAVIOR."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- d. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG**: A SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE FOR STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) extended with pre-/post-conditions on STATE DIAGRAM TRANSITIONS and with a final state. (https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567) [04/2023 – CURRENT]
[statecharts, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages]

"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG complies fully to David-harel statecharts ["Statecharts: a visual formalism for complex systems" (https://www.wisdom.weizmann.ac.il/~dharel/SCANNED.PAPERS/Statecharts.pdf)] which is a visual formalism for states diagrams."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- e. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS**: UNIT TESTING PROJECT for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. [06/2022 – CURRENT]
"THIS test unit suite is there to check peculiarities of project YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF; As a Free And OPEN SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (foss), I strongly recommend using it before committing changes to the main git-branch project."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS

- f. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF / YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime [06/2022 – CURRENT]

[model-based testing, reactive system analysis, computer software program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software integration testing with SQL and GUL, runtime monitoring]

"YOU SPECIFY USING A STATE DIAGRAM AN ERRONEOUS SUT (System Under Test) TYPE STATE STYLE BEHAVIOR with YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. USING YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, YOU CHECK AT RUNTIME WHETHER SUCH AN ERRONEOUS SUT SEQUENCE BEHAVIOR OCCURS."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

13.13.1 TAXONOMY : Software Verification vs. Program Code Verification

Figure 18: "Program verification (including model checking)" is a subset (C) of "SOFTWARE VERIFICATION". (See also research goal 13.)

Figure 19: Embedded program verifier notifier within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runs as a background process service.

Software System verification is a discipline to verify whether a software, meaning a product use at customer level and full-featured, conforms to certain software system user related usage properties.

In contrast, **program code verification** checks only program at the level of their source code or binary code product against code programming related properties. And not necessarily at level of a full featured user level product. Thus all code programming related properties could be cast down to certain software system related properties. **It follows PROGRAM VERIFICATION is a Subset Of Software (System) Verification: illustrated in Figure 18 !**

Program Analysis by Xavier-yerith (<https://zenodo.org/records/10990601>) !

13.13.2 How to use YERITH_QVGE

A software component or a whole running software binary could be verified against SQL correctness temporal properties by USING **YRI_QVGE**, as illustrated in Figure 16:

- The 1st layer illustrates the runtime verifier tester monitor engine: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, that entails several custom runtime monitor specifications, provided by user.
- The 2nd layer shows the **SUT (System Under Test)**; or **PUA (Program Under Analysis)**; layer that communicates with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF through QT socket calls (via Dbus messages). Each event message is sent to all runtime monitors. **The SUT source code has been instrumented first, so to specify which program statements actions are to be packaged as messages to YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could also be used to instrument program binaries at runtime directly, Avoiding recompilation and even usable where source code of SUT (PUA) is unavailable.**
- The 3rd layer illustrates a library or plugin (i.e.: **MySQL**) that is being monitored via instrumentation of the **SUT**; in this case, the **SUT** is YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum. **Other providers could modify An Open Source Code Version (FOSS) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF to verify and monitor another library-plugin other than MySQL.**
- The 4th and last layer shows the Operating System (OS) layer and its communication via systems calls with the 3rd layer of the library-plugin.

13.13.3 How to use YERITH_QVGE in relation to verification cyber-security detection remediation methods.

1. Model Checking (<https://wikipedia.org>):

Temporal logic formalisms, such as **LTL (Linear Temporal Logic)** (<https://>); Could be used to create **State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM)** (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) [1d] and generate a binary executable of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b] to perform runtime monitoring, and runtime SQL recovery of Graphical User Interface (GUI) supported software (And also not supported GUI software). Users must only note that "SDMM" specifications are **fail (forbidden) trace behavior specifications of a program under analysis (SUT)**.

Structures could be created on how to translate simple LTL constructs into simple "SDMM"; So to ease usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

2. Runtime Verification (Monitoring; including Software Cyber-Security Exploit Detection Remediation):

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from:

- **Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;**
- **WEB-APPLICATION RUNTIME MONITORING[?]; Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;**
- **Firewall security rules enforcement filtering;**
- **Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement : (E.g. : Figure 20);**
- **Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;**
- etc.

Could be solved by usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF GIT-REPOSITORY[1b]: **git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>**. **"Pr. Prof. Dr. Jean Yang, Ph.D." from CMU-"Carnegie Mellon University (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>)" could be a potential competitor in this area of research.":**

A. "Jeeves Programming Language" – last updated "October 2015" (<https://projects.csail.mit.edu/jeeves>)

- **API usage rule check at 'AKITA Software (<https://www.akita.com>)' in USA; California (CA).**
- **"Jeeves Programming Language" enables static typing;**
- **Dynamic code source rewriting to achieve Semantics; implemented as an embedded Domain Specific Language (DSL) in Python programming language (IT is unclear in which document [PROFESSOR JEAN yang checks] that this code is correct).**

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

Table 8: Jeeves Programming Language Versus (Vs.) The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

"Information Flow and Policy Control"	YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Jeeves Programming Language
1. Specification as a Domain Specific Language (DSL)	Yes (stand-alone SDMM (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [1d] DSL specification; Based on MEALY MACHINE AUTOMATON; "HAREL-statechart (https://www.wisdom.weizmann.ac.il/~dharel/SCANNED.PAPERS/Statecharts.pdf) compatibility") ✓	yes (DSL embedded into Python)
2. False (Positives) Warnings	No (1 formal proof exists in journal paper (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [1d]) ✓	* yes (CHECK A REFERENCE)
3. DSL Specification CARRIES DATA too	Yes (as Qt-DBus NETWORK data parameters) ✓	yes (as local stack function/method parameter)
4. As program annotations	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes ('Jeeves' instructions)
5. USABLE in a any programming language	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	no (Only Python)
6. ONLY usage with Python	No (any programming language that could emit Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes
7. Embedded in a programming language	NO ✓	yes (Python DSL library)
8. CRASH could occur during analysis and / or policy enforcing	NEVER	YES
9. Execution runtime overhead	No (concurrent event stream analysis monitoring verification) ✓	Yes (Embedded Python runtime dynamic source code rewriting)
10. Persistent storage technology	Yes; "MariaDB (https://www.mariadb.org)" ✓	Yes; "PostgreSQL (https://www.postgresql.org)" ✓

Table 8 compares tabularly the "Jeeves Programming Language" and "The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF". In contrast to the "Jeeves Programming Language" that specifies information flow policy and control enforcement for Python, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is not implemented as programming language feature, and thus could be used for any software system that could emit Qt-DBus signals ; Thus, information flow control and enforcement is run as a separate process, concurrently to the system under analysis (verification or monitoring) as pictured in Figure 16.

Figure 33 illustrates a sample SDMM ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [1d] specifying that a "FILE SHALL NOT be written-updated after it HAS BEEN CLOSED-DELETED".

13.13.4 Runtime Dynamic Program Interpretation Rewriting with "Jeeves"

The information flow policy control and enforcement solution provided by the "Jeeves Programming Language" is as follows :

1. A domain-specific language (DSL) is defined and embedded in a modification of the dynamic interpreted programming language Python. The drawback of an embedded DSL is a non re-usability in using other programming languages and framework other than those related closely to Python;

2. Only certain cases are flow policy control and enforcement are solved statically by "Python-Jeeves" type system;

It means that 'false positives warnings' cases still exist in programmer code and couldn't be removed by static compilation and / or dynamic code interpretation.

In contrast, "the mixed formal methods – runtime dynamic analysis monitoring" I used in "YRI_QVGE", don't allow by construction for 'false positives warnings': A 'false positive warning' is a message from the analyzing system that indicates an error accepting state while THERE IS IN EFFECT NO ERROR found yet.

3. Flow policy enforcement is solved dynamically at runtime by dynamic code rewriting; WE HOPE that this feature could be proved sound for all program statements because it might create uncertainty of valid flow policy enforcement at all.

Differently, "YRI_QVGE" uses SQL database statement query for performing error accepting state recovery (or also called "Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement").

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

13.13.5 Sample Comparison BETWEEN Object-ORIENTED programming languages”

Table 9: COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C++, Python, AND JAVA. JAVA has an (interpretative and / or JIT-compiled) virtual machines that are in FACT reactive systems (E.g. : A "GUI software" is as well a reactive system) ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)

FEATURES	C++	PYTHON	Java
1. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE PHILOSOPHY	object-oriented	object-oriented	object-oriented
2. MACROS	✓	”	
3. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE	✓		
4. support INTERFACES	✓	✓	✓
5. STATIC COMPILATION	✓	✓	
6. RUNTIME MONITORING & VERIFICATION	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)
7. UNIT TESTING FRAMEWORK	✓	✓	✓
8. NETWORK CAPABLE	✓	✓	✓
9. CROSS PLATFORM PORTABLE	✓	✓	✓
10. include FILE LIBRARY CAPABILITY	✓	✓	
11. MULTI THREADING	✓	✓	✓
12. WYSIWYG GUI DESIGN TOOL	✓	”	✓
13. VIRTUAL MACHINE IS A REACTIVE SYSTEM			✓

13.13.6 "Formal Methods – Runtime Dynamic Analysis" Vs. "Compiler Static Analysis Technology"

Figure 20: Runtime Verification Monitoring with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Figure 21: YERITH SDMM based runtime monitoring verification analysis.

Figure 22: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

I advocate :

1. Solving problems using compiler static analysis technology; that is based on lattice-theory is more safe than formal methods algorithms at first because MANUAL model checking has to be used to prove formal methods solutions correct, which could be very tedious and lengthy; "OR EVEN INTRACTABLE". SEE the state explosion problem (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Model_checking).

On the other hand static dataflow analysis algorithms based on lattice-theory are safe by construction and don't need no more proofs of consistency and validity as long as they only follow the base-pattern algorithm as for instance defined by "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)".

THE previous statement also applies when using an instance of a static dataflow analysis based on the IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) algorithm from "THOMAS reps" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) at "The University of Winsconsin-MADISON-mad". (<https://www.wisc.edu>)

2. The formal method approach I use in solving problems listed in "Subsection 13.13.3"; a combination of formal methods with runtime dynamic analysis is as perfect as the "static dataflow analysis" standard algorithm by "Gary A. kildall", because **YRI_QVGE** uses only "fail (forbidden) traces" specifications and only exactly 1 outgoing edge for each transition in a state diagram mealy machine specification (<https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567>) [1d]:

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from :

- Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;
- Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;
- Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement: I.E. ...
- Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;
- etc.

3. Runtime Verification Analysis Results Combined With Static Dataflow Analysis Algorithms à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" as ; for instance implemented in "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) :

- o One could combine runtime verification analysis facts with static dataflow analysis so to reduce fail state accepting code source location paths.

For instance, applying **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b] to find an API violation rule such as a "FILE-Write-AFTER-FILE-close" as specified in Figure 33; that specifies a "SDMM DSL code (<https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567>) [1d]" for finding a write after close program execution :

- a.) WHENEVER such a "file Close-WRITE API rule violation usage" is found by a runtime monitoring verifying analysis program binary, this information could later on be used by a static analyzer on code sources to eliminate manually from the program code sources code the found API violation RULE.
- b.) Our work : "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) on detecting tainted path with an application for finding API usage rule violation in C++ code as ILLUSTRATED in Figure 35, COULD be used for instance !
- c.) Symbolic Execution / test-cases-test-data generation :

WHENEVER a fail-state accepting state is found by a run execution of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

- 1.) Such a run could only be executed with some test data stored somewhere in the SUT; a test case is also available for free since of the trace event log.

Such acquired test cases & test data could then be used later on to create some "testing suites" to exhibit this fail-state accepting error sequence run !

Symbolic execution run with finding of test data using a constraint solver like "Microsoft-Z3" (<https://www.microsoft.com/research--idiot--z3>) for instance, is only needed in case more test data and / or test cases are required for this fail-state accepting run.

13.13.7 CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) TOOL for Software System Verification AND / OR algorithmic trading trade-time

Figure 23: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

Figure 24: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL ERROR EVENT LOG.

1. [YERITH_QVGE] has also applications in specifying real-time trading operations based on trade-time; YERITH_{r&d} is going in the next years, to develop an algorithmic trading platform for free, Especially for exchanging inventory physical stock products (goods) for AFRICA; this is an ongoing project as an extension of the Enterprise Resource Planing SOFTWARE [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM[?]; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME].

HAVING as physical good a currency bill and / or coin is Not impossible: THIS is what we daily practice when we buy items at a cashier and / or in street rural market; So people possessing a bill and / or coin may have advantages over people having only inventory physical consumer goods for their exchanges; SO it must be that parts of markets might Not ACCEPT currency bills AND / OR coins "for equity and fairness" since not everyone can afford buying currencies and / or bills-coins at a bank and / or financial institution. !

Having to buy currencies to European UNION, for instance for CMR, is very expensive. PART of exchanges within AFRICA borders could be done just by physical product (good) exchange between people and / or governments; Especially since getting currencies bills and / or coins is very expensive.

■ RELATED work at "QUANTstamp.com"; Venture funded initially by Y-COMbinator from STANFORD.EDU (<https://www.stanford.edu>) :

QuantStamp.com (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) is a firm that works mainly on solving the main problem on 'How to verify, check, a correct con-formant "bitcoin" contract on an Ethereum-platform trading (<https://>) : a so called SmartContract (<https://www.iq.wiki/wiki/quantstamp>)'.

"Figure 31 shows in French language a similar "stock-physical exchange" architecture based on an Ethernet-network "RJ45, and / or Giga-USB;" for YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum users."

2. Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an ISO-related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE-ISO certifications for Healthcare: [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

Figure 25: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS:

- a.) "ON-the-fly (Add-hoc)" online / offline RUNTIME Verification MONITORING of all financial transaction operations at a financial institution; ATTACH a device at each computer and / or server using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A comparable instance figure is illustrated for a control console device at Figure 25; WHEREAS one replaces a "control console LINAC" device with SERVER / Computer.
- b.) A linear accelerator control console communication protocol runtime monitoring (E.g.: Figure 25). A more detailed explanation graphical occurs in "Figure 20, Section 13.13.6";
- c.) A railway track controller program runtime monitoring console at site;
- d.) An aero-plane Maneuvering Characteristics Augmentation System (MCAS) runtime monitoring device
- e.) etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III – Distributed & Operating Computing Systems (ERP; Software & Hardware)

Figure 26: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 27: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

1. **CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC enterprise resource planing (ERP) software system** [Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]
 [STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA; agile development method, [enterprise resource planing software], software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]
 - a. **RENDER ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE SYSTEM USAGE AND MANIPULATION AS EASY AS READING A LEISURE OR RECREATIONAL BOOK SO TO REDUCE USER STRAIN SIZE !** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 - b. **CONTRIBUTE TO REDUCE POVERTY BY IMPROVING SOFTWARE SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY FOR ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP).** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 1. **All following advantages of using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum contributes to reduce waiting files; THUS increase the number of customers and clients of an entrepreneurial organization !**
 2. Best and accurate technology SHALL REDUCE management effort and produce more reliable and cost-minimized business financial accounting information that enables to anticipate and reduce time of decision making.
 - 1.) **Gathering an overview over all financial and commercial; And customers / clients transaction information comes in JUST 1 button pressing from business dashboard window.**
 - 2.) **Exporting data onto Tabulator software such as 'LibreOffice-Calc, etc.' as Comma-Separated-Values (CSV), is as easy as selecting requested database table columns and Export them by pressing a button;**
 - 3.) **Calculating beneficial and interests costs is just as easy as reading it from business financial dashboard report generated automatically real-time and real-data from sales and customers, and / or Acquisitions databases tables.**
 3. Best and accurate technology reduces time execution of commercial business transactions, and thus, associated costs.
 - 1.) **Business Analytics : Ranking about sold and transferred goods and / or item stocks is best and just as easy done by reading it from a business commercial window dashboard; Ranking data decides what to order next for a better business turnover for your commercial financial entrepreneurial organization;**
 - 2.) **Ordering new item stocks is as easy as reading item stocks quantities from stocks window stock's inventory value.**
 4. So entrepreneurial commercial organizations could reduce a selling price without reducing its profit.

14.14 R&D Hardware & Software System Components

- o YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET [docs] — for Security / Safety.
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA [algo] [docs] 📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>
- o YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[?] (🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9))
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] 📄 [YRI_QVGE\[1\] \(git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif\)](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] **TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!**

14.14.1 Detailed Presentation View

1. **HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring:** ★ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.
 FOSS documents location to..come.on..github.com/yerithrd (<https://github.com/yerithrd>)
2. **ERP software itself:** ★ YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
 FOSS code location; **WARNING : we migrate 'varchar(256)' into 'varchar(50) mostly' !** 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
3. **Component 1:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-configurations-data": Configuration data for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
 This software component entails:
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0.properties" that contains MariaDB database connection parameters data.
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0-system-local-configuration-ENGLISH.properties" that contains local computer device and storage configuration parameters data.
 - A folder "yerith-erp-9-0-sql-backup-restore" where YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM database backups will be stored.
4. **Component 2:** ★ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[?]: Web Sites Generator Software Component.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)
5. **Component 3:** ★ [YRI_QVGE\[1\]: Runtime Monitoring Analysis Verification System.](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)
 FOSS code location 1 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)
 FOSS code location 2 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)
 FOSS code location 3 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
 FOSS code location 4 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS)
6. **Component 4:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon": Service daemon for human resources related payments.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon)
7. **Component 5:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon": Service daemon for alerts over inventory stocks, assets, and financial expenses.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III – Distributed & Operating Computing Systems ("Adversaries systems")

Figure 28: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 29: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Table 10: Comparison between 'YERITH-ERP-9.0' and 3 top tier-1 ERP systems

Features	'YERITH-ERP-9.0' (≈ 10 years old)	'Contr-ALL' (≈ 7 years old)	'Sage Gescom i7' (≈ 40 years old)	'SAP Business One' (≈ 40 years old)
★ HR & CRM & Accounting full featured ERP	YES	NO	YES	YES
★ runtime monitoring checks enabled	YES (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	NO	YES	YES
★ Documentation online available fully	YES (Here For Instance) (https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724)	NO	NO	NO
separate views per user role	YES	YES	YES	YES
complete training (or solution)	at least 4 weeks	at least 3 weeks	at least 2 months	at least 3 months
★ difficulty in navigation	easy	easy	very difficult	very difficult
usage language in software	easy everyday English	simple	simple	technical
financial accounting knowledge	no	no	no	useful
advanced marketing knowledge	no	no	useful	useful
★ internet connection	optional	useful (not at all internet means no access to any of your business resources.)	optional	optional

Table 10 illustrates 3 other top-ERP Systems that I deem to be serious competitors of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for now and in future time because of the quality of their design and / or features; As Implemented for now As I could find out.

Some Observations

1.) 'Contr-ALL' is a youngest one with only at time of initial investigation after an interview Questions & Answers with its creator "Rostand-MOUNGAM", 7 years old !

"Rostand MOUNGAM" rents 1 of my apartment for his legal living & business consulting services, Together with "NAOMIE" his wife !

2.) 'Contr-ALL' seems very close to a good ERP System like 'Sage Gescom i7' !

'Sage Gescom i7' is at time of writing (June 2025) around 40 years old !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 3 – "ALGORITHMS CREATED / INVENTED"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC enterprise resource planing software (ERP)

[Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]

["YERITH R&D" Publications, STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

15.15 Summary of Created And / Or Invented ALGORITHMS in this ERP Project

Figure 30: Manager Main Window in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)

1. *Non intermingling of QT-timer & User-button-pressing events for Cancellation Confirmation.* ["class YerithERPCancelModificationTimingObject"]C++; YRI_QVGE.
 - a.) *Dynamic selection of Cancellation withing each window frame based on user interaction.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
2. *Concurrent algorithms using semaphores so to allow disk configuration data usage between multiple users.* ["class YerithPOSUser; class YerithWindowsCommons"]C++; Qt 5.
3. *Manual Selection & Viewing of user QTableView columns.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5; mathematics-geometry.
4. *Checking of daemon service running processes & emitting signals onto user viewing buttons.* ["class YerithAdminWindow"]C++; Qt 5; Bash; lxqt-sudo.
5. *Automatic online English / French translation algorithm.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
6. *Password detection & MD5-hash-Coding / Decoding for QT-widgets automatically.* ["class YerithPushButtonPASSWORD"] C++; Qt 5.
7. *Selection of each ERP sale-service function within only 1 window frame.* ["class YerithEntrerWindow"] C++; Qt 5.
 - a.) *Graph coloring algorithm to find paths.* FSA; Graph-based algorithms.
8. *Pagination of QT-table data structure view-layout("QTableView")* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
9. *Printing & Creation of PDF documents based on LaTeX documentation system* ["class YerithTableViewPRINT_UTILITIES_TEX_TABLE"]C++; Qt 5; LaTeX.
 - a.) *Progress bar automatic Delivery for PDF-printing.* ["class YerithProgressBar"] C++; Qt 5.
10. *Online textual search & display of database query for window table frame items.* ["class YerithAbstractClassYerithSearchWindow"] C++; Qt 5.
11. *Automatic upgrade of SQL database between versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0.* [folder "yerith-erp-9-0-upgrade-sql/"] Git, Bash; SQL.

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA — Algorithms Excerpt

<https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>

1. *BASH-scripts to automatically generate a ".deb" file that entails configuration data for ERP-system software YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum !* DEBIAN LINUX 11; Bash.

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)

1. *Translation algorithm from QT XML interface design-drawings onto YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 !* ["class YERITH_WEB_SYSTEMS_MAIN_GENERATOR"]Qt 5-QXmlStreamReader.
2. *Translator to generate PHP; HTML5; CSS code sources from YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0.* ["yerith-web-pages-generator/src"]YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0; flex; bison.

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)

1. *FSM based communication RPC algorithms to monitor and verify temporal properties scheme of [GUI] software.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"]DBus; C++; Qt 5.
2. *BNF grammar YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG Translator into a State Diagram Mealy Machine FSM.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"] flex; bison.
3. *State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) library that enables runtime monitoring on-the-fly.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"] C++; Qt 5.
 - a.) *Fully compliant to David-harel statechart visual formalism.* David-harel [statechart](#).
 - b.) *O(n) graph traversal algorithm (Method "YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(string)").* finite state automaton; forbidden (fail) trace specification.
 - c.) *Grammar in Backus-Naur Form (BNF) for specifying State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM).* BNF (Backus-Naur Form).

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON — Algorithms Excerpt

[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

1. *THREAD conform compliant algorithm to process stocks, & stocks-based alert messages triggered on time and / or quantities.* C++; Qt 5.

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt

TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 2 – "DOCUMENTATION"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC *enterprise resource planing software (ERP)*

[Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]

[STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

16.16 Summary Documentation of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 31: *Generic Schema of Trading Realtime with YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum (French language)*

■ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)a. *Database network connectivity – FRENCH*

Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)

https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-multi-sites-base-de-donnees/YERITH-ERP_multi_sites_base_de_donnees.pdfb. *Installation GUIDE – FRENCH*

Installation GUIDE – FRENCH

<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8060217>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA

📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM

TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES II – Dissertation Thesis Doctor–PH.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering

Figure 32: YERITH-SAINT (LGPL license) : Accessing JAVA code with "Polyglot LLVM frontend"

A Mealy Machine State Diagram (SDMM) Specified Using Figure 33: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF Specification Language for NO-WRITE-AFTER-CLOSE memory check API file usage rule.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_Write_after_close_file
2. {
3.   START_STATE(closed):IN_PRE(g, is_alias(g, f))
4.   -> [in_set_trace('DELETE.file.f', STATE(closed))] / 'UPDATE.file.g' ->
5.     FINAL_STATE(WRITE_AFTER_CLOSE):IN_POST(g, is_alias(g, f)).
6. }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by static dataflow analysis mainly for the JVM-Java Virtual Machine; by late **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

a. **Research Proposal (Doctoral Ph.D. Thesis) in Electrical & Computer Engineering :**

🔗 **"Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software;"** (Advised by **Nomair Naem** | **Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** | **Patrick Lam, Ph.D.**) |

[UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH STATE DIAGRAM MEALY

[June 2024 – June 2024]

MACHINE (🔗 SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d]))

[YERITH R&D — [Software Safety], API (application programming interfaces) typestate checking;, tracematches, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, YERITH R&D — [computer software cyber-security, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION]

17.17 RESEARCH WORK OVERVIEW

THIS IS A PRELIMINARY WORK ON CHECKING TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES USING A TRACEMATCH-ALIKE SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE; SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) AND DATAFLOW ANALYSIS IS USED TO PRESENT A STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS.

TRACEMATCHES alike specifications enable developers to specify API usage rule drawing, as a deterministic finite automaton (<https://www.wikipedia.org>). Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented short overview slides of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010 ! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>). PDFSAM (<https://www.pdfsam.org>), and sample other Open Source Code Software (FOSS) ARE USED as benchmark for project evaluation.

18.18 SOLUTIONS WITH LLVM BY CHRIS LATTNER AT "APPLE LTD."

Instead of the 1st proposed Java-Soot approach as a whole program static dataflow analysis, a whole program context-sensitive dataflow static taint analysis for C using LLVM could successfully be implemented and described in 🔗 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34].

The 1st YERITH-SAINT algorithm was implemented for programs written in C programming language, and used a pre-processing step for analyzing points-to set using "poolalloc" (<https://github.com/poolalloc>) from Chris Lattner (<https://www.llvm.org>).

BECAUSE our static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework (Example : <https://github.com/polyglot-compiler/JLang>); See for instance Figure 32 !

20.20 RELATED WORK: DYNAMIC PROGRAM ANALYSIS API-RULE CHECKER "TRACERORY"

"Unread memory verification" is an instance of API (Application Programming Interface) usage rule checking.

""TRACERORY" runtime unread memory verification tool of Jon Eyolfson" (<https://www.hdl.handle.net/10012/6206>) ; "Detecting Unread Memory Using Dynamic Binary Translation at RV 2013 in Turkey" (<https://www.YRITOLOOKFOR.org>) , Of my former office roommate at "ECE-Waterloo-formal-method Davis Center Room" (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>), 1st floor, and colleague in static dynamic program analysis, could be outperformed with use of 🔗 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b]: "a runtime monitor container for state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)".

"TRACERORY" uses runtime program binary code instrumentation in "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) to instrument running programs for purposes of detecting unread memory; I ignore whether "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) has an open-source FOSS competitor at time yet; — Jan. 15, 2025 —.

Figure 33 illustrates a sample "SDMM" specification with instrumentation of source code with statements 'DELETE.file.f' and 'UPDATE.file.g' for runtime verification monitoring of API usage rule for checking memory write integrity: Runtime function "is_alias(g, f)" tells whether heap variable "g", and "f" refers to the same memory address. Such a "SDMM" specification is synchronized against a running program within a runtime monitor container: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .

21.21 CONCLUSION

"Due to incompatibilities with Patrick LAM; after March 10, 2015, I abandoned this research idea because I couldn't afford being laid-off without any letter or any other formal mean of communication other than telling a lie about a supposed ["Ph.D. Research Seminar"] at EIT building in Waterloo main (200 University Ave West) Campus! " (Ph.D. Dissertation Defence at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015")

It is easier to specify forbidden-fail-traces instead of saying how traces shall be like. Required 2 courses from overall 4 courses to pass where completed in year 2013-(CS846 & ECE750); in addition to before Examination completed courses (ECE725 & CS744). 4 experts in software systems were committee members of my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination AT UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA :

1. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.

Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca

2. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca

3. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca

4. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: lintan@purdue.edu

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Courses I VISITED while at the University–racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[ECE 725 / CS 745 – "Fall 2009",
CS 744 – "SPRING 2011",
First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques – "SPRING 2011",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
YERITH R&D — [program verification],
model checking,
compiler design]

Summary–PAGES

Table 11: Visited Courses at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 725 - Nancy Day" / "90%"	Fall 2009	Computer–Aided VERIFICATION	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 744 - Ondřej Lhoták" / "86%"	SPRING 2011	Advanced Compiler Design	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "1 st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques" / "N.A"	SPRING 2011	First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques	menlo–racist–college (https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml)

Table 11 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral Ph.D. in electrical & COMPUTER engineering degree program at the UNIVERSITY-white-racist of waterloo.

- 1.) [Visited courses as a post-doctoral researcher.]

- 2.) [Advanced Compiler Design]:

This project–racist–based course gave me the opportunity to learn perfection my theoretical knowledge and foundations in the following topics:

- COMPILER structure and optimizations

- 3.) [Computer–Aided VERIFICATION]:

This assignment-based course gave me the opportunity to learn foundations of the following topics:

- MANUAL THEOREM proving (also interactive theorem proving with "interactive theorem prover" ISABELLE–HOL (HIGH ORDER LOGIC))
- MODEL checking (EDMUND clarke et al.)
- Temporal LOGIC

The course instructor NANCY idiot day, was very verse in this material and could answer almost all questions without searching somewhere else than herself.

- 4.) [1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques]:

This marvelous experience gave myself opportunities to meet and hear-listen from best talented researchers in following areas of industrial research among other topics that I CANNOT ALL REMEMBER :

- "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS"
- "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation"
- "Hardware / Software Co–Design"
- "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)"

I AM ALWAYS GRATEFUL to professor idiot NANCY day for having given myself this marvelous experience through her personal recommendation, As required for admission in the summer school !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED AS POST-DOCTORAND-FELLOW – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. [Courses I VISITED while at the University–racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]

[ECE 750 – "SPRING 2013",
CS 846 – "WINTER 2013",
Online Software Security Course–racist–extreme – "WINTER 2013",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
program verification,
model checking,
YERITH R&D — [Cyber–SECURITY],
compiler design]

Summary–PAGES

Table 12: Visited Courses as post–doctoral researcher professor at THE university–racist of waterloo, ontario, canada–idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 750 - Patrick Lam" / "88%"	SPRING 2013	Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 846 - FRANK Tip" / "88%"	WINTER 2013	Program Analysis for Web Apps	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "Online Software Security Course–racist–extreme" / "85%"	WINTER 2013	Online Software Security Course–racist–extreme	Stanford university adult education online

Table 12 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral PH.D. studies degree program in Electrical & Computer Engineering at the UNIVERSITY–white–racist of waterloo.

1.) [Program Analysis for Web Apps]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to DISCOVER, design and implement a web–based dynamic TAINT analysis for a PHP–JAVA interpreter; I.E. a "JAVA application server" that also interprets and use PHP libraries and code :

📄 "A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) :

1. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)
2. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)

2.) [Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to design and implement a static TAINT dataflow analysis: 📄 YERITH–SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293/>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

I didn't appreciate that instructor PATRICK–lam came to contest my Correct and Righteous definition of taint source and taint sink in front of class during my presentation; AND THAT he was wrong when he said we shall check the internet media; IT DOESN'T make sense to contest something that a doctor–PH.D. has prepared at least 4 weeks in advance such as he did !!!

3.) [Online Software Security Course–racist–extreme]:

I took this software security course to acquire more knowledge in software security vulnerability analysis and detection from a pioneer–leader as university in this area of research as demonstrated by publications and startups created by alumni.

MONICA–lam (<https://stanford.edu/suif>) for instance is a very renowned scholar and tech–entrepreneur in security vulnerability research and analysis. THIS online web course was very interesting from a content point of view for me as a doctor–of–engineering–ph.d..

ESPECIALLY because I WAS working on my "YERITH–SAINT algorithm" (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) FOR detecting, with static dataflow code analysis "à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)", and fixing the HEARTBLEED–security breach bug in "OpenSSL–1.0.1–F" source code (<https://heartbleed.com>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

"BUT i could notify when i started passing the online examination for getting a printed sent per mailbox certificate; THAT there was a kind of re–make in another stand so "that I WOULD NEVER PASS with more than 95%" as required to acquire that certificate – (I HAD PAID around \$500 USA dollars for attending this online graduate adult education course)" !!! "

"I Was almost always getting a "84% grade" ("3 times") ! THIS actually represents the successful passing required academic grade for a doctoral level course at WATERLOO."

"I HAD EVEN visited the premises of STANFORD university together with SANDY–beidu–gay–idiot–from–ghana–cuon–pd "in year 2011" while attending a formal method techniques school at AHERTON–COLLEGE nearby "by around 40 minutes drive"."

YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

- I have prepared, and presented a static dataflow analysis in November 2010 at *IBM workshop CDP CASCONE 2010* (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>).

[Workshop-CDP; IBM casCon 2010]

The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software.

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for courses:

1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)";
2. "Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)".

- I have successfully attended the course ("CS 745 / ECE 725") – *Computer-Aided Verification* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>), taught by "Prof. Dr. Nancy Day". I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-ECE 725

THIS psy-professor is somewhat "a culprit of canadian armed robber forces only for black-descendants; Including iranian; holy-bible-CYRUS-ISIAH-45" (<https://www.sainteibible.com/lsg/isaiah/45.htm>).

1. OCAML functional programming language
2. Propositional Logic
3. First Order Logic (Predicate logic)
4. Higher Order Logic (Lambda Calculus) "with Haskell"
5. Theorem Proving
6. Interactive Theorem Proving with "Isabelle HOL"
7. Model Checking (with use of "SMV model checker")
8. etc.

- *I have met in-person "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem" (HELP with understanding of static dataflow analysis algorithms): "Especially with context-sensitive parametric analysis".*

- *I have as roommate and best-friend [Diplom-Ingenieur-Informatik (Dipl.-Ing.-Inf.)] THOMAS REIDEMEISTER, 'aus MAGDEBURG'. He is also a computer engineer graduate student "in ECE at THE university of Waterloo, ON".*

THOMAS (<https://www.reidemeister.com>) is so much helping to myself including recommending myself a "JAPANESE toyota corolla LE 2003-(plate BLAB 045)" car as buying tip because of low costs in maintenance in ontarian-Canada.

I learned at least 80% of a happyfull life in ontarian Canada from THOMAS as a kind of senior brother of mine.

- (a) Difference between brunch and lunch; with an invitation for a brunch in KITCHENER: I cannot remember the name of this very nice restaurant by a sunday-morning;
- (b) Farmer's market in Kitchener;
- (c) * * *—*Asian food market stores in Kitchener*—* * *;
- (d) etc.

"THOMAS moved-in into our student house as replacement for a nigerian so called CHRISTIAN-faked TOMIWA ADAMURULA (tom)."

"AS I have matured myself, "today, in 2024, "September 1st," THOMAS must be from NAZI-ss-combat engineering against black-descendants like "cameroonian MARTIN tchangoue", employed at LABFORGE.CA (<https://www.labforge.ca>)".

I could remember being very happy all time with * * *—*JOHN and ANNA GULDEMOND*—* * * the sweet-nice landlords.

20.20 YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

— I have met in-person Prof. Dr. Eric Bodden at our (Xavier, JON eyolfson) office room in "Davis Center".

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. **"Program Verification (Ph.D. thesis from Patrick LAM)"** (<https://patricklam.ca>)
2. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book **"Introduction to Algorithms"** ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVfEd1BzcVOqunH6HMFduvfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwlldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));)
3. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;
5. Static Dataflow Analysis by Gary A. KILDALL (<a href=));
 - a. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) ;
 - b. **"Tracematches formalism by Hendren, Lhoták, et al."** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>)

— *I have attended following workshops and conferences:*

[IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

1. **"IBM workshop CDP CASCON 2010"** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)
 - a. I could talk briefly with Patrick Doyle from **J9-JAVA** (<https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/configurepricequote/10.0?topic=machines-j9-jvm>) JIT-compilation team at IBM Toronto Software Lab
 - b. **Maxime Boisvert Chevallier** (<https://scholar.google.ca/citations?user=ISg6I8gAAAAJ&hl=en>)

[OOPSLA 2010]

3. *"I have attended the conference **"Programming Language Design And Implementation (PLDI 2009)"** in Toronto:"*

[International CONFERENCE-pldi-racist-extreme; PLDI 2009]

- o **Pr. Prof. Dr. JEAN yang, she was a then Ph.D. student and candidate at "MIT"** (<https://people.csail.mit.edu/jeanyang/index.htm>) " (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>) .
- o **"Nurudeen Lameed (from Nigeria)** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~nlamee>)", "and other **SABLE-mcgill** (<https://sable.mcgill.ca>) graduate students" and I presented to each other;
- o **"Pr. Prof. Dr. Tom Ball from Microsoft Research (MSR)** (<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/people/tball>)", and I presented each other.
- o **"Florian Zuleger (from Austria)** (<https://informatics.tuwien.ac.at/people/florian-zuleger>)", and I presented each other.
- o **"Stephan Zucker, PhD (from Switzerland)** (<https://>)", and I presented each other.

21.21 YEAR "2011"

Summary-PAGES

— "December 20th, 2011":

I have prepared and successfully passed my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination in front of at least 4 experts in Software System:

1. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.
2. Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
3. Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
4. Prof. Dr. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

— I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for course:

1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)".

— I have successfully attended the course "CS 744" – **Advanced Compiler Design** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/cs744>), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták".

I could learn about following topics:

1. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)
2. Meet Over Paths (MOP)
3. Basic Block (BB), Control Flow Graph (CFG)
4. Three-Address-Code ("3-Address-Code")
5. Static Single Assignment Form ("SSA form")
6. Pointer (Alias) Analysis
7. Static Dataflow Analysis by **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall);
8. Transfer flow functions
9. Components of an advanced Compiler (E.g.: Optimizer, backend, etc.)

COURSE-CS 744

— I have met in-person "**Michael Pradel**". (https://software-lab.org/people/Michael_Pradel.html)

— I have met in-person "**ALEXIE tcheuyap-idiot-cuon-pd**". (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheuyap>)

— **I have, in summer 2011, received a personal visit of "Mae Wandji", baby of my uncle maternal "Théodore & Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoun": she was accompanied by "her mother Aurélie Yagno Wandji" ! "Mae Wandji", and her mother "Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoun", I dedicate a successful PhD comprehensive examination ! "**

— I have met in-person **Prof. Dr. MARTIN vechev**. (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aZ1Rh50AAAAJ&hl=fr>)

— I attended successfully the summer school: "**First Summer School on Formal Techniques**" (<https://fm.cs.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>); organized by The "National Science Foundation (NSF)" located at SOFTWARE RESEARCH INSTITUTE INTERNATIONAL (SRI International), at "Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA" from May 22, 2011 until May 27, 2011.

[ATHERTON-COLLEGE] / ["1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"–2011]

Topics we learned about and practiced where among others:

- o "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Natarayan Shankar")
- o "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. David Moniaux")
- o "Hardware / Software Co-Design"
- o "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Villem WISSER–neger-racist-stelenbosch-university-SA")

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book "**Introduction to Algorithms**" ([Holy-Ghost. YERITH-NISSI. \(JEVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN.\)](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-to-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVFeD1BzcVOqunH6HMFduvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));
2. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
3. JAVA component-based software development by OSI architecture and Eclipse IDE (Integrated Development Environment);
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;

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22.22 YEAR "2012"

Summary-PAGES

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick & Derek Rayside & Jon Eyolfson & Leo Passos, etc. for courses:
 1. "Compilers (ECE 351)": *Python scripts were written to automatically correct programming assignments from code source repositories.*
- *I went for an academic and professional internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab;*

I wanted to improve my programming languages design and implementation skills as well as BASH-scripting.

I spent 2 Academic terms (8 months) in Markham (Ontario, Canada) for this internship.

I worked there under supervision of [*Patrick Doyle, M.ASc.*,] and then "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*".

 - o I worked principally as a tester for certain optimization features of the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server (Servlet container) *IBM Websphere* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IBM_WebSphere_Application_Server) under "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*". I was writing BASH-scripts to run and evaluate implemented certain optimization features for the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server.
 - o I could attend to lectures given at IBM Toronto Software Lab by "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Clark Verbrugge*" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>) from "*McGill University*" on Creating Optimizations for Compilers.
 - o I could improve my skills with the following tools among others:
 1. "GNU-bash" (<ftp://ftp.gnu.org/pub/gnu/bash>)
 2. "GNU-vi / GNU-vim" (<https://www.vim.org>)
 3. "GNU-screen" (<https://savannah.gnu.org/projects/screen>).
- "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*" wanted myself to be back next summer for another internship with him at IBM: unfortunately I resigned from this engagement because I felt I had to go back in my home country: Cameroon !
- I befriended myself at IBM with "*Aayush Prakash, M.ASc. (Waterloo, 2013)*" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>).
 1. I had a toyota corolla 2007 LUXUS EDITION; that's why Aayush PRAKASH 1st contacted me so I could help him mornings.

I tried trice but I COULDN'T anymore because I COULDN'T wake up so early; because MARKHAM is a very big city with so much traffic. BUT WE STAYED friend for ever.

THX. BRO.
 2. We then became roommate in Waterloo the following fall (September – December) term; I COULD appreciate someone nice and very comfortable with my living style since I am the one that was principally renting the 2-bedroom apartment on 16-457 ALBERT-STREET.

HE never not paid his subrent; and was also kind to learn more about how to better maintain a common washroom.

THEN he moved to IBM after successfully graduating with a M.ASc. in Electrical & Computer Engineering from PROFESSOR-racist HIREN-patel-racist !

I then went several times to visit AAYUSH when he moved to Toronto.
- I befriended myself in Toronto with the following fellow Cameroonian:
 1. "~~Prof. Dr. Alexie Tcheyap, Ph.D. (Laval, "French Literature", Quebec, Canada, 2008)~~" (~~GAY-maker-assassin !~~) (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheyap>);
 2. "Erick Djeuyou Pokem, B.ASe. (Lilles, "Business Informatics-MIAGE", France, 2007)";
 3. "Audrey Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc. (Laval, "Actuarial Sciences", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 4. "Judith Ngaleu, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Telecommunication Engineering", Quebec, Canada, 2005)";
 5. "Eunice Gapie Yemte, B.Sc. (Luxembourg, "Software Engineering", Luxembourg, 2008)" (assassin);
 6. "Valérie Yogho, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Electrical Engineering Power", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 7. "Tobie Guilliane, M.Sc. (Paris, "Financial Accounting", France, 2008)" (ASSASSIN);
 8. "Francis Mbiele Kamga, MBA (ESG, "Business Management", Paris, France, 2007)" (ASSASSIN).
 9. "~~FABRICE wilfried siemeni, B.Eng., (FH Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2005); Diploma (IHN, "applied HOLISTIC NUTRITIONIST", Mississauga, Toronto, Canada, 2012); -M.Sc. (FH Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2006)~~" (ASSASSIN).
- *I have attended following workshops and conferences in 2012*, together with "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM, Ph.D.*" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>), after completion of the internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab (*IBM Canada Ltd* (<https://www.ibm.com>)):

[WORKSHOP-local MITACS Ontario; International CONFERENCE; PLdi 2012]

 1. "*MITACS Ontario* (<https://www.mitacs.ca>) at the University of Waterloo on how to behave properly when having lunch and dessert with other professionals."
 2. "*Programming Language Design and IMPLEMENTATION (PLDI 2012)*" (<https://>) in Toronto downtown.
 1. *I COULD TALK TO several researcher among employees of GRAMMATECH-racist-negger* (<https://www.grammatech.com>) from THOMAS-reps at WISCONSIN-madison. (<https://www.wisc.edu>)

23.23 YEAR "2013"

Summary-PAGES

— I talked in-person with "Mahesh Tripunitara" about some of my non understanding about Doctor-PhD advisor of mine "Patrick Lam"; "MAHESH TRIPUNITARA" said I shall look for research collaborations within University of Waterloo and just put the name of "Patrick LAM" at end of a publication !

I AM STILL VERY GRATEFUL for this insight into my life as a scientist that led me to try and talk successfully with following pro-eminent fellow computer scientist:

- "Vijay Ganesh"; very proud of having learned much of how to write a paper and / or reviews of other papers with him; I cannot be a Ph.D. or doctor without this collaboration !

THIS IS SOMEONE very good at teaching research skills only. I cannot say much about his private behavior since I generally don't mix my private life with professional life !

- ["Mohammad Hamdaqa" from THE STAR research lab (<https://star.uwaterloo.ca>)]
- "Aayush Prakash" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>) (from IBM internship in Markham)
- "Leo Passos" from Generative Software Development research group at university of waterloo (<https://gsd.uwaterloo.ca/~lpassos>)
- "Frank Tip" (from IBM Research then as Professor at the University of Waterloo): AT all the very much inspirational about 'A SO CALLED taint analysis' in my research area at all.

Before visiting CS846 of "Frank Tip", I cannot know anything about what is a Taint Analysis (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

THIS CS846 (Program Analysis of Web Apps) is my best course as a graduate student in terms of working on related papers and writing reviews. Frank Tip is a very good and proud research manager !!!

"Only 1 tip, and you get all the clue about what you really need to do."

- "Pavel Parizek" (https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=M_9_-WsAAAAJ&hl=en) (from Programming Language Research Group (PLG) (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>), invited by "Ondřej Lhoták")
- "BORZOO" (<https://>) (very respected in RV conferences series)

THIS [friend-kkk] of sebastian fischmeister from AUSTRIA-adolf-hitler (<https://uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>) is so kind that he let myself in his office to present what I really want to perform as research. BUT i could notify an office with kind of ground-tapestry for WHAT-the-fuck.

24.24 YEAR "2013, 2ND PAGE"

Summary-PAGES

— I co-taught and assigned marked with "Mahesh Tripunitara" and "Igor Ivkovic" for courses:

- 1.) "Computer Networks (ECE 428)";
- 2.) " * * * Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) * * * "
- 3.) " * * * Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) * * * ".

Several employees from "Google Waterloo Inc. (<https://www.google.ca>) " attended lectures ("Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651)", and "Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650)");

[DIVAM JAIN racist from CA-U.S.A. even tried to make me hired there once ...].

— I started implementing a *LLVM context-sensitive solution to my Research Proposal Thesis* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) ; Because *SPARK pointer analysis in SOOT* (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) didn't permit for pointer-analysis data as a stand-alone pre-processing step, as *my early design of the static dataflow analysis suggested* (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

— I have successfully attended the course [Program Analysis of Web Apps ("CS 846")], taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr. Frank Tip" (<https://northeastern.edu/~ftip>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-CS 846

1. web applications
2. Javascript
3. dynamic analysis
4. static dataflow analysis
5. "Quercus server" dynamic taint analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) [3] by practicing within a personal single project
6. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have successfully attended the course Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE) ("ECE 750"), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-SASE-ECE 750

1. dynamic analysis
2. static dataflow analysis
3. "static taint analysis" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34] by practicing within a personal single project:

"I am the only one who had this idea of performing static taint analysis, because I previously did a dynamic taint analysis in FRANK-TIP-CS846—racist-course. *THE CS OF UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO wasn't* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca>) even capable of [finding this racist-cs846 segregative course curriculum] when I asked for it in year 2022; Even FTP, the creator of it WASN'T confident to give it to a black from AFRICA ! "

[r-IT Seems NDJATIE-from-rotary commanded again FTP from the inside.]; *EVEN her husband ["pr. shanda; YVAN-plumber-bafang-babouantou"]*, is very well recommended by YAOUNDEACS these days. (<https://>)

[AHHHH, also THE general of science KLAUS HAVELUND from N.A.S.A (<https://www.nasa.gov/YaoundeACS>) was also invited by my emails so to acquire some knowledge about [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF] since his paper with SFISCHME wasn't very proper.] (<https://www.ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>)

4. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have On the website of *stanford university* (<https://www.stanford.edu>) in the state of CALIFORNIA; IN-the-U.S "unsuccessfully (with "84% grade") attended" the course *Software Security*. I could learn about following topics:

[STANFORD.EDU—online-course-software-security 2013]

1. PRIVATE / PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE—key (GPG); CERTIFICATE—authority
2. CYPHER DECYPHER CRYPTOGRAPHY—algorithm
3. SSL-Secure—socket—layer protocol on HTTP protocol
4. ATTACKS strategies:
 1. SQL injection
 2. Buffer—overflow attack
 3. MAN-IN-MIDDLE attack
5. etc.

25.25 YEARS "2014" – "03 / 2015"

Summary-PAGES

— I find a very imposing book that explains in my better terms algorithms fixed point static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>):

- "*Advanced Compiler Design & Implementation*"; ISBN: "978-1558603202", by Steven Muchnick.

THIS book doesn't destroy your brain like the book:

- "*PRINCIPLES OF PROGRAM ANALYSIS*"; ISBN: "978-3642084744", by Flemming Nielson.

I implemented my own static dataflow fixed point algorithm in C++ object-oriented, and I published it on my student Ph.D. page <https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~xnoumbis>; And on my defunct GITHUB.COM-web-page: <https://github.com/xnoundou/saint>.

I then improved and finished my static dataflow taint analysis, and starts preparing my Ph.D. research seminar as presented in booklets present in "ECE graduate students room" in EIT building !

NOT very long after this online internet-web publication; I LEAVE WATFFORM for Cameroon where I created YERITH R&D, and affiliated software systems programs.

— I met Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) in-person for a review of my created LLVM context-sensitive static dataflow analysis: HE WAS RELUCTANT only because of 1 missing application of the analysis.

— *I assisted students in the LABORATORY for coding in C++ during 2 weeks:*

C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)

1. "C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)".

[!!! Iranian canadian university of waterloo professors !]!!

My colleague JON EYOLFSON (<https://jeyolfson.com>) with Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan (<https://ece.star.uwaterloo.ca>), went to suppress my appointment illegally since I legally, according to ECE department regulations for 2 weeks vacation for personal illness purposes, sent JON eyolfson as a replacement laboratory instructor to myself to LADAN !

I couldn't recover my job as teaching assistant in laboratory at my stay-return from JON EYOLFSON that I sent to Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan, for only 2 weeks replacement of myself !

— I have prepared, and presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis in January 2015 at a DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE programming language research group (PLG) seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Dissertation Defense at PLG]

I had this work successfully approved at PLG by "dear-racist-idiot Ondřej Lhoták" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>).

The title of my talk was: **CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM** (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) ; the presented application was the finding of a buffer-overflow security vulnerability in SSL (Secure Socket Layer) protocol as found in the "HEARTBLEED bug" (<https://heartbleed.com>) .

"Dr.-PH.D. ALI TELAGHANI was the 1st iranian university of waterloo Ph.D. Candidate I reviewed. A former trainee of nancy day from watform. (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>) "

AT THE conference presentation table were present among others :

- (a) Pr. Prof. Dr. MAGNUS MADSEN (<https://www.cs.au.dk/~magnusm>)
- (b) Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. "Peter Alan Burh" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/about/people/pabuhr>)
- (c) etc.

— I have prepared, and successfully presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis on "April 16, 2014" at an ECE graduate seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Research Seminar]

The title of my talk was: **CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM** (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) .

There was around at least 20 other students attending this seminar (kind of lecture).

[The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software by static dataflow taint analysis.]

26.26 RESEARCH OUTCOME HINDRANCE

Summary-PAGES

IT WASN'T POSSIBLE TO IMPLEMENT THE STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS AS PRESENTED because of the non possibility to acquire points-to information as a pre-processing standalone phase/step from SPARK POINTER ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK IN SOOT.

It wasn't in my research interest for a "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering" to dive into recreating a pointer analysis for SOOT by modifying for instance research outcome work of "AAKARSH NAIR, MASC (2009)".

It would be more productive to perform research with "Ondřej Lhoták" in "Mathematics Department at DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) rather than with DR.-PH.D Patrick LAM at ECE Department. So I stayed out of this area of research for the "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering"; Computer Software Engineering is more focused on developing methodologies around software rather than creating complex computer algorithms for calculation purposes; AS this is done in Computer Sciences (E.g.: "Ph.D. in Computer Science").

It is somehow also feasible for a "Computer Software Engineer" easily to implement a "pointer analysis as a Ph.D. in Computer Sciences could do whenever needed" !

I ("Doctor–PH.D. of Engineering Xavier Noubissi Noundou") have, for instance demonstrated, I could at least at level of a pointer dataflow analysis design and implementation performed by implementing the 1st openly (FOSS) published on the internet (2015): [CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC DATAFLOW ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ! \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\) \[34\]](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) : "git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>".

27.27 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM

Summary-PAGES

- 1st of all, I need to mention that JON eyolfson has tried to remove all connections to my person in his documents I could see on the internet media and / or wherever else.

FOR instance, JON eyolfson doesn't mention anymore he reviewed papers for OOPSLA 2010; I ASSUME because my name stays also in the document viewable from the web I COULD SEE last .. (https://dl.acm.org/action/showFmPdf?doi=10.1145%2F1869459&ved=2ahUKEwiboYOExb6IAxXdgP0HHfm0A2YQFnoECCIQ&usq=A0vVaw0DwvmxPoRXI7v__J6preu)

"Doctor–PH.D of Engineering JON EYOLFSON" (<https://www.ece.utoronto.ca/people/eyolfson-j>) could for instance implement a Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall) static dataflow pointer analysis based on my research outcome in ["XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU'S DOCTORAL EXCERPT DISSERTATION" \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293); Even though he didn't cite my previous work and also Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

Instead, HE WENT ON TO CITE "John B Kam and Jeffrey D. Ullman", in 'Monotone Data Flow Analysis Frameworks' !

I could also notify that the description of the flow functions in JON EYOLFSON's doctoral thesis, Acknowledged by "Professor Doctor–PH.D of ENGINEERING "Ана-Міланова" from RIP (Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute) (<https://www.cs.rpi.edu/~milanova>)", Wasn't compliant to the highest academical standard as IT IS DUE for a university in ONTARIO–CANADA.

"Jon" instead of performing a pre-processed step pointer analysis result searching, went on to implement a whole program static dataflow analysis, INCORPORATING an LLVM-based pointer analysis, copied from my work, Without citing it ("I finished that work in 2015", While "JON Eyolfson" defended his Ph.D. thesis containing this pointer analysis in 2018).

"I could also note it seems ["Ondřej Lhoták"] wasn't a member of JON eyolfson dissertation defence examination committee (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), even though HE ('Ondřej Lhoták") is the most famous scientist in this area of research at the UNIVERSITY of WATERLOO based on his publication and citation record (<https://dblp.org/pid/05/469.html>). "

Better said HE is kind of a JOHN–Hopcroft level academical professional scientist based on my research time worldwide & abroad of GERMANY & Cameroon–Africa !

2. " My intellectual and copyrighted work with "DIVAM JAIN, M.Math", now at ["Google Waterloo Inc."] (<https://jobs.google.com/about/>), has by now produced at least 11 scientific published papers worldwide, with money rewards, [without my name on neither on them.]"

INSTEAD, other people reward from it:

1. Dr. Patrick LAM;
2. Dr. Reid Holmes;
3. Dr. Derek rayside;
4. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc. (<https://dblp.org/pid/170/1472.html>)"; (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)
5. etc.

QUARRELED PAPERS:

1. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

Plagiarism

28.28 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM – CONTINUED – 1

Summary-PAGES

1. "Professor Araving Machinry" also used code sources results from my Static Dataflow Analysis without any citation of it in his Award winning USENIX paper; I mailed him in 2017; HE said that my work wasn't published by a peer-refereed conference and/or workshop, or whatsoever, THAT'S WHY he couldn't cite it.

Instead of citing the 1st original publication of a Free and Open Source Software code (FOSS), 2015, As I have published in on 'www.github.com (git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>)'; ARAVIND cited instead my competitor BODDEN-ERIC (<https://www.bodden.de>) (from Germany (<https://www.fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Allemagne>) and Previous colleague of Patrick LAM (<https://www.patricklam.ca>) at McGill University (<https://www.mcgill.ca>)).

Long after terminating my research collaboration with Patrick LAM at University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA; I could then notify that he was talking especially to "ARAVIND machinry my competitor about my research under his supposed supervision without telling it to myself!"

2. A ghanaiian ignorant, wretched worldwide called SANDY-beidu thinks he could behave so to alter my JEOVAH-NISSI-confidence at his underground-peggist home in bavaria-waterloo.

BEcause I rented a "ford fusion" during my travel to the "1st summer school on formal techniques" in ATHERTON, california; So to be mobile because I HAD TRAVELED to united states of america before when I WAS an employee of bavarian Siemens-medical-solutions; THIS guja went on to buy as his 1st car a similar "ford fusion" since he thought I WANTED to show up in front of him and ANOTHER black-afro-descendant from long-islands.

I AM EVEN wondering how this lady from basement science could be invited to the summer school ! AT ALL ! may be a call-girl !

FROM academic level point of view, this ignorant doctor of philosophy in computer science, SeEms to ignore what I COULD BUILD AS [enterprise resource planing (ERP-system) software !!!!!!!!]

3. JAN peleska from GERMANY, didn't say anything about the law against myself in Cameroon because he is the one who went to report false behaviors of myself to Cammeroon authorities about my living style in Germany without telling anything to me about.

Even at German Embassy in Yaounde, I could notify a strange behavior of people working there against myself while I came to complain against FRANGK-BIYA, son of PAUL-BIYA. THIS-GAY-with-my cousin-PATRICE-GABRAL-SHANDA-SANOU (deceased by now since March 18, 2024 went to destroy my investment by creating a forestry society just opposite of my lawful building for peaceful habitation usage) !

JAN peleska from GERMANY, also seems to be the one that said and commanded PATRICK LAM to destroy my career because I reluctantly refused to pursue doctoral Ph.D. research (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/gesy>) under his supervision at the University of Bremen; I.E. Jan peleska insulted violently myself in front of HELGE LOEDING (<https://www.LOEDING-ONLINE.de>), SERGE FOPOUSSI NONO ACHILLE (<https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/person/gnd/141875240>), etc.

I cannot live with racial segregation !

Figure 34: YERITH-SAINT ([LGPL license]) Algorithms Architecture. "poolalloc" pointer-alias analysis tool from "Chris Lattner" at "APPLE Ltd." is re-used.

Figure 35: A sample **API rule violation** as tainted path "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i)) L4–L7–L9–L10–L11" (orange colored lines of code); on LLVM THREE-ADDRESS-CODE.

```

1      ssize_t write(int fd, const void *buf, size_t count); // taint sink
2
3      uint SAVE_Document (unsigned x, int fd, const void *buf, size_t count) {
4  L1: uint sum = 0;
5  L2: uint i = 0;
6  L3: if ( x == 2)
7  L4: close(fd); //API rule violation(--taint) source; "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i))"
8  L5: else //not VALID api rule check !
9  L6: sum = 0;
10 L7: if ( i >= x)
11 L8: goto L12;
12 L9: sum = sum + i;
13 L10: i = i + 1;
14 L11: write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i));
15 L12: goto L6;
16 L13: return sum; }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of [Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by taint analysis] – Continued

b. Doctoral "Ph.D. degree" Dissertation in Electrical & Computer Engineering: "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"; (Advised by Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem | Pr. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Frank Tip | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Vijay Ganesh) |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[SEP. 2012 – AUG. 2015]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH TYPESTATE-API USAGE RULE CHECKING; STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM[1d]))

[JUNE 2024 – JUNE 2024]

[Software Safety, API (application programming interfaces) tystate checking, tracematches, temporal safety property verification, cyber-security, software security vulnerability analysis, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION, Disputation-january-2015-DC-room-PETER-ALAN-BUHR]

The same class of problems that solve taint analysis issues resolve also API usage rules checking for specification of forbidden usage rules as a tystate specification. A violated API tystate (tracematch-alike) usage rule corresponds to a tainted path or a sub-tainted path (E.g.: path "L4–L7–L9–L10–L11" in figure 35).

You specify a forbidden (fail trace) [sequence of method calls that shall not occur in the source code]. Using static dataflow taint analysis, you check whether this specified forbidden (fail trace) corresponds to a tainted path or a subpath (of a fail trace).

"API (application programming interfaces) usage rules [tystate formalism is a similar paradigm of specification possible for input for this static context-sensitive taint analysis; "subsequent research of mine alone reveals state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) as a subset of tystates (SDMM[1d]),"] of JAVA or C++ library are another realm of application of this static context-sensitive (parametric) dataflow taint analysis."

"In contrast to Tracematches that specifies WISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM TRACE) of API user interface rule calling method sequence; as illustrated in "Hendren, et al. work" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>), "state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) BY XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU, SPECIFIES UNWISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM FORBIDDEN FAIL TRACE)" (SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d])."

"One effort could be to give a formal translation methodology from "tracematches onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM)"; Thus enabling automatic reuse of all tracematch specifications directly into a runtime monitor engine like YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) ."

"Patrick has not at time understood that this application is also possible by static dynamic program analysis tool created by myself at YERITH-RD: YRI_QVGE[13.13]; a Free and Open Source Code Software (FOSS)."

"Patrick LAM my former advisor since '2015-MARCH-10' is missing !"

"Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented a short overview presentation of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)"

A SINK IS AN ACCEPTING (error) STATE; A SOURCE IS A START STATE. Sources and sinks are methods from the library (or plugin) used by the program under analysis (PUA). Edges are other method program instructions as seen by a THREE-Address-Code representation such as Jimple (SOOT), Gimple (GCC), etc., and, or LLVM three-address-code format.

Since YERITH-SAINT our (Xavier, Vijay, and Patrick) static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, and perform as well API USAGE RULE check.

IT means in effect that any programming language that could be inputted to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, COULD BENEFIT FROM THIS SOFTWARE STACK api (application programming interface) rule checker.

- YERITH-SAINT (Figure 34) : [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)
- [PH.D.—RESEARCH—SEMINAR TALK] GIVEN AT AN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING) GRADUATE SEMINAR TALK SERIES, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf)

"Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), A world renowned scholar and scientist from the University of Waterloo in Waterloo, Canada, Ontario; Has reviewed this work with only 1 recommendation: add an additional application sample example apart from the presented "FORMAT STRING VULNERABILITY (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uncontrolled_format_string)" analysis done in the research paper."

1. *L' INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE—Yaoundé—Centre D'excellence PAUL—biya—rdpc. |*
 INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE, YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION, CAMEROUN

"2016"

[1 *institut* (<https://www.iaicameroun.cm>) atypique,
 ARMAND—claude abanda,
 NANGA.]

Summary-PAGES

I. D'enseignant vacataire à ENSEIGNANT consultant "20 heures—la—semaine de cours" À "6,11 EUROS" par heure:

Mes rapports d'encadreurs académiques de SALABESSI—cuon—pgsiste de MBANJOCK :

1. *JE postule via "4 heures" d'attente au sale bureau du courrier pour être reçu par 1 ingénieur inférieur au rang de "bachelor of science" (ndlr.: LICENCE en informatique);*
2. *Après être reçu pour 1 entretien special avec M.ARMAND—claude—abanda—idiot; je passe 2 interviews supposées professionnelles;*
3. *A l'issue de la 1^{ère} interview qui n'est qu'1 vérification brève du curriculum vitae et de très petites connaissances pédagogiques; L'ON ME propose plutôt 1 poste d'ENSEIGNANT consultant plutôt que celui de vacataire à 8 heures de cours hebdomadaire auquel j'ai postulé.*
4. *L'on ma redemandé de donner tous des cours que je pensais être en mesure de distillés; SUR cette palette de cours, l'on m'a octroyé "Architecture des ordinateurs" comme 1^{ère} mission pour la 1^{ère} année de GÉNIE—LOGIGIEL en section anglophone de leurs cursus d'études.*
5. *Après seulement "2 semaines et demi", 1 certain "salabessi" vient me donner l'injonction de commencer aussi à donner le cours "ADMINISTRATION SYSTÈME programmation système".*
6. *JE décide de partir de cette institution puisque ce rythme de travail serait insoutenable pour ma santé fragile à cette période de l'année au vu du changement du climat hivernale canadien au climat tempéré de YAOUNDE—raciste—tribaliste—mado—BIR :*
 - a.) *Toute heure de cours est payée ("8 heures par semaine" dans mon cas); IL ne m'est jamais mentionnée auparavant que 20 heures de travail la semaine ne concerne que la dispensation des cours au tableau.*
 - b.) *Toute autre heure de travail est impayée :*
 - *PRÉPARATION des données pour des devoirs surveillés;*
 - *CORRECTION des examens et devoirs surveillés;*
 - *RÉDACTION d'1 support de cours en langue anglaise.*
 - *[IL semblerait que 1 sœur utérine à ma personne; "Ingride TCHITCHUI noumbissi, Épse chandriand—TEUNTCHOU noumeni" serait allée dire que je suis 1 patient psychiatrique pour destituer ma vie, telle qu'elle aurait organisée en FÉVRIER 2021 avec le "rotary—club de abanda armand à ÉDEA".]*
 - *PARTICIPATION tous des mercredi à 1 réunion d'enseignants consultants; (EX.nihilo; je n'ai participé à aucune d'elle en 3 semaines de travail vu le temps d'adaptation à la localisation très éloigné du centre de cours de NKOLN'ANGA).*

II. Mes Conclusions SUR LA QUALITÉ de cet institut de merde :

- 1.) *[JP-kamgain, le cas d'échec patent de l'IAI cameroun !!!]*
- 2.) *PAS de suivi exact des besoins et difficultés de nouvelles recrues;*
- 3.) *ABANDA—amougou—belinga (<https://>), écroulé par des heures de cours sans avisé des enseignants :
2 fois consécutives, on me redemande de dispenser plutôt 4 heures de cours et exercices d'affilés plutôt que des 2 heures de cours prévues dans le "planning" pour CAUSE que l'enseignant du cours suivant s'est absenté.*

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
Jon eyolfson—idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
SARAH—white—kkk—peggist; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. ["Professor RAYSIDE"]

2. ["Student JON eyolfson, then Master of Applied Science JON."]

" This idiot white-supremacist-racist, that is watching videos about a murderer called 'LUCIFER' in our common office room while taking his lunch, is JUST A DISGUSTING kkk."

THIS junior computing engineer couldn't create a website for Watform lab (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>) after around 7 years doing a PH.D. in Computer Electrical Engineering: HE Had been mandated to do so in year 2009 when I started my "Ph.D. degree in Electrical & Computer Engineering" program as a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]. from the so-called-elite-universität-BREMEN-germany-de. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)!

3. "Student Hang chu (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/2656af1b-8829-45fb-bc5b-d1f49762ad49>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science HANG—chu."

THIS very-well-to-do person from China main island came to myself for a recommendation into a position as software developer in MISSISSAUGA-Toronto-idiot; I Accepted and tried to be very honest and humble in a form request form that was sent to myself the same day by a lady from "PHILLIPS subsidiary company" newest created !

4. "Student Wenzhu MAN (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/5ac24928-7279-41f1-9c58-634873430305>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science Wenzhu—MAN."

THIS ugly lady from CHINA main island, came into the lab-space rented to us by PATRICK-idiot-advisor during my 2nd year of doctoral PH.D. studies.

SHE seemed very intelligent but very hostile to black people as I could see her behavior when I asked her if she would like to collaborate on my ongoing static dataflow analysis YERITH-SAINT project, after I ASKED for this with, a positive approval from our common idiot supervisor ["PATRICK-vietnamese-vietkong LAM"].

SHE was reluctant and we never had any opportunity to present and/or Work on anything together; AS this was the same with [JON eyolfson; Who instead copied my work only !]

5. "PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG, WEST REGION, CAMEROON)"

" THIS sample ignorant on "algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers" that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the "ELITE-UNIVERSITÄT-BREMEN" (<https://www.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON."

"I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes-FRANCE in "2004" when he visited "GRENOBLE laboratory" with PROFESSOR tchindo-gilbert."

"I tried to contact him during "September-2011" because I HEARD from MARCELIN TALLY, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?] " like our common age-class colleague Oscar MOURBARE from Ngaoundere-Cameroon. [Dr.-Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS-Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>). "

"HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone call while I was in Cameroon ! "

ISSUES and Misunderstandings 2 |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
 Jon eyolfson-idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
 SARAH—white—kkk-peggish; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. **ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:**

6. "FORMER friend and now enemy Godrick CHEKETE H. from Benin—vaoodoo"

I encounter this idiot and voodoo man as I just entered my second year of doctoral studies at the university—racist of waterloo in ONTARIO, CANADA

THE Ghanaian so called YAW BOAKYE-agyeman, that I EVER met 1st time in African student association of the university of waterloo: "AFRSA" (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>) as I was in my 3rd week in the city of Waterloo.

IT is the west—african student YAW, BOAKYE-agyeman, from ashanti—tribe that told myself that he would like to introduce me to another FRENCH-speaking student from WEST-AFRICA.

WE then met 3 of us in a restaurant inside the main campus located at 200 University Avenue West; I DON'T REMEMBER the name of the idiot-wwhite—racist restaurant for students.

7. "FORMER enemy MARTIAL ategomo YEMELE from Cameroon"

I encounter this vagabond because GODRICK—chekete recommended HIM (martial ategomo yemele to myself as a cameroon student in need of crucial help in life)

Normally I NEVER friend myself with such Cameroon people that seemed to have traveled with fake ID and other faked documents as I could imagine from his physical being.

IN year 2013, as I went to build a gate for my compound in YAOUNDE, Godrick and MARTIAL ATEGOMO YEMELE came ask myself that I sublet my bedroom-only for 1 month only to MARTIAL for "400 cad". I accepted and I needed afterwards to tell him very deeply to go out after "1 and half month" because HE seems to be wanting to stay even more than 6 months in my 2-bedroom apartment located at "16—457, ALBERT-ST., N2L 5A7, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA—racist-idiot".

Martial ategomo and Godrick Chekete H.; I stopped any collaboration with both these ignorant right after asking MARTIAL and GODRICK to leave my apartment around 11 : 30 PM at night.

8. "ECE Master & Ph.D. programs coordinator Sarah Landy, MSc."

THIS very racist girl with a master of science, arrogant at all wanted myself to believe that SHE is a professor of mine even though I am wondering even today if she could even work somewhere else than a place where systemic racism is the norm and not the ANORMAL life day—work !

"This slot for professors of ECE is the one that on "MARCH 10th, 2015" told myself; "as she was a PH.D. & MASTER program coordinator in ECE department" of the university-racist of waterloo: "[Patrick (lam)] sent an email to cancel the event (MY SO CALLED PH.D. RESEARCH SEMINAR) according to academic graduate studies regulations of year 2015 ! " "

" SARAH as I could experience even when I PASSED ONTO HER HANDS my doctoral thesis; called research proposal at ECE department, has a personal grievance to my person from somewhere I CANNOT even imagine; because THIS document wasn't published anywhere or registered publicly on the university-racist of waterloo internet, or intranet—world ! "

9. [Professor idiot lin tan]

10. P[rofessor Patrick LAM]

11. [Professor LADAN]

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "December 12, 2025"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA:

1. Doctor Christian Eyoum–sawa-rotarian–criminal–seasoned–psychiatrist (Laquintine HOSPITAL DOUALA, CMR (<https://>)) [Around "2021"]

THIS seasoned psychiatrist that assassinates at least 500 persons a year was sent to me by "ROSE sangnou" my female genitor so to hijack my private–inherited apartment in "DLA-cité-des-palmiers" as I was just finishing a psychology family and personal treatment because OF "LAURENT-tchandeu", a criminal uncle paternal side of mine.

IT is at age of 6 years old that I lost my dear criminal genitor "THÉODORE noumbissi-salau"; I called this genitor of mine a "salau" because this freemason had a booklet on economy written by "KARL–idiot-mars" where I COULD SEE just a month after his sudden death, caused probably by NTOMANI–Racist, THAT theodore-noumbissi said: "GOD is stupidity and dirt !" !

IT is at age 35 years old that I understood that this mason of my genitor, "THÉODORE noumbissi"; tried to hijack myself but loose his own soul because mainly of his junior brother "LAURENT tchandeu".

"CHRISTIAN-eyoum" is only someone that destroys in all plans of life any person sent to him by "SECRETARIAT-D'ÉTATA-LA-DEFENSE (sed)", a so called SERVICE-SECRET.

IT seems the culprit eyoum sent some people from his hospitals to rent my 1st–storey house bedroom-apartment so to hijack people that want to travel to western countries.

I am suspicious of this because I cannot foresee an issue in the legal case I started at DLA-ndokoti justice palace in February 14th; After christian eyoum and state hospital laquintinie sent at least 9 people at night around 23 : 30 to hijack my real–estate property and life.

Also, eyoum walks with a walkie-talkie of cameroonian defense forces; SO he is somewhat a criminal of the army that must be arrested by SEMIL–ndlr.: Sécurité MILITAIRE: a so called anti-gang unit against criminal from cmr defense forces.

2. Doctor KLAUS HAVELUND–idiot (Caltech, California Technology Institute CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (<https://www.caltech.edu>)) ["2022"]

Klaus is an idiot because HE wasn't capable of coming clearly with his expectations as I contacted him to review my at that time ongoing and starting project on CREATING A RUNTIME MONITORING VERIFICATION testing framework 📄 [YRI_QVGE\[1d\]](#) for state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) having following characteristics compared to opponents like; "TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System)" implemented in real-time testing tool 📄 [RT-Tester \(https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf\) \[?\]](https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) of the society in germany: "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) "; AND opponent tool ""DejaVu" (<https://>) ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic")" :

- o A Domain–Specific LANGUAGE (DSL) for specifying forbidden traces (fail traces) of mealy machine, formalized as state diagram: "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG".
- o A compiler–translator that generates free C++ code as runtime monitoring verification module to be run and watched "within runtime monitor container 📄 ["YRI_QVGE" \(https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf\)\[1d\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)".
- o "fail (forbidden) traces specification".
ALL competitors were having 'wished behavior trace specification';
- o "NO FALSE POSITIVES"; guaranteed with a formal proof demonstration in "YRI_QVGE" paper: "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF : a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of [gui] software at runtime"; ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [1d]

Klaus is never clear–minded in terms of being humble because he even insulted myself in 1 of his email that I received at my email–address: "Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com".

MAY be because of his friendship, undeclared at the time I was under supervision of JAN PELESKA–cuon.

KLAUS havelund is part of the group of people who have been trying to cover myself with in-competencies by using my research-work results without mentioning my names or anything about source of their work.

FOR instance I have never at time seen a "FLEX–BISON" parser written by PELESKA or KLAUS havelund when I finished my compiler–translator [\[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP\]](#).

Let's observe what comes up in coming years from both deceptive white teacher–professors.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "December 12, 2025"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA — Continued – 1]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA:

1. Christopher-NGOSONG (MCGill, MCGill University
QUEBEC, CANADA (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) ["2012" – onward]

THIS guja came visit personally myself in my sublet basement apartment in MARKHAM-ontario around end of year 2012 as I was finishing my sabbatical-year-Internship with "J9-Java Just-IN-Time Compilation TEAM of VIJAY Sundaresan", at, IBM Toronto Software Laboratory (<https://www.ibm.ca>).

THIS male-female boy from BUEA-mutengene was sent to myself by an uncle paternal called "David Demo NOUNDOU", coming for a postdoctoral research stay in Canada after graduating his doctorate in agricultural studies from Germany.

I invited him to oversee my project in Yaounde for a small research institute combined with a technological entrepreneurship project after we had a dinner at a whittist-canadian Soccer-MMA-grill Bar somewhere in Markham, ON, Canada.

HE even manifested interest in co-creating this research technological institute by participating both in research & teaching as I can remember since we didn't communicate much after year 2012 together (NGOSONGK@yahoo.com).

"I could observe on the website of the University of BUEA (<https://>) lastly (2024) that HE became department chief for agricultural sciences. "

2. Dr.-B.Sc. Rodrigue Wankap Emmanuel MOGO—assassin (Rennes University,
FRANCE—assassin (<https://www.>)) ["2021" – onward]

THIS family MOGO where I could try to be investigated and cured for following diseases in their mansionian Hospital Clinic BUILDING in DLA-05 ème cité-des-palmiers;

- Disruption of well-function of my whole left leg after a fall on ground due to trying to send a small stone far away with my right hand;

A culprit-MD-anesthesiologist-trauma hired by YVES-MOGO, senior brother of my secondary school—ALFRED-Saker mate-colleague Assassin-WANKAP comes and tells me after around 30-minutes auscultation that MY left leg must be open-operated.

[I said I will think about this trying-to-open my nerves twice; THEN I DISAPPEAR from this assassination-begger-online MD-owona-rdpc-cpd.m-assassin funded Clinic.]

CANAL+ (<https://www.canalhorizon.com>) in France employs Rodrigue & YVES-mogo senior brother MD-assassin in HEXAGONE-assassin-slave-for-boyard & other TV-scam programs; EVEN sensual payments-only-viewing.

SISTER GHISLAINE-MD-mogo is kind-of CHRISTIAN-eyoum-rotarian-club in USA; Last news in MARYLAND-MA, a psy; IN cameroon she could get her secondary-school-final-certificate BAccalaureat via a payment to a certain deceased minister JOSEPH-owona-kono !

- HYPERGLYCEMIA because of not begin knowledgeable that CHRISTIAN-eyoum has tried to put into my blood via forced-in-taken pills and forced-in-taken injections;

The lady that is supposed to be a diabetes specialist medical doctor kind-of [EYOUM-christian-murderer] and that I don't remember names and / or whatsoever credentials; SHE gives myself insulin such at a high level that I stopped taking this promptly after 1 week, because I COULD sense that I DON'T HAVE ANY DIABETES !

3. Béatrice (IUT-Douala, University of Douala
Littoral Region, Cameroon (<https://www.>)) ["2025" – onward]

THIS super lady from my Grand-father neighborhood in Douala-NEW DEÏDO, is a professor at the Institute of Technology of the University of Douala since age 40 years old with a Doctorate-Ph.D. degree from China as I have heard from our common neighborhood.

HER husband that I have never met personally could help me with information on how to trace a prototype for YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET; As HE owns a super-chain of eye glasses from his China originating venture "BioLUXE".

ACADEMIA world worldwide contacts |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)
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 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]
 [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA:**

1. **MASTER–of–applied–science HYPOLithe–cuon-pd-TEKEU (IUC – INstitut UNIVERSitaire de la COTE, DOUALA (<https://www.myiuc.cm>), littoral REGION, CAMEROON)**

THIS megere-bamile tribe ROSE–sangnou, a genitor of my physical being went on to recommend myself to apply for a position at so called canadian–cooperation–institution IÛC.

I was 1st told I COULD earn "500 000 Xaf"; AFTER a prompt and passed successfully interview; WITHOUT any indication that I AM A socalled DR.–ING;

hypolithe–tekeu–pd–racist–tribal–bamileke–dschang–idiot offers myself "200 000 Xaf".

I COULD NOT say no period.

THIS idiot even put myself under a so–called professional master of engineering from his dirty and prostitution institute IÛC. JUNIOR–mbe; THIS junior–mbe–fosso is now as far I COULD OBSERVE in internet–world in socalled pragmatic-quebec-cuon-land-freedom–CANADA.

TODAY I can say that it is pretty much impossible for such a low–class institution to employ an ivy–level league USA graduate university ! GUIMEZAP himself culprit with all his children couldn't even get a doctorate degree outside of DSCHANG–village where they originate from in the OUEST.

This C.P.D.M–rosicrucian–sone institution also tries to destroy life of people together with SHANDA–tonme jean-claude of village BANGOU–batchingou in OUEST.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)
 UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:**

1. **PROFESSOR thomas ndié djotio** (École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY (<https://www.polytechnique.cm>), CENTER REGION, CAMEROON)

This older than [myself] so called 'maître de conférence', English as "associate professor", was very kind to receive myself and to let me give him a short presentation of my professional and academic projects as "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.) (UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)":

- I. [YRI_QVGE](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [24.24] June 2022 – currently
- II. [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>) [?] MAR. 2015 – currently

I could identify "[Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié-Idiot]" through his online website located at: "<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>". I could also see his resume-online (~~<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>~~) that was asserting and presenting him as doctor-of-engineering graduated from the "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé" in year "2008".

ALL this afore mentioned websites were canceled by "THOMAS ndié djotio" it seems; For a more official resume (https://polytechnique.cm/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Biographie_Djotio-Ndie-Thomas.pdf).

HE 1st contested that I was a doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering because I didn't at that time of year 2022 asked for an official graduate transcript from the [UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, in Waterloo (Ontario, Canada)].

I could then obtain free-of-charge from "MRS. Nancy HEIDE" (nheide@uwaterloo.ca), at time of request As "Director of Student Services OF THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO", a certificate via electronic mail (Email) at my own request of "Official Graduate Transcript" that normally is charged \$20 CAD. I even had "Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié" copied-conform (cc) to my email since I am trying to get hired by "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé".

I CANNOT REMEMBER have failed any examination my entire candidacy of Doctor Ph.D., since I successfully graduated with "88%" as "Doctor-Ph.D. in electrical & computer Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)" on "December 20th, 2011"; with THESIS title:

["Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software"](#) [34]

I have appealed that I HAVE BEEN rejected from my [PhD research seminar] on "March 10th, 2015" by PATRICK lam that said 3 years later to myself when I was back in Canada to resign my canadian shit-citizenship, He didn't recall that he could foresee results from my program as pre-defined after we setup the PH.D. research seminar, together with my "PhD comprehensive examination committee members":

- A professor of age greater than 70 years old was the rapporteur:
- Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca
- Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca
- Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
- Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: lintan@purdue.edu

THE Ph.D. Dissertation Defense occurred in "January 2015" at PLG. IT was successfully approved by other following people among others:

["Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"](#) [34]

1. Peter Alan Burh, Ph.D. Alias ~~FABRICE siemeni-wilfried remp-canadian-armed-forces~~ Email: pabuhr@uwaterloo.ca
2. * Vijay Ganesh, Ph.D. Email: vganesh@gatech.edu
3. * Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@uwaterloo.ca
4. * Patrick Lam, Ph.D. Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
5. Magnus Madsen, Ph.D. Email: magnusm@cs.au.dk

ALL professors before mentioned marked with a "*" sign are collaborators in this project. Others approver were reviewers and were both ("Magnus, and Peter") present !

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR maïgari-idiot-secessionist (Former director, Cameroon-consulate in BRUssels-belgium (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "March-April 2015"]

2. PROFESSOR yves emvudu-cuon (INFORMATION SYSTEMS DIRECTOR deceased by now, Higher Education Ministry in Yaounde (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "August 2015"]

THIS idiot didn't even counseled me properly about the educational system employed in Cameroonian UNIVERSITIES. HE didn't even inquired on either my passed qualifications nor my credential documents; Since with his position, we could together query all required documents from an official position research in high education ministry for me.

HE just sent me to École Normale Supérieure so to meet a professor for MATHEMATICS that I forgot names and qualifications since I could never see him at ENS-yaounde.

THE other professor for mathematics I was supposed to meet, even though I AM foremost a computing engineer and developer was a MATHEMATICS professor at École Nationale Supérieure POLYTECHNIQUE de YAOUNDE. THIS man that seemed very kind but dangerous just gave me advise to put my publications of '<https://www.archive.org>'. "THIS older man than Yves-emvudu was a doctor from WEST-germany", whereas "YVES-emvudu was doctor from east-germany" !!!

ALSO, I was told by EMVUDU to apply for a teaching assistant position at SIANTOU-supérieur, and also Congo-CAMEROUN science university in a remote area of Cameroon I even don't remember the name.

"Merci au fainéant de Tonme de ne plus repasser où j'entre sur cette terre !!!"

[IT is exactly because of my "assassin-uncle-paternal-Laurent-TCHANDEU" that I went o search and encounter "YVES emvudu" of SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT A LA DEFENSE (sed) without knowing he might create a procedure to destroy me mentally because it might be inappropriate for a criminal like LAURENT to act directly on my body because of the blood-genetic-connection-with-his-own-kids !!!]

3. PROFESSOR bertin nyemb (École Normale Supérieure de Yaoundé – ENSY (<https://>), Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "May 2022"]

THIS very not humble professor for german language and cultural-ism is a very humble and not contestative person because he has always been trying to hijack myself as a member of DGRE.

I SUSPECT this idiot spy of biya-regime to have even sent false opinions of myself to german authorities at the UNIVERSITY-racist OF BREMEN after I MET HIM once again here in Yaounde in year 2022 !

SO this man of "Bassa"-tribe is at least 3 times recidivist in trying to check what makes someone like myself an ignorant by psychiatric methods like the ones [EYOUN-rotarian-CHRISTIAN] has been trying together with PR. DR. shanda-tonme, and EMVUDU.

I acknowledged at his request to be member of his stupid [Rotarian] organization so called PROvac ("PROMOTION des valeurs au Cameroun").

THIS has been more than 22 months now, he has never replied to any message about trying to computerized his membership list and cards using my humble open-source software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

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[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon–ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG (<https://>), WEST REGION, CAMEROON) [Around "September 2011", then around "September 2015]

“ THIS sample ignorant on ”algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers” that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the ”ELITE-UNIVERSITÄT-BREMEN” (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON.“

“I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes–FRANCE in ”2004” when he visited ”GRENOBLE laboratory” with PROFESSOR tchindo–gilbert.“

“I tried to contact him again in "September–2011" because I HEARD from ”diplom–informatiker marcellin tally”, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM–INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.–INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?] " like our common age–class colleague ”diplom–informatiker oscar mourbare” from Ngaoundere–Cameroon. [Dr.–Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS–Bremen (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>). “

“HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone calls while I was in Cameroon ! “

2. PROFESSOR kolyang (University of MAROUA (<https://www.univ-maroua.cm/fr/node/76>), FAR NORTH REGION, CAMEROON) [”Around December 2015”]

“ I remember greeting him when entering an elevator as he was visiting Bremen while I was in my undergraduate level of education in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN in Germany where HE Graduated several years in front of myself.“

“HE didn’t answered at all and I felt he is not very comfortable with young cameroonian studying in BREMEN.“

“KOLYANG was then a DOKTOR–INGENIEUR (Dr.–Ing.), that could graduate from BREMEN with PROFESSOR BERND KRIEG BRÜCKNER (BKB) as DOKTOR–VATER (main principal PhD advisor).“

“Professor JAN peleska–cuon said I shall contact him in year 2016 when I was looking for a research position back in Cameroon 1st time, before returning into CANADA–shit to resign a CANDIAN–idiot–citizenship I acquired because I needed to travel via Europe without visa request at GERMAN embassy. I could succeed to send him an email at an email–address received from PELESKA–cuon, that I don’t remember; BUT I never got a return reply message at all.“

“WITH idiot–joseph–djoumessi that invited myself in his christian–rosicrucian–peg congregation CMCI–obili (<https://>); I heard from someone that was in academia at the UNIVERSITY OF YAOUNDE 1 that KOLYANG was not anymore in academia for working on research, But KOLYANG was doing agriculture !!! “

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "December 12, 2025"]

[*Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy, Color of origin payments, non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal, racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario, DEREK rayside idiot, INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING), racial systemic segregation]*

- I. ★ I Was very positively surprised to receive as POST–doctoral advisor, additionally to PATRICK lam; *An Ivy–league Stanford graduate called Dr. Vijay Ganesh* (<https://www.stanford.edu>).
- II. I came to this super MIT–graduate "*Patrick Lam, Ph.D.* (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)" because HE was from *Ivy–league–Massachusetts Institute of TEchnology MIT* (<https://www.csail.mit.edu>).
- III. *Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam* (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "*Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T* (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam :

1. *I spent 6 years under supervision of PATRICK-idiot-lam, (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=36fAXB4AAAAJ&hl=en>) without having at least 1 scientific paper published under his supervision anywhere in my visible and observable internet WORLD !*

[!!! I got this ([FSE–soqua 2006]) with only 2 years at THE university–racist-of-bremen.de !!!]

"THIS is the only time "PELESKA et al." could attend such a high–prestigious class–A conference in NORTH america of mine." (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/jp_papers_e.html#publications)

2. [JON EYOLFSON], an idiot that worked for PATRICK-lam as a MASTER student (M.ASC.) and then as a PH.D. candidate, **COULD COPY MY WORK** more intelligently & silently, and even 'EHHH' got a high paid position as an "**ASSISTANT PROFESSOR (teaching stream)**"; after 4 years at ~~UGLA~~–with–~~HARRY-XU~~ (<https://web.cs.ucla.edu/~harryxu>) as Postdoctoral fellow; AT THE ece–department OF **THE UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO** (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279–alexie–tcheuyap>), ontario, canada.
3. *Patrick recommended myself to IBM Toronto Software Lab manager "Dr. MARCEL mitran" after I told him I was looking for an internship just after my PhD COMPREHENSIVE EXAMINATION[32]; Before returning to University of Waterloo, ON.*
4. *Professor PATRICK lam gave myself a lot of presentation skills attitudes that I can today not all of them remember.*
5. Patrick sent me to several research academical venues through my doctoral Ph.D. studies at the University of Waterloo, ON:
- "*First Summer School on Formal Techniques*" (<https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) (2011);
 - *MITACS Ontario* (2012);
 - *PLDI – Programming Language Design and Implementation* (2009);
 - *IBM CASCON – IBM Centre for Advanced Studies Conference* (2010);
 - *ICSE – International Conference On Software Engineering* (2012).
6. Patrick gave myself 1st hand detailed explanations on static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" with help of his slides from *McGill University* (<https://www.mcgill.ca>).
7. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep my LaTeX document code straight and maxed 80 lines.*
8. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep reading papers as long as I don't really master them, before coming back to talk to him !*
9. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to dig very deep into researching and probing an idea before there is an excellent outcome out of it: THIS IS WHAT I APPLIED TO get my 1st implementation of my doctoral dissertation work YERITH–SAINT !*
10. Patrick gave me hints about contributing to open source projects by modifying their code source and reuse it for my research; I for instance applied this when creating Computer–Aided Software Engineering (CASE) tool *YERITH_QVGE*.
11. *PATRICK lam is also the one that permitted for myself to gain a TEACHING EXPERIENCE at the UNI–racist of Waterloo : I AM ALWAYS grateful to him for this great Experience at the UNIVERSITY–racist of WATERLOO in Ontarian CANADA.*
12. [PERSONALLY I am planing to pay him some money from my soft- and hard-ware revenue in the future.]

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "December 12, 2025"]

[Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy,

*Color of origin payments,
non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal,
racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario,
DEREK rayside idiot,
INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING),
racial systemic segregation]*

- I. Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam:

13. "PATRICK lam has never done a "program analysis by himself" as far as I have been working with either as his research assistant or as a scholar that could see this somewhere in a world. "

"They (PATRICK and FELIX) even attempted to remove my name from git repository (<https://>) history when "Divam Jain" left and PATRICK said to FELIX-fang to continue that research WITH me also as a supervisor under PATRICK-lam."

"AS far as I am knowledgeable, scientific conference and / or whatsoever papers that stem "from research work of Divam Jain", that I see as plagiarism since my name as a co–author has never been written, are existent because I am the only originator of this work; as a supervisor of DIVAM jain, at the beginning of his "Master of Mathematics (M.Math.)"; and this at request of dear PATRICK lam":

"Deceased idiot former dean of engineering "PEARL sullivan", [that I went to confront with facts about these plagiarisms], Sent by a black–idiot police officer from UWATERLOO racial–police services; Sent a british giant muscular idiot white–police–officer to arrest me illegally and very violently just at the ground level of the "Davis Centre BUILDING of racists." "

"BECAUSE i removed my clothes in front of surveillance digital cameras in a uw–office racial-police, Where the british–racist-police-from-scotland did tell me to sign papers that I DIDN'T EVEN had opportunity to read at all; THEY sent me in jail–custody to KITCHENER-waterloo criminal justice court. "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" let all investigations done and concluded that I HAD NEVER ASSAULTED this idiot police white-british office that charged myself with 'ASSAULT TO POLICE OFFICER' ! "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" told me she called "the office of THE president of the university of waterloo" to ask them to let myself defend my "Ph.D. degree dissertation"; BUT they told her with attorneys of law of the president of the university of waterloo: "What is a crown attorney doing in the office of president ?" "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" then on another did tell me that someone from the office of the president-idiot–racist of the university of waterloo; said that they have certain attitudes that are based on their local culture!

Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy

went on to harass the university of waterloo police ; ESPECIALLY (ambinns@uwpolice.ca); to say Like a HE-girl–pom–pom–shit that: "THIS black gay guy is so huge that he must be destroyed mentally !!!

this kind of race–sarah–landy MUST never be admitted anywhere else in this black world other than her anus....zizi.

[THIS happened in year 2018 as I WENT TO DESTROY my so-called—white-oblivier canadian–CACA–shit—citizenship–pegg–kkk.]

"I AM THE one who told to MRS. cuon-idiot–racist–white–quebec–tabawec—"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY", that THIS IS CALLED discrimination !"

- a. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

I. **Formal Training for occupying teaching positions** |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**TEACHING ASSISTANT training;**
CUT-1 - Certificate in University Teaching 1]

[Summary-PAGES]

1. **Training in ECE Department (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department):**

Before starting my 1st formal appointment as a teaching assistant at the University of Waterloo, ON, CANADA; In year 2009, I received a group training for graduate students of the ECE (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department).

2. **Passed QUALIFICATION interview to teach OBJECT-ORIENTED PROGRAMMING WITH JAVA:**

I SUCCESSFULLY passed a presentation slides lecture for qualification interviews OF 30 minutes added with "Q&A - Questions & Answers" session; to teach Object-Oriented Java Programming to 1st year students at THE university of Waterloo in year 2012.

NEVERTHELESS, I was not chosen as THE committee said: I QUOTE THEM: "Xavier might no be able to manage this very young age students in a class of 100 or more." I WAS AGED MYSELF 29 years old in year 2012 when this happened ! THX TO PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM

PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM is only 4 years older than myself. (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)

IT seems PATRICK and lin-tan-AGED-exactly as myself were trying to avoid a so-called-negger at a high paid position at UNIVERSITY-OF-WATERLOO. "Lin tan" is born 1983 like Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU ! (<https://cs.purdue.edu/lintan>)

THE class was given at the end to a seasoned professor named **SEBATIAN FISCHMEISTER** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>), that leads the **Embedded Research Group in ECE** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>).

3. **This was optional. CUT-1; Certificate in University Teaching – 1:**

"THE university of waterloo in ontario, Canada"; offers a formal training program in 4 certificates to qualify graduate students and / or whatsoever qualified persons for teaching at a UNIVERSITY.

I attended the level 1 certificate in 2010, but didn't pursue the last 3 levels because I felt I couldn't perform as fast as I wanted my doctoral research due to the high level of academic requirements due by researching in the "static code program analysis" area of research; At **WatForm (WATERLOO FORMAL METHODS group research)** (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>); led by "Prof. Dr. JOE atlee of the CS (Computer Science) Department" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>).

AFTER my free registration, at my own request and without asking PATRICK-idiot-lam; and attendance of all 1st level courses at "DAVEN-PORT library on main (200 UNIVERSITY AVENUE WEST) campus" of the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, I notice IT would be impossible to myself to finish my research in due time without issues with my doctoral advisor !!!

WE were around 10 in a sumptuous and luxurious carpeted room at kind of 3rd level in the main building !

ESPECIALLY added to the fact I WAS EARNING SUCH A LOW 999-CAD, so I HAD to TA-teaching assisting PATRICK lam.

THAT'S why I resigned.

[I EVEN feared PATRICK lam was trying to make myself sick because of the amount of stipend I HAD, compared to other students like JON eyolfson who also add other stipend from NSREC-CANADA !!!]

"I was under supervision of my doctoral Ph.D advisor Dr.-Ph.D. of Engineering PATRICK lam".

I. Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[*TEACHING ASSISTANT training*]

- o SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '2' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses.
- o Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)
 1. Creating a "JUnit 4-tutorial" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>) [14] and got it reviewed by PATRICK LAM; THIS is not a task PATRICK as instructor asked me to perform; I did this in my free time and put it as sample training material for students. – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 2. GOING in class to teach JUnit for exercise session – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 3. Creating SAMPLE solutions to assignments – *"(+) Professor task level"*
 4. MARKING ASSIGNMENT à la patrick lam – *"(+) Professor task level"*
I felt very improved for my teaching software technical testing skills.
- o Programming for Performance (ECE 459)
 1. *TAKING some time in my time of research for my ["PH.D. in electrical & Computer ENGINEERING"] to receive students visit at my office; and teach them what they couldn't understand either in class, and / or for the course material ! –* *"(+) Professor task level"*

" Since my PH.D.-advisor patrick was the Director of Software Engineering study programs, I Think he thought I could replace him as a lecturer and he wanted to test these skills."
 2. *"Really I didn't much like this course as taught by PATRICK because it was more a kind of programming course that wasn't very solid in mathematical and engineering foundations; Except for theories and histories on processor speed "MOORE-law" expansion and development ! "*

"THIS was more to gain money because I was only earning \$999 Cad as a "master of science, PH.D. candidate" under supervision PATRICK-lam; coming from a middle level-paid good money position."

I. Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Jan. 2012 – 10 MARCH 2015]

[TEACHING ASSISTANT training]

◦ SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '3' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses; '2' graduate ("Master", "PhD", "Ph.D.") level courses.

◦ Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)

1. Because of my resignation act in front of all committee members of my doctoral Ph.D. comprehensive examination and DISSERTATION COMMITTEE members;
I resigned !

◦ Compilers (ECE 351)

1. I did during my time in BREMEN, a course called ("Übersetzer GENERIERUNG mit LEX und YACC") that could be translated in English-white: "Compiler / TRanslator GENERation with LEX & YACc".
2. Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer programs as assigned for students in ECE 351 class of racist DEREK-GAYSIDE.

◦ * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650)

1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – "(*) Professor task level"

"deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "

"IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."

◦ Computer Networks (ECE 428)

1. "Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer client-server programs as assigned for students class of racist-idiot Mahesh-Rayside."

◦ * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651)

1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – "(*) Professor task level"

◦ [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)]

1. Working with "iranian in north-america", as being a black-afro-descendant is not recommended at ALL !

"JON eyolfson is a burglar incompetent GUJA that is not even capable of respecting an agreement of 2-weeks replacement for his office mate."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (TEACHING ASSISTANT — UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

- I. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.) Xavier Noumbissi Noundou | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
- 1.) [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D-advisor PATRICK].
 - 2.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of INSTRUCTOR "MAHESH rayside-idiot":**
 - o **Computer Networks (ECE 428)** Winter term (Jan.-Apr.) "2013"

"THIS ignorant professor couldn't be even capable of clearly defining programming assignments, AS I had to tweak the Python code for automatically correct student code source from Gitlab-repositories created by a so called [PATRICK-lam]."

[THIS ignorant didn't even know I was a perfect computer software developer since age 18 in Cameroon; as demonstrated by my professional record of employment in GERMANY that is at least trice more developed technologically than idiot CANADA.]
 - 3.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Derek rayside-idiot":**
 - o **Compilers (ECE 351)** FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2012"

"THIS idiot from massachusetts-gay institute of technology cannot even define what is mathematical relation WITHOUT saying: I quote him: 'a relation is like a table'... (<https://csail.mit.edu/sdg>)

"I was kind of surprise that we MUST had to code source code to correct programmings assignments as "styles of programming for instance, comments, etc," MUST be also marked and more importantly advised, Especially from a performance confirmed seasoned software developer as myself: DR.-PH.D. of ENGINEERING XAVIER noumbissi noundou. (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) "

"I was very surprised to see a [culprit called MATTHEW MA] that was Master of Applied Science of DEREK, COMING to myself with his mother and offer me "\$400 CAD so to code for his MASTER PROJECT in Computer Software Engineering from derek." "

"Thinking that derek went to pay around \$30 000—CAD to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG, (<https://mathgenealogy.org>) so my free registration from "[PATRICK] AND rinard-martin; (<https://csail.mit.edu/~rinard>)" from 'PH.D.' onto 'ABD' be changed without any formal justification as specified [[here];] DEREK-GAYSIDE is only someone that hijacked to get a degree from renowned MIT." "
 - 4.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "LADAN":**
 - o **[C++ LABORATORY (ECE 250)]** FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2014"

"THIS in german so called 'HURE'-prostitute (<https://Wikipedia.org>) Declares be a professor for software system.

I cannot testify this as "her student MOHAMMAD HAMDAQA" was so ignorant and had a tremendous background in business but knew nothing on software system at all ! "

"I spent hours talking to ladan via her idiot student from JORDAM-kingdom that seems to have even acquired a faculty position at so called "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL-qc-chien-tabawak-satan" (<https://www.polymtl.ca>) "
 - 5.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "deceased-Igor Ivkovic-idiot":**
 - o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650) Winter term (Jan-Apr.) "2013"
 1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – "(*) Professor task level"

"deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "

"IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."
 - o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651) Spring term (May-Aug.) "2013"
 1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – "(*) Professor task level"
 - 6.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructors "Patrick LAM", and "LIN tan":**
 - o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)** Winter term (Jan.-Apr.) "2015"
- II. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]
- 1.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Patrick LAM":**
 - o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)** Winter term (Jan.-Apr.) "2010"

"I AM THE one that creates the only sample solution to midterms. PATRICK is not very good at kind of creating technical solutions based on graph-theoretical foundations as for instance when creating equivalence class based test sequences solutions." — 📄
"Sample TESTING material I Created." (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>) [14]
 - o **Programming for Performance (ECE 459)** Winter term (Jan.-Apr.) "2011"

I co-create with other teaching assistants such as [JON-eyolfson] solutions for assignments and / or midterms exams.

I also receive students during predefined weekly time frame so to help them out with understanding of learning courses material.

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – APR. 2015]

[PROOF READING,
static code dataflow analysis,
SCALA,
JAVA, C++, *JUnit* testing,
research ideas talks and development,
computer programming teaching]

[Summary-PAGES]

I. Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:

1. ["Matthew Ming Ma, M.ASc., Mechatronics, Engineering":]

- o How to configure a "developer" JAVA virtual machine under Ubuntu LINUX;
- o "I gave him contextual help in writing JAVA code for his Master of Applied Science project, under supervision of Derek Rayside".
- o HE then got a so called, at "**APPLE INC. LTD.**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) , **software in test developer** (<https://www.apple.com/jobs>) job;

That is why even a "**WIFI-connection**" to a laptop doesn't work with APPLE phones as I COULD experience myself in CAMEROON (a white phone paid for \$120 CAD).

2. ["DR. JON eyolfson, Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering":] (<https://www.jeyolfson.com>)

- o How to use efficiently and effectively double pointers in C++ function / method calling argument parameters;
- o "I gave him my full LaTeX doctoral Ph.D. thesis (ECE calls this a research proposal) document for helping him out with a template at his own request".

3. "Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering":

- o Thorough discussions and talks about his research ideas and on computer programming related topics (mostly on the "Watform LAB white-board").

4. "Divam Jain, M.Math., Computer Science", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- o Gave "DIVAM" sample code of my sample projects in JAVA about static code dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : A **unified approach to global program optimization** (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)"; As opposed for instance to static code dataflow analysis " à la **IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>)" from "**THOMAS-reps at the university of wisconsin-madison**" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) .

IBM provides WALA as library for working with IFDS framework. (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>)

- o Introduction and supervision on how to use **SOOT** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) ;
- o Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for JUNIT test case generation;
- o Declared "Master of Mathematics" title at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Detecting Test Clones with Static Analysis**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/7943>).
- o FOLLOWING plagiary by [zheng FELIX fang] and [PATRICK lam] originate from this seminal initial work where I contributed partly in code source writing:

A) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

5. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc., Electrical & Computer Engineering", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- o Overview of ["Divam Jain's"] previous work on SOOT and static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.
- o Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.;
- o "Declared MASTER OF APPLIED SCIENCE title" at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Test Clone Detection via Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/8831>);
- o FANG then got a position at MICROSOFT corporation in SEATTLE.
- o [1 scientific conference paper came out of this supervision-advising :]
 - a.) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. HELPIng black–descendant students from the UNIVERSITY of waterloo–racist–on |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Oct. 2009 – apr. 2015]

I. Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:

1. "Amirhossein Vakili, Ph.D., Computer Science": (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili>)
 - o How to use MAKE;
 - o static dataflow analysis explanation.
 - o "1st at all functional programming with SCALA introduction".
2. **STUDENTS in cameroon association rowac. (<https://rowac.ca>) "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - o **We at ROWAC (formerly CCAKW (Camerroonian Community Association in Kw)); Have invited ambassador-pd-idiot of Cameroon in OTTAWA (ontario) during summer 2014 if my thoughts are exact. THIS was during the soccer tournament we organized.**
 - o I presented and gave out certain documents I wrote about computer web software security vulnerabilities protection; AND measures to protect documents and computer–laptop during, after 1 general meeting evening around 06 : 00 PM.
 - o AFTER graduating, and came back into canada to resign an idiot-canadian citizenship acquired for travel-without-visa-purpose-only to EUROPE; I then discovered that several members of ROWAC were secret–servicess-agent of my assassin of paternal uncle LAURENT-tchandeu, PleniPOTENTIARY–minister:
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Vincent Nanga
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Innocent Tchigio
 - Dr.-PHARM. (M.Sc.) CHEONGWA wandzi-cheongwa@yahoo.com
3. "Godrick–chékété, Ph.D., French literature": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET "Godrick–chékété" via "YAW boakye-agyeman, ph.d. student in recreational studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA";
 - o Help in FINDING HIS way after his divorce from his spouse from BENIN (house searching, car fixing, etc.);
 - o HELP in looking for a financial loan at a Canadian bank.
4. "Eric Brefo–Mensah, Ph.D., Chemistry": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET Eric brefo-mensah via "CHIWANZA-kasanga";
 - o Help in proof reading his Master Thesis LaTeX document before his final submission in "year 2018".
5. Shirley Ddamba, "M.ASc. Civil Engineering": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET SHIRLEY at a bible study at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA;
 - o Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario.
6. Esther Lambert, "Ph.D., Geography, University of Toronto, 2017": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"
 - o I MET ESTHER while she was cashier at ZEHRS–churchill–street.
 - o Help in proof reading her Master thesis for the department of geography;
 - o Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario;
 - o ESTHER then pursue 1 year internship at ONTARIO green–belt institute; SHE then was admitted at the University of Toronto for "doctoral Ph.D. in GEOGRAPHY".

RESEARCH AND TEACHING ('PROFESSIONAL' TEACHING ASSISTANT – CONTINUED [2] - THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

I. *Professional Computer Engineers living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada":*

1. "A paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon" (<https://www.ank-technologies.com>).

r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou" who at 1st was an illegal migrant worker idiot in GB–great britain, a junior brother of my late father and genitor "Théodore Nounbissi, B.Sc., Electrical & Computer Engineering"; was a student in Information Technology student at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug" (<https://www.tuhh.de>), and graduated from there with a "Bachelor of Sciences (B.Sc.)".

"Demo" then obtained a position as "PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer" at "Canon LTD.", based in Germany - Osnabrück !

AT least trice (3 times) a month, I will receive a phone call from Germany requesting software programming and / or database technical help from this GUJA.

Each time I could solve his issues until HE stopped calling around August 2014, when I became a CANADIAN citizen, and when himself *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* went for a marital union with *r-"Astride Patibé"*; a nurse from Cameroon – Baham – BAFANG tribe.

r-"CÉLESTIN puene" is another (Food–processing) engineer from Cameroon that came to myself sent by "his natal village Babouantou" friend paternal uncle *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* .

HE came saying he needed help in buying a mechanical truck from the USA for his brother in cameroon who possessed a road construction society in YDE. *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* was first living in Frankfurt–GERMANY, before moving around 3 years after myself, into Canada [WASKAGANISH, qc; and "then Brampton, ON"].

" *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* and *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* are now member of [** +-"ROTARY CLUB INTERNATONAL"-+ **]; *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* was initiated by *r-"MBOUM, MD, Ph.D. (surgeon)"* from OSNABRÜCK–germany. I could say I do not want to be member when *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* asked for this in year 2014".

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[2016 – 2017]

A. "ENGINEER-ENSPY job seeker-gay PAUL:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I started teaching C programming to this young gay electrical engineer from CMCI-communauté missionnaire internationale chrétienne OBILI-obédience (CMCI-obili); While he was looking for employment for almost 6 years after graduating as BSc.-electrical engineer from "École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY"."

HE stopped attending just 2 weeks after starting participating in group meeting with the 2 following scientist-educators.

HE said his financing person wanted him to focus only in applying for positions in industry such as "BRASSERIES DU CAMEROUN", etc.

B. "Scientist-educator-cuon KITIO:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

He could find a position as computer science teacher in a secondary school in west cameroon !

C. "Scientist-educator-cuon CHARLES-eteme; now working at Yaounde GENERAL hospital:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

HIS father could find him soon a position at "Yaounde GENERAL hospital" where he was earning "250 000 Xaf" to start his career as a staff web developer.

TODAY, as I have been living in Cameroon for more than 6 years now full time; I believed he was a "SED"-anti gang; IT means someone hijacking people from west-region so to make them wretched as a political argument for PAUL-biya-idiot-CPDM-president.

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[Jan. 2021 – "December 12, 2025"]

A. "Engineer JEAN-PIERRE kamgain-idiot:"

This not professional computer science & computer engineering graduate, from "THE university of Yaounde 1", and from "IAI Cameroon"; was interested in various web-related tasks for searching employment within Douala.

1.) *plain code source "C" application programming interface development;*

A sample task was a development of a translator from "Qt 5 user interfaces (".ui" files)" onto "HTML5 pages";

2.) *JAVA servlet & apache tomcat server;*

A sample project using *APACHE-maven* (<https://>), for car maintenance & rental was developed both by myself and by JP-kamgain-culprit.

THIS sample exegete of "IAI Cameroon" wasn't capable of clearly write JAVA code as supposed with a "*bachelor of honours in Computer Software Engineering*" from both "IAI Cameroon"; And "University of Yaounde 1 (UY 1)".

3.) *PHP software development.*4.) *Training P.C.T.B-sarl employee on YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum:*

The culprit and school-mate NGADJEU-francis, refused to utilize JP because he went without asking advise from me recruit a so called call-girl-*IUC-cameroon* (<https://myiuc.com>).

5.) *Indicator for destruction of YVES-landry-galax-etoga in person:*

"JEAN-pierre kamgain has been trying to hijack my properties, both physically and emotionally because I COULD notify that HE was trying to spy my activities for "C.P.D.M party as NGADJEU-francis from P.C.T.B.-sarl did"“;

"Also JP-kamgain is the one that went to propose my ERP software system to BONTÉE sarl in AKWA-sud douala.“

6.) *[COPLATEC sarl is a psy-company for hijacking people at home:]*

OUR experience in Africa has been that at least "85% of societies" that are of type "SARL-ndlr-société à responsabilité limitée", 'GmbH (<https://WIKIPEDIAlinkDefinition.ORG>)-in-German-language';

"are companies for gay owned by soldiers FOR hijacking male and/or female consultants like myself that do not participate officially in lesbianism and homosexuality-zoophyte.“

ARLETTE-sibeufo seemed to be also member of SED.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (POSTDOCTORAL RESEARCHER AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
- [VIJAY-ganesh-chenapan, static dataflow taint analysis, dynamic binary program analysis, "INTEL-Pin", LLVM]
- A. Duties completed by Researcher [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:
1. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [Sep. 2012 – MAR. 2015]
 - a.) ["Program Analysis for Web Apps"] "Grade 88%";
 - b.) ["Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)"] "Grade 88%".
 2. **SOLE and INDEPENDENT idea and research of development** of static dataflow taint analysis with use of "compiler framework LLVM", for solving following complex software engineering problems: [Sep. 2012 – MAR. 2015]
 - a.) "Application Programming Interface (API) usage temporal rules";
"QUANTAMP.COM (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) uses for instance part of this research outcome to solve the problem of checking the conformance of BITCOIN-related-software-automated-contracts."
 - b.) "Detecting software security vulnerabilities" that endanger normal workflow, PER user-requirement elicitation, OR per software usability engineering: "BUFFER-OVERFLOW problems"; "SQL-injection problems"; "FORMAT-STRING attacks problems"; "AUTOMATIC test case and test data generation solution classes";
 - c.) "VERY PRECISE AND DETAILED collaboration with Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. VIJAY-ganesh";

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – 2014]

[Vijay-GANESH-from Ph.D.-at-stanford.edu (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>),
RESEARCH outcome plagiarism,
RESEARCH outcome hindrance,
"JAN-peleska-crédible; best-ever-professor of mine",
"student advising-MISSING paper",
static dataflow taint analysis,
LLVM (<https://llvm.org/racist-apple>)]

- A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING.-PH.D.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

[Summary-PAGES]

1. EXPERIMENTATION WITH IFDS-FRAMEWORK FROM "REPS ET AL."

[JAN. 2013 – JUNE 2013]

I discovered the "IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) problems algorithm by THOMAS reps from UNIVERSITY-of-WISCONSIN-MADISON (<https://www.wisc.edu>), and from "Grammatech" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) ;

"I really enjoyed this graph-based software system interdependence algorithm; and accompanying free FOSS IBM-wala library (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>) ".

NEVERTHELESS I tried a personal implementation of the IFDS-framework using SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) & Java-SCALA with no successful binaries; BECAUSE the ideology for using "IBM-wala" was quite strange to my understanding !!!

I then renounced & abandoned to pursue and implement "The KILDALL-style" ("Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)") using C++ and a book-Advanced Compiler Design-from ...IBM author... !:

 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34]

2. [Work on "Dynamic PROGRAM Analysis with FRANK-tip" in course CS846] & [Work on "Software System Security by Software VERIFICATION"]

3. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D.-advisor PATRICK.]

[Sep. 2009 – Mar. 2015]

4. [Previous RESEARCH-development at AGBS—UNIVERSITY-OF-BREMEN.DE] :

"JAN peleska is my 1st best ever professor because I learned the best research skills from him while working in his research group in Germany-bremen-racist (E.g.: Unfortunately for myself; I couldn't get any professional-vocational student software developer position in a commercial company installed in Bremen.). (<https://informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>) "

[FSE-soqua 2006]

"More importantly we had a paper at Foundations OF Software Engineering research conference in 2006 while I was working on my "Diplom-Informatiker degree [Dipl.-Inf.] (Master of Science equivalent)" in his research group at the University-of-bremen.de (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>): "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) — ("VERIFIED.DE" (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>)) !!! "

5. Follow-up on research started by [DIVAM-jain] with following other fellow researchers at ECE:

- o DEREK-rayside
- o PATRICK-lam
- o REID-holmes
- o LIN-tan-idiot-gay-non-sense-girl
- o FELIX-fang
- o etc.

I started collaborating with DIVAM jain because PATRICK-lam sent DIVAM jain to me for learning about static dataflow code analysis using SOOT.

"WHEN divam-jain-racist left, I pursue this same research with FELIX fang, and then with researchers afore-mentioned in office of the director of software engineering program PATRICK-lam; Where we attended to group collaborative meetings."

THEN he was more about the problem itself; IN this occasion, how to automatically generate "JUnit test suites test cases" based on static code dataflow analysis of unit test code of the analyzed projects.

"A benchmark of "at least 100 open source JAVA libraries" was used to test these projects JUnit test code.

From this research came out at least 11 conference peer-reviewed papers and some journal articles, AND i wasn't mentioned as a co-author either:

- 1.) "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2014 – 2018]

["sodomite-peggish-JULIA-rubin-AT-UNIVERSITY-of-british-columbia-CANADIAN-rate-gay-Israelite-ANTI-JESUS-OF-Nazareth",
dynamic binary program analysis,
"INTEL-Pin"]

A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

4. **DEVELOPMENT of certain features of PHP-JAVA-judo-quebec web application for management of club members:**

[JUNE 2014 – NOV. 2014]

THE research paid-provision was around "1000 \$CAD" a month, which was very insignificant because of all the technologies working together such as: PHP, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), etc.

5. **PATRICK-idiot lam research idea**, and personal sole development of a dynamic binary program analysis for moving "PROGRAM-POINT" during runtime execution based on certain loop-condition; USING "INTEL-Pin" :

[SEP. 2014 – OCT. 2014]

PATRICK-idiot lam didn't allow myself to complete the program under his sole supervision.

I WASN'T really happy because he interrupted my main project on static taint dataflow analysis; HE didn't tell me anything about any outcome, and/or later done publication or whatsoever.

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

6. **!!-sodomite-peggish-woman-attention-patrick-JULIA-rubin-ece-british columbia-faineant-chien-tabaweak-canaoe** said she will continue research with myself at **UBC** (<https://www.ece.ubc.ca/mjulia>) so I WILL GRADUATE as a "PH.D." !

[2018]

" IT was dereak-gayside that said I SHOULD TRY TO apply somewhere else than university-racist-of-waterloo since they-idiot-of-lam could call the police to arrest myself ILLEGALLY on waterloo dirty-racket-pd-cuon-tabaweak-quebec-salaud main campus !!! "

PLEASE FOLK that may think a white-racist Gives you a residence permit to allow yourself to fulfill your peace dreams; IT'S NOT THE CASE.

" THE WHITE-GAY-DAY-nancy-racist is only trying to reduce the speed of perfectionism and development of your country of origin by harassing you there with corrupt-gay authorities so you will try to go outside. "

" All these mansory-free-rotary-club-ETC.; CATHOLIC-gay-church is only a way to hijack your life in anti-christ-of-negger-jesus-of-nazareth like myself I HAVE BEEN experiencing for 7 years in ontarian-CANADA-shit-people-race. "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[Algorithms dis-pension,
finite automaton theories,
"Year 2010 report",
"Year 2011 report",
"1st summer school on formal techniques",
[IDIOT-black-afro-descendant Sandy BEIDU from ghanaian land]]

I. Duties completed by Research Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.; MSc)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my advisor-PH.,D. PATRICK].
2. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [SEP. 2009 – DEC 2011]
 - a.) ["First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"] "participated with certificate";
 - b.) ["Computer-Aided Verification-racist-nancy"] "Grade 90%";
 - c.) ["Advanced Compiler Design-cuon-plagiarism-of-jon"] "Grade 86%".

3. I went to **menlo-racist-college** (<https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) in California, USA, to the 1st summer school on formal techniques from "May 22, 2011" until "May 27, 2011"; under a recommendation-required (from professor doctor NANCY-idiot-day (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>)).

I was accompanied by the GHANAIAN called SANDY-cuon-beidu supposed to be a very famous computer scientist originating from my home continent AFRICA.

[THIS hideous ignorant fellow, from a very poor material background arrived at the university of waterloo "WatForm-waterloo formal methods" in year 2010 if I have good memories; Saying to the world he is a JESUS-christian;]

This kind of black-afro-descendant is so disgusting that I believed that the racist **JO-atlee-his-research-advisor** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>) went to pick him so to dishonest myself in front of the extremely dominant ["iranian female population in ECE graduate student folks"] !

HE even thought that I RENTED my "ford fusion" to tell them (Sandy-idiot-day, and a lady from long-island-black-prostitute) that I AM A WELL-TO-DO-MAN in front of them.

[I JUST remembered my BUSINESS-trip while I WAS TRAVELING for SIEMENS-medical-solutions-erlangen IN concord-ca-usa; And I KNEW I NEEDED to be mobile; THAT's why I RENTED A luxurious "ford fusion" from my savings account from my HARD-job at SIEMENS.]

[SANDY-idiot-poor-man-in-all-system thought when the other ghanaian idiot-story-teller-Dr-PhD-ERIC-brefomensah brought me to his travesty-basement-slot in WATERLOO, in ontario, 2018; THAT i needed some drink from him !]

[PLEASE folk from basement places in GHANA; Cameroon don't need this kind of down-treatment as CAMEROON is way more advanced as demonstrated ONLY by me !!!!!!!]

4. I have worked on topic "temporal property verification in plugin-based software"; and created a computer-Libreoffice-Impress presentation slides for the **IBM workshop CASCON 2010-CDP-compiler-...** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); [IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

THIS research as "**Master Of Science**" (so called "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.-INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?]") led to my "**Doctoral Thesis / PhD comprehensive examination**" released research technical document : "**Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)

5. I have created sample program static code analyzes using the **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) so to acquire skills in static code program analysis.

A very short introduction: " " (<https://>) to SOOT framework by

6. I HAVE IMPROVED my algorithm design skills by implementing popular algorithms using the Following ALGORITHM POPULAR BOOKS:

- A. **Computer Systems: A PROGRAMMER'S PERSPECTIVE, 2nd edition** ("ISBN 13 : 978 – 0 – 13 – 610804 – 7"); by "**BYANT**"-racist & "**O'HALLARON**"-racist-sexist;
- B. **Introduction to Algorithms-Isbn: " "**; by **THOMAS cormen** (https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crd=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjojMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVfEd1BzcV0qunH6HMFdUvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWVHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABi7cszQqi1XxeWBu8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gw1drRqhl2Alh8huCTZ2PeIofPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fio1k8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWazLVBUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1).

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANCE FROM FOLK-IDIOT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**"JOHN HOPCROFT"**, **"samaneh navabpour–racist–extreme"**, **"1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"**, **LLVM**, **SOOT**]

I. **People from [the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] whom I got academic help:**

1. "AAKARSH nair, M.ASc., Computer ENGINEERING, 2009"

- "AAKARSH nair was the 1st student of DEAR-idiot PATRICK lam I have ever met.

HE is the 1st one to give me sample code on static dataflow analysis with "JAVA–SOOT framework (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)" à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" "

2. "NANCY day"

- "Professor DAY wrote a very good and tremendous recommendation that was used to admit myself to [**"First Summer School on Formal Techniques"**] (<https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>), by THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA; in year 2011".

3. "Samaneh Navabpour, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering"

- SAM gave me 1st explanations about LLVM by using her previous work for **a paper–RITHM** (<https://uwaterloo.ca/embedded-software-group/sites/default/files/uploads/documents/main.pdf>) she worked on in SEBASTIAN fischmeister embedded computer research group; She confessed not having exactly applied a static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)";

BUT used only control flow graph related features to perform static dataflow analysis; this is NOT exactly **CLANG** (<https://clang.llvm.org>).

4. **Pr. Prof. Dr.–Ing. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nanaeem>)

- NOMAIR was the 1st person apart from Patrick, my doctoral Ph.D. advisor that took so much time to help me understand and proof read my **doctoral Ph.D. Thesis** ([HTTPS://WWW.SEMANTICSCSCHOLAR.ORG/PAPER/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33](https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33)) [32];
- NOMAIR helped myself in understanding the intricacies of a context–sensitive static parametric analysis by explaining from his **research paper Interacting objects ...** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~nanaeem/papers/oops1a08PhD.pdf>).

5. **Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>)

- Professor Lhoták accepted to review my **YERITH–SAINT** algorithm thoroughly.
- Ondřej was very kind to help me with source code of 1 of his 1st **LLVM** dataflow analysis, before I started my own.

6. **Pr. Prof. Dr.–Ing. JOHN hopcroft–SEXIST, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.cornell.edu/jeh/>)

- Explanation, at my email request, and very promptly and generously about an algorithm in his compiler book.

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (GRADUATE INTERN AT INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS MACHINERY (IBM))

1. Perform duties assigned by big manager and PATRICK doyle in JAVA-J9 JUST-IN-TIME OPTIMIZATION team (, located in Markham-ONTARIO-canada); (advised by Prof. VIJAY sundaresan, M.Sc. (MCGILL, QC, CANADA) | Patrick Doyle, (M.ASc., UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, Ontario, CANADA))) |
IBM TORONTO-IDIOT SOFTWARE LAB. [01/2012 – 08/2012]

[AS canadian-idiot permanent resident;

Automated Software TESTING with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIFY (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verify>),

Program OPTIMIZATION (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), "Clark-salau Verbrugge, Ph.D. (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>)";

JVM – JAVA virtual machines, IBM – WEBSPPHERE, Managers are really understandable,

DOCTOR-ENGINEER,

Racism from restaurant in india-bangalore-IBM-gay]

[Summary Of D.ENG. [DR.-ING. in "French language"] (PH.D.) Review Research-PAGES]

I. Comfort excellent for work research at IBM:

1. I was working into a brown cubicle and had so much freedom in work that I WAS SOMETIMES afraid that I AM NOT PERFORMING well.

BUT when I STARTED working closely more with VIJAY I felt so busy that I WAS DREAMING of going home around 03:00PM in evening;

IN total, IBM in MARKHAM offers very good working and research conditions for his employees, *even better than my previous 1st full-time job as JUNIOR-SOFTWARE-DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS in Erlangen, BAVARIA, GERMANY !!!*

SIEMENS Medical solutions was really good in Erlangen; But i didn't like seeing "BOSS gerhard" watching his arm watch any 2 minutes to make sure we only had 45 minutes lunch-break; "Secretary "gudrun" is also really helpful and smiling ! "

II. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. **Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, MSc. – from Bangalore, INDIA**

THIS daemon of work was so kind that I ONLY FEEL I have satisfy him as much as he wanted and could !!!

HE is very attracted to good and fast male workers; because female workers would only try to hijack his time for a snack !!!

I am very proud of having work with such an amazing scientist at all !!!

ALSO the team managers, including the chinese woman, were very kind to myself as the only male afro-descendant from AFRICA !!!

2. **Patrick idiot Doyle, M.ASc. – from Ireland-CANADA**

THIS ignorant as a teacher and / or mentor couldn't even pick myself at time when I Was waiting for my hiring team for the internship to come at my encounter in the biggest room where we all intern were awaiting 1st day of internship.

III. Duties of Graduate INTERN [Doctor of Engineering] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. **FIX SOFTWARE TESTING FEATURE AUTOMATION USING BASH SCRIPTS**

I felt a lot better at this task because I could feel having a positive impact on the project team lead by manager that I don't remember names and academic titles.

ALSO vijay sundaresan wasn't very disgusting as people working in the restaurant, that always served myself BURNed food, especially pagan-an-food.

Vijay sundaresan is a very talented software lead and developer that I could ever see in my career; I VERY MUCH LIKED THE INTERACTIONS with him compared to PATRICK doyle.

TODAY I FEEL there are 2 factors that helped:

- A. **MCGILL university** (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) graduates in Computing Sciences are very much talented compared to other students from ONTARIO.
B. VIJAY-sundaresan was born also outside of Canada-racist-systemic like my recruiting manager that I forgot about names;

2. **MAINTAIN CERTAIN DAYS BUG DATABASE**

AT all not very difficult, since I WAS USED TO use CHARMNT in my previous full-time job at Siemens Medical Solutions in Erlangen, BAVARIA, germany.

3. **ATTEND TO COURSES AT IBM TORONTO-IDIOT LABORATORY GIVEN BY "pr. prof. dr.-ing. clark-salau verbrugge" FROM MCGILL.ca** (<https://mcgill.ca>) "on Creating Optimizations for Compilers"

4. **SOLVE AS MANY AS BUGS IN COMPILER OPTIMIZATION CODE SOURCE IN C++**

Coming from a program analysis research team, that performed more static code analysis using framework like S00T, and LLVM; I WAS KIND OF not performing very well at this task at all because of the very applied and complicated data structures; Especially because PATRICK-indigeneous-iranian-irish-from-british-kingdom never even got me to a small talk for explaining me briefly what was the governing ideas leading the development team in MARKHAM.

INSTEAD, i only received so many documents that I had to read and detect understand myself.

Earning as much as 3 000 \$CAD monthly, I FELT SO BAD that I Went to complain to the manager; a very kind person; that allowed then myself to work with the team lead VIJAY sundaresan...

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' (WEB DEVELOPMENT INTERNSHIP AT BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN – HTML, CSS, PHP, JSP – CODE SOURCE FOR a Content Management System – as an EVENT MANAGEMENT SOFTWARE ONLINE racist (advised by MARTIN ...) |

BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST, BREMEN, GERMANY-RACIST-PEGGIST

— March. 2004 —

[[WEB software development with PHP, CSS],

Peggist-racist colleague Martin...,

[JSP, HTML5,]

Samsung CONTACT Server on Redhat LINUX]

I. Duties of Web Development Intern [Vordiplom-B.Sc candidate (In Computer Science)] Xavier Noundou:

1. *Before attending and applying for this position; I attended courses workshops on Web development using MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP during around 1 semester (4 months) at the Department of Computer Science ("FACHBEREICH 3) of the University of Bremen. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)*
2. *Create configuration in Redhat LINUX for the Samsung Contact Server system.*
3. *Create HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP combined code into a Content Management System for managing Event that are to be published on a specific date on the Bremen4u-Gmbh website.*
4. Martin was always having a very bad mouth-breath because of smoking cigarette all day together with drinking black dark coffee with no milk at all.
5. THIS was a very disgusting place to work as a new person living in Germany; also young girls from secondary school as internship workers; With almost no sense on respecting black african race at ALL !

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVISOR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[NOV. 2007 – July 2009]

[C++,
Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer),
Software Integration Testing [21],
UNDER german-traveler work-permit;
ROBOTER-linac,
Radiation Therapy Treatment,
IMRT beam treatment,
TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

1. Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer) [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. "MARVELOUS TRAVEL to Concord, CALIFORNIA, USA : my greatest and high paid experience of work since I was given birth in 1983 !!! — 5 000 EUROS

THANK you boss gerhard-idiot-SENG !!!!!!! "

2. "Participation in cancer treatment (IMRT) radiation therapy training, and all other software development related training for this position as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER."
3. "C++ coding and defects fixing of DMIP control communication protocol as heart of Software component TXSUPERVISOR: around 110 000 Lines of code (SLOC)."
4. *Conception & Development of an automated software integration test infrastructure:*
 - a. Cygwin bash-scripting
 - b. Microsoft COM component as [CORBA] agent communication used
5. Software Integration testing using "IBM Purify Plus".
[\(COMPETITOR FROM "PR. PROF. DR-ING. Xavier noumbissi Noundou":](#)
[YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481\) \[1b\]](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481);
 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif) ;
6. "DMIP Control Console" device as user control management for simulating radiation therapy linear accelerator "SIEMENS Linac Artiste" in our laboratory in Erlangen ground-base;
7. Focal entry point of all bugs of "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software. INVESTIGATION, and then redistribution, according to defect type, to an appropriate sub-team VIA team-lead "Gehrrard Seng".
8. Support technical in writing software user manual with software testers.
9. Support technical with software testers in using "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
10. Phone support technical in TROUBLESHOOTING "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
11. Maintenance of communication development support from software developers from Siemens Concord in California, USA.
12. Maintaining using "MS office" of design documents of TXSUPERVISOR and "DMIP control communication protocol"; based on "FSM state machine theory": United States of America's FDA (U.S.A – Federal Drug and Administration), as well as CE (European Community) had to review the digitally signed documents; stored in "SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)".
13. Assisting "DARIO meraviglia" in selection of interns based on their qualification as reported on their CV – resume.
14. Advising of 2 software testing maintenance part-time employees:
 1. 1 from Germany, from The University of Bamberg (Bayern, Germany);
 2. 1 as an intern, from India.
15. "VMWare" (<https://www.vmware.com>) as debugging image creator development tool.
16. "MS Windows 2000", as well as, "MS Windows NT", as software development operating systems platforms.
17. "Visual Studio C++" as IDE;
18. "IBM Rational ClearCase" as Code BASE source management control software used;
19. "IBM CharmNT" as bug management platform used;
20. [LEGAL requirement summary experience with HANDLING of Design Documents Functional Specification for Medical Software according to "CE" ; "FDA".]

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIROR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[11/2007 – 07/2009]

[C++,
Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer),
Software Integration Testing [21],
UNDER german-traveler work-permit;
ROBOTER-linac,
Radiation Therapy Treatment,
IMRT beam treatment,
TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

1. ISSUES – Problems with some colleagues:

1. Gerhard Seng and Dario Meraviglia told myself I should be promoted to the position of Dario as "technical lead of the software module component TXSUPERVISOR (only 1 developer)" if I could succeed in gaining a full-time permanent contract after an initial successful 6 months period of work under direct leadership of DARIO MERAUVIGLIA.

"AFTER SUCCEEDING the trial period of 6 months, I obtain a change of software developer contract from a full-time limited contract to a full-time permanent contract with "Siemens Medical Solutions"."

"HOWEVER after an additional 15 months of work, I am not anymore promoted to a higher level position of Technical Lead."

"This is why I decide to make the effort to go back to academia and pursue [a doctoral Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering (Computer Software)] at the University of Waterloo, in ONTARIO, CANADA; WITH [Dr.-PhD patrick lam as academic adviser] !! "

2. "Merlin Tonka from Cameroon" is calling me even before my first day at job in Erlangen to tell me he hopes I will be able to perform well and thus keep my job beyond the 1st 6 months period of try: He tells myself HE got my email from boss "Gehrrard Seng";

"From NORTH of GERMANY WHERE I STUDIED AND LIVED for almost 6 years before being recruited and before moving to Fürth-BAVARIA-Germany, this is not "SACK-ARBEIT": I.E. one shall not mixed private life affairs with business matters at all: THIS IS HOW I LEARNED IT in HAMBURG, and BREMEN ! "

3. "Merlin Tonka" one day follows myself in metro and bus so to tell me that HE shall be promoted as a team of a new testing and developers team, And that he shall be my manager.

" I was wondering silently (because very young in year 2008 with only 23.5) years old ("Merlin Tonka was at least 40 years old in front of my age"), that someone less qualified than myself and currently employed as only a software tester, which is a lower level required qualification; Put aside you are PhD-doctor-of-engineering; and that was recruited only 1 week before my personal recruitment, will become my manager by telling it to me only in streets ! "

"THE italian master of science-level engineer Dario Meraviglia is my technical lead, followed by Gerhard Seng, our common teal lead at Syngo-RTT-Therapist-SW-Realize team" !

4. After leaving "Siemens Medical Solutions" legally by resigning with a signed letter 3 months before leaving my IG-METAL-tariff-vertrag employment in year 2009; I sent a letter to thank "MERLIN TONKA" for the positive professional collaboration I had with him as a fellow cameroonian, despite a lot of troubles we had; I sent this letter only around 1 month after starting studying in Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.

"THE answer from "Merlin Tonka" is so negative minded and outspoken that I need to reply to tell him truth about not trying again to tell me he is superior to myself; I.e. Merlin tries in a letter to tell me I could not perform well in software developer job, that's why I resigned !!! "

"Only smelling the same dirty "grey-shirt" MERLIN was wearing almost every day was not comfortable because he was sitting just opposite side of my office-desk ! "

"I today in year 2024 can remark as a citizen living inside CAMEROON that killer from governmental agency [DGRE wear generally grey-shirts !]"

"UDM-université des montagnes (<https://WIKIPEDIA.ORG-racist>) later on in year 2009 invited DGRE-activist MERLIN tonka through THE KILLER OF MY GENITOR théodore noumbissi; So called [HUGUES NTOMANI tiako], which is sleeping with genitor ROSE sangnou so to perform crimes on my person even now in year 2024 ! "

"WHITE-blond supremacist slave-maker; PLEASE stop to hijack black afro-descendants that are talented. TILO. MÜCKE. DARIO. MERAUVIGLIA. MERLIN. TONKA ! "

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING – CONTINUED (1) (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |
SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY [11/2007 – 07/2009]

III Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at Siemens Medical Solutions:

1. **"paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon".**

Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug".

[Help in proof reading his Bachelor–Thesis.]

IV Students living in Canada I helped during vacation time by my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji":

1. Co–roommate of Théodore Wandji at 5850 Rue Souart, #7, H3S 2E8, Quebec, Montreal, CANADA:

"Basser from Syria":

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Master of Applied Sciences (M.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

2. **"Fabrice TCHOUMI from Cameroon":**

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Bachelor of Applied Sciences (B.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

V Software Development Colleagues were:

1. Senior Software Developer "MAMIDI" from INDIA.
2. Senior Software Developer "Detlef Kendelbacker" (Contractor) from Bayern–Germany.
3. Team Lead "Gerhard seng" from Bayern–Germany.
4. Software Architect Balakrishnan; from India.
5. Software–Engineer [Diplom–Informatiker : [Dipl.–Inf.]] Xavier Noumbissi NOUNDOU; from Cameroon.
6. Technical Lead DESIREE görisen; from Bayern–Germany.
7. Technical Lead [Dr.] GANESH gopalakrishnan; from India.
8. Technical Lead [Diplom–Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.–Inf. (FH)]] Johannes Bauer; from Bayern–Germany.
9. Technical Lead [Diplom–Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.–Inf. (FH)]] Martin Maier; from Bayern–Germany.
10. Technical Lead [Ing., Polytechnico Di Milano] Dario Meraviglia; from Italy.

VI Software Testing Colleagues were:

1. Test Manager [Diplom–Informatiker : [Dipl.–Inf.]] "TILO mücke"; from Germany.
2. Software Tester "Merlin Tonka, M.Sc. (Computational Engineering, University of Erlangen–Nürnberg, Germany)" from Bagangte, Cameroon–French–Island
3. Software Tester "Suschma" from India
4. Software Tester "Swapnil, Bachelor (Mechanical Engineering)" from India
5. Software Tester "Dhananjay" from India

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (STUDENT SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT GEWETE GMBH)

1. CREATE SQL databases JAVA Servlet programs and C++ communication protocol software programs (advised by SVEN KAMRATH | JENS MÖLLER) | BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH (NOW GEWETE GMBH), GERMANY [03/2005 – 04/2007]

[CE – EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en), UNDER german-traveler student part-time-work-permit, C++, MAKE, "JSWING", Hibernate, JAVA, Servlets, apache ANT, Eclipse IDE, XML (e.g: JAXP library), Qt, SQL, Vending machines, Communication protocol – [debugging at YERITH R&D Now !](#)]

I. APPLICATION FOR A STUDENT DEVELOPER POSITION AT "BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH":

I stumble on this offered position while I WAS LOOKING FOR A NEW DEVELOPER position part-time when I KNEW MY PROJECT with "PROF. DR. RER. POL. KLAUS–racist bönkost" would not be renewed.

THE position was advertised on a website for student jobs of the TUHH (<https://www.tuhh.de>).

II. Duties of Student Software Developer [Vordiplom in Informatik] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project development, and its installer Graphical User Interface (GUI) program developed using "JSWING" ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Swing_\(Java\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Swing_(Java))) JAVA library technology."
2. "MESO": "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing follower project development."
The novelty in this follower project is that I INTRODUCED, based on my research skills, acquired in BREMEN, an object–relational database object mapper called "**Hibernate** (<https://www.hibernate.org>)"; THIS was to be capable of giving newer customers ORACLE 9i functionalities from "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project" !!!
3. "C++ coding of a "Sap-ABAP protocol communication interface" to put "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" vending machines in communication with vending machine of Hamburg public library that used "BIBLIOTHECA software library"."
4. "C++ coding of SIPv2 control communication protocol (https://handwiki.org/wiki/Standard_Interchange_Protocol)."
5. Migration from "ORACLE 9i database tables" onto "MySQL database tables" for the MESO project (follower of LaDIVA software project); I used following technologies:
 - a. BASH–scripting
 - b. AWK scripting language.

III. Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "Bergmann Automaten GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg":

1. "paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon".

Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug" (<https://www.tuhh.de>).

"Demo" then obtained by "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" a position as "Bachelor student working on its thesis, project–based":

- a. I talked to "Mister Sven Kamrath of this request", by "Mister Demo Noundou", of a Bachelor Thesis Project.
- b. HE ("DEMO") then refused a final offer as full–time "JAVA software developer" because he felt he couldn't perform well in a "JAVA plain object (JPO)" software development environment.
- c. "[2008] Demo Noundou, B.Sc." then accepted a position at "Canon Ltd. as PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer in Osnabrück; HE can–also wear title Dipl.–Ing. (FH).".
- d. " [2015] DEMO NOUNDOU is now at his own company in web development & training in HAMBURG. (<https://ank-technologies.com>) "
- e. " [2024] DEMO is also a consultant in african universities curriculum development based in KENYA, and others. NO ONE CAN BE A PROPHET IN HIS HOME–YAOUNDE. (<https://SAINTEBIBLE.COM/jesusquoteTOCHECK>) "

"DEMO NOUNDOU, B.Sc." also had a "grade of (10.5/20)" which is not a very good grade to enter such position as the one I GOT LATER ON AT siemens medical solutions; A "GRADE OF 14.5/20" is required to apply for any entry level position at ["SIEMENS AG GERMANY–low–payer"].

IV. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. Herr Sven Kamrath was very angry at myself 1 day during my stay in Rellingen to talk about an ongoing project 'LaDIVA XML Servlet Parser Server' !
"He found a subtle bug that I then fixed the same day."

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (WEB-HTML-CSS DEVELOPER AT ZENTRUM FÜR MULTIMEDIA IN DER LEHRE (ZMML))

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN websites – www.s-hb.de (<https://www.s-hb.de>) mainly – for KLAUS-racist-extreme BÖNKOST (advised by PROF. DR. RER. POL. criminal Klaus Bönkost) |
 ZMML-UNIVERSITY-RACIST-SEXIST OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY [Feb. 2003 – Feb. 2005]

[UNDER german-traveler student work-permit;
 'dunklefarbige mitarbeiter xavier aus Afrika',
 HTML5,
 CSS,
 "photoshop",
 IMAGE-dateien,
 FADRI,
 SVEN schu]

I. Duties of WERKSTUDENT [candidate vordiplom in INFORMATIK] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "Reception, and implementation, of design documents (e.g.: "photoshop images", etc.) from FADRI-racist."
2. ["Programming of HTML5, CSS web pages."];

[Participated 1-month to a training internship at Bremen4u-GmbH.]

3. "Programming of RAD-server programs with Graphical User Interfaces (GUI); With programming support of Sven-schu-nazi."

"RAD-server programming language (<https://wikipedia.org...>) is a sample VISUAL BASIC dialect domain specific language. "

4. "Participation in weekly meeting on development of websites and test facilities for students in economia."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – UNI-RACIST BREMEN

1. CREATE A MODEL-BASED TESTING FRAMEWORK TO AUTOMATICALLY GENERATE STATECHART MODEL TEST CASES FOR REACTIVE SYSTEM SOFTWARE ([advised by Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. Jan Peleska]) |
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY — "NOT fully described curriculum by myself" [09/2002 – 05/2007]
- a. "Diplom-Informatiker" : "MASTER 2" IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS (DIPLOMARBEIT): "STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (GRADE 18/20)"; as part work for the FSE-SOQUA (2006) Research Conference Proceedings full research paper: "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (VERIFIED.DE), AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [12/2006 – 05/2007]
- [“V”-“WATER FALL”-MODEL of Software Development, reactive system, UML 2.0, HybridUML profile, [statechart](#), Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), uniformly distributed statistical test case generation, MBT-RT-Tester, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF as of now a doctor (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .]
- Algorithms developed by myself for this 'Master of Science research-based Thesis ("Diplomarbeit" in German)' (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html) [1a], based on 'Prof. Dr. Marie-Claude Gaudelle' research outcome, as a mathematician in France, are used in the RT-Tester tool of the verification and validation research and German society "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) .
- b. C++ CODE GENERATION PLUGIN IMPLEMENTATION WITHIN CASE tool "Borland-Together", AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2006 – 02/2007]
- [reactive system, UML 2.0, [statechart](#), Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), C++ code generation, MBT-RT-Tester]
- Our algorithms are for the "TDIOHS: Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System" (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) state diagram formalism, that could be visualized by [statecharts](#) for instance using a 'Verified Systems International GmbH plug-in' for 'Borland-Together 6' (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Micro_Focus_Together) .
- c. "Research Master in Computer Science Software 2-Years PROJECT" : CogAG project : "Robot "Arni" usage in framework of creating mapping recognition algorithms and cartography.", Cognitive Systems Group (CoSy), "Christian Freksa as Project creator and lead", CoSy – University of Bremen, GERMANY [01/2005 – 03/2007]
- [Cognition, Cartography, RFID-tag technology, TEXT-TO-SPEECH (<https://>), Robot control, sensor, actuator, Debian Linux, C++, Qt, systemic racism]
- "My personal contributions were mostly in creating QT user interfaces code for controlling the virtual shop and the roboter "ARNI". I also was very much implicated in Software Engineering round-about code such as blackbox code for keeping a BB-blackboard software architecture between our software components and the MySQL database tables used to share some of the data between components of the software system."
- "I also worked on cognitive cartography algorithms using C/C++, together with "ALINA, Christian, Sasha, and SERDAR". I was moving the robot for scanning RFID sensors stapled onto our real test grocery store, and then trying to find a way for the robot-ARNI based on customer commands on the robot that were at entrance to help them find their way into the real test grocery store. I used text-to-speech technology to talk with robot-ARNI to customers. "
- I was also involved in:
1. HELPING in general project organization for instance:
 - A. Writing project meeting minutes.
 - B. Looking for places in train, buses for project week-end ("PROJEKT WOCHELENDE"). Etc.
 2. Searching for places ("Student sleep places – JUGENDHEBERGE") for project-week-end in groups for fasting our project development;
 3. Writing LaTeX documentation for project reports;
 4. Writing JUnit testing code for GUI code;
 5. Writing BASH-scripts for tackling connection problems between actuators and the Debian Linux Operating System (thanks to Christian).
- "Unfortunately I received a grade of only 2.7 (14/20) because I wasn't interested in cartography and cognition algorithms since this was the specialty of "Christian Freksa" and "CoSy Group of Research" (<https://cosy.informatik.uni-bremen.de>)."
- THIS IS THE REASON our project advisors "FRANK dylla", and "LUTZ frommberger" gave as justification to this baddest grade during my entire curriculum in ACADEMIA at all !
- I also need to mention that I was the only "SCHWARZNEGGER – black from africa" in this research group of mainly white-blond-racists like "MICHA", and "STEPHAN"...
- THESE 4 racists-idiot said some day I may not be very comfortable in group working with white-intellectual. I THINK "frommberger the female-male-gay-BORN-male was at origin of such systemic" sexist discrimination around myself; even during my research time under supervision of male-female-chevalie-boivert-PATRICK-lam !
- d. "A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMA AND TIMED AUTOMATA (Grade 20/20)", AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2004 – 12/2004]
- [Vordiplom in informatik – INDEPENDENT STUDY, Bachelor Independent Study, MATHEMATICS for Computer Science, Theoretical Computer Science, timed automata, büchi automata, timed csp, set algebra]
- I developed a set of transformations functions that take as input a büchi automaton and generates a timed automaton. This work was the 1st work under supervision of "Jan Peleska", at our request, because we had interest in working in avionics software development in his company "Verified Systems International GmbH" (<https://www.verified.de>)."
- It is my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji Ngongang" who is the one that gave me this advise at that time of my life where I was around 20 years old in Germany; "Just at my 2nd year of University."
- "Finally a small offer a 200 Euros monthly came after I performed 100 % for this work unpaid [details at link 1b], t hat I used as Independent study. "
- e. "1st & 2nd Semester Software Development PROJECT (Grade 18/20)", ST-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2002 – 09/2003]
- [“V”-“WATER FALL”-MODEL of Software Development, Software Engineering, Project Requirements, "Gant Diagrams", UML 2.0, XML, PHP, MySQL, JAVA]
- "This 1st and 2nd semester project, divided in 2 parts consisted in creating a multi-user dungeon server (MUD-server) where a virtual world existed; 1st year was used to elicit user software program requirements, and establish "Requirement documents using UML 2.0".
 - "telnet (port 23)" protocol was used as client-server communication mechanism."
 - "I involved myself in a project where I contributed around 7 000 lines of plain JAVA code of program development."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY-CARE – UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN

1. Psychological care | [10/2002 – 07/2007]
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- A. "DIPL.-PSYCH. RALF ERIC STREIBL.", MATHEmatics and Computer Science Department, University of Bremen, Germany [10/2002 – 07/2007]
["Dipl.-Psych. Ralf ERIC Streibl".]
- "As a student of computer science in the "FB3" of the UNIVERSITY OF Bremen, In city Bremen, HANSEATISCHE-CITY, Germany, WE had a psychologist as 1 of our lecturer called "Dipl.-Psych RALF-idiot Eric Streibl". "
- RALF-idiot was kind of very reluctant to discriminative opportunities because I remember having visited courses on web creation based on PHP, and MariaDB, since I WAS having [a student-job (WERKSTUDENT) at "ZMML"].
- Eric RALF-idiot also gave myself a so called course titled "PROPÄDEUTIK" where we students learned on how to effectively, clearly present our projects or work; THIS was done in groups and individually !
- B. "AT-HOME-RACIST-IN-BREMEN PROGRAM", Foreigner office-"Sekretariat für AUSLÄNDISCHE studierende", University of Bremen, Germany [JULY 2005 – AUGUST 2017]
["RAÏNER schulze-smidt".]
- THIS program was exclusively addressed for foreign country students to gain access to german in-born families in order to accustom one to germany as a home country.
- "I joined this program because my maternal uncle "THÉODORE WANDJI" recommended it to myself because He was emigrating to CANADA-montreal, And would have been very far from me. "THÉODORE wandji ngongang" was the one person that welcomed and invited myself to study in BREMEN ! "
- AT this effect, each volunteer foreigner student would be connected to a single volunteering family of BREMEN. IN my specific case, I was assigned to the "ARISTOCRATIC"-bürgerliche family "SCHULZE-SMIDT", originating predominantly from HOLLAND into GERMANIA.
- MISTER "raïner-schulze-smidt", and his 2nd"SPOUSE GABRIELLE schulze-smidt" were really kind and nice to myself.
- "RAINER was "sole investor and proprietor-German-INHABER of an insurance company in Bremen, and in LONDON-great-britain", WHERE he did his apprenticeship as "INSURANCE-business-man". HIS 2nd spouse Gabrielle that I met in person; Was a part-time "physiotherapist" for the football team of Bremen city : "WERDERBREMEN (<https://>)". "
- Through them, I could know more about the origins of the autonomous-HANSE-STADT of Bremen, since "GOVERNOR SMIDT" as upper-upper grandfather of "MR. RAÏNER Schulze-Smidt", was governor of BREMEN for 50-years, and is the one person that acquire land from "HANNOVER-autonomous-STATE", to create a water-port-German-haven; "BREMERHAVEN", as a city and port for the autonomous city-federal-STATE of BREMEN.
- People and places I visit, and met, through organization of RAINER and GABI :
- 1.) HIS cousins from Brazil by talk-only & pictures (<https://>); that I DON'T remember family names;
 - 2.) HIS cousins from JOHANNESBURG by talk-only & pictures (<https://>); that I DONT remember family names, but that are having a wool factory for exportation in the state of BREMEN-recist germania;
 - 3.) VISIT of "evangelic church" on King-JESUS birth day "December 25th";
 - 4.) VISIT of MUSEUM-"Fockemuseum";
 - 5.) VISIT of "musical-theater" in "BREMEN-DOMSHEIDE";
 - 6.) "Bernhadine", "Caspar", "Johann" & "senior sister JULIA" schulze-smidt.
 - 7.) Several friends of them in need of computer technical help in terms of Software installation, and support.
 - 8.) "DOROTHEE" and "her brother Dr. oec. Sebastian Dettmers (<https://>)";
 - 9.) "Kryenhop family" (<https://>) : a leader in industrial transfer And sale of asian food and products into GERMANY :
 - a.) Father "Rolf";
 - b.) Daughter "SVANTSKE";
 - c.) etc.
- "I quit this family relationship at request of "RAÏNER" and "his 2nd spouse GABRIELLE-gabi", because they thought I lied to them that I have got a position as a temporary "SOFTWARE DEVELOPER" employee earning "70 000 Euros" annually at "AMADEUS Germany GmbH", Via THE frankfurter human resource company """. "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY-CARE – YERITH-RD-TEST

2. Psychological care |
 COLLÈGE INTEG –FROM-LAQUINTINIE-HOSPITAL-EYOUM-CHRISTIAN-IDIOT-CRIMINAL,
 DOUALA, CAMEROUN [01/2021 – 06/2021]
- A. "DR. (PH.D.) JEAN MOUBEB", Collège Integ –from-LAQUINTINIE-hospital-EYOUM-christian-idiot-criminal,
 Douala, Cameroun [01/2021 – 06/2021]
 ["DR. (Ph.D.) Jean MOUBEB".]

"ROSE sangnou-chienne-génitrice; a sanguinary mégère that is said to have caused a sudden death of her husband THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot; my biological genitor; ORGANIZES that I am brought by force to a psychiatric institute called Douala-laquintie-hospital because we had a talk at her mother's place where I WAS SAYING that I NEED my documents from my real-estate properties be given back to myself by her."

"AS I am currently writing this small report on NOVEMBER 20th, 2024; ALL my belongings weren't given back to me by VICTOR koliou noundou that detains this official documents that I MUST possess by inheritance right as summoned by a judge just after the death of my father and dear genitor THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot."

"INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni-chandriand, born-geboren Ingrid TCHITCHUI noumbissi is trying to take away all my real-estate properties, together with LAURENT-tchandeu free mason !!! "

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS I

1. **2003 – 2005:** [ZMML – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE ENHANCED LEARNING CAPABILITIES of economics students at the University of Bremen by DEVELOPING WEBSITES AND STUDENT SELF-LEARNING COMPUTER PROGRAMS, together with THE TEAM OF PROFESSOR KLAUS BÖNKOST.
2. **2006:** [FB 3; University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE created a website for the AFRICAN STUDENT ASSOCIATION "Nasgen e.V (New African Student Generation eingetragener Verein)" !
3. **2006:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE pleaded FORMER CAMEROON STUDENT serge achille fopoussi nono TO COME WITH MYSELF CONTRIBUTE at work research group of PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
4. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE completely alone, installed and deployed a networked installation of LaDIVA at a section of "KARLSRUHE city council !", SO TO ALLEVIATE DUTIES OF dear mentor DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH) SVEN KAMRATH !
5. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY pinpoint TU HAMBURG-HARBURG CAMEROON STUDENT david demo noundou TO MR. JENS MÖLLER of GEWETE GmbH ¹, FOR HIM TO HELP MR. DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU with access to FINAL SCHOOL YEAR WORK EXPERIENCE, AND BACHELOR OF SCIENCE THESIS-WORK.
6. **2006:** [University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I could successfully provide "MS WINDOWS SOFTWARE" INSTALLATION, TROUBLESHOOTING, and TRAINING to several GERMAN people because of "DEAR MR. RAINER SCHULZE-SMIDT" and HIS SPOUSE "MS. GABRIELE SCHULZE-SMIDT".
THESE EXPERIENCES WERE VERY POSITIVE FOR my finances !
7. **2005 – 2007:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **2007 – 2009:** [SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Erlangen, Bayern, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY MAINTAIN All Oncology Care Systems HOSPITALS customers, throughout the whole planet, ON FRONT-LINE OF problem/defect RESOLUTION WHENEVER technicians on CRITICAL problem phone resolution lines 1, 2, and 3 COULDN'T SOLVE SOFTWARE TECHNICAL ISSUES of linac.
9. **2009 – 2011:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE socially, WITH COMPUTING TECHNOLOGY, helped following afro-descendants from CAMEROON:
 1. CÉLESTIN puene: helped him search on the internet, and call, because of his poor English language knowledge, U.S.A businesses for inquiring on buying trucks for his brother in Cameroon.
 2. FABRICE Kouam Kamdem: maintained and improved an on-line website for FREE for his cameroon oriented professional association.
 3. ALBERT HERVAIS Ngagom Piewe: taught Debian-Linux basic shell command usage, Java and C++ programming on phone and internet.
 4. I HAVE presented orally and given personal written material ON SOFTWARE SECURITY AND SAFETY to CAMEROON ASSOCIATION of migrants in KITCHENER-WATERLOO: "ROWAC".
10. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE INTRODUCED skilled migrant cameroon worker, as ACTUARY in TORONTO, "AUDREY Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc (Université de Laval, Québec, CANADA)" to use and exploitation of FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE (FOSS) "Debian Linux".
11. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE advised, counseled, and even developed an on-line website for fellow CAMEROON expatriate YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (ÉCOLE SUPÉRIEURE DE GESTION, Paris) ON HIS ABANDONED PROJECT (WITH DAUGHTER OF FORMER ENERGY MINISTER of cameroon) FOR SOLAR ENERGY PRODUCTION in cameroon.

I WAS INTRODUCED to "YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (E.S.G, Paris)" BY MY AUNT-HUSBAND pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.
12. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY buy and implement foundations of "IMMEUBLE YERITH_{r&d}" which WILL STEM as a "PREMIER COMPUTING RESEARCH AND "Software Testing & Validation"" center in CENTRAL AFRICA (yaounde, center region, cameroon) !

I BOUGHT THIS PLOT OF LAND FROM hon. THÉODORE DATOUO; vice-president of parliament in YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION IN CAMEROON !

Land title CERTIFICATE nr.: 560 792, in SIMBOK, mfoundi vi (6), vol. 265 !
13. **2014:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE searched information, on how to WELCOME and ACCOMMODATE CAMEROON AMBASSADOR IN OTTAWA, for "ROWAC", a cameroonian ASSOCIATION of high skilled migrants (MOSTLY PROVENING FROM GERMANY) in KITCHENER-WATERLOO.

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS II

14. **2021:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE built a partnership with Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe and his societal NGO so to provide his NGO with VERY CHEAP AND APPROPRIATE software solutions for a NGO financed foodstore.
15. **2022:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY trained Mr. NESTOR Kenfack in ONLY 3 days at basic usage of our ERP software system YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for hardware shop selling. Mr. NESTOR Kenfack IS ONLY holder of a "B.E.P.C".

USUALLY in Yaounde, a holder of a "B.E.P.C" couldn't be trained to use COMMONLY present ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEMS (e.g.: 'Sage Gescom i7', 'SAP Business One', etc.), BECAUSE THEY ARE MEANT for highly qualified users.

Mr. NESTOR Kenfack HAD NEVER GOT exposure to an ERP system in the past.
16. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have given software cyberspace security counsels to Santa Lucia AHALA by talking to a computer technician employee because I could see vulnerabilities at cashier while paying for my goods.
17. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have counseled a business owner to start a bigger grocery shop and gave him ideas and ways on how to realize this using YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM, and, also, my unfinished two-storey building.
18. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have started YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), so to improve computing skills of fellow citizen, and also, of any other person that conforms to Cameroon laws !
20. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I try to have SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA AS 1 OF MY CLIENT THESE COMING YEARS so to have YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM there working instead of 'Odo'.
So they (SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA) will contribute in improving quality by thorough usage of this new platinum-platform.
21. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I am now working with ALT PLUS in YDE-AHALA so to have a working Supermarket in one, Instead "of a hardware-shop + a food-store separately, BUT JOINED physically".

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS I

1. **YEAR-2005:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the JAVA servlet XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA", AND ITS GUI (JAVA-SWING) configuration and installer program; for GEWETE GmbH !
2. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF "MESO"; the IMPROVED and revised version of the XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA" for GEWETE GmbH !
3. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the library computer systems communication protocol SIPv2 for GEWETE GmbH vending machines !
4. **YEAR-2005:** INVENTION OF A PROCEDURE TO systematically transform A BÜCHI AUTOMATON into A TIMED AUTOMATON ! TASK COORDINATED BY SHAREHOLDER PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
5. **YEAR-2006:** CREATION OF (with higher study part team CogAg of the University of Bremen [Cognitive Systems Group led by DEAR LATE PROFESSOR CHRISTIAN FREKSA]) ROBOT "arnie"; AND PROCEDURES TO automatically map a supermarket both geographically AND store item-wise with RFID technology by HELP OF A ROLLING ROBOT "arnie" !
6. **YEAR-2007** [FB 3! AGBS: Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)]: IMPLEMENTATION OF statistical uniformly distributed test cases generation for HAREL-statecharts ! COMMERCIALIZED BY VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
7. **YEAR-2007:** [FB 3! AGBS: University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **YEAR-2008:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the communication and control protocol DIGITAL MEVATRON INTERFACE PROTOCOL (DMIP) version 13 for THE LINEAR ACCELERATOR "linac" of SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Oncology Care Systems (OCS) !
9. **YEAR-2009:** Stopping my career; AFTER 21 MONTHS; as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS (Oncology Care Systems) in ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY; with 0 defects / faults returning FROM CUSTOMERS because OF non achievement protocol repair ! Award saying from BOSS GERHARD SENG; MY TEAM LEAD !
10. **YEAR-2011** [ECE! Ph.D. in Computer Science]: I HAVE INVENTED AND INTRODUCED A PRACTICAL AND SIMPLE STATIC ANALYSIS BY ITERATIVE DATAFLOW ANALYSIS, to check temporal safety properties, expressed with tracematches, of JAVA programs !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* Similarly, but as a dynamic analysis technique) MASC thesis (2011; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR JON Eyolfson of the UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, ON, CANADA !
EVEN THOUGH JON Eyolfson MASC (COMPUTER ENGINEERING) SUBMISSION WAS EARLIER THAN MY Ph.D. in SOFTWARE ENGINEERING THESIS DEFENSE, because of finding an examiner (reporting) within ECE DEPARTMENT, I AM THE ONE THAT GAVE A PROTOTYPE DESIGN AND PROTOTYPE DOCUMENT FOR HIS SUBMISSION !
11. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY DEVELOP manual and automatic BASH (Bourne Again SHell) programs (scripts), THAT LEAD TO A 0.5% improvement of WEBSPHERE computing performance !
12. **YEAR-2013:** CREATION OF A RUNTIME dynamic taint analysis for the QUERCUS PHP INTERPRETER !
13. **YEAR-2015:** FIRST WORLD-WIDE OPEN-SOURCE (foss) RELEASE OF AN LLVM-BASED ON INTERMEDIATE REPRESENTATION (IR) static iterative KILDALL (gary kildall) DATAFLOW ANALYSIS named 'YERITH-SAINT' !
'YERITH-SAINT': <https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint> !
14. **YEAR-2015:** CREATION OF A CONTEXT-SENSITIVE FLOW-SENSITIVE tainted paths generation algorithm by iterative dataflow analysis !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* EXACT same technique) PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at VIRGINIA TECH, VA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR SAZZADUR Ahaman AT University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ, U.S.A !
 2. PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, SANTA BARBARA, CA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ARAVIND Machiry AT Purdue University, IN, U.S.A !
15. **YEAR-2020:** FIRST OFFICIAL RETESTED RELEASE OF THE full featured OPEN SOURCE enterprise resource planing software "YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE"; FIRST OFFICIAL RELEASE OF THE OPEN SOURCE AUTOMATED BACKUP-SYSTEM AND ALERT ("yerith-erp-3.0"-system-daemon": <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>) !

"YERITH-ERP-PGI-standalone, server, academic, client" ARE THE DIFFERENT VERSIONS OF THIS FOSS-ERP-PGI-FRENCH !

SERVER AND CLIENT are mainly meant for a supermarket having several cashiers offices, AND A SERVER directing MYSQL-commercial options in common for different client-cashier-OFFICES !

ACADEMIC is meant for use WITH an IN-MEMORY DATABASE like "SQLite" !
16. **YEAR-2021:** First stable release of YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE at PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE MAKÈPÈ !

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS II

17. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST DELIVERY OF a compendium OF DOCUMENTS concerning OUR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE !
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>
18. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE state transition diagram LIBRARY FOR RUNTIME DATAFLOW VERIFICATION (YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))
20. **YEAR-2022:** MODIFICATION OF A Free Open Source Software (FOSS) "QVGE" (<https://showroom.qt.io/qvge-qt-visual-graph-editor>) TO DESIGN state diagram TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES ! "YR_QVGE" ! YR_QVGE is a commercial tool of mine priced at 3 000 EUROS a single executable copy.
21. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE FRAMEWORK for runtime dataflow analysis (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF | YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif) | 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))!
22. **YEAR-2022:** I have added a runtime check verification view within FOSS-ERP ("YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER": 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)) IN ORDER TO VIEW LOG MESSAGES SENT TO YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !
23. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION of a systematic method, AND / OR PROCEDURE TO TEST AND / OR verify dataflow of thick-client (or web application), AGAINST A SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY SPECIFICATION expressed as a STATE DIAGRAM (modified mealy machine) !
24. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST OFFICIAL REPORT in FRENCH LANGUAGE OF ACTIVITIES of YERITH R&D SINCE RELEASE OF FIRST STABLE VERSION OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum!
"REPORT in french: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>" !
25. **YEAR-2023:** creation of a domain-specific language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG) to describe *state diagram mealy machines* (📄 [SDMM](#)).
26. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION with flex and bison OF A DOMAIN-SPECIFIC LANGUAGE COMPILER to create source C++ code files for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
27. **YEAR-2023:** SUBMISSION OF A FULL TECHNICAL PAPER ("YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF: A FRAMEWORK FOR VERIFYING SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTIES OF GUI SOFTWARE AT RUNTIME") TO SPLASH-ICTSS 2023 CONFERENCE in May 2023.
28. **YEAR-2023:** Implementation of more than 2-states *state diagram mealy machine* (📄 [SDMM](#)) in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)), and YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)).
29. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION of guarded condition expression specification within YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)), and automated code generation of guarded condition expression in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
30. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
31. **YEAR-2023:** First release of our CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) drawing design tool "📄 [YRI_QVGE](#)" official commercial document.
32. **YEAR-2023:** online ENGLISH INTO FRENCH, and vice versa LANGUAGE TRANSLATION within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
33. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION of a viewing graphical user interface application for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF in JUNE.
34. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF FIRST RELEASE OF automatic EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP SALARY CALCULATION. Cumulated pay groups for a single employee salary calculation is included.
35. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION OF a user's guide for YERITH_QVGE.
36. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED IMPLEMENTATION OF a user sample project AUTOMATIC binary executable generation in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
37. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE programs under analysis (PUA) monitoring within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
38. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE runtime monitors WITHIN A SINGLE EXECUTABLE for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
39. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED journal article (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8381187>) for STTT official journal release.
40. **YEAR-2023:** started a predicate logic for deriving SOFTWARE RECOVERY ACTIONS for sdmm ("state diagram mealy machine").
41. **YEAR-2023:** started writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10515549>).
42. **YEAR-2024:** finished writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report*: THIS REPORT specifically says that CPDM ruling party has tried to destroy my life using *CHRISTIAN eyoum* (<https://scholar.google.fr/citations?user=eHvsI1UAAAAJ&hl=fr>).
43. **YEAR-2024:** started writing courses curricula and content for several courses of [YECEFOIQ](https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm) (<https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm>).
44. **YEAR-2024:** started creation of a web site application for teaching computer science center YECEFOIQ.
45. **YEAR-2024:** I have implemented case insensitive search for financial expenses list within YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
46. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paused new features in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (I.E.: Human resource management, and Financial Accounting management) due to advancements required for their quality assurance, WITH 📄 [YRI_QVGE](#)!

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS III

47. **YEAR-March 2024:** I could finally find 1 company commercial that rented my 1st 3-bedrooms apartment in DLA for "90 000 Xaf" monthly !
48. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paid "50 000 Xaf" as starting advance funds for incorporating YERITH R&D SARL.
49. **YEAR-March 2024:** I am recruiting 1 commercial financial-entrepreneur for ~~YECEFOHQ~~ (LOOKING for investment funds).
50. **YEAR-JUNE 25, 2024:** Returning client N.K hardware shop for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 !
51. **YEAR-2024:** Refining automatic stock CSV data entry.
52. **YEAR-JULY 29, 2024:** Still training "Christelle Akamba" for just 1 000 Francs an hour.
THERE is no money outside in Yaounde; and my rental apartments are still not having renters due to LAURENT TCHANDEU that I know has been trying to disrupt my activities in the open source software (OSS) era.
53. **YEAR-September 08, 2024:** *I AM working on ground to perfection building YERITH.*
THERE is lack of funding even though I could have my judicial affair against CHRISTIAN-EYOUM and others to get sent back to NDOKOTI prosecutor.
UNFORTUNATELY attorney SYNCLAIRE-NJEUTCHA-TCHANA has been trying to disrupt my activities with some money-bribery he received from genitor-organizer of assassination of mine !!!
I now try to get ATTORNEY-tchonang-albertine on my side these days. C.P.D.M wolfgang owona idiot political party has been trying to take down all my activities so to destroy a non-gay citizen.
54. **YEAR-2024:** Incorporating unit of measure like gram, etc. for inventory stock entry creation and pricing.
55. **YEAR-2024:** Started incorporating Financial debt entries creation in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
I am also specifying YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME for a new idea as good-physical stock exchange start-up marketplace idea.
56. **YEAR-NOVEMBER 2024:** I have re-introduced new color schemes for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME, AND also started a document for SPECIFYING and DESCRIBING the already existing and ALREADY IMPLEMENTED: C++ runtime monitoring verification library SDMM (STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE) :
1. YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF : [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif) ;
 2. ITS usage as algorithmic trading stock exchange library and runtime monitoring engine with help of a FOSS *"STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE"* (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) monitoring container for real-timing.
57. **YEAR-JANUARY 2025:** *I have incorporated "FR", "EN", USA-american flag and FRANCE-flag onto YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM so to hint users on Translation from English into FRENCH; And vice versa.*
58. **YEAR-JANUARY 2025:** *We are trying to render incorporating of sdmm[1d] as plug-gable dynamic libraries into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.*
59. **YEAR-FebRUARY 2025:** *[I am also trying to check conformant thread calls from runtime QT-QTimer instances whenever a user tries to cancel his modification / insertion work; FOR instance a special case is whenever 'INSERT/UPDATE' button is pressed and then there is intermingling with the checking mechanism introduced for verifying whether a user cancels his work on the window frame or not !]*
60. **YEAR-March 2025:** *I am struggling with INGRID-own-sister that digest all time my genitor because of 6 children with less than 2 years separation birth time between them !*
61. **YEAR-April 2025:** *Currently doing major research & inspection work for a web shop by using partly our; At YERITH R&D, new invention WYSIWYG-Tool for web HTML pages (YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL) !*
62. **YEAR-April 2025:** *NO body originating from West Cameroon seems to be living peacefully in CMR with bulu tribe since event a ["president bulu of the republic"] is embezzling young researcher in science and / or engineering like myself so to perpetuate going to IMF-fucking-idiot to pertain African in under poverty world for ever-devilish !*
63. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[JUDGE yager] seems to think of taking my complaint more seriously these days since I was advised to meet another justice attorney working a kind of on my file; Directly this coming 20th week of year 2025 (May-12 up to May-16) !*
64. **YEAR-May 2025:** *Eyoum Christian sends even people as kind fo rental management agent into my house to act so to hijack myself again : "Soumbil" living here at Cité-des-Palmiers.*
65. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[I am also these days trying to incorporate a dynamic taint analysis within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum as an instance incarnation of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF and / or "SDMM" specification & accompanying source code.]*
66. **YEAR-May 2025:** *We are working on our 1st prototype complete product that automatically generates a webshop from QT-trolltech user-interface files again this month; We plan a travel abroad !*
67. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[Soumbil, a molester of myself via a so called paternal uncle-gay-hijacker seems to not understand that as a mature researcher professional, And born-again Christian; There is no need for myself to talk with non sense village-babouantou-born people like KOLIOU-gay-idiot VICTOR-noundou !]*
68. **YEAR-JUNE 5, 2025:** Currently refactoring YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum !
69. **YEAR-JUN.-NOV., 2025:** *I am solely working on all projects so to try having YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum in the software program market starting JAN. 2026 !*

20.20 'VALKYRIE' upgrade to DEBIAN BULLSEYE (11.0); QT-5

VALGRIND USER INTERFACE: *valkyrie* (<https://www.valgrind.org/downloads/guis.html>)

July 2023

- Free open source code:
https://www.github.com/yerothd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL

'VALKYRIE' is a dynamic analysis CASE tool for verifying memory errors, and using VALGRIND as backend program server for analysis.

21.21 CONTEXT SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ("YERITH-SAINT")

October 2009 – March 2015

- Free open source code:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>

'YERITH-SAINT' is a static taint analysis that computes tainted paths in C programs and that doesn't require any program annotations. 'YERITH-SAINT' is built upon the iterative dataflow framework and has been implemented using the LLVM compiler infrastructure. 'YERITH-SAINT' is interprocedural, flow-sensitive, and developers can choose to run it either with context-sensitivity or without. THE HEARTBLEED bug (april 2014; security breach in open ssl 1.0.1f) IS A POTENTIAL FINDING OF yerith-saint.

22.22 YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

Mars 2015 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE !

23.23 YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON': AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DB-BACKUP SYSTEM FOR 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

Mars 2015 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DATABASE BACKUP SYSTEM FOR FOSS-ERP YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE !

24.24 YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF': C++ Library FOR RUNTIME MONITORING (Safety Temporal Properties) FOR State Diagram MONITORING !

June 2022 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) C++ library, THAT ENABLES TO IMPLEMENT STATE DIAGRAM SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY RUNTIME CHECKING (and/or VERIFICATION).

25.25 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF': RUNTIME VERIFICATION OF TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES IN 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE'

June 2022 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
- YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM:
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE), AND REUSABLE DYNAMIC RUNTIME ANALYSIS AND TESTING INFRASTRUCTURE created for FOSS ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' !

26.26 [YRI_QVGE](#)

'YRI_QVGE': Design and Creation of Runtime SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTIES FOR State diagram MONITORING C++ Library
'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' !

2,500 Euros a single executable copy FOR DEBIAN-LINUX
June 2022 - Currently

27.27 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE](#): an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE: an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software'

PRICE DEPENDS ON installations ! (STARTS AT 200,000 XAF per node-computer; ONLY AVAILABLE FOR DEBIAN-LINUX)
Mars 2015 - Currently

(GRADUATE) STUDENTS ADVISING / COUNSELING

- 1.) ["AMIRHOSSEIN VAKILI"], Ph.D. (www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 2.) ["DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU"], BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF HAMBURG-HARBURG, HAMBURG, GERMANY
- 3.) ["DIVAM JAIN"], M.MATH (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/7943>) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2013
- 4.) [Dr "ERIC BREFO-MENSAH"], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/13341>) (CHEMISTRY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2018
- 5.) [Dr. "ESTHER ELIZABETH LAMBERT"], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://ca.linkedin.com/in/esther-lambert-5b869414>) (GEOGRAPHY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2009
- 6.) ["Basser (from Syria)"], MAsc (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING, ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2008
- 7.) ["FABRICE tchoumi"], MAsc (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING (AVIONICS), ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2007 – 2008
- 8.) ["FELIX FANG"], MAsc (<https://www.patricklam.ca/papers/15.pppj.af-analysis.pdf>) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2014
- 9.) Dr. rer. nat. "HASHIM CHUNPIR" (<https://www.igi-global.com/affiliate/hashim-chunpir/324991>) (MSC, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2005 – 2006
- 10.) DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. "SERGE ACHILLE FOPOUSSI NONO", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 11.) "DERRICK FIEDLER (born YAPI YAPO)", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 12.) "INES NGAKOU TEMOU", (BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 13.) "DAVID KAMGA ADAMO", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 14.) C++ MATRIX programming : "Dr. MOHAMED RIDHA MAHFOUDHI", MBA, PhD (Financial Engineering, University of Laval, QC, Canada). 08 / 2009
- 15.) www.assiw.com; "MARCELLIN TAALY" (<https://www.tally-tech.com>), (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY)
- 16.) "MATTHIAS (from Germany)", DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH); INFORMATIK-INGENIEUR, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 17.) "Virginie kamche" (<https://www.virginie-kamche.de>), DIPLOM-INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 18.) "MAÏMOUNA BAMBA" (https://www.linkedin.com/authwall?trk=gf&trkInfo=AQFQXYFtwV7oPgAAAZpFVPT4EKXGTEW7GH101CD4u_8N1S0xGKwMs5KN2sOZJwAIdn182N7jf-ZVEP0M88eq9AJpYmzhwyCmFnDfOVkLrgeYIiR8GwDj91RrPXUtYQsjgqcSZI=&original_referer=https://www.google.com/&sessionRedirect=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.linkedin.com%2Fpub%2Fdir%2FBamba%2FMaimouna) (from COTE-D'IVOIRE), DIPLOM-INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 19.) ["Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D."] (Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 20.) ["JON EYOLFSON", Ph.D.] (M.Asc. / Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/6206>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 21.) "THÉOPHILE TCHIENCHO", DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH), INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES, BREMEN, GERMANY

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - I

1. SHANDA family as a destructive life for BOTH noumbissi, and NGONGANG and whereabouts families

"SHANDA Ndjatie Dorothee, and her spouse official TONME-shanda-JEAN-claude" are the 1st persons that started destruction of my life by coming into my family with so called psychiatrist, via WOLFGANG-owona.

"OWONA wolfgang" seemed to getting married with ANGELA which is a cousin maternal of mine because HE WANTS to sell my soul to AMERICAN USA societies in the sense that HE put myself into troubles via GOVERNMENTS AGENCIES, all of them Are linked to secret services to which he belongs, as I HAVE HEARD from ANGELA myself.

Frequently, HE idiot wife says he traveled to USA, so he would talk to people that want my OPEN SOURCE entrepreneurial adventures to be stopped; GET money from them, Then organize hijacking with following agencies:

- 1.) Social Services; so I AM NO MORE independent in the state of biya-regime;
- 2.) HOSPITAL like "laquintinie", etc.

Dr.-wolfgang, which is born from MINISTER owona-joseph-deceased, And mother as daughter of MINISTER owona-Gregoire has tried to put Rosicrucian organization AMORC into my life via Angela who proposed to me to join a so called "lectorium-rosicrucae" based at external relations ministry Where WOLFGANG attends with her.

2. WAAH (anne), spouse Kemmegni, is a subject of BIYA SPOUSE !!!

This 'megere' of my grand mother mother's side; Tchuitchui-ELIZABETH;

Is obviously a devilish demon that possesses super-natural powers in dark kingdoms; Based of 3 sacred objects I have last seen in her house in Byemassi-YDE.

1. "Buffle" horns as a representation of Money-laundry-BAPHOMET-satan
2. 2 turtles carapaces in the back of the "Buffle" horns.
3. 2 portraits of girls invoking and respectively crying;

3. "SANGO, spouse Bernadette Noundou" IS SOMEWHAT a suspect at origin of this family tragedy !!!

This pseudo-suspect seems to want to acquire my place at KING.

Laurent tchandeu ministry plenipotentiary is a subject of itself at Batchieu-Babouantou kings places.

Obviously, every member of GRAND-FATHER noundou nuclear family is a subject to this GUJA.

4. "Victor Koliou NOUNDOU" IS A NOBODY into my life;

THIS idiot, junior brother of my deceased late father "Théodore Noubissi" is contacting people INCLUDING "derek rayside (drayside@uwaterloo.ca)" (Already talking with other ignorant paternal unwanted uncle "Jules NTETA noundou (julesnteta@gmail.com; julesnteta@yahoo.fr)" from Cameroon external research criminal agency (DGRE));

The idiot Victor presents itself as a chief of a family where I am supposed to belong with some faked official documents from uncle politician LAURENT tchandeu-IDIOT.

OFFICIAL registered document that "Victor KOLIOU NOUNDOU" refused to give a copy to myself when I asked him about, since I am the only, according to documents written by my late grand-father Michel NOUNDOU, Legitimate SUPERVISOR OF HIS left over to children and descendants, WEALTH AND MATERIAL POSSESSIONS !

"Afriland first-bank" and "Intelligentsia employee "Jean-PAUL-yamtche"; And CEO currently as of April 2024", A person that I really don't really know whereabouts in his genealogy or affiliation to my late grand-father; "Jean-PAUL-yamtche" owns a big storey house just opposite face of our main common house entrance in Babouantou idiot village !

"Afriland first-bank" and Intelligentsia MAIN CREATOR AND INSPIRATORY person; "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne", was, according to sayings of my genitor Rose Sangnou, 1 of an intimate friend of my late father and genitor "Théodore NOUMBISSI" !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" went to a place of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)", according to "Rose Sangnou" told myself in person when I reached age 32; That they ("LAURENT Tchandeu my paternal uncle" and "Rose SANGNOU" my genitor) gave money (BRIBED) to an employee of "CCEI-BANK" where "late Théodore NOUMBISSI" owed "4 000 000 XAF" at his death so that MORTGAGE ("hypothèque" in French) on his property-land in BONABERI-DLA (700 m²) would be erased everywhere in computers and documents of former 'CCEI-bank' !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" also told me, after I had an employment interview with "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne"; that my later genitor and father "Théodore NOUMBISSI" is the one, together with "HUGUES NTOMANI TIAKO", his business partner and soul-mate at that former ancient time, THAT computerized totally all enterprises businesses of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)" !

I remember seeing my late father only 1 time in a day, around 19 : 00 at diner time; this is before we moved to Yaounde in year 1990; After he quits "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-DLA" to open and manage solely "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-YDE" !

5. "LAURENT tchandeu (ltchandeu@yahoo.fr)" ASSASSINATES in an hospital "THEODORE noumbissi"; late father of mine on January 1992;

AS an orphan at age of 7.5 years old, I remember uncle paternal Laurent came into our biggest house in YDE-Essos to settle in the secondary apartment at the back of our house.

6. "LAURENT tchandeu" Tries with "Hugues Ntomani Tiako" "VIA judith ngaleu in Etobicoke (Toronto, Ontario, Canada)" to crash "my Toyota Corolla LE-2003" in December 2013

This sorcerer freemason ("Hugues Ntomani Tiako"), and Christian-so-called-ORTHODOX-catholic of Roma, acknowledges that IT SHALLN'T be that I gain cause in the court of justice process THAT I have against "LAQUINTINIE and SED", that sent 9 people, including "Christian Eyoum, MD, PsyD"; in February 2021 at night around 23 : 30, to hijack and attempts to kill myself.

SED sent myself 1 time in a CABANON Because they receive 15,000 FCFA from "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou and my genitor ROSE Sangnou", IN douala 2018.

"Galax Yves Landry Etoga" is personally, as a CPDM political party member, AND not as a SED authority implicated in trying to kill myself through psychiatry and / or any other means !

"Laurent Tchandeu (assassin of Ingrid's father and his elder brother in Babouantou-village)" is the one that connected "Ingrid TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI", born (geboren in German) TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI; my uterine sister, to marry officially "THE IDIOT AND PSY-CHILD since age 12 CHANDRIAND TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI".

7. "LAURENT tchandeu" Deems and Dares OR-DONATES to squeeze my financial money income VIA genitor of mine "Rose SANGNOU" Since September 2023 until TODAY.

8. "***JULES NTETA NOUNDOU extremely dangerous person" is a consanguine brother (same father; another, still living mother, in same marriage) of "LAURENT tchandeu"; And his helper in almost everything dirty and / or clean here in CMR!

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - III

9. ("Derek Rayside drayside@uwaterloo.ca") pays money to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that an equivalence to my "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering degree from UWATERLOO", will be turned from PhD into the non-academic degree ABD; just 2 weeks after talking with "JULES NTETA NOUNDOU" at his dirty-office in "YDE-élig-essono"
10. "David demo noundou" tries to connect me to Laurent external security research agent "Jean-Daniel-tujilo-tchokote"; "VIA his natal village idiot babouantou friend Célestin puene (cpuene@cscmonavenir.ca)".
11. "David demo noundou" has written documents in Germany that I was mentally ill while staying 3 days in his rental apartment in September 2018.
12. "David demo noundou" is A student of myself at the TUHH; benjamin brother of my late father "THEODORE noumbissi"; since I could help him get an bachelor internship At "GEWETE GmbH", Where I was working while a student at Bremen University state.
13. "LAURENT tchandeu" was a "Minister Plenipotentiary of Cameroon Embassies in France, Belgium, etc. for around 30 years outside of Cameroon". Especially promoted sent outside Cameroon 1 year after assassinating his elder brother "THEODORE noumbissi".
14. "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" tries to physically arrest and violates myself in front of at least 7 other people in his private residence of Bankepche-Bangou with no apparent reason other than humiliate myself.

"Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" vows a personal and individual cult to 'Shanda Owona Biya', especially as an appointed, not applied CPDM (RDPC) political party, vice-president in Bankepche-Bangou; with "Honorable Datouo Theodore" as his president.

15. "**RODRIGUE alain sienchié ngongang** (sienchie@gmail.com)", Ancient psychiatric patient in Düsseldorf-Germany Sends messages everywhere So I could again be hijacked into a Cabanon-cell FOR mad-ill-people; "Xavier Noumbissi Noundou" paid in total amount 2,000 Euros to help him get back "to his paternal family NGONGANG" in Deido-Dla-CMR !
16. "**Théodore Wandji Ngongang, And Aurélie Kamdoum Yano his spouse** (takouengongang@yahoo.ca; ngongangtietie@yahoo.ca)", ows myself around "1 500 EUROS" since year 2005 as he fled out from Germany to emigrates into "Montréal-Côtes-des-neiges" !
17. "**Idiot Angéla Tchamou Shanda Wolfgang Owona** (krauserminrex@gmail.com)", a maternal cousin of mine, tries to hijack myself in buses because She deems being a very important personality ("VIP") in front of myself.

"HER spouse Dr Wolfgang Junior Fernand Owona" was making her ("Angéla Tchamou Shanda Owona") come to myself and harassed me with: "Wolfgang wants to be president of the republic" !

This idiot of Wolfgang is the grandson mother side of "Grégoire Owona", who was implicated in the sudden death of his former colleague "Theodore Noumbissi (Late father of mine)".

"Grégoire Owona" is today inviting "my remaining genitor Rose SANGNOU" to his village houses in "Gomedzap-Center-Region-CMR"; so to think her How to destroy my life as a black and renowned scientist universally from the University of Waterloo; THIS in conjunction with former uni colleagues such as "Dr. PATRICK lam"; etc. "Grégoire Owona" -

For 2 days now (December 12, 2025.); my profile is down at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project; And at same time I felt several people trying to hijack my person here in Cameroon because a certain "#PASTOR-landry ENTERS MY PERSONAL HOME WITH A WEAPON."

In cameroon, as I have heard from people in background, CRIMINAL-ASSASSIN FROM yves-galax-landry Wear name PASTOR.

Derek Rayside has put back a vietnamese idiot on my file at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that I cannot be upwell in Cameroon.

My official university of waterloo graduate transcripts says:

"Program: Engineering Doctoral;

"PhD" Comprehensive Examination.

Status: Completed

Date Completed: 12/20/2011

In good english: "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering ("PhD" in Electrical & Computer Engineering)".

In french language: Docteur-Ingénieur (Dr.-Ing.).

IT means I must also have *Ph.D.* exactly as My former room colleague Jon Eyolfson that is since 2022 an Assistant Professor in Teaching only at the University of Toronto, ON.

18. **"S2TBED main proprietor-ally A SO-called gangster-Simplice-KAMENI was seen 2 days ago here in a luxurious car by myself.**

"IMMEDIATELY, today, *"/Friday-Sep.-27th, & Saturday-Sep.-28th/*, both days in year 2024, I and neighborhood start again to experience energy supply disruption for more than 4 hours."

SIMPLICE KAMENI seems to be a cocaine dealer that works on laundering money through usage of wood processing & wood sale activities via intermediary White-racist-extremist—italian so-called "MARCO".

ALSO, I could experience certain "neggers" working there from far-north cameroun coming along my foot way to dance kind of like I am their aid.

KAMENI simplice is also implicated in financing together with my cousin culprit-theodore-MOISE-tebiwo-yamkam my properties entirely in Cameroon; Starting year 2013 when TEBIWO-yamkam-moise traveled to Canada.

BOTH moise-yamkam-tebiwo, and SIMPLICE-kameni-ebacka; are sleeping in so-called orgy-sexist-FRANCK-biya gay personal property estate here in YAOUNDE.

19. **"HONORÉ WUCHE, a genitor of mine Spouse; ", EVENTHOUGH her cousin uterin, as hijacker into my life.**

"THIS honore-wouche has been calling me on my phone cell while I was a doctor of Engineering working on my doctoral Ph.D. degree in year 2013; GIVEN TO HIM BY ROSE sangnou."

HONORÉ WUCHE has lost already at least two wives he got kids with them as a guja.

HIS uterine cousin "Rodrigue Alain NGONGANG SIENCHIE", that tried to break my neck last August 2024 while I was attending home for 4 weeks and visiting faked "church Chapelle De la GLOIRE-DE-CHRIST by FAKED-devilish-racist-bassa pastor-so-called MARK-DJENG-DJENG";

Said to myself in front of honore-wouche that: 'SEND "xavier-noundou-ph.d." Again to MAD-person cell at "laquintinie" AS you did twice at least; I didn't even knew who was this gay-honore-wouche with black tattooed wrist-arm-bracelet for gangster and riders.

IT seems this cousin of my mother-genitor; together with another man-lady-cousin-uterine so called NANA; are working on molesting myself in life here in Cameroon; HE-honore-wouche told me laughing that 1 of his daughter was working in south-cameroon in farming for PAUL-biya-family.

20. **"Bulu-Sud-East-Akan tribe AS stealer in CMR"**

- Year 1983 was changed into year 1985-(*ingrid-teuntchou-noumbissi birth year*) so to allow later on a hijack of my property via a marriage to a uterine sister; Called "INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni", Born-geboren "Ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi";

[TEUNTCHOU-isaac & JOSUE-nkwouano; & RICHARD-mfeugwang agreed on a dinner time of my passing away with all means via a psychiatric injection treatment by LAQUINTINIE-hospital;]

[LAURENT-tchandeu could then secure a prosperous career after the killing & hijacking of money of his blood-brother Théodore-noumbissi-rosicrucian-rotarian !]

- "BULU-biya" tribe in CMR-c.p.d.m-r.d.pc are trying to hijack any wealth of Well-to-do rich cameroonian so to secure presidential leadership for ever.
- Bulu notary-justice attorney [*"MENYE-Ondo Xavier-FRANCOIS"*] & *"LIMA-rose (at time in 2012, 2013 years)"* change effectively & voluntarily year of birth of mine in my [LAND-title certificate of MFOUNDI-VI.]
- GENOCIDE of West originating people started in CMR

"MARIE-commissary-of-DEA-05ème-arrondissement-od-City-DOUALA, in Littoral region, sent 8 burglars on street to arrest myself while I was relating to CMRnian that BIYA regime has tried to spoliolate all my belonging via TEUNTCHOU-isaac."

"INGRID-teuntchou couldn't say no to this fake-marriage only to destroy my life as a super engineer and scientist originating from WEST-cmr."

"[TEUNTCHOU-isaac] used since she was aged 15 years old while I went outside of CMR to study in GERMANY-racist-culprit; NGATCHOU-henri-bertrand, a maternal uncle of myself & Ingrid to beat her & accustomate her to perform only what was told to her via JOSUE-nkwouano, senior brother of NGATCHOU-henri ! "

- 2025, AVRIL —18—*"DLA-ndokoti-palace seems to be for now out of service due to atrocities that I have related internationally via web-site "zenodo.org" ! "* (<https://www.zenodo.org>)

"ATANGA NJI idiot minister; Cannot prepare elections without asserting NON-Sence propaganda to Cameroon people."

- Laurent-fainéant TCHANDEU, a paternal vernacular uncle of mine seems to be an ally of people in Zürich working in Avionics !

TCHANDEU, TCHINGWA, KOLIOU, and HAKOUA seems to be working for whittle racist supremacists in other to destroy any afrique-intelligentsia out of a psychiatric cyclops and / or poverty; So no black intelligent person wouldn't gain his money out of independent intellectual work; & intellectual property.

TCHANDEU, the lead, a so called diplomat, Hires only personal people from his own blood family against scientists & engineers here in Cameroon in particular.

[Koliou, TEUNTCHOU have been associated together in their rosicrucian association de destroy my financial life as I COULD observed since February 2021 when TEUNTCHOU tried to kill me.]

21. ***"EKONDY-PONDY tries to humiliate myself publicly by arresting me without any paper from a judge and / or prosecutor, so called in french procureur-de-la-république !!!***

- ***THE president of the republic PAUL-biya has tried to assassinate myself several times.***

THIS is why I JUST reply by describing what happens on the internet media so 1-day, christian will see what is happening in life of a christian-JESUS-of-nazareth life here in CMR.

- Myself I only repeat like anyone that wants his life saved here that I support him for 2025 presidential elections !
- YOU just see a police man that has no police uniform come to your home and tries to open gate as you were a gangster. THIS time it was ekony-pondy, a commissary with 4 stars on his shoulder that came in person because my sister thought I must go again for a psychiatric treatment, because she belongs to people habilitated to decide so !!!
- 1 day I believe she will notice that she can do sp because BIYA wants to use her to destroy my brilliant career that doesn't accept homosexuality call marriage.

A country where the eldest girl-child of PAUL-biya says she is a lesbian without any fear of jurisdictions-justice because she is the girl of PAUL-biya !!!

JEOVAH-NISSI in heaven, please do your will in my life !!!

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (1.)

28.28 HIJACK OF MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY BY laquintinie on FEBRUARY 2021

[r-DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM – tALKING AT *BBC-british-broadcast-corporation* (<https://>), AND *+--rotarian--+* club member in douala-sawa-tribe, chief of psy staff of LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL IN DOUALA (LITTORAL REGION, CAMEROON)], has sent in FEB. 2021, without any official document, 7 people to break into my privately owned (closed with a steel gate) house in DOUALA, so to hijack myself and terrorize me. THIS HAPPENED AT NIGHT AROUND 11:00 PM, with BERTRAND, breaking my gate seals with a weapon of some sort (BERTRAND, was the lead thief of DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM).

THIS HIJACK OR ATTACK on my person happened just 1 day after I denounced to *PRC.CM* and *SHANDY-SHANDY-CABINET.COM* (biological father of my mother's side cousin ANGELA) a fake "BACCALAUÉAT"-DEGREE from 'ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA', because her sister-cousin CYNTHIA NKWOUANO told me about this: "ANGELA WENT TO CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC and received her diploma in a hotel".

I ALSO BECAME AN AGENT OF CAMEROONIAN DEFENSE AND SECURITY FORCES ON FEBRUARY 14, 2021.

DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM after this kidnapping, held me at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL for poisoning me 2 weeks, AND THEN RELEASED AN OFFICIAL DOCUMENT TO MY RELATIVE ROSE SANGNOU.

ROSE SANGNOU has since been using the fake document to go meet my clients to say that I AM A PSY PATIENT AND THAT THEY SHALL NOT DEAL ANYTHING WITH MYSELF. ROSE SANGNOU also went to meet all my privately-owned real estate properties' neighbors TO DO THE SAME.

I HAVE COMPLAINT BEFORE DOUALA-NDOKOTI JURISDICTIONAL TRIBUNAL in front of JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SINCE FEB. 2021:

- 3 convocations have been sent by now to DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM; he hasn't come to respond to prosecutors.
- I am now awaiting for a "MANDAT D'EMMENER" AGAINST DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM, a form of order from judge that will bring DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM in front of prosecutors by police force.

29.29 Kidnapping on FEB. 2023 WHILE WALKING BACK IN MY YAOUNDÉ REAL ESTATE PROPERTY

1. DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI accepts to send 2 thugs-burglars on the road to kidnap myself, while I was walking on street to get back into my house, and to bring me in a cab at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ; this is requested by DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA, spouse pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI is chief of psychiatry staff at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI IS VERY WELL KNOWN IN YAOUNDÉ to say disturbing voices against BAMILEKE-TRIBE, an ethnic group of the west cameroon to which, I by birth, and not by spirit [I AM A BORN AGAIN CHRISTIAN], belong.

2. AFTER 2 WEEKS OF POISONING AND TRYING TO DESTROY MY BODY WITH DRUGS AND PILLS, a yellow clothed (level of BACHELOR OF SCIENCE) gate guard OF "HÔPITAL JAMOT" that I don't remember the name, tries to SNEAK INTO my private life by calling me on my private cell phone number [(+237) 6 52 39 69 50] every other day.

I SAID TO HIM THAT I DON'T ENTERTAIN RELATIONSHIPS WITH PEOPLE LIKE HIM.

PS: THIS GATE GUARD, yellow-clothed with an uniform, is of BETI-TRIBE like DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI!

3. S2TBED, a so-called forestry society here in Yaoundé seems to be a secret agency against black-owned societies here in Cameroon.

30.30 Attempt to give me a psy consultation by ROSE SANGNOU's sister DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM

AFTER RELEASED FROM 'JAMOT', i stop taking the drugs that i was forced to intake by drink.

Knowing that this is judicial information time, I accept to talk to DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, which is DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA and ROSE SANGNOU sister, by my own request.

My goal is at time to collect as much information as possible.

She (DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM) tries to convince me that i should intake psy drugs in order to be more sociable !

31.31 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JUNE 2023

In June 2023, in its 25th week, a relative, ROSE SANGNOU, living and based in Douala for more than 60 years, comes into Yaoundé, and settle for 1 week at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA's house, at her (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) invite.

ROSE SANGNOU, whom was told, no more to persecute myself, during her interrogation time at prosecutors' office in Douala-Ndokoti, starts calling me increasingly and says she is in Yaoundé because her sister (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) son, PATRICE SHANDA SANOU CABRAL, is very ill and hospitalized at Yaoundé general hospital.

ROSE SANGNOU insists that we shall meet because she is my mother. I then accept, but refused to meet up her at my private owned property in Yaoundé-Ahala-Nsimbock. We then meet up first at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA house, then at supermarket 'supermarché carrefour EKIE' in YAOUNDÉ-ÉKIE.

THIS PERIOD IS judicial information investigation time, that is mostly why I accepted to meet up with her.

I NOTICE with an impression THAT my mother ROSE SANGNOU COULD HAVE BEEN BRUTALIZED ON HER LEFT KNEE. SHE SAID SHE FELT DOWN IN THE BACK OF HER SISTER'S HOUSE (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) because the maid woman SPILLED water with amidon on the floor.

AFTER FINISHING our lunch, my mother ROSE SANGNOU says I SHOULD START AGAIN TO TAKE psychiatric drugs: I IMMEDIATELY STAND UP FROM LUNCH TABLE AND RETURNS TO MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY, 'immeuble yerith'.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (2.)

32.32 MY SUSPICIONS about real activities of pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude and his wife

SEVERAL TIMES, pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude invited myself to hotel PARFAIT GARDEN in yaoundé so that I COULD SEE HIM ACTING as managing director of expatriate US CITIZEN ELECTRICAL ENERGY COMPANY.

so i suspect pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude receives money from some big giants NORTH-AMERICAN COMPANIES, so to disrupt my activities in the free open source software (FOSS) AREA.

33.33 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Victor Koliou Noundou IN JULY 2023

PREVIOUSLY. HÔPITAL ADLUCEM, a hospital in Douala-BONAMOISSADI, that I went with paternal uncle Victor Koliou Noundou to threat a hyperglycemia, established with him (uncle Victor Koliou Noundou) THAT I SHOULD BE BROUGHT USING AN AMBULANCE to 'LAQUINITIE-CABANON' because Dr. MVONDO felt that I am not well behaving !

Victor Koliou Noundou, a brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi ASKED MYSELF, relentlessly, if I still take the psychiatric drugs.

I need to note here that, WITHOUT ANY APPARENT REASON, another brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi, Laurent Tchandeu, former minister plenipotentiary, sent A TRUCK WITH 6 firefighters to take me by force from my privately rented apartment in yaoundé, in the year 2015, SO TO BRING ME TO A PSYCHIATRIST OF 'JAMOT': Dr. Kamga.

IN FRONT OF ME, Dr. Kamga SAYS TO Laurent Tchandeu AND ROSE SANGNOU THAT HE CAN'T KEEP ME THERE AT 'JAMOT' BECAUSE I AM NOT A PSYCHIATRIC DISEASED PERSON.

Dr. Kamga ALSO MENTIONS THAT IF I GO TO COURT AGAINST HIM, HE WOULD PUT ALL TROUBLES on ROSE SANGNOU since WHAT SHE SAID TO HIM SO THAT HE SENT A FIREFIGHTER TRUCK to take myself by force from my privately rented apartment is wrong.

Laurent Tchandeu IS TRYING SINCE Théodore Noumbissi, my deceased (JANUARY 9, 1992) father (and chief of the NOUNDOU family), passed away, to sack my POSITION AS CHIEF OF THE FAMILY NOUNDOU:

- IN MAY 2023, politician GRÉGOIRE OWONA, grand-father of MY COUSIN MOTHER SIDE "ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA", comes with Laurent Tchandeu (and spouse DR. HENRIETTE POLA) in my village BABOUANTOU to open a primary school as gift from political party R.D.P.C (C.P.D.M).

34.34 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Laurent Tchandeu ON AUGUST 3rd, 2023

DR. Laurent Tchandeu, a paternal uncle of mine, tries to harass myself with taking psychiatric drugs.

HE DID THIS USING TELEPHONY APPLICATION "whatsapp".

35.35 WAITING FOR judge JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA

JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SEEMS TO WANT TO destroy evidences against state hospital laquintinie since He (JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA) hasn't call by police force DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM to come answer allegations against him about TRYING TO KILL ME with psychiatric drugs at night after HIJACKING MY PRIVATE PROPERTY IN DOUALA-CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS !

36.36 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU harasses ROSE sangnou my mother

ROSE SANGNOU, my mother, complained to myself that KÉMAJOU is calling her very frequently to tell her I (PROF. DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU) is not mentally sane since HE is doing a lot of christian cross-sign while walking on Yaoundé streets.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (3.)

37.37 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU destroying my life as a neighbor

A FORMER SED (SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT À LA GENDARMERIE) retired colonel of cameroon gendarmerie, who has spying devices AT HOME TO HEAR PHONE, OR WHATSAPP conversations; MAKES CURRENT ELECTRICITY cut-off whenever I RECEIVE MONEY so I cannot cook and refrigerate my food properly.

THIS VERY POOR PERSON, both in spirit and financially; whose wife makes money out of cooking food for street workers, COULD SUCCESSFULLY intimidate people not to come attend work or anything else into my real estate properties.

COLONEL (retired) of Army Gendarmerie KÉMAJOU couldn't lie and convince people that I DON'T POSSESS A Ph.D in Computer Engineering; since his son "Jonas Kémajou" who he also in gendarmerie told me once: "Myself I also POSSESS A Ph.D QUALIFICATION WITH NO DEGREE AT HOME" !

I am wondering in Cameroon why army intermediates in civilian life and affairs; THIS DOESN'T HAPPEN usually in rich and developed countries like Germany.

This day of **Saturday November 18, 2023**; while I was talking to a computer technician neighbor named Gabriel Takoumbe, KÉMAJOU came along walking with an indigo "Garde Présidentielle (special unit of cameroon forces attached only for the President of The Republic.)" T-shirt.

COLONEL kemajou tells me HE WANTS MY PERSON NOT TO WRITE anymore on his forfeitures against myself; in front of at least 7 young men and women, saying He didn't call my genitor mother any day before.

COLONEL kemajou sect named JÉRUSALEM APOSTOLAT, sacks every public entry road to my real estate 2-storey building (unfinished yet).

Yves Landry Galax ETOGA, chief of secret services of Cameroon seems to like to try harassing competent professors of science and technology like myself. May be He works against CAMEROONIAN SKILLED ORPHANS like my humble person in JEOVAH-NISSI in heaven !

PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA and DR. PATRICK LAM have never said anything against what is happening to myself since 3 years ago; ALSO, Patrick is a member of Rotarian organization ROSICRUCIARY !

"29" November 2023: I HAVE RENOUNCED TO AN ATTORNEY since TCHANA NJEUTCHA Synclaire is clearly going against my personal interests !

"03" December 2023: KEMAJOU and its troops that call themselves Christians ARE HARASSING PEOPLE COMING HOME.

"04" December 2023: I cannot recognized Cameroon where someone high qualified by myself is permanently harassed physically by illegal neighbors like KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel Criminal.

KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel tries on the street to talk to myself while I am coming back from a hardware shop.

It seems to myself that illegal neighbors religious sect "Jerusalem Apostolat" is trying to make confusion about my humble person wherever I go in my life; Kemajou gendarmerie colonel has tried around my neighborhood, with help of SECTARIAN OF JERUSALEM APOSTOLAT; to make noise that XAVIER noumbissi noundou IS A PSYCHIATRIC PATIENT that doesn't want to take pills !

38.38 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JANUARY 2024

ROSE SANGNOU, despite that JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA gave her prohibition to come to my home in Yaounde during year 2023, came by force with someone that I don't know whereabouts To my neighbor "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" To incriminate her about chairs she owns by now;

I destroyed chairs that were not in good shape last year from my humble home by throwing them away outside. It seems "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" put them in her personal home without asking myself since I just threw them away; which is normal since They don't belonged to me anymore !

"30" January 2024: It seems my genitor mother ROSE SANGNOU went to talk to gendarmerie people so they could harass myself to go for an illegal psychiatric treatment; because while I was talking to Justice "ME. ANDRÉ Mbet" today, I saw 1 gendarmerie man came into his personal office where he also, with his wife, Owns a financial transaction center.

I immediately told Justice "ME. ANDRE Mbet" about this attitude of gendarmerie people coming inside where I perform businesses to make some kind of visual and gesture signs to owners of businesses, So they wouldn't deal with myself anymore !

"24, 25" April 2024: 1 man wearing a talkie-walkie came across my personal road in Simbock YDE.

I went to talk to him since I was looking for a technician that didn't finish a work in my humble house. For 6 days now, this technician wasn't in my house anymore despite myself telling him to finish his work on my steel door.

I suspect again justice ("huissier") SHANDA-DJATIE and her spouse Pr. JEAN-CLAUDE shanda-tonme to harass my genitor and mother Rose SANGNOU to try to bring myself by force to a psychiatric destructive mind place.

JERUSALEM-APOSTOLAT rosicrucian sect tried to follow myself these last 2 days using the brigand 'Moise BATOMEN', and another person male, THAT I don't know whereabouts but that live behind "Carine Lele Njougep Tchana" house for at least 6 months from now backwards in time !

Just 1 month before, I was stopped from walking by to our main official road by a sectarian female of Jerusalem-APOSTOLAT. I now see that it was meant to bring myself to other roads were they don't have their own people on it, so they could hijack myself properly to bring by force to a psychiatric hospital so to try to deteriorate my physical and psy body.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (4.)

39.39 SHANDA SANOU patrice cabral idiot son of Dorothee Shanda Owona passes away at age 33 (March 18, 2024)

"Dorothee Shanda Owona" who had tried to make myself sodomized "by Bertrand of Laquintinie" in Feb. 2021, illegally by police force.

SHE leaves now her son out of life after 3.5 years trying to destroy my life; Probably because she got some laundry money for this dirty task against A BORN-AGAIN-CHRISTIAN !

NONE of the people I have heard from coming back "from some kind of obituary ceremony" could even see any corpse of ATTORNEY OF LAW, deceased, Patrick Cabral SHANDA SANOU !

40.40 Dr. Annie Metiam, Spouse Eric-POKAM-WAM tries to say something illegally about my mental health publicly (May 23, 2024)

A sister of my mother and genitor ROSE SANGNOU, DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, sends a RECORDED AUDIO MESSAGE via whatsapp-phone-android-application, without any request from "Rose Sangnou" and / or my person about a supposed mental health abilities report that She as GASTROENTEROLOGIST has wrote based on our investigation whatsapp call that was done in year 2023 during around the month of JUNE.

This retarded personage that was initially at "Alfred Saker School" oriented to perform Commerce AND Accounting, WITH A grade of 10.00/20 is an idiot; Not just because *she doesn't even have a "degree of Doctor of Medicine (Dr. med.)"*.

This happens unsolicited as I am having a talk together with "Rose Sangnou"; AND "PASTOR marco OF Pentecostal Christian CHURCH" ' 'chapelle de la gloire de christ" in DLA.

I AM SUSPICIOUS of this corrupt C.P.D.M aunt that has german citizenship to be from Central Intelligence Agency (CIA); hired specially to try to kill me by any means; even using sorcery.

41.41 YAGER MABOMA is an idiot of justice judge here in CMR

Since 2021, February that I have complaint for a group of harassers that came into my compound to brutalize myself in front of a so called judge of instruction from sawa tribal tribe, I STILL RECEIVE PEOPLE TRYING TO AGGRESS and Harass myself.

42.42 I-xavier-went on roads to shout That I required JUSTICE for my saved life by SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA

- o **Wednesday 28th of JUNE 2024:** "Proverbs 1 : 18 – 21 (in Holy bible of JEOVAH-NISSI in Heaven)"

Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA was sodomized both physically and mentally to release myself as a client, So I will go in front of a judge without the initial attorney I have chosen myself.

I went to road "in AHALA-simbock" to shout at populace that I MUST HAVE JUSTICE DONE against people who broke my gate in the night of FEBRUARY 2023 to kill me with psy-drugs involuntarily.

Politics is going on thoroughly because the year 2025 must released a president of the republic of cameroon !

43.43 YAGER MABOMA has sent my documents to Attorney-prosecutor

- o **SATURDAY 31th of AUGUST 2024:**

I hope I can finish this matter without a judge that has been sodomized by "BIYA-clique".

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" said to myself on my cell phone that I sent to him at least 2 other attorneys of law so to replace him; Which is FALSE.

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" has received money from PAUL-biya.

"Tchonang albertine" is now the person I asked for, for assistance."

"I received this name and contact from my friend and customer "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL SARL" based in Akwa-douala ! "

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (5.)

44.44 Police of AHALA – 19ème arrondissement harassing myself because of SHANDA-tonmeo **Friday 6th of September 2024:**

"NESTOR kenfack tries to talk to my genitor and adversary ROSE-Sangnou without asking anything to myself."

"ROSE-idiot sangnou went to give certain objects to "NESTOR and VALÉRIE kenfack" that are supposed to be my sole customers and friends; Without any intermingled relationship with ROSE-sangnou since I told both of them THAT I am not interested into talking with someone who has tried to kill myself."

"I KNOW that it is C.P.D.M that went to give money to these burglars ("NESTOR" & "VALÉRIE") so they will try to intervene against my interests when court justice comes AS this has been the case with my personal attorney of law the culprit "SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA"."

45.45 CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Saturday 10th of November 2024:**

"A culprit called CLOVIS kemmegne, an intelligence secret service agent of GENDARMERIE NATIONALE of CAMEROON is tring to put troubles into my life via false divulged information around my new business relationships with a new tenant that I could gained via a so called "RENTAL PROPERTY MANAGER"-EMMANUEL-idiot."

"NOW that i have been staying in douala for more than 4-days in a row since my last hijack-attempt, in a so-called inherited property of noumbissi-vilain-idiot THÉODORE; I can see that clovis kemmgne changed the colours GREEN-Yellow-gendarmerie of his GAY-young-porn-female-clairvoyant-boy-jackdaniels; INTO a BLUE-presidential-GRAY-porn-DGRE colors."

"INSTEAD of doing is openly called business of electronics computer technician, and also, "GAY-handler-bar-JACKS.", THIS guja-gay is hiding himself behind my sister and my mother-side family to plan a so-called "CONSTAT-de-FAIT" for the idiot of justice judge HUGUES-alain-yager maboma-faineant."

"THE other gay-called napoa-maxime-eteme; a viagra-gay that seems to be a burglar to myself since BAMKOUI said to me he didn't worked at all for SEMIL; BUT is working for CMR-navy in DOUALA; came openly salute myself, together with another idiot called KAMGAIN jean-pierre;"

"i hope only "jean-loïc siewe and belvianne" that seemed to be young fellow cameroonian entrepreneurs are not intermeddle here."

"i can already see that siewe's mother is from the idiot-village-Babouantou !."

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (VI (6).)

CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Wednesday 13th of November 2024:**

"SIEWE and BELVIANNE his collaborator of my new rental property seem to be not able to accommodate well due to destructive actions in water plumbery that seemed to be have done by a previous renter called; AND from R.D.P.C-C.P.D.M-south-bulu-tribe: GERMAIN Blaise ndzie and his wife called Geneviève Ndzie."

"~~Dr. —NOMO siméon-replacement~~ by C.P.D.M.-eyoump-psy; A so-called MAXIME-napoa-eteme called someone I am not sure "Docteur" while I was crossing a street at DLA-cité-des-palmiers yesterday evening; THIS gay-female-psy-hijackist; THAT seemed to be an organizer of my killing via the hijack of my private property in DLA-FEBRURAY-2024 is the one that talked to my 1st before a same day at night I was hijacked. "

"~~MAXIME-napoa-eteme~~ the gay-female-idiot is also from BETI-ekang-amougou-beling-TRAIBAL-tribe as a previous renter called NDZIE geneviève. "

o **SUNDAY 17th of November 2024:**

"IT seems there are no repression against criminals that come officially against my personal and / or familiar interests in CMR. "

"FOR INSTANCE, a family from "BATIÉ-ouest-cmr" that bake "beignets" and that used to transport "Pouse-Pousse" has built a 'bidon-ville-taudis' directly closed to my compound, Where my late father dear THEODORE-idiot noumbissi built a ground foundation, Without any rejection from SOUS-Préfecture that I contacted using my Attorney at law Mr. JUSTICE (Maître Synclair NJEUTCHA tchana)."

"Some folk around this place in Béedi told me that:

1. "A beauty-gay hair-cut society wearing black and /or rosa T-SHIRTS, based on the opposite side of road to CLOVIS-telecom-Alias-kemmegne-gendarmerie-nationale-CMR";

"Sent a hijacker wearing finger-female-paint to say to people around where I was sitting reading my Bible-holy; That I AM SAID to be a mad-person; "

"BEFORE this physical attack even though I WASN'T talking to that gendarme that seems to act as a gay-female-hair treater; I COULD see a woman from CHRISTIAN-eyoum-tribal-tribe called Assassin. "

2. "Clovis telecom Alias clovis kemmegne" has repeatedly summon several people to harass me with no fear since he is well connected with ETOO-fils, a burglar called in CMR Soccer-player-female-male-born-again-gay-hijackist-Christian-eyoum "
3. "Maxime NAPOA-eteme is the one who told this very strange family since they don't do anything apparently to survive in Douala other than sneaking other people properties; WHERE enforced by "NAPOA ETEME, MAXIME" to Hijack myself even physically because I AM A NOBODY IN THIS COUNTRY called CAMEROON. "
4. "i suspect the current president of the republic of CMR called PAUL-biya to be behind this multi-attempt to destroy my life; Since for all my legal complaints nothing could be done for at least more than 12 years. "
5. "paul-biya-junior is mad; a culprit from mvomekaa. "

o **WEDNESDAY 27th of November 2024:**

"This new renter of mine a so-called-CALLPRIT jean-loïc siewe, And BELVIANNE meleu nossi seem not to even welcome very nicely their clients because they left so dirty the entrance step-feet of their rented apartment for 138 EUROS monthly. "

"ALSO this belvianne aged of 25th years old seem not to understand that I AM NOT CONFIDENT of renewing their rental agreement because of all inconsistencies I COULD notice since they entered this apartment inherited of mine:"

1. Her national identity card says she is "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala".

THERE was a so-called "gendarme-etoga-idiot" call Jonas-Kemajou-fainénat that scammed myself around 3 000 EUROS, And that was wearing a gendarme-green-attire, And that also has this "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala" instead of something professional-criminal-armed-robber-south-west-CMR.

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 1

- 1.) **STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS, MASTER'S DEGREE THESIS DEFENSE TALK, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE (FB 3), UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY** |★| **MAY "2007"**
- 2.) **STATICALLY VERIFYING API USAGE RULES USING TRACEMATCHES, 9th Workshop on Compiler-Driven Performance, CASCON 2010, Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham Conference Centre, MARKHAM, ONTARIO, CANADA** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>) |★| **NOVEMBER "2010"**
- 3.) **TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-based SOFTWARE, PH.D. THESIS EXAMINATION COMPREHENSIVE !, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) |★| **DECEMBER "2011"**
- 4.) **Course project small talk-presentation in front of PATRICK-lam-idiot & course ECE 750 students, 1 EIT room I don't remember code room number digits, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** **Spring "2013"**
- 5.) **(prepared based on result outcome of talk given during Spring 2013 for course project.); CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAIN T ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, ECE GRAD TALK, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** **April "2014"**
- 6.) **CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAIN T ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES SEMINAR, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** **JANUARY "2015"**
- 7.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; sns cameroon ltd (Mr. DIVINE Njobati); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **JANUARY "2016"**
- 8.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; best car care & services (Mr. HENRI ngatchou); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON** **JANUARY "2016"**
- 9.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; snob bazar outlet stores (Mr. LAVOISIER); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **MAY "2016"**
- 10.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; expert3dev s.a.r.l (Mr. Momo); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **JUNE "2016"**
- 11.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bilingual entente bookshop (Mr. JACQUES); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **JANUARY "2017"**
- 12.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; BLACK & WHITE snack bars (Mr. TOM & Mr. AURÉLIEN iloga iloga (ecobank poste centrale yaoundé)); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **JUNE "2017"**
- 13.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for COMPUTER INFORMATICS ENGINEERING TRAINING; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; IUC [Institut Universitaire de la Côte] (Mr. HYPOLITHE Tekeu); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON** **SEPTEMBER "2017"**
- 14.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS TALKS; Dr. SANDY beidu; Dr. ERIC brefo-mensah; WATERLOO; ON; CANADA** **JUNE "2018"**
- 15.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for CROWD FUNDING REQUEST PROPOSAL; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION (for "MS WINDOWS"); BAFIASOFT (Mr. CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong); WATERLOO; ON; CANADA** **SEPTEMBER "2018"**
- 16.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; coplatec s.a.r.l (Mr. CONSTANT Kemmogne); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON** **MAY "2020"**
- 17.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and drugstore selling; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pharmacy fiango lycée MAKÉPÉ (Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **JANUARY "2021"**
- 20.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and INDUSTRIAL logistics; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bontée s.a.r.l (Ms. ARLETTE [Sibeufo-mpay-army-general-spouse-in-official]); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **FEBRUARY "2021"**
- 21.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and PRODUCTION planing; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; CROQUE-MATIN (Mr. MOUSSA Saliou); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **MARCH "2021"**
- 22.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL ("MS WINDOWS 2000"); elektro maképé (Mr. ARMSTRONG); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **JUNE "2021"**
- 23.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; établissement kenfack (Mr. KENFACK); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **JULY "2021"**
- 24.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; clinique de l'espérance (Mr. YVES Mogo); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **SEPTEMBER "2021"**
- 25.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjou Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **OCTOBER "2021"**
- 26.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie la confiance (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON** **NOVEMBER "2021"**

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 2

- 27.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie n.k. (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **NOVEMBER "2021"**
- 28.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mr. FABRICE Siemeni); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **JANUARY "2022"**
- 29.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjou Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **JANUARY "2022"**
- 30.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND networked installations; quincaillerie aimée (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **JUNE "2022"**
- 31.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND commercial financial accounting; poissonnerie plus (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **SEPTEMBER "2022"**
- 32.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0 BRIEF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL PRESENTATION; ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE YAOUNDÉ - ENSPY (PROF. DR.-ENG. THOMAS NDIÉ DJOTIO); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON* **May "2023"**
- 33.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER TRAINING; happiness potential sarl (DIPL.-ING. (FH) DR. FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI, M.Sc); Douala; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **August "2023"**
- 34.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER financial accounting SHORT PRESENTATION VIEW DEMONSTRATION; quincaillerie aimée sarl (Ms. CHRISTELLE spouse NAMEKONG, B.SC.); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **December "2023"**
- 35.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 VERY SHORT INFORMATION SESSION; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mrs. Hecna Ngayam) ; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON **May "2024"**
- 36.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-FOSS SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Hilaire Yimdjo, B.Sc. in Computer Science (entrepreneur in car care and management); Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON **May "2024"**
- 37.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in hardware shop and grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **June 12, "2024"**
- 38.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 Installation hardware checks; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **June 13, "2024"**
- 39.) Aborted installation & training of family association "MA-sangnou-idiot-bangou"; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON. **March "2025"**
- 40.) **Presentation & Questions & Answers (Q&A) with a young entrepreneur-woman-lady from Douala-sawa tribe; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON.** **March, "2025"**
- Based on our remarks to this lady of very low class revenue, we could find that we may add an option for "automatically recalculating cost-price of acquisition."*
- WE see here an opportunity to examine how to improve quality & revenue of this low-class entrepreneurial adventure !*
- THIS kind of entrepreneurial organization is very pro-eminent in Douala-sawa tribe as customers come into living-house to buy. !*
- 41.) **YERITH-ERP-9.0 design introspective view talk accompanied with Q&A (Questions & Answers) by management consultant IRIS mbieukop; [M. Iris-mbieukop] is an expert using MS-excel & PowerBI (BUSINESS intelligence).** **April, "2025"**
- VERY impressive questions that could make our start-up "YERITH R&D" [improve YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum in terms of Ergonomics (color management)], and / or functionality; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON*
- **June 11, 2025 :**
- [This guja seems to be an EYOUM because he was looking quite strange while I just great him yesterday night while entering DLA.] Kind-of son of a guja call PAUL-fokamn-kemmogne—idiot.*
- 42.) **[YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum short introduction]; MBA-Claude BISSEG (bisseg@yahoo.fr); Very interesting introspective towards reconfiguring pricing options !**
- Very similar to Microsoft Dynamics & Sales Forces software. MBA-Claude BISSEG seems to want trying this as a rental software monthly around "20, 000 Francs CFA monthly".* **May 12, "2025"**
- HIS father, M. BISSEG is a very well respected member of Lions-Club Douala, TOGETHER for instance with Dr.-criminal GWET-bell !*
- Attorney of JUSTICE-congolese-brazzaville Vicent GOMEX & President-Congolese Sassou are also members of Lions-Club-INTERNATIONL-criminal !*
- 43.) **Presentation & Questions & Answers (Q&A) with a young entrepreneur named ROSTAND-moungam. Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON.** **June 2, "2025"**
- ROSTAND is a startuper that uses Programming language "DART" and also website builder application "flutter flow" to give maximal power to its clients that are in need of a webshop !"*
- ROSTAND is at time skeptical in trying YERITH R&D product YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum because it seems to him not very simple to implement according to his web presence requirements !"*

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"XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU [PR. PROF. DR.-ING.]"

R&D — RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT — SUMMARY

— RESEARCHING GOALS IN "DISTRIBUTED & OPERATING COMPUTING SYSTEM" (CONSTRUCTION & ANALYSIS & VERIFICATION & VALIDATION) —

- Create technology for easing life in Africa • Make human-being life easier and cheaper •

Research KEYwords : Yerith-Xavier-NOUNDOU ✓ ([2025]-(YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0); [2022]-SDMM; YRI_QVGE; YERITH-SAINT; [2006]-(Peleska. Yerith et al.); [2022]-KLAUS HAVELUND (LogSCOPE); [2017]-Frank-TIP-Koushik-SEN (EVENTRACECOMMANDER); [2007]-"Hendren, et al". (tracematches, S00T); THOMAS-reps (IFDS; IDE); [1977]-Gary-KILDALL ✓ (static code lattice-based "dataflow analysis"-seminal); [1977]-Patrick & Radia-COUSOT (Abstract INTERPRETATION);.

Figure 36: "Portrait of YERITH-NISSI. now 42 years old."

DOCTOR-Ph.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING. / PH.D.) in Electrical & Computer Engineering; UNiversity of waterloo-mutilative; '12/20/2011'!

★ — ★ DOCTOR-PH.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING. [21]) ★ — ★

Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree ("B.Sc & M.Sc." / Dipl.-Inf.); UNiversity-racist of BREMEN.; '05/25/2007'.
— Diplom-INFORMATIKER (Dipl.-Inf. [?]) —

■ UNIVERSITY publications | [Tranng](#) | [TALKS](#) | [LAtest](#) | [Figures](#) | [Tables](#)

■ PUBLICATIONS at ["Start-Up YERITH R&D"]

- Resrching goals.
- Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise.
- PUBLICATIONS in FRENCH.
- PUBLICATIONS in English.
- Summary of PRO-eminant Contributions.
- Contacts with ACADEMIA—other than myself!

— Scholarships & Awards

- "Post- & Doctoral Research and Studies" at the UNiversity-RACIST of WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada — " ≈ 30 + 27 = 57-months" —.
- "GRADUATE [students] : Dr. ridha | Basser | Divam jain | Zheng FELIX fang".
- "Teaching for the UNiversity-RACIST of WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada — " ≈ 24-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "Graduate INTERN" at International Business Machinery (IBM), MARKHAM, Toronto, CANADA-idiot (<https://www.ibm.com/ca-en>) — " ≈ 8-months" —.
- "(PART-TIME) Student Software System Developer" for AGBS - Arbeitsgruppe Betriebssysteme (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>), UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-racist — " ≈ 6-months" —.
- "(PART-TIME) Student Software System Developer" for Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH) (<https://www.gewete.com>), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY — " ≈ 24-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "JUNIOR Software Developer" for SIEMENS-racist Medical Solutions (now SIEMENS-healthineers) (<https://www.healthcare.siemens.com>) — " ≈ 21-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "(Part-Time) WEB AND 'RAD' APPLICATION DEVELOPER" at ZMML-racist, UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-angeber (<https://www.uni-bremen.de/en/zmml>) — " ≈ 25-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "Research Curriculum" at the UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-racist — " ≈ 54-months" —.

46.46 Professor-professional Computing Scientific Association Memberships

■ Current: "~~aem: The Association for Computing Machinery~~"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

47.47 Hardware Products

■ ★ "Portable Computer for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring" : YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>).

48.48 Software (System) Products ("Progiiciels en langue Française")

■ ★ "WYSIWYG Web Designer Generated Tool : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL" (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)[?].

■ "Runtime MONITORING tester verifier" : YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b].

■ "Computer-Aided Software Engineering (CASE) Design Tool for creating SDMM" : YRI_QVGE (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [1d].

■ "An Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) & Stock-live trading platform; ALL-in-one" : YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662181>).

49.49 Research Impact.

Table 13: Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D]

N°	RESULT	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION AND / OR REFERENCE
1.	ERP – PGI introduction because of creation & proof-tested YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2025	Insertion of a placebo ERP-PGI software system by R.D.P.C.-C.PDM-biya-in-year-2025	N/A
2.	★ Secured Web-browser architecture only 2-tiers layers .	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2025	1 st 2 layers web-browser based software architecture with security proof code backed and secure via model-checking runtime verification monitoring!	N/A
3.	★ Hardware YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2024	1 st open-sourced runtime verification on-the-fly; Also as Hot plug-in device embedded	CE
4.	★ Software YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL Software YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2024	"1.) WYSIWYG-Tool for HTML pages." 2.) HIGH-level view imperative Programming language for HTML pages dynamic; 3.) Automatic generation of safe & secure web sources files	N/A
5.	Software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2015	1 st Simpler to use ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing). Starting age 12 years old.	N.A and / or O.H.A.D.A (not required at all)
6.	Program YERITH-SAINT	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2013	1 st temporal property verification by (staged-alias analysis) static taint analysis framework-algorithm in LLVM	N/A

RESEARCH IMPACT — CONTINUED

Table 14: Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D] — Continued.

N°	RESULT	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION AND / OR REFERENCE
7.	A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine).	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2022	1.) 1 st fully compliant to "David-harel statechart"—"mealy machine" STATE DIAGRAM formalization for runtime monitoring verification & automatic model-based statechart-code-generation; 2.) Checks for forbidden trace specification across software system with no additional runtime overhead as demonstrated by concurrent event stream analysis technique	N/A
8.	Software YRI_QVGE	CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool	YEAR-2022	1 st CASE-Tool for designing by drawing state diagram mealy machine (SDMM); 2.) 1 st model checker at runtime that encompasses Mealy-machine as opposed And not KRIPKE-structure !	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
9.	Software YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2022	1 st open code sourced Runtime MONITOR container (generator) software for "SDMM"	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
10.	Algorithms not published in any journal And / Or conference due to missing financial funding.	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2015	Various algorithms for creating working User-QT software easily	N/A
11.	[UWATERLOO-SE 465-ECE 453] — Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL".	Unit Testing	YEAR-2009	Pragmatic Junit 4 Tutorial aided with "Cobertura Test Coverage Analyzer"	N/A
12.	Software "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (N.A).	Static Program Code Analysis Checking	YEAR-2013	Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints.	N/A
13.	Software YERITH-XRESIN-SOFTWARE.	Web Apps Program Analysis	YEAR-2013	A dynamic taint analysis software for Security for PHP in a JAVA PHP Interpreter.	N/A
14.	Taxonomy of Program-Software Verification & Analysis.	Software Verification	YEAR-2023	Unique positioning and specification of PROGRAM-software Verification & Analysis.	N/A
15.	MASTER thesis – Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems (N.A).	Test Cases / Test Data — Generation	YEAR-2007	Statistical uniform distribution generation of test cases for statechart diagrams.	N.A and / or A.R.I.N.C
16.	Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata (N.A).	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2004	A set of transformations from Büchi automata to Timed Automata.	N/A

- Our commitment to create software tools & programs for insuring a better and safe software system quality as both open-sourced and priced products, Enables now young immature software developers and engineers in under-developed Africa to have better products and quality at a low cost price : ["Software Products at YERITH R&D"]. TABLE 13, TABLE 14 illustrate sample products, both potential-in-preparation hardware, and already available (accompanying) software.

THIS statement previously made is also available for medium sized companies in west developed countries where even not far as for in year 2000, and also years before; CRASHES of aircraft "Ariane 5 occurred and other airplanes from Airbus and BOEING, causing lost of several human being lives.

- YOUNG adults aged around \approx 12 years old can now start learning using a full-featured ERP-trading stock exchange software that uses a very simplified everyday language as testified by our previous report of "Start-Up YERITH R&D" for years 2022 – 2023 : "REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023) (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>)".

This couldn't be possible years before starting 2015 when I started creating YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM; Our previous assertion is corroborated by deployment of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum at at least 5 locations in Yaounde & Douala, in main cities of Cameroun, which is the leader of central africa economic zone C.E.M.A.C (<https://www.cemac.int>).

50.50 Tools & Programming Language Expertise

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, VALKYRIE YERITH[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming and Compiler Frameworks (including IDE):** DIFF, Patch, Txl, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

51.51 Teaching for the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada–racist.

Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Compilers (ECE 351) | [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)].

52.52 Summary of Professional Training in USA, Canada, & Germany

- "Professional international workshops and conferences". 2001 – 2015

53.53 Teaching / summary of competencies Acquired at THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA–RACIST.

- "Formal training at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2009 – 2011
- "Competencies acquired during courses teaching during doctoral studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2009 – 2011
- "Competencies acquired during courses teaching during post–doctoral studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2012 – 2015

54.54 Teaching ONLINE on the World Wide Web UNIVERSITY–level (graduate) Students.

I currently live in Africa, Cameroon where I cannot have a position at my level of knowledge and experience in a formal Cameroonian UNIVERSITY.

 "POUR les usagers de la langue FRANÇAISE : "Enseignant d'université"; ET NON Enseignant–employé d'université (d'État); EST 1 des définitions du mot professeur."

 Enseignant d'université signifie divulguer des enseignements académiques de rang doctoral et post–doctoraux aux apprenants des universités du monde. "LE titre et grade académique de *Ph.D. et / ou Docteur-de-3^{ème} cycle universitaire*" en est l'approbation universellement reconnue en ma connaissance.

Nonetheless I still teach via WWW books & tools, & programs that I deem at University level graduate courses level; Based on my "doctoral & post–doctoral Ph.D. studies In Computer Software Engineering" & work at the University–racist of Waterloo.

I am developing course material for online worldwide university level (graduate) students as depicted online on "zenodo.org" (<https://www.zenodo.org>) :

I.) Topic : SOFTWARE SYSTEM

- 1.) **FORMAL METHODS** using state diagram mealy machine ([SDMM](#)) for runtime monitoring and verification (via *model checking*) :
 - YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>)
 - A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine) – *Book Preprint* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) ;
 - User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) ;
- 2.) World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH–WEB–DSL–9.0" : book in preparation, together with accompanying CDROM–USB-key dongle. (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)
- 3.) **SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE** : SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH–ERP–3.0[?]: (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf);
- 4.) **SOFTWARE VERIFICATION AND ANALYSIS** : " Temporal Property Verification in Plugin–based Software by Program Analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10990602>)".

II.) Topic : ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE & TOOLS

55.55 Research Expertise (PR. PROF. DR.-ING.)■ **Business Informatics** ⇒ *illustrative figure of business workflow of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.*○ **Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery**

- 1.) ERP-trading Stock Exchange Software: "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"[?]; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0> C++; Qt 5; [03/2015 -]

■ **Software Engineering**○ **Web Apps Program Analysis**

- 2.) 3 A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus; <https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis> JAVA; Firebug; [01/2013 - 04/2013]

○ **Web Apps Automatic Generation** ⇒ *illustrative table of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 (Section 27.27.5).*

- 3.) YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL[27.27]; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9> flex, bison; [06/2024 -]

○ **Debugging Tool**

- 4.) 20.20 Open Source Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; https://github.com/yerithrd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; [07/2023 -]

○ **CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool**

- 5.) 1 "MBT-RT-TESTER PLUGIN" FOR "Borland-Together"[1b] C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "www.verified.de" [09/2006 - 02/2007]
6.) YRI_QVGE[1] C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 -]

○ **Compiler Technology**

- 7.) 34 Ph.D. dissertation: A Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM; <https://github.com/AmesianX/saint> LLVM; — 03/2015 —
8.) 1d A State Diagram Mealy Machine Description Language; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; [04/2023 -]

■ **Software Engineering** ► **Software Verification** ⇒ *figure illustrating components of it (Section 13.13.1).*○ **Static Program Code Analysis Checking à la "Gary A. Kildall: A unified approach to global program optimization (https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945)".**

- 9.) 1(1)4 Conference Article: Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints JUnit; SOOT; JAVA; — 2013 —
10.) 32 Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software SOOT; JAVA; — 12/2011 —

○ **Dynamic Program Binary Runtime Analysis Verification**

- 11.) 1 YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime;
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> C++; Qt-DBus; [06/2022 -]
12.) 1f A Runtime Monitoring Mealy Machine C++ library; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 -]

○ **Unit Testing**

- 13.) II Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL" JAVA; JUnit; "COBERTURA coverage analyzer" — 10/2009 —

○ **Test Cases / Test Data — Generation**

- 14.) 1a Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "RT-Tester" — 05/2007 —

■ **Theoretical Computer Science**○ **Concurrent Systems, AUTOMATA theory**

- 15.) 1d Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata Set-Algebra; — 12/2004 —

56.56 Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise

- A.) **C++**; & **JAVA**; & **SQL – DBMS (Database Management System) MariaDB** with **DEBIAN LINUX & SVN** (E.g. : *(Part-Time) Student Software Developer Position* (<https://www.gewete.com>))
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) *Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER — Team Lead of myself at that time* 2005 – 2007
b.) *Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH — Technical Lead of myself at that time* 2005 – 2007
- B.) **C++** with **MS Windows (XP, 98,2000,7,10,11)** & **FSM (Finite State Machines)** & **Rational ClearCase** (E.g. : *Junior Software Developer position*) (<https://www.healthcare.siemens.com>)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) *Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG — Team Lead of myself at that time* 2007 – 2009
b.) *Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAUIGLIA — Technical Lead of myself at that time* 2007 – 2009
- C.) **ERP System YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum** with **Javascript, XML, HTML5, CSS, PHP, MAKE, Qt 5, C++, MariaDB, flex & bison** (E.g. : *Inventor & Developer*)
SUCCESSFULLY Used & Re-Tested.
a.) *Annual reports : REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17689313>) 2021 – 2023
b.) *[Document local link !]*
- D.) **Software Testing (UNIT, Integration)** with **UML 2.0-HybridUML (Statechart by David-HAREL)** & **C++** (E.g. : *Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN-racist-idiot, BREMEN-germany, Germany-racist*)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) *Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska — MSc-advisor of myself at that time, Stakeholder of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH.* 2004 – 2007
b.) *Prof. Dr. Rolf Drechsler — MSc-advisor of myself at that time* 2004 – 2007
c.) *Diplomarbeit Kolloquium MASTER-thesis defence* May 25, "2007"
- E.) **JAVA** with **JUnit** (E.g. : *SE 465-ECE 453 — Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL"*)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) *Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — Course Instructor.* SPRING term (Jan. – Apr.) – 2010
- F.) **Web Apps Automatic Generation** with **Javascript, XML, HTML5, CSS, PHP, MAKE, Qt 5, C++, MariaDB, flex & bison** (E.g. : *"WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0"*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/17466696>)
a.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. OWOLABI Legunsen, Ph.D., Cornell University, ITHACA, USA-*
b.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Christian RIKONG Nguoyong, AS-degree in Computer Science, Santa monica-california, USA-*
c.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Djotio Ndie-*
d.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. Patrick-LAM-*
- G.) **Web Apps Program Analysis** with **Quercus & JAVA** (E.g. : *A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus, CS846 at THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) *Prof. Dr. Frank Tip, Ph.D. – COURSE instructor* APRIL 30, "2013"
- H.) **Program Code Binary Analysis** with **SDMM & YERITH_QVGE** (E.g. : *Software Testing of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum & Runtime Monitoring Verification.*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>)
a.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. OWOLABI Legunsen, Ph.D., Cornell University, ITHACA, USA* December 20, "2025"
b.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska — Stakeholder of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH.* October 7, "2025"
c.) *REVIEWER-Proposal of KLAUS HAVELUND, Researcher at N.A.S.A., U.S.A.* July 11, "2025"
- I.) **Program Code Static Analysis** with **apache ANT, SOOT & JAVA** (E.g. : *Doctoral TheSis at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) *Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — PH.D.-advisor of myself at that time* December 20, "2011"
b.) *Prof. Dr. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO) — at my request before my PhD Comprehensive Examination* December "2011"
c.) *PhD Comprehensive Examination – ECE-University of waterloo* December 20, "2011"
- J.) **Software Vulnerability Analysis** using **LLVM & C++** (E.g. : *Doctoral Dissertation in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada*) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) *Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. — at my request before my ECE graduate research seminar talk* "2014"
b.) *ECE Graduate Seminar Talk Series at THE university of waterlloo-racist, ontario, canada* April, 16 "2014"
c.) *PhD Dissertation Defence – CS-University of waterloo* January "2015"

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)

- 1.) A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMATA AND TIMED AUTOMATA, INDEPENDENT STUDY, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA. JANUARY 2005
- 2.) STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html), MASTER'S DEGREE IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, AND PROF. DR. PHIL. NAT. ROLF DRECHSLER. MAY 25, 2007
- 3.) RESEARCH MASTER PROJECT REPORT cognitive agents, [Research Project Report Robotic-Cognition-Cartography], UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, ADVISED BY DR.-ING. LUTZ Frommberger, DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. Frank DYLLA, PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. Christian FRESKA. July 2006

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.uwaterloo.ca>)

- 1.) JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>), UNDERGRADUATE COURSE LECTURES NOTES 'SOFTWARE TESTING, QUALITY ASSURANCE AND MAINTENANCE', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. OCTOBER 31, 2009
- 2.) TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-BASED SOFTWARE (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8ald09b015f29b33>), PHILOSOPHY DOCTOR (PH.D.) DISSERTATION, (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8ald09b015f29b33>) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. DECEMBER 20, 2011
- 3.) DYNAMIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR PHP IN QUERCUS (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) (◆[git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis); ◆[git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)), PH.D. GRADUATE COURSE PROJECT 'program analysis of web apps', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY FULL PROFESSOR FRANK TIP. APRIL 30, 2013

**JAVA application server "Quercus" — JAVA-PHP-interpreter
PROGRAM analysis of web apps
SOFTWARE cyber-security**

- "[THIS course CS846 project led by Professor doctor Frank TIP], was about creating a security taint analysis program code in JAVA for the "Quercus JAVA PHP Interpreter", which is a web application server, COMPARABLE to Apache-Tomcat (<https://www.tomcat.org>); And that enables PHP developers to use existing JAVA libraries within their PHP code as well. "
- "I have implemented and tested a dynamic taint analysis using Firebug, and FirePHP. THIS taint analysis enables to warn developers about data and values that originate from outside the webserver, and / or also about values that emerge as results from operations that involve "tainted values"; MEANING values that are considered not safe because they originate from the outside world of the Quercus web application server. "
- "Taking particular care of unsafe outside world data and values (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) allows developers to avoid web cyber-software security vulnerabilities attacks such as SQL injection, BUFFER-OVERFLOW attacks, format string vulnerabilities, etc.."

► YEAR-2024

IN our project YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0, we will need to instrument binaries of a running JAVA virtual machine; Most probably "Debian-Linux OpenJDK Runtime Environment" (<https://docs.oracle.com>).

THIS binary instrumentation technology from INTEL-pin (<https://www.intel.com/missingfornow>) has an advantage over reinstrumenting and recompiling code sources each time any Qt-DBus message has been introduced and / or modified in tool YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>).

- 4.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK, (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. MARCH 10, 2015

**Heartbleed BUG security breach SSL-1.0.1-f (<https://heartbleed.com>)
Static PROGRAM code analysis of C programs
LLVM code; SOFTWARE cyber-security**
- 5.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM TOOL USER'S GUIDE (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051299>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK artifact, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. [OCTOBER 2015]

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (in English language) (II)

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

57.57 YERITH R&D – Algorithms Excerpt not published in conference papers due to resources.

1. [Created Algorithms Link].

58.58 YERITH R&D – Reports

2. *REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17689313>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, November 23, 2025. November 23, 2025.
3. *REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023)* (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, October 1, 2023. October 1, 2023.

59.59 Business Informatics Management Knowledge

5. *YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum SOFTWARE SYSTEM PRODUCT SHEET* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17661983>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
6. *ADVANTAGES OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum COMPARED TO OTHER TOP ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEMS* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662017>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
7. *INFORMATION BROCHURE OF ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662117>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
8. *INSTALLATION GUIDE FOR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum* (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060182/>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021. MARCH 2021.

60.60 Associated Computer Devices

9. *YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum RECOMMENDED POINT-OF-SALE HARDWARE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17661831>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.

61.61 Advanced Software Technology

10. *"WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0"* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>),
BOOK, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, March 2025. March 2025.
11. *Concepts around real-time trading for physical and / or virtual stocks with software system: YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME* (<https://zenodo.org/records/14505133>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, DECEMBER 17, 2024. DECEMBER 17, 2024.
12. *A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
Book in preparation, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2025. 2025.
13. *User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2023. 2023.
14. *YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>),
DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MAY 2022. MAY 2022.
15. *Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>),
Journal article in preparation, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, August 2023. August 2023.
16. *Compendium of Documents About the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, June 2023. June 2023.
17. *SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/uploads/17662181>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
10. *YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051303>),
CONFERENCE article in submission, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, February 2023. February 2023.

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (en langue française) (III)

[LIEN interne à ce document sur mes Spécialités en recherche académique et / ou Professionnelle.]

62.62 YERITH R&D – Algorithmes scientifiques (En Anglais) – Non publiés dans 1 journal pour causes de ressources financières entre autres.

1. [Lien sur des algorithmes repertoriés et Créés par moi !]

63.63 YERITH R&D – Rapports

2. *RAPPORTS DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17689313>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
3. *RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0 (années 2015–2022)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, OCTOBRE 2022. OCTOBRE 2022.

64.64 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Connaissances Marketing

4. *BROCHURE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680727>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025

65.65 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Management des données

5. *GUIDE DE L'UTILISATEUR 'MANAGER', PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/record/8058259/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, JUIN 2018. JUIN 2018
6. *YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0: ESSAI DE PRODUCTIVITÉ ENTREPRENEURIALE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071437>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021. MARS 2021
7. *GUIDE PRATIQUE DU LOGICIEL DE GESTION COMMERCIALE ET FINANCIÈRE YERITH-PGI-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680818>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
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MAI 2022